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**THE JORDANIAN POLICY TOWARDS THE SYRIAN
CRISIS 2011 – 2016**

Ph.D.Thesis

By

Mohammed B. E. Saaida

MMAJ ACADEMY OF INTERNATIONAL STUDIES

JAMIA MILLIA ISLAMIA

NEW DELHI-110025

JANUARY 2019

THE JORDANIAN POLICY TOWARDS THE SYRIAN

CRISIS 2011 – 2016

Thesis

Submitted to

JAMIA MILLIA ISLAMIA

In partial fulfillment of the requirement of the award of the
Degree of Doctor of Philosophy in
International Studies

by

MOHAMMED B. E. SAAIDA

Under the Supervision of

Dr. SHAHID TASLEEM

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DECLARATION

I, **MOHAMMED B. E. SAAIDA**, a student of PhD hereby declare that the thesis titled "**THE JORDANIAN POLICY TOWARDS THE SYRIAN CRISIS 2011-2016**" which is submitted by me to the **MMAJ Academy of International Studies, Jamia Millia Islamia**, New Delhi, in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Doctor of Philosophy has not previously formed the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Associateship, Fellowship, or any other similar title or recognition. This is to declare further I have also fulfilled the requirements of para 8((viii and ix) of the Ph.D. ordinance, the details of which are enclosed at the end of the Thesis, and that there is no plagiarism.

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To the best of my knowledge this work has not been submitted in part or full for any Degree or Diploma to this University or elsewhere.

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Mohammed B. E. Saaida

List of Abbreviations

ACC	Arab Cooperation Council
CIA	Central Intelligence Agency
COMESA	Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa
DoS	Jordanian Department of Statistics
EU	European Union
FSA	Free Syrian Army
GCC	Gulf Cooperation Council
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
ILO	International Labor Organization
IMF	International Monetary Fund
ISIS	Islamic State in Iraq and Sham
JRP	Jordan Response Plan
JRPSC	Jordan Response Platform for the Syria Crisis
MENA	Middle East and North Africa
MFA	Ministry of Foreign Affairs
MKO	Mujahedin-e-Khalq Organization (People's Mujahedin of Iran)

MOC	Military Operations Center
MoE	Ministry of Education
MoPIC	Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, Jordan
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
NRP	National Resilience Plan
OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
PLO	Palestinian Liberation Organization
UN	United Nations
USA	United States of America
UNCHR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
USSR	Union of Soviet Socialist Republics
WTO	World Trade Organization

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Introduction

1.1 Introduction:

This thesis tries to examine the policy of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan towards the Syrian crisis during the period 2011-2016, as Jordan was one of the principal countries to be affected directly by the crisis. In six years, the Syrian conflict escalated from peaceful protests to militants and insurgency then to bloody civil war, gaining regional as well as international dimensions; it resulted in not only a human tragedy by forcing about 1.3 million Syrian to seek refuge in Jordan, thus triggering a sudden demographic change,¹ but also prompted security threats for the country, in addition to other internal and external implications stemming from major changes in regional and international politics in the West Asia region. The crisis begot a concomitant displacement of nearly 13 million Syrians by the end of December 2016, with more than 6 million displaced internally within Syria, while the vast majority of others moved to Turkey, Lebanon, Iraq, the European Union countries, and other remote countries, according to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNCHR) statistics.² All challenges, including internal pressure on society and security threats in Jordan, along with changes in regional and international politics, were met by Jordanian policies created and implemented by the Jordanian leadership and successive governments.

Historically, the relations between the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the Syrian Arab Republic, go back to their creation from former Ottoman dominions, by Britain and France, after World War I. Since their independence after World War II, the bilateral relationship between the two states is best described as largely unstable, alternating between good,

¹ Mirkin, B. (2013). *Arab Spring: Demographics In A Region In Transition*. United Nations Development Programme, Regional Bureau For Arab States. 28-29.

² UNHCR. (2014). *Syria Regional Refugees Response*. Retrieved from <http://data.unhcr.org/syrianrefugees/regional.php>

lukewarm, hostile and tensed, to even sporadically violent. As the political circumstances, factors, and actors in the conflict shifted dramatically, the domestic conflict in Syria which began in February 2011, rose to regional and subsequently to international levels, with violence reaching deplorable levels, causing death of thousands of Syrians and destroying a number of urban areas;³ a huge number of Syrians fled for their lives into neighboring countries posing great challenges to the hosting communities, Jordan being a significant party, considering that its border came under fire more than others because of its vicinity to the conflict on account of sharing 379 kilometers of border with Syria.⁴

The Syrian crisis is not the first conflict to afflict Jordan; through its history, the kingdom has been subjected to the consequences of surrounding conflicts: the Arab-Israeli wars leading to the Palestinian exodus (Nakba) in 1948 and the Naksah in 1967; the Second Gulf War (Desert Storm) in 1990-1991; the American invasion to Iraq in 2003. Although, Jordan is comparatively far from the circles of conflicts, it encountered sudden influxes of people, which put it in an unenviable position. In response, the official Jordanian foreign policies were formulated keeping in mind various internal and external determinants, to maintain, preserve, and achieve the national interest of Jordan internally and externally. The positions and policies reflected the Jordanian popular, and especially the official attitudes towards each issue interiorly, regionally, and internationally.

Through growing activity in Syria, Jordan stayed neutral and tried to remain diplomatic by distancing itself as much as possible from what is going on in Syria, considering it an internal affair of Syria that should not be interfered with. Unlike other Arab countries,

³ Bhardwaj, M. (2012). *Development Of Conflict In Arab Spring Libya And Syria: From Revolution To Civil War*. Washington University International Review, 1(1), 76-97. p: 90.

⁴ Index Munde. (2017). *Jordan Vs. Syria*. Retrieved from <https://www.indexmundi.com/factbook/compare/jordan.syria/geography>

Jordan did not evict the Syrian ambassador until 2014, despite receiving indirect threats every now and then, to expand and move the conflict to Jordanian territories. Persistent in its endless debate on Syria, the Jordanian diplomacy remained ambivalent regarding the Syrian crisis ever since its outset. The kingdom has refrained from endorsing any military intervention, and continued its advocacy of a political solution as the best recourse to ending the crisis. This stance on Syrian predicament was ultimately based on Jordan's political, security, social, and economic considerations. Jordan continually strove to attain a balanced policy that stems from realistic factors, but could at the same time help the country strike a balance between its interests and its alliances, at the lowest possible cost.

In order to understand the developments in Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis, this study will go through the different variables, whether internal or external, that control this diplomacy. The study aims to examine if there have been any changes in the Jordanian diplomacy since the outbreak of the crisis, and to what extent these have affected Jordan's future diplomacy towards Syria. Several reasons necessitated this dissertation: 1) the thesis will supplement the existing literature in this field by providing explanations for the response of the Jordanian policy to the Syrian crisis; 2) previous works have failed to provide answers to the main questions posed in this thesis; 3) the thesis, at its culmination, clarifies how Jordan as a state has reciprocated to the Syrian crisis, not only independently but also in conjunction with the regional and international political dynamics and circumstances in the West Asia Region; and finally, 4) exploring more than one side of the Syrian crisis and its implications will highlight the interactions, contradictions, and

overlaps between the local, regional, and international state actors, while also contributing to the current work, research, and related literature in this regard.

The most significant implication of the Syrian crisis for Jordan has been the flow of over 600 thousand registered refugees seeking asylum. So, based on determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy and the decision-making process, this research aims to uncover Jordan's response to the Syrian refugees' issue and to the rise of terrorism. Another important aspect explored in this work is Jordan's regional policy towards Arab and non-Arab regional countries, along with the great powers. It is also imperative to scrutinize Jordanian perspective towards the changing dynamics of its relationship with Syria. Analysis of the collected data helped examine the sources of changes in, and the rationale behind, Jordan's policy towards the Syrian crisis.

The possibilities for amendments in Jordan's position on Syria are endless, regardless of whether the Syrian state falls or not. However, the deepening crisis, continued conflict, and Jordan's geographic location will make it harder for the country to deal with the Syrian question in the same ambiguous manner in the future, as it has adopted to date.

1.2 Statement of the Problem:

This research aims to analyze the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis during 2011-2016. It primarily explores and explains the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy, in addition to the decision-making institutions, while also detecting any changes in policies in response to the emerging challenges internally, regionally, and internationally.

Changes in Jordan's foreign policy towards the Syrian crisis have aroused much debate regarding the reasons behind such changes. There have been statements clarifying such

internal and external policy changes, however, the disagreement over what initiated change, is quite apparent. This work tries to explain these changes by investigating the possible, necessary, and sufficient reasons for policy changes during this period. This attempt will be in vain if the variables that affect and rule the Jordanian policy are not studied; these factors, through a complex network of domestic, regional, and international relations, direct decision making regarding the Syrian issues.

The problem is clearly reflected in the words of King Abdullah II:

"On the political level, we are working with all possible means in cooperation and coordination with the Arab brothers and the international community, including the United States, Russia and European countries, to find a political solution that will preserve Syria's unity and stability and ensure that Syrian state institutions sponsor their citizens to encourage Syrian refugee brothers not only in Jordan, but also in all neighboring countries to return to their country. On the other hand the work is to provide international financial support for the costs of hosting the refugees' responsibilities. In all our dealings with the Syrian crisis, protecting the interests of Jordan and our dear people was our first and last goal. If the world does not move and help us properly, or it becomes a danger to our country, we can at any moment, take measures that protect our country and the interests of our people"⁵.

When it comes to Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis, four factors majorly influenced decision-making. First and foremost, being the Syrian refugees' matter. Jordan turned home to over 600 thousand registered refugees seeking asylum in the country,

⁵ King Abdullah II Speech. Ceremony Of Graduation The 26th Batch Of Officers In Mu'ta University. 16 May 2013. Mu'ta University. Jordan. Jordan TV. Retrieved from https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ihnjflxg7_q

pushed by the violence in Syria, in addition to another 700 thousand Syrians (unregistered). Jordan being a country with finite resources, it is believed that the refugees' crisis had an adverse impact on its economic, social, and security dimensions. Jordan with its limited economic resources tried its best to host the refugees: the government built five refugee camps in Zaatari, Azraq, Mrajeeb Al Fhood, Rukban, and Hadallat, but many refugees had ventured into cities and villages, creating immense pressure on public services in the country.

Second, increasing terrorism threats from Syria. The chaos caused by the Syrian crisis brought about the rise and strengthening of fundamental terrorism organizations resembling The Islamic State in Iraq and Sham (ISIS), and Jordan was one of the first countries to be alarmed by terrorism threats. Since the time of the Arab Afghans' return to their home countries at the beginning of the 1990s, time and again, Jordan found itself face-to-face with situations that could neither be ignored nor underestimated by the Jordanian authorities.

Third, the emergence of new internal security challenges within Jordan. Jordan not only suffered threats of terrorism by organizations such as the ISIS; but to make things harder for the Jordanian government, there existed incubators for such organizations in the Jordanian community as well, led by Jordanian Islamist groups carrying similar thought. This resulted in threats opening up on an internal front, for Jordan's leadership.

Fourth, the inability of the Syrian government to deal with its internal conflict domestically, thereby dragging intervention of outsider powers. The regional and international powers found the Syrian crisis to be a new playground for their competition and an opportunity to

accomplish their interests at the cost of others.⁶ Amidst all this, the Jordanian diplomacy found itself in a whirlpool of politics among the great powers and their regional allies: the United States and its allies vs. Russia and its allies. Jordan is an ally of the United States, and has important political and economic ties with its other allies, especially with the Gulf countries such as Saudi Arabia. At the same time, Jordan also has interests and investments in Russia, which it did not want to let go of. This complexity imposed on Jordan, wisdom in selecting the most suitable positions and policies to deal with the Syrian crisis.

1.3 Research Questions:

The research problem critically raises a number of questions that need to be addressed in this thesis. This research study thus attempts to address the following questions:

1. What were the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy? What were the institutions that govern the Jordanian foreign policy? How was the Jordanian foreign policy created?
2. What was the Jordanian regional policy towards Arab and non-Arab regional countries, and the great powers, the US and Russia, in light of important issues like the Palestinian-Israeli conflict, the Arab Spring revolutions, and terrorism?
3. What were the implications of the Syrian crisis for Jordan? What was the Jordanian response to these implications?
4. What was the Jordanian perspective towards the changing dynamics of its relationship with Syria? What were the internal and external variables that affect Jordan's policy

⁶ Salloukh, B. F. (2013). The Arab Uprisings And The Geopolitics Of The Middle East. *The International Spectator*, 48(2), pp: 32-46.

toward the Syrian crisis? What were the regional and international influences on Jordan's position towards the crisis? What had been the changes in Jordanian policy, in the context of its relations with actors in the conflict?

5. What was the Jordan's response to the security and terrorism threats?

The core questions are:

6. Did security implications and terrorism organizations inside and outside Jordan form an existential threat for Jordan?

7. Was there any shift in the Jordanian foreign policy because of changes in the regional environment?

8. Did the Jordanian foreign policy acquire new dimensions in the backdrop of changing international relations in West Asia?

1.4 Research Objectives:

This research aims to:

1. Define the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy.
2. Elucidate the history of Jordan-Syria relationship, and factors affecting their bilateral relationship.
3. Analyze the Syrian crisis and its implications for Jordan.
4. Examine the Jordanian policy towards Syrian crisis in particular.
5. Evaluate any changes in the Jordanian policy vis-à-vis the Syrian crisis.

1.5 Hypotheses:

The hypothesis of this study can be summarised in the following points:

1. The security implications of the Syrian crisis on Jordan posed an existential threat for Jordan.
2. There was a shift in the Jordanian foreign policy because of changing regional environment.
3. The Jordanian foreign policy acquired new dimensions in the backdrop of changing international relations in West Asia.

1.6 Research Methodology:

As the Syrian crisis, along with its implications on the neighboring countries, has been discussed both officially, academically, and via uncountable media sources, it would be incorrect to rely on a single source or data set. Data collection was focused on accumulating relevant information, needed to understand the causes and resulting consequences, with a minimum margin of error. Hence, the methods of data gathering comprised both primary and secondary sources, in order to appropriately answer the research questions and achieve its goals by testing the hypotheses. The primary sources of the study include Jordanian governmental formal reports, International Organization reports and Non-Governmental Organization reports, press releases, and newspaper articles written by prominent Jordanian, Arab, and international scholars and writers, in both English and Arabic languages. The researcher has utilized secondary data from related sources including books, articles, journals, and newspapers that highlight different perspectives and narratives about the issue. Web resources have been used extensively for this study; such data is inherently prone to weakness and uncertainty. In addition to that, the researcher may have been exposed to biases to some sources, however, there was a conscious effort to refer quality sources and provide authentic data. Data gathered from various sources was

compared to verify facts and to ensure that no misleading, fraud, biased, or weak information is used. The researcher has tried to obtain a comprehensive view of the history of Jordanian policy to understand the trends and traditions that help inform the Jordanian approach to the world, Syria in particular. The nature and scope of this research is qualitative, dealing mostly with accounts and appraisals of chronological historical events, and incorporating original analysis before offering conclusions. Therefore, existing literature is thoroughly reviewed in order to discover relevant information regarding the formulation of Jordanian internal and foreign policy towards the Syrian crisis. The variables that caused the supposed turn in the Jordanian foreign policy vis-à-vis the Syrian crisis have been analyzed in order to prove or disprove the study hypotheses. This methodology was the basis for adopting an objective analytical and descriptive route, to ascertain to what extent the Jordanian foreign policy is influenced by the impacts of the Syrian crisis and its actors' control on the policy-making process.

1.7 Research Structure:

The thesis is divided thematically into six chapters, preceded by an introduction, in order to simplify the complex nature of the research topic.

Chapter One: The purpose of this chapter is to present a theoretical and conceptual framework of the key concepts of the study. The chapter is divided into four parts: part one addresses theories of foreign policy such as the Realism theory, the Liberalism theory, the Marxism theory, and the Constructivism theory; part two presents the definition, concept, aims and objectives, characteristics, and the internal and external determinants of foreign policy; part three discusses differences between foreign policy and related items, such as international relations, diplomacy, international policy, and domestic policy, in addition to

foreign policy decision making and foreign policy orientations; part four addresses the crisis and crisis management, and other concepts such as national interests and national security.

Chapter Two: This chapter aims to delineate the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy. It addresses the internal determinants which include geographical location, population, social structure, public opinion, economy, natural resources, military power, and the political system of the country which is based on the 1952 Constitution of Jordan and consists of the executive authority, the legislative authority, and the judiciary authority. The chapter also addresses external determinants such as the international order, international organizations, world public opinion, Jordanian diplomatic relations, and alliances and treaties. It further elucidates the institutions of Jordanian foreign policy: the King of Jordan, the royal court, cabinet of Jordan, the ministry of foreign affairs and expatriates, the legislative authority, and the security institution. This is followed by a review of the fundamental principles, objectives, duties, and the process of decision-making of Jordan's foreign policy, along with the role of authorities in Jordan's foreign policy decision making, the types of the decision making and their stages. The chapter ends with a conclusion.

Chapter Three: This chapter addresses the Jordanian regional policy. The chapter is divided into two clear parts: part one traces the changes in the Jordanian foreign policy from the reign of King Hussein to King Abdullah II, including the current Jordanian regional policy, Jordan's foreign policy from King Hussein to King Abdullah II, Jordan's domestic concerns, external security interests, and how King Abdullah adopted a different external policy; part two addresses Jordan's regional policy with surrounding

Arab and non-Arab countries, in addition to major issues like the Palestinian-Israeli conflict, the Arab Spring revolutions, and terrorism. The chapter ends with a conclusion.

Chapter Four: This chapter focuses on the Syrian crisis and its implications for Jordan. It starts with the Syrian refugees' influx in Jordan from March 2011 till December 2016, and its political, economic, social, and security implications for the country. The economic implications included sectors of water, energy, environment, and transport, while the social implications included education, healthcare, shelter, justice, social protection, livelihood, food security, local governance, and municipal services. The security implications included Islamic terrorist groups' threats to Jordan, the terrorists among the Syrian refugees, Jordanian fighters joining the terrorists groups, the rise of crime in Jordan due to bad economic situation for the refugees and for the people of the hosting community, and Jordan being under the huge threat of ISIS. The positive implications of the Syrian crisis on Jordan have also been addressed, including the Syrian investments, how challenges are being converted into opportunities, and the economic opportunities with the help of international community. The chapter ends with a conclusion.

Chapter Five: This chapter illustrates the changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relationship from the Jordanian perspective. It starts with an overview of the current Jordanian foreign policy and its relation with "Jordan First" slogan. The chapter then moves on to the changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations, an evaluation of the Jordanian position on the Syrian crisis during 2011-2016, the regional and international influences on Jordan's position, the public opinion, internal stability. The chapter then delves into Jordanian policy towards Syrian asylum in Jordan including accommodation and housing requirements, the policy of refoulement, Jordan's economic policy in response

to the Syrian crisis, the components of Jordan Response Platforms to the Syrian crisis (JRPSC) and its purpose as well as the governing principles. Security policy has also been discussed covering Jordan's concerns on northern borders, confronting terrorism, the major motivations which encourage ISIS to look to Jordan from Jordan's perspective, Jordan's policy to combat terrorism internally and externally with legal, military, and security measures. The chapter moves on to Jordanian political position towards the Syrian peace process and the contradictions in the Jordanian political position towards the Syrian crisis. Finally, the chapter focuses on reasons for shift in Jordan's position, if any, causing changes in the Jordanian political discourse, accompanied by the political strategy and military strategy. The chapter is ended with a conclusion.

Chapter Six: This chapter synthesizes the conclusions from all aforementioned chapters, in order to explicitly answer the research questions. It begins with a summary, followed by the major findings, then addresses the hypotheses, and is ended with limitations of the study followed by recommendations for further research.

1.8 Literature Review:

1.8.1 Studies on the Impact of Syrian Refugees on Jordan:

1. Master thesis entitled *The Protection System of Refugees in Jordan: The Syrians as a Case Study*,⁷ by Hiba Saeda (2015) - The study aimed to interpret and analyze Jordan's policies on the treatment of Syrian Refugees, including Palestinian refugees who fled from Syria to Jordan. The researcher attempted to examine Jordan's legal, constitutional, and international obligations toward these refugees, in addition to studying its impact on

⁷ Saeda, H. (2015). *Manzumat Himayat Allajiiyn Fi Alardn: Alsuwriuwn Kahalatan Dirasiatan [The Protection System Of Refugees In Jordan: The Syrians As A Case Study]*. (Master Thesis). Birzeit University.

refugees, in terms of their rights and freedom. While Jordan perceives the presence of Syrian refugees on its ground to be a threat to its national security, this research argued that reinforcing refugees' legal and humanitarian rights in no way conflicts with the host country's national security, rather strengthens it. The researcher concluded that although Jordan's practices towards Syrian refugees residing in its territory are incoherent with its international obligations, still this should not be construed as a condemnation of Jordan, given that despite its deteriorating economic capabilities, it has taken on the burden of hosting Syrian refugees more than any other country in the region.

2. Report in the book entitled *Impact of Syrian refugees on the Jordanian labour market*,⁸ by Stave, S.E., & Hillesund, S. (2015) - This report revealed the main results of the household survey conducted between February and March 2014 in the Jordanian governorates of Amman, Irbid, and Mafraq, aimed at assessing the impact of the flow of huge numbers of Syrian refugees, on the labor market in these three regions. The findings of the survey were based on the information collected on current labor market situation, as well as changes in the same since the beginning of the flow of Syrian refugees to Jordan in March 2011.

The report concluded that there is 1) a loss of opportunities for employment of Jordanians in newly emerged low skilled jobs; 2) increased unemployment and competition for existing jobs; 3) future threat of crowding out in the labor market; and 4) an overall deterioration in working conditions, leading to increased work deficits in Jordan.

This study was pioneered by the International Labor Organization (ILO) and implemented and guided by the Fafu Institute for Applied International Studies, in cooperation with the

⁸ Stave, S. E., & Hillesund, S. (2015). *Impact Of Syrian Refugees On The Jordanian Labour Market*. ILO.

Jordanian Department of Statistics (DoS) which administered the fieldwork. The study was funded primarily by ILO, with additional contribution from the Norwegian Ministry of Foreign Affairs (Norway MFA) through the Royal Norwegian Embassy in Amman.

3. Paper entitled *Social protection and employment for Syrian refugees in Jordan*,⁹ by Kattaa, M., presented in the Conference on Networks for Regulating Decent Work, Geneva (2015) – The paper analyzed social protection and employment legal framework for the Syrian refugees in general, with specific focus on the level of implementation at national and regional levels. The paper concluded by providing policy recommendations. It indicated that despite not being allowed to work in Jordan legally, many of the Syrian refugees are in fact involved in unskilled labor and low-paying jobs which Jordanian citizens do not want to engage in. The illegal status, however, has forced them to take up provisional job opportunities, translating in a lack of work benefits such as insurance, meaning that these workers would not be able to claim compensation if they were exposed to trauma at work.

4. Thesis entitled *Jordan: Surprisingly Stable*,¹⁰ by Ådnegard, E. (2014) – The thesis was aimed at analyzing the stability in Jordan, and explaining the persistence of this stability in the face of the massive influx of Syrian refugees. The researcher found that conflict has generally been found to spread to the host country as a consequence of massive influx of refugees, and so the main objective of this research was to explain the absence of dispute

⁹ Kattaa, M. (2015). *Social Protection And Employment For Syrian Refugees In Jordan*. In Conference On Networks For Regulating Decent Work, Geneva. Amsterdam Institute For Advanced Labour Studies (AIAS). Netherlands org/uploads/submission/full_paper/20/social_protection_and_employment_the_case_of_syrian_refugees_in_jordan.pdf.

¹⁰ Ådnegard, E. (2014). *Jordan: Surprisingly Stable*. (Master Thesis). University Of Oslo.

in Jordan after hosting a surge of Syrian refugees accounting for nearly 10% of Jordan's population during 2011-2014.

The study concluded that three major factors kept Jordan away from instability - first, a majority of Jordanian population's demand for stability, driven by fear of landing in the exact situation as Syria; second, the political and economic aid from foreign countries and organizations; third, Jordan's readiness and its ability to control its borders and provide security. The study showed that all three factors were interconnected, as stability was being secured via monetary and military support, which helped Jordan endure the military expenses needed to avoid spillover from Syria, in addition to paying for the political support from citizens through subsidies and public sector employment in an effort to shield the citizens from the *de facto* deteriorating economic situation. This fragile constancy sustained in Jordan during 2011-2014, nevertheless there were no guarantees that this will continue.

5. Book entitled *Seven Syrians - War Accounts from Syrian Refugees*,¹¹ by Diego Cupolo (2013) – The book captures the stories and struggles of those caught in the middle of the armed conflict ravaging Syria. Refugees' lives form the core of this book, from the gap between the demands of the refugees and the politicians in EU, Turkey, Syria, and the international organizations, to the huge difference between dreams and reality.

The author has discussed crisis factors including growth, which was not uniform, and the youth unemployment rate, which by 2010 was still around 20%. In 2011, the discontent among Syrians in response to economic pressures, and the lack of political reforms, reflected the mood in other parts of Middle East and North Africa (MENA)—Tunisia, Egypt, Yemen, Bahrain, and Libya—where popular protests had already begun to topple governments on the back of significant democratization attempts. In March, the so-called

¹¹ Cupolo, Diego. (2013). *Seven Syrians: War Accounts From Syrian Refugees*. 8th House Publishing.

“Arab Spring” came to Syria, as children and teenagers in the city of Daraa were arrested for painting anti-government graffiti on the walls of a school. When demonstrators demanded release, the police cracked down resulting in the death of dozens of protesters. The president, facing calls for his resignation, promised changes, but then the government ordered troops into Daraa to subdue protests. Since then violence has escalated between Assad’s forces and rebel groups fighting to bring down the government. In July 2012, the Red Cross declared the conflict a civil war. Over the years, the stalemated conflict has become more violent and complex. The Free Syrian Army, led by generals who had defected from Assad’s army, does not fight government forces alone; al-Qaeda-linked jihadist fighters have also joined the effort. Meanwhile, the government is supported by Iran and Russia.

Looking at the region from Diego Cupolo's eye, photographs and first-hand accounts compiled in his work, remind us that it is civilians who suffer the brunt of the atrocities of war. In a series of humanizing portrayals, Diego Cupolo leads us into the lives of those fortunate enough to have survived the conflict that is decimating their homeland. Forced to flee their homes and families, these men, women, and children, are no different than ourselves and our neighbors, telling us of their struggles, triumphs, pains and fortitude, and of the monstrosity of war in a world where all seek the same security and opportunities.

6. Book entitled *Protecting Syrian Refugees: Laws, Policies, and Global Responsibility Sharing*,¹² by Bidinger, S., et al in Boston University Law Students (2014) – It shows how the Syrian civil war since 2011 forced approximately 2.7 million Syrians to leave their country, and double that number were estimated to have fled Syria by the end of 2014. The

¹² Bidinger, S., Lang, A., Hites, D., Kuzmova, Y., Nouredine, E., Akram, S., ... & Kistner, T. (2014). *Protecting Syrian Refugees: Laws, Policies, And Global Responsibility Sharing*. Boston University School Of Law, International Human Rights Clinic.

Syrian refugee crisis has brought tremendous challenges for the entire Middle East region, and this research attempted to map out the one aspect of the crisis that received very little attention: the laws and policies at international, regional, and domestic level, affecting the rights and status of the refugees flooding out of Syria.

Various statistics show that the countries currently hosting the vast majority of refugees' flow out of Syria are stretched to their limits in terms of resources. Jordan, Lebanon, and Egypt have huge refugee populations pre-dating the Syrian influx; many of these preexisting refugee groups live in desperate conditions, as host countries are unable to meet all assistance and protection needs of these refugees. Jordan is the fourth most water-stressed country in the world, with insufficient potable water for its own people, and so the authors talk about the impact of Syrian refugees on the water resources in Jordan. The book also studies impact on Lebanon and Egypt, which have extremely volatile political environments and unstable governments; how the Lebanese consider the Syrian conflict to have already crossed into their territory and fear another civil war as a direct consequence of the Syrian war if it is not resolved soon.

1.8.2 Research on Regional and International Environment, and the Jordanian

Foreign Policy and Position Regarding the Syrian Crisis:

1. Essay entitled "*Jordan first*": *Jordan's inter-Arab relations and foreign policy under King Abdullah II*,¹³ by Ryan, C.R. (2004) – The research essay discusses the important milestones of the Jordanian foreign policy before the Syrian crisis. It showed that Jordan

¹³ Ryan, C. R. (2004). "Jordan First": Jordan's Inter-Arab Relations And Foreign Policy Under King Abdullah II. *Arab Studies Quarterly*, 43-62.

under King Abdullah II placed immense emphasis on stabilizing and strengthening its inter-Arab and other regional relations. The Jordanian regime has succeeded in many respects in these actions, including establishing stronger ties with its traditional Western allies and major global economic institutions, despite the fact that external actions - from the Intifada, to 9-11, to U.S.-Iraqi aggression - threaten to tear down all that the new political system has achieved.

The Kingdom of Jordan, under the rule of King Abdullah II, solidified its alliances and support links with both the United States and the United Kingdom, while also reinforcing ties with the European Union as a whole and working closely with the IMF, World Bank, and World Trade Organization. King Abdullah II spent a great deal of time in key western capitals, lobbying not only for raising aid and assistance and restructuring debt repayments, but also to increase foreign investment in Jordan. Jordan's economic development plans and official statements continually emphasize the importance of foreign investment not just in Amman, but throughout the country; steps taken in this direction include establishment of a number of special economic zones.

2. Article entitled *Jordanian foreign policy and the Arab Spring*,¹⁴ by Ryan, C.R. (2014) – The article dealt with the Jordanian foreign policy towards the Arab Spring. The author talks about Jordan's relations with countries that encountered popular political movements. The Jordanian dilemma regarding Syria was certainly rooted deeply in the refugee crisis, but the regime was also worried about potential Islamist dominance in Damascus after the war, even suggesting that a Muslim Brotherhood axis of new Islamist-led regimes might

¹⁴ Ryan, C. R. (2014). Jordanian Foreign Policy And The Arab Spring. *Middle East Policy*, 21(1), 144-153.

be emerging in the area. The same government that had previously feared a Shia axis with Lebanon, Syria, Iraq, and Iran was now imagining a possible Sunni axis, but not one noticeable by Jordanian-style moderation. Jordanians also feared the rising Islamist militancy in Syria, and the return of Jordanian salafi jihadists once the war was over. The regime was concerned that the unrest will, in effect, be imported into the kingdom through either Islamist militancy or Baathist sleeper agents activated by a Damascus government angered by Jordan's alleged support for the rebels.

According to the article, the Jordanian government continually insisted that it was neutral in the Syrian civil war, though media reports suggested that Gulf countries — especially Saudi Arabia and Qatar — were purchasing arms for the Syrian rebels and funneling them into Syria from both Turkey and Jordan. Media reports in the West continually discussed CIA training of Syrian rebel fighters, in Jordan, despite Jordanian government denials. Syria's President Assad complained that Jordan was meddling in Syrian affairs, warning that this was playing with fire. The strain on Jordan's economy, social services, water resources, and political stability, was severe, particularly in the context of economic collapse in a deeply indebted country. Although, it is difficult to exaggerate the security challenges to Jordan, yet many liberal and progressive reformists fear that the regime's security concerns will ruin Jordan's own already limited and incomplete political reform process. Even so, as the regime and its opponents worried about the impacts of regional crises on their internal politics, the very tangible challenge of the refugee crisis continued to grow.

3. Thesis entitled *Syrian Crisis In the Light of Regional and International Power Balance*

Change 2011-2013,¹⁵ by Siham Abu Mustafa (2015) – The main concerns of the study are nature of the Syrian crisis, its causes, and its repercussions on the internal environment, as well as the extent of influence on international and regional environments. The study starts off with a major question reflected in the title and content of the study, that is, why has the Syrian crisis turned into a complex international one? And what repercussions would it have for the future of international and regional alliances and balances. The study focuses on the main hypothesis that the multiplicity of regional and international parties may lead to further convolution of the crisis. In addition to that, the existing alternatives are incapable of resolving the crisis; it has been emphasized that the Syrian crisis cannot be settled through the strategic military option. The study concluded that a number of national and international determinants are complicating and prolonging the Syrian crisis. The crisis, since its inception, has also revealed the existence of a state of laxity and weakness in the regional Arab regime after its inability to contain and solve this crisis, which turned into an international crisis. This has resulted in changes in the position and role of players in the international and regional arena. Consequently, the United States is no longer the only superpower, as new powers have emerged, trying to secure their position beside the United States.

4. Study entitled *The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis of Neighboring Countries' Stances*,¹⁶ by Satik, N. and Mahmud, K. (2013) – The study deals with the stances of neighboring

¹⁵ Abu Mustafa, F. S. Siham. (2015). *Al'azmat Alsuwriat Fi Zili Tahul Altawazunat Al'iiqlimiat Walduwaliat 2013-2015 [The Syrian Crisis In The Light Of Regional And International Power Balance Change 2011-2013]*. (Master Thesis). Al Azhar University.

¹⁶ Satik, N., & Mahmud, K. (2013). *The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis Of Neighboring Countries' Stances*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Studies.P: 24.

countries on the Syrian crisis, Jordan being one of them. The authors say that since the outbreak of the Syrian revolution, Jordanian diplomacy has been characterized by ambiguity, and endless debate on Syria. The monarchy continues to publicly favor a political solution as the best option to ending the crisis, and refrains from promoting any military solution to the same.

They added that early in their tenure, Jordanian King Abdullah II and Syrian President Bashar al-Assad inherited a legacy of tense relations between the two countries, though they were able to navigate through these difficult relations owing to their mutual interests. Political tensions between the two countries increased in 2004 when King Abdullah II warned of the formation of an Iranian-led “Shiite crescent” in the Arab Levant, including Syria. One could claim that the provincial split between the two axes, the moderation and the resistance, was the main cause behind Syrian-Jordanian political relationship since the American invasion of Iraq in 2003. However, this does not deny the existence of cooperation on economic level and on trans-border security issues.

The authors have tried to present and analyze the factors that affected the Jordanian foreign policy towards Syrian crisis including regional and international factors, specifically the nature of Jordanian-US relations, in addition to its local conditions, vital interests, and the need to preserve the interests of its people and its internal stability.

1.8.3 Research on the Impact of Terrorism and Security Threats on Jordan:

1. Article entitled *Jordan and the New Front in the Fight Against ISIS*,¹⁷ by Rothe, M.C. (2015) – The article talks about the international coalition led by USA against the ISIS,

¹⁷ Rothe, M. C. (2015). Jordan And The New Front In The Fight Against ISIS. *International Institute For Counter-Terrorism*. pp: 45.

and how Jordan became more and more involved in the combat against ISIS. This involvement increased only after the ISIS released a video showing the brutal immolation of a Jordanian pilot, which prompted a strong response from King Abdullah II, who ordered execution of two convicted terrorists and carried out a series of air raids in Syria in the days following the release of the video. However, Jordan's people do not appear to share their king's strong desire for revenge.

The author also elucidates how Jordan's involvement in the U.S. led coalition against the ISIS, has been a subject of heavy criticism in the country, as groups like the Muslim Brotherhood and other members of the Jordanian parliament have spoken out opposing military intervention. By getting Jordan to become involved in the apparently endless Syrian civil war, the ISIS hopes to isolate the Hashemite Monarchy from its largely anti-interventionist citizens. ISIS barely poses a direct threat to Jordan's military, but it can strengthen its dominion in the kingdom by taking advantage of Jordan's fragile economy and national instability. Indeed, if Jordan wants to efficiently confront ISIS, the monarchy will need to stress on social and economic reforms, over military involvement.

2. Article entitled *Terrorism in Jordan: Politics and the Real Target Audience*,¹⁸ by Worman, J.G., and Gray, D.H. (2012) – The article traces the background of terrorism in Jordan. The authors through their analysis found that throughout the forty-year period from 1970 to 2010, Jordanian interests were, by far, always the primary target of terrorists. Only during 2000-2006 terror events did United States' interests come under attack, and still never as the sole interest of any terrorist organization. The authors state that in all the attacks that might have been considered directed toward US interests, only one American

¹⁸ Worman, J. G., & Gray, D. H. (2012). Terrorism In Jordan: Politics And The Real Target Audience. *Global Security Studies*, 3(3), 94-112.

diplomat fell victim, and that no physical property, including the US naval assets, was damaged.

The Global Jihad website highlights Laurence Foley's death on 28 October 2002, as having been orchestrated by al-Zarqawi, and all evidence demonstrates that he was not a random target of opportunity, but a targeted political attack by al-Zarqawi based on support to the Jordanian government. Since the US and Jordan are close allies as are Israel and Jordan, it is easy to deduce that terrorist organizations will always consider all three countries as potential targets; however, this understanding is blatantly false, as the facts of this paper outline.

3. Paper entitled *Fighting Passions: A Developmental Examination of the Salafi Jihadi Movement in Jordan and the Roots of Extremism*,¹⁹ by Ragland, R. (2005) – The writer focuses on the roots of Islamic fundamentalism, and outline the development of the Salafi Jihadi movement in the Kingdom of Jordan through political, economic, cultural, religious, psychological, and ideological factors. The author also discusses that while the current approach to understanding violent Islamist groups provides insight on their structure, strategies, and tactics, it does little to address the crucial issue of why and how they exist, nor does it answer the question of who, in fact, “they” are. Between the jihadists and the free world is a facing-off of ideologies, a clash of civilizations, and a socio-economic crisis countered only by the best listener; the eventual win of one, or consolidation of both, will ultimately be validated and confirmed by the masses purely because they constitute society itself. The paper states that eventually, the goal of both sides is the founding of a certain

¹⁹ Ragland, R. (2005). *Fighting Passions: A Developmental Examination Of The Salafi Jihadi Movement In Jordan And The Roots Of Extremism*. *SIT Graduate Institute*. pp: 52.

way of life, the presence of a social circumstance acceptable to each correspondingly, and that if human lives are really the concern, the only legitimate approach is one in which the circumstances essential to make such a choice exist in the understanding of the beholder. The author concludes that extremism, in any form, is not a security problem, it is a human one.

4. Article entitled *The Global Terrorism between Dialectic Concept and Opposite Means*,²⁰ by Ghazi Ismail Rababa'a (2012) – The article presents the major dimensions related with terrorism, as it shows that terrorism is not limited to a certain class or a certain religion, meaning that it has no religion and is not limited to the military forces, but there are other dangers such as intellectual terrorism. Terrifying people is considered an introduction to the terrorism practiced by some states; the Islamic world must become more alert and more serious in facing the Western attack against Islam, represented in accusing Islam with terrorism.

The author says that preventing and fighting intellectual terrorism, directed in a methodological way towards or against Islam and the Arab World, should be a prime concern, and recommends orchestrating an international conference to define the meaning of terrorism to avoid mixing its definition with the definition of resistance, as defining the concept will help settle on the places of its existence, and then fighting and eliminating it to achieve international peace and security.

5. Paper entitled *Jordan stands at the front line of combating terrorism*,²¹ by Ayasrah, A. (2009) – The paper begins by providing a historical background to terrorism and its

²⁰ Rababa'a, G. Ismail. (2012). The Global Terrorism Between Dialectic Concept And Opposite Means. *International Journal Of Humanities And Social Science*. Vol. 2 No. 24, (149-161).

²¹ Ayasrah, A. (2009). Jordan Stands At The Front Line Of Combating Terrorism. *Army War Coll Carlisle Barracks Pa*. 32.

characteristics: terrorism does not respect boundaries, sovereignty or religion; this is one of the most heinous crimes against humanity. The author then moves to 9/11 attacks which were a watershed, with far-reaching global implications, and when international terrorism, in all its forms and manifestations, was seen more clearly as a global threat.

The author offers that Jordan has countered various types of terrorism through its history, and its skills may offer significant insights into the greatest ways to combat terrorism. As a member of the campaign of international powers against terrorism, Jordan plays an important part in the Global War on terror, led by the United States.

This paper inspects the reasons for terrorism, the present terrorist danger levels, and the various courses of fighting terrorism. While it centers on Jordan's policy and strategy for battling terrorism, including legal, political, and security actions, it also analyzes the implications for the area and recommends short- and long-term procedures for maintaining peace. A key assumption is that Jordan has developed advanced methods to face terrorism and is an important element in continuing the fight against terrorism.

1.8.4 Research Focused on the Roots of the Syrian Crisis:

1. The report entitled *The Syrian Crisis: Roots & Economical and Social Consequences*,²² by Naser, R., Mahshi, Z., and Abu Ismael, K. (2013) – The book discusses the economic problem behind the Syrian crisis, and the human, social, and institutional factors that led to its rise. It also focuses on the demographical changes and economic consequences of refugee movement internally and externally, and governmental response to the same.

²² Naser, R. Etl. (2013) *Al'azmat Alsuwriat: Aljudhur Walathar Alaiqtisadiat Walaijtimaeia*. [The Syrian Crisis: Roots & Economical And Social Consequences]. Syrian Center For Policy Research..

The value of this work lies in that it shows how Syria, the peaceful and secular country, is getting destroyed: half the population is displaced, nearly one-fifth of its people are refugees abroad, an estimated 1% of Syrians have died, and over half the population is in desperate need of humanitarian assistance. Whatever may be the reasons for the crisis, whoever may be the responsible, the immediate need is to find a way to end the violence; this is going to be an enormous task, given that there are groups of people supported externally, that are outside the jurisdiction of international law.

2. Book entitled *Factors of Civil Peace and Civil Conflict in Syria*²³ (2013) – The book tries to detect the factors of peace in the Syrian society during the Syrian crisis: the solutions that refugees seek, political reforms, social justice, and human rights, in addition to aid solidarity, people's unity, forming of civil government, and refugees' return home, etc. It also points out the civil conflict factors like continuation of refugees' crisis in the neighboring countries, revenge, and the absence of democracy.

The book points out that the Syrian revolution is an attempt to impose a fundamental change in all aspects of life- political, social, and economical. As with any military conflict, the Syrian crisis is producing all forms of human right violations and bloodshed brought on by a clash of various new thoughts and ideologies. In the face of this crisis, terrorist groups are spread all over Syria and violence is widespread, with even official militaries practicing violence. The Arab Spring scenarios had had a similar effect on Syria, forcing its people to flee, and now settling the refugees either within Syria or outside in regional countries like Turkey, Lebanon, and Jordan, poses a big dilemma. The Palestinian refugees

²³ Amer, Nariman, et Al, (2013). *Eawamil Alsilm Al'ahlii Warunb Al'ahli Fi Suria [Factors Of Civil Peace And Civil Conflict In Syria]*. Center Of Civil Society And Democracy In Syria.

had been settled in Jordan and they became Jordanians with full civil rights. The big question is: Is the same going to happen again for the Syrians in Turkey, Lebanon, and Jordan? Especially, given the fact that refugees are a source of constant inconvenience for hosting countries, not in the least because some of them might have relations with perpetrators of the crisis.

Even within Syria, the new temporary lands used for housing will cost the government a lot of money to provide even basic services, which is another hurdle to growth. The book underlines how this crisis and the concomitant loss of education for a whole generation can be a factor for instability in the future. People will be left stuck in the loop of poverty and ignorance, inciting a new cycle of violence. The authors understand that this issue has to take priority in the agenda of the government in Syria.

The authors are a group of researchers working in various Syrian universities and research centers, and are specialized in the social issues of the Arab cities. They express several points of views about the factors of the crisis and suggest solutions through scenarios.

1.8.5 Comments on the Literature Review:

Unfortunately, majority of prior researches, including books, dissertations, articles, and reports, revolved around components of the Syrian crisis. The studies on Jordan and the Syrian crisis included in this literature review can be categorized as:

- a) Recent studies and researches examining the impact of Syrian refugees' influx on Jordan, in the context of other affected countries, and the legal situations and protection of Syrian refugees in Jordan.
- b) Prior researches discussing the regional and international environment, Jordan's relations with neighboring countries, Jordanian attitude towards the Syrian crisis, and other related issues such as the Arab Spring.

- c) Previous researches concerning the security and terrorism threats on Jordan.
- d) Research focused on the roots of the Syrian conflict.

It is thus evident that few researches focus on the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis. Even so, a number of questions in this context remain unanswered because the authors took other directions of research, but it is important to address these questions. The literature discussed in this thesis, both Arabic and English, have dealt with several issues related to the Syrian crisis and its impact on Jordan, and have helped gain a clear view of the subject, in addition to revealing the gaps and shortcomings of previous researches. Most importantly, this review increases the challenges for the researcher, to produce a more comprehensive work with correct results and answer naturally arising questions appropriately.

A decorative graphic consisting of a vertical green line and a horizontal green line intersecting at a point. The vertical line is on the left, and the horizontal line is in the middle. The text is positioned to the right of the vertical line and above and below the horizontal line.

Chapter One

Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

Chapter One: Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

The Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis can be researched from two different perspectives: 1) the foreign policy domain directed to the Syrian crisis as a whole, with all its components; 2) the domain of the Syrian crisis implications for Jordan, caused by Syrian refugees who fled to Jordan, in addition to other consequences. The Jordanian government has to handle both external and domestic policies regarding the Syrian crisis, along with containing its impacts domestically in two respects- the Syrian refugees' needs in Jordan, and the affected vulnerable hosting communities in the country. The purpose of this chapter is to present a theoretical and conceptual framework to the key concepts discussed in this study.

2.1 Part One: Theories of Foreign Policy

As a result of great and rapid developments in the international political system during the last century, especially after the Cold War, foreign policy has undergone major changes and developments at various levels of knowledge and methodology.¹ The various theories of foreign policy reflect the progress made in foreign policy as a knowledge field, with its subject, methods, and the laws that govern it.

Foreign policy theories have continuously tried to explain the changes in the course of a country's behavior toward other states. While political science scholars kept trying to provide an integrated and acceptable theoretical framework for understanding the behavior of states, they could not agree on a unified approach to identify the specific and explanatory variables of state behavior.

¹ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhah Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p:2.

Thus the inception of different foreign policy theories, which aim to analyze how states behave towards other states, by studying the main actors and active forces; the main actor being the state, an integral unit in the analysis of foreign policy, and the active forces being the tools that the state possesses and has the choice to use, in order to achieve its external goals. There are three levels to analyzing foreign policy:²

1. Structure of the International System: The structure of the international system refers to the great powers that influence the behavior of states through a number of units such as multinational companies, international organizations, and international relations between states, and the role of law at the level of the international system.

2. State Structure: State structure means the nature of the political system, democracy vs. dictatorship. It also includes the behavior of countries outside their territory and the basic environment for decision-making at homeland, both of which are greatly affected by the economic situation at homeland.

3. Structure of Individuals: It refers to the personality of the decision-maker, such as aggressive vs. peaceful, religious vs. non-religious, as well as the perception and the natural psychological environment of the decision-maker.

2.1.1 The Realism Theory:

The Realism theory, which gained momentum during World War II, believes that there are no universal principles to guide what foreign policy should be adopted by a state, instead it calls for the adoption of a position that primarily focuses on self-interests of the state, and if necessary, abandon the interests of other countries in doing so.³

² Abdul Salam, Ikhlef. (2010). *Levels Of Foreign Policy Analysis*. Constantine University, Algeria. p: 22.

³ Mcglinchey, S. (2017) *International Relations*. Bristol: E-International Relations. p: 48.

Realism is based on the principle of self-interest, and pursuit of benefits associated with power and authority. This theory deals with politics as a completely separate aspect from economics, ethics, or religion, and it proclaims that the motives that drive political actions, must be centered on the concept of power. The proponents of realism believe that it is possible to anticipate the moves that politicians may make in the future, based on steps taken by them in the past and the present. Thus, realism calls for understanding, i.e., finding facts through the application of reason and thought rather than emotion,⁴ and this school of thought is usually linked to the use of force and does not condemn aggression against nations, including wars between certain states. From realistic point of view wars may be viewed as natural, even required, to protect the personal interests of the state⁵. Realists believe that the global system is a game that does not make any profit, because the profits achieved by a country are equivalent to the losses suffered by others.

2.1.2 The Liberalism Theory:

Liberalism opposes the thesis of Realism. The Liberalism theory calls for application of foreign policy in accordance with the ideal global objectives. The Liberalism theory, rooted in the ideology of Woodrow Wilson and the foundation of the League of Nations after the First World War, is linked to the concept of universality and a liberal political philosophy. Liberals tend to view the global system as a game in which everyone plays and wins (profit for all), especially through economic means (neo-liberalism) or through international organizations and cooperation (traditional liberalism).

⁴ Aref, Naser. (1998). *Comparative Policy Theories And Methodology Study Of Arab Political Systems*. 1st Edition, Virginia: University Of Islamic And Social Sciences. p: 29.

⁵ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat* [The Foreign Policy]. Gaza: The Islamic University. pp:45-46.

The main principles of liberalism for international relations are:

- the national states are important but they are not the only ones, and in some cases they are not actors in external relations;⁶
- there may exist a special institution, exercising control over the sovereignty of national states;
- chaos is, if possible, eliminated, harmonized, calmed, and updated;
- the actions of the state on the international scene are not confined to the logic of maximizing national interests, but also to the common values recognized by all states;
- government is not the only institution responsible for foreign affairs, and their understanding and implementation, though it can understand the processes of international relations and even have a partial impact on them;⁷
- the security of the state against possible external fears is the cumulative goal of society, and the direct way to achieving it, is the democratization of all countries of the world;
- the nature of the state and of mankind is constantly changing, and improving the growth of freedom and the strength of democratization, increased tolerance, and civic responsibility;
- the final step is the identification of normative and ideological motives and values as well as objective factors and mechanisms, which have a material and rational basis.

⁶ Wadi, Abdul Hakeem. (2013, March 25). *Mulakhis Hawl Alnazariat Fi Alealaqat Alduwalia* [Principals Of Theories In International Relations]. Rachel Corrie Center. Palestine.

⁷ Ibid. pp: 5-6.

2.1.3 The Marxism Theory:

The philosophy of Marxism adopts materialism in its analysis of international relations and foreign policy. It looks at the whole issue as class struggle. Marxism holds that conflicts in society and between states are due to the desire of the controllers of elements of production to dominate the labor force and the products of economic process, and to deprive the lower classes of their rights. It aims to liberate workers from exploitation by the royal classes (capitalism), which control all elements of production.⁸

By focusing on the economic and material aspects, the Marxist view of the causes of conflict excludes several factors that contribute to global conflicts; for example, the role of intellectual ideology and religion in international relations or in community relations within a single state, has been overlooked by the materialism perspective.⁹

Marxist theory is similar to realism in that they both focus on the analysis of the structure of international system, but each differs in its view within that structure.¹⁰ While realism emerges from the perspective of balance of power, Marxism takes the economic perspective of who owns and who doesn't, with the idea that rich countries dominate poor countries, thus hindering their growth and prosperity.

2.1.4 The Constructivism Theory:

Constructivism focuses on the influence of ideas. Instead of focusing on power politics, constructivists believe that international relations are formed by ongoing social interactions which shape interests and identities of actors. Constructivism scholars lay great emphasis

⁸ Na'na, Abdulqader. (2006) *Alruwyat Almariksiat Lilealaqat Alduwaliat Alrrahina* [The Marxism Vision To Current International Relations]. Al-Sharq's Future Center. London. p: 3.

⁹ Ibid. p: 5.

¹⁰ Ibid. p: 4.

on discourse in society, because discourse reflects and forms beliefs and interests, at the same time establishing acceptable behaviors. Therefore, constructivism is concerned mainly with change or transformation. This approach has largely replaced Marxism as the radical approach to international affairs.¹¹

The end of the Cold War contributed to validating constructivism, as realism and liberalism failed to not only anticipate this event but also found it difficult to explain. Constructivists were able to explain it, especially with respect to Mikhail Gorbachev's revolution in Soviet foreign policy by embracing new ideas such as collective security.

From constructivism point of view, the central issue in the post-cold-war world is how different groups perceive their identities and interests. Although constructivism analysis does not rule out the variable of power, it is primarily based on how ideas and identities emerge and how they interact with each other to shape the way states view and react to different situations.

Constructivism theories do not give us a unified view of their expectations on any of the issues at conceptual level. Alexander Wundt believes that the realistic perception of chaos does not give us an adequate explanation regarding the causes of international conflicts. The question is how to understand this chaos? According to Wundt, 'chaos is what states have done.'¹²

Another trend in constructivism focuses on the future of states, and considers that transnational communication and the sharing of civic values have undermined traditional national loyalties and created new forms of political associations. Some constructivism

¹¹ Walt, S. M. (1998). *International Relations: One World, Many Theories*. *Foreign Policy*. p: 40.

¹² *Ibid.* p: 41.

scholars also believe that control and regulations through international law, have eroded the traditional concepts of sovereignty, as well as the legitimate purposes on which states exercise their powers. However, the common theme among all trends is the ability of discourse to shape how actors determine their identity and interests and as a result modify their behavior.

2.2 Part Two: Foreign Policy

This part tries to work on three assumptions regarding foreign policy: 1) the more accurate the concept of foreign policy, the more comprehensive is the interpretation that leads to the reality of international policy; 2) foreign policy does not accept multi-orientations; 3) the power of foreign policy is not subject to the nature of its determinants. The methodologies used in this chapter are a combination of descriptive methodology and a comparative approach on the basis of theories of international relations.

2.2.1 Foreign Policy Definition:

The scholars of political science have not agreed on a single definition of foreign policy, and disagree depending on the bases used to build their definitions.

According to Dr. Mohammed Salim Al-Said, “foreign policy is the declared program of work which had been chosen by the official representatives in the international unit from a group of possible programmed alternatives in order to achieve specific goals in the surrounding environment.”¹³ This definition is a precise definition, which includes the following dimensions: unit, official, public, optional, objective, external, and

¹³ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 7.

programmatic, which are the distinguishing characteristics of foreign policy. But, the definition characterizes foreign policy as a program made in the absence of internal and external environments. This might lead to misunderstanding of foreign policy, because foreign policy is not only a program with specific goals, but also a mixture of several behaviors of the decision maker in the state, which are the result of interaction with both internal and external environments.

George Modelski defined foreign policy as “the system of activities evolved by communities for changing the behavior of other states and for adjusting their own activities to the international environment.”¹⁴ In his definition, Modelski focuses only on variation in the current performance of states, as the main aim of foreign policy. Actually, foreign policy incorporates both, changing the present behavior as well as continuing with behaviors from different times.¹⁵

Padelford and Lincoln stated that, “foreign policy is the key element in the process by which a state translates its broadly conceived goals and interests into concrete courses of action to attain these objectives and pressure its interests.”¹⁶ They explained two purposes of foreign policy, i.e., achieving its broadly considered goals, and emphasizing the national interests.

In the words of Charles Herman, foreign policy “consists of those distinguished official behaviors by the official decision-makers in the government or their representatives, which are meant to influence the behavior of external international units.”¹⁷

¹⁴ Modelski, George (1962). *A Theory Of Foreign Policy*. London: Pall Mall Press. pp.6-7.

¹⁵ Kumār, M. (1972). *Theoretical Aspects Of International Politics*. Shiva Lal Agarwala. pp:256.

¹⁶ Padelford, N. J., Lincoln, G. A., & Olvey, L. D. (1976). *The Dynamics Of International Politics*. Macmillan Publishing Company. p. 197.

¹⁷ Herman, Charles, (1982). *Policy Classification: A Key To The Comparative Study. Foreign Policy. New York: Free Press. p:22.*

The disparity in the definitions of foreign policy in various political literature impedes reliance on a particular definition.

2.2.2 The Concept of Foreign Policy:

Foreign policy is considered one of the most important research subjects in the field of international relations. Foreign policy, when addressed fully, helps understand the relations between nations. Foreign policy was separated from International Relations field, after the behavioral revolution, and in the beginning of the 60s, as the number of international units increased the phenomenon of foreign policy was clearly developed.¹⁸

Studying foreign policy became essential to understand the external orientations of countries and to explain the reasons behind formulating foreign policy in different paradigms in the international context.¹⁹ The study of foreign policy makes it possible to discover national strategies of the countries against the external environments, whether these countries are superpowers or regional ones, and determine to what extent this guides them towards more powerful roles.

Foreign policy is a reflection of the political system of any country, based on which the international community treats the country negatively or positively. The foreign policy is closely associated with international relations, which is characterized by great complexity and interdependence. There have been many serious developments that have changed the international system,²⁰ including an increase in the number of member states after the elimination of colonialism. Their emergence led to a change in the international political

¹⁸ Alnuaimi, Ahmad. (2001). *Alsiyasat Alkharijia [The Foreign Policy]*. Amman, Jordan: Zahran Publications. p: 19.

¹⁹ Ibid. p: 20.

²⁰ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijia: Drrasat Fi Almafahim, Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]*. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p: 3.

equation, as these new political units had visible influence on decisions within the system controlling the trends of international politics.

The foreign policy of a country is understood as its interaction relations with any foreign partner, whether it is a country, a nation, an organization, a company, an individual or a group of people, in the times of peace and war. It means “a government's policy on dealing with other countries,”²¹ including its components. The foreign policies of all of the world’s countries, in effect produce what is known as international relations. The Encyclopedia Britannica describes foreign policy as ‘general objectives that guide the activities and relationships of one state in its interactions with other states.’ The development of foreign policy is influenced by domestic considerations, policies and behaviors of other states, and plans to advance specific geopolitical designs. Even though, Leopold von Ranke emphasized on the pre-eminence of geography and external threats in shaping foreign policy, subsequent writers emphasized domestic factors. Diplomacy is the tool of foreign policy, and war, alliances, and international trade may all be manifestations of it.^{22,23}

2.2.3 Aims and Objectives of Foreign Policy:

The basic objectives of foreign policy are:

1. To preserve the independence, sovereignty, and national security of the state, and pursue the highest national interests. National interest is one of the most important goals of foreign policy. However, states also seek alliances for the protection and

²¹ Cambridge Dictionary (2016). Foreign Policy. Retrieved from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/foreign-policy>.

²² Encyclopedia Britannica Online. (2016). Foreign-Policy .Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/foreign-policy>.

²³ Jonsson, C., & Hall, M. (2005). *Essence Of Diplomacy*. Palgrave Macmillan. p: 17.

promotion of common interest; diplomatic negotiations are a basic component of foreign policy.²⁴

2. To establish good relations with members of the international community through adoption of policy of conflict or co-operation towards them with a view to promote its own interests including economic, political, security, social, etc.
3. To increase the power of the state through growth of the economy. Economic development is one of the most important objectives of foreign policy, as the status of a state in international sphere is determined by the economic condition of the state. Economic development not only affects economic relations, but also social, political, and cultural relations in the society.²⁵
4. To facilitate dissemination of ideology and culture, i.e., the enhancement of the influence of the state either by expanding its area of influence or reducing the other states to a position of dependency (USA and USSR followed this policy during the Cold War era). Enhancing of power is an important consideration while developing foreign policy as power in this modern period is the cornerstone of international influence.²⁶
5. To promote the foundations of regional and international peace in international forums and organizations. This goal is often a public objective for all states.

²⁴ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. pp: 9-10.

²⁵ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat* [The Foreign Policy]. Gaza: The Islamic University. pp: 59-60.

²⁶ Ghosh, Peu. (2016). *International Relations*. Fourth Edition, PHI Learning Private Limited. Delhi. pp: 100-101.

2.2.4 Characteristics of Foreign Policy:

1. External character: This means that foreign policy is directed at the external environment, while being created within the internal institutions of the state. The implementation is outward, i.e., in the external/international environment.²⁷ The external environment is the framework in which these behaviors are tested and wherein the established foreign policy objectives are achieved.
2. Formality: Formality means that foreign policy is formed by an official body in the state, and no unofficial body can have a say in the direction of foreign policy. Although individuals, personalities, and informal institutions have visions and views about the objectives and interactions of foreign policy, and information and facts can contribute to reinforcing these objectives, they are not formal in the sense that they do not control how the state officially reacts to external issues.²⁸

The official foreign policy is drafted by the executive authority, which is often represented by the Head of State, the Prime Minister, the Minister for Foreign Affairs, the Minister of Defense, and other persons representing the official institutions of the state. Foreign policy is not limited to countries as conventional international units, it also extends to modern international units such as international organizations or regional political parties.

3. The character of optional: This means that foreign policy programs and decisions are selected from several proposed alternatives: any international position does not require a single inevitable reaction from the concerned state and that the state possesses a range of options and possible alternatives to choose one according to its objectives and

²⁷ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat* [The Foreign Policy]. Gaza: The Islamic University. p: 27.

²⁸ Ibid. p: 29.

national interest.²⁹ Foreign policy is made by those who are authorized to exercise any policy from the available alternatives. In addition, to a range of alternative policies to choose from, the policy makers also have the flexibility to make changes in the foreign policy when circumstances or contexts change.

4. The unilateral nature: This means that foreign policy includes programs and strategies adopted by one international unit towards other international units. This dimension distinguishes foreign policy from international relations. International relations assume interaction, i.e., action and reaction between international units.³⁰
5. The nature of the objectives: This indicates that any foreign policy must be directed towards achieving the goals planned by the decision makers, and all available resources are mobilized to achieve those goals.³¹ Based on this, foreign policy can't be considered just a reaction to the external environment, instead it is a conscious process that seeks to influence the external environment to enable the state to be an effective actor in the international system or to achieve and maintain national interests at the very least.

2.2.5 Determinants of Foreign Policy

The determinants of foreign policy are those factors that affect in one way or another the components and direction of a country's foreign policy. It also means the study of foreign policy as a dependent variable based on a set of independent variables dictated by the dynamics of the internal and external environments.

²⁹ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p: 4.

³⁰ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 75.

³¹ Ibid. p: 76.

2.2.5.1 The Internal Determinants:

Internal determinants fall within the state's territory and are linked to its structural composition, through which the state can draw and determine the objectives and directions of its foreign policy.³²

Internal determinants include geographical determinants, population determinants, societal determinants, political determinants, and military determinants.

1. Geographical Determinants: These include geographical location, area, terrain, and climate, which are essential elements in geopolitics of the state. These factors directly affect the dynamics of foreign policy by determining the state's ability to implement its foreign policy and thus govern its international status.³³ Geographical location can provide strategic advantage to the state, enabling it to play a significant regional or even international role, and can contribute to building the power of the state.

The geographical location of Turkey, for example, has made it a significant regional player country, as it interacts with several regional circles such as the Middle East, the Caucasus, the European Union, and Central Asia. In contrast, geographically closed countries are not allowed an active role in the international system.

Given their importance in developing international strategy, geographical factors can affect foreign policy directly as well as indirectly, by determining the elements of power of the state which in turn determine its ability to implement its foreign policy.

³² Kurbalija, J. (Ed.). (1998). *Modern Diplomacy*. Mediterranean Academy Of Diplomatic Studies, University Of Malta. p: 64.

³³ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p: 8.

However, strategic geographical location alone is not enough to determine an effective foreign policy.³⁴

- 2. Population Determinants:** The human factor affects the determination of foreign policy as an important element in building a military force capable of achieving the goals of policy during peace and war. It is also an important factor for the supply of labor, both inside and outside the country. However, this is not a fixed measure of the power of the state militarily or economically. There are countries, such as Indonesia, that may have a large population but may not be the basis of military force in the face of technological development.³⁵ On the other hand, population explosion can be a burden on the state and disrupt the track of its economic development, especially when the rate of population growth is much higher than the rate of economic growth which must then rely on external debt forcing the state into international commitments that may affect its foreign policy.
- 3. Economic Determinants:** The more powerful and strong the economy of a country, the more its ability to achieve its external objectives. Natural resources are important sources of power for the state; they provide a state with varying degrees of energy sources, minerals, and food resources that contribute to its economic independence and enable it to play an active role in its regional and international environment, as an economic force capable of taking international positions in line with its foreign policy orientations.³⁶ The clearest example in this regard is Germany, which is a great economic power; it has succeeded in influencing the internal or external policy of the

³⁴ *Ibid.* p: 9.

³⁵ Al-Kafarneh, Ahmad. (2009) *Aleawamil Almuatharat Fi Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Alsiyasat Alkharijiati* [The Factors Affecting Decision Making Of Foreign Policy]. *International Studies Journal*. Vol. 42. 13-41. p: 30.

³⁶ *Ibid.* p: 31.

European Union countries and in taking positions that contradict the positions of other powerful states like the US.

- 4. Military Determinants:** Military factor is a major indicator of a state's power and is considered an effective tool for achieving its foreign objectives. A state's possession of huge arsenal, sophisticated military technology required to acquire various smart and destructive weapons, and highly efficient military leaders, enables it to achieve its policy objectives either through intimidation or war.³⁷

In general and despite the various definitions of foreign policy, it does not go beyond the state's external activities targeted at achieving long and short term objectives. Foreign policy is characterized by the formality of governments, and is controlled by several orientations and directions, whether regional or global. In addition to that, the determinants of foreign policy have the final say in planning and implementation of a foreign policy.

2.2.5.2 The External Determinants:

- 1. International Regimes and Organizations:** Changes in the form and nature of the international public order affect the foreign policy of the state as one of the constituent units of this system. States under a multipolar system have greater freedom of movement. Smaller countries have a greater ability to maneuver abroad by waving to join a particular alliance, or withdraw from the organization.³⁸

The structure of the international system has become an important factor in influencing the decisions of foreign policy and the extent of its implementation. This importance

³⁷ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat* [The Foreign Policy]. Gaza: The Islamic University. p: 68.

³⁸ Ghosh, Peu. (2016). *International Relations*. Fourth Edition, PHI Learning Private Limited. Delhi. p: 107.

has emerged in contemporary times, as a result of the following:³⁹

- a. The presence of international organizations such as the United Nations, human rights organizations, and civil society organizations.
 - b. Legal relations between states, according to international law. Many political decisions have become international in nature based on their impact on the outside world as a result of positive and negative relations between states.
 - c. Economic and military blocks affect foreign policy decision-making of the member states, as these policies reflect the objectives, methods, and ideas of the blocks.
- 2. World Public Opinion:** Internal public opinion is an essential determinant of the foreign affairs of a state. Even so, it is important to take into consideration the world public opinion as it shows the way other states think. Issues of environment and human rights can now be spread all over the world in a matter of minutes, especially with the emergence of new technologies like social media channels.⁴⁰
- 3. Foreign Policies of Other States:** The external environment of a state consists of foreign policies of other states, thus its own foreign policy takes into consideration the existence of the policies of other states making it a three dimensional process: 1) implementing planned external strategies to achieve certain goals; 2) cooperating with other allies; 3) acting in reaction to other foreign policies.

2.2.6 Tools of Foreign Policy:

Achieving the objectives of foreign policy requires the use of a number of tools as well as mobilization of resources. Without resources and in the face of a crisis, it becomes difficult

³⁹ Al-Kafarneh, Ahmad. (2009) *Aleawamil Almuatharat Fi Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Alsiyasat Alkharijiati* [The Factors Affecting Decision Making Of Foreign Policy]. *International Studies Journal*. Vol. 42. 13-41. p: 31.

⁴⁰ Ibid. p: 108.

for a state to achieve foreign policy objectives unless the achievement of those goals is assigned to another international actors,⁴¹ which again requires the use of a range of diplomatic tools to persuade international actors to carry the burden of these objectives.

Dr. Mohammed Salim Al-Said mentions eight basic tools of foreign policy:⁴²

1. Diplomatic tools.
2. Economical tools.
3. Military tools.
4. Internal political tools.
5. Intelligence tools.
6. Symbolic tools.
7. Scientific and technological tools.
8. Natural resources.

2.3 Part Three: Foreign Policy Related Items

2.3.1 Differences between Foreign Policy and Related Items:

1. **Foreign Policy and International Relations:** The concept of foreign policy is less comprehensive than the concept of international relations. Foreign policy is a set of general orientations adopted at a particular historical beginning, or, more simply, it is the general orientation prepared when a new government comes into power. Foreign policy is aimed at defending the country's national interests to achieve determined

⁴¹ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiya* [The Foreign Policy]. Gaza: The Islamic University. p: 53.

⁴² Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia* [Foreign Policy Analysis]. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. pp: 82-83.

objectives;⁴³ it is developed inside the state and is a reflection of its internal policies. International relations, on the other hand, include all of the flooding through the borders among the world's countries with their components. It includes all activities of governments such as diplomacy, negotiations, trade, wars, etc.

2. Foreign Policy and Diplomacy: Diplomacy differs from foreign policy. Foreign policy of a state guides the state's activities with other states. It defines the approach adopted by a state to maintain its external political, financial, military, cultural, and economic relations, while diplomacy is just a tool for implementing foreign policy. Diplomacy is soft power,⁴⁴ practiced by presidents, ministers, diplomatic leaders, and any other authorized persons. Also, diplomacy is inherently characterized to be practiced in peaceful ways,⁴⁵ while foreign policy can be practiced in both peaceful and violence or aggressive ways because it is characterized by commitment to safeguarding national interests.

3. Foreign Policy and International Policy: International policy is the interaction, characterized by expected confrontations in most cases, as a result of differences in goals and decisions that come out of more than one political unit. While international policy is reflected in countries, international organizations and other active groups, foreign policy is made within the states establishment itself.⁴⁶ International policy is

⁴³ Wasike, S., Kimokoti, S. N., & Wekesa, V. (2016). Connectivity Between Diplomacy, Foreign Policy And Global Politics. *International Journal Of Humanities And Cultural Studies. (IJHCS. ISSN 2356-5926, 2(2)*, p: 520.

⁴⁴ Oscarson, S. J. (2009). *The Art Of Diplomacy: The Use Of Art In International Relations*. (Master Dissertation). Georgetown University. pp: 20-21.

⁴⁵ Ibid. p: 522.

⁴⁶ Alnuaimi, Ahmad. (2001). *Alsiyasat Alkharjia [The Foreign Policy]*. Amman, Jordan: Zahran Publications. p: 29.

more comprehensive than foreign policy as all international policies cumulatively foster international relations.

2.3.2 The Relation between Foreign Policy and Domestic Policy:

When it comes to the relationship between foreign policy and domestic policy, two completely different opinions exist: 1) the foreign policy of any country, whatever its nature, is a reflection of the interaction of internal environment variables; 2) foreign policy begins where the domestic policy ends.⁴⁷ However, both domestic and foreign policies are formulated within the borders of the state and are implemented by the concerned authorized institutions of the country. Domestic policy is directed to be implemented internally, while foreign policy is directed to the external environment. There is a systematic ambiguity in the relationship between the two policies, where an international unit adopts a certain internal policy but in practice this policy leads to achievement of goals in the external environment. In the same way, some foreign policy may aim to achieve internal goals.

Logically, it is clear that understanding the relationship between internal and external policies requires the limits of foreign policy to be distinguished from domestic policy.⁴⁸

The relationship, as discussed previously, is represented on two levels, i.e., there are indications of overlap between domestic policy and foreign policy, as well as indications of dissociation between the two. However, what can be clarified in this regard is that an overlapping relation does not indicate similarity of the two policies, and the indicators of dissociation do not indicate complete separation between them.

⁴⁷ Henry A, Kissinger. (1969). *Domestic Politics And Foreign Policy In; Jame N. Roseneau, International Politics, And Foreign Policy*. New York: The Free Press. p: 261.

⁴⁸ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 27.

Thus, there is some kind of correlation between domestic policy and foreign policy, which is explained and understood within the state as a source of the two policies.

2.3.3 Foreign Policy Decision Making:

Foreign policy decision making requires a deep understanding of the various factors and determinants affecting policy-making directly and indirectly. Foreign policy decision makers encounter issues that have to be dealt with immediately. The decision-making process involves selecting one course of action from a group of alternatives. The choice should be such that it maximizes the winning opportunities and minimizes the losses for the state. Using factors such as media wisely, helps a lot in hauling the public to the desired side.

The process of decision making in foreign policy goes through several stages. It includes knowing the standards and limitations of decisions in the foreign strategy and the actual existing alternatives. Any decision must be feasible in terms of implementation, and achievement of desired goals. The process keeps swinging between action and reaction till the issue is settled.⁴⁹

In any state, there are a specific institutions that have the authority to make decisions regarding foreign affairs. The Executive and the Legislative authorities come first in administrating any foreign policy. The ability to have more influence depends on the shape of the political system in the country. The execution of foreign policy outside the country

⁴⁹ Al-Kafarneh, Ahmad. (2009) *Aleawamil Almuatharat Fi Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Alsiyasat Alkharijati* [The Factors Affecting Decision Making Of Foreign Policy]. *International Studies Journal*. Vol. 42. 13-41. p: 5.

is primarily controlled by the Ministry of Foreign Affairs.⁵⁰ Foreign policy can also be practiced by authorized officials in the state like ministers or military leaders or any related external organizations.

Decision-making bodies vary widely from state to state, as the Constitution of the state determines who is responsible for foreign policy decisions. The Constitution may empower a particular body to make policy decisions, and these decisions come as a reaction to various subsystems. The operation of these regimes depends on the nature of the political system on the one hand, and the nature of the emerging situation on the other.

The foreign policy decision-making process can be entrusted to the chief decision maker (Head of State), as in most developing countries, in addition to help from some advisers around him. The role of the political leader is eminent in cases where foreign policy is chosen without relying on a particular party.⁵¹

The foreign policy is also affected by other factors and institutions such as political parties, the social advocacy and lobbying groups, public opinion, and personality of the leader.^{52,53}

2.3.4 Foreign Policy Orientations:

Each state follows a specific trend in its foreign policy, sustained over a period of time that may be prolonged or shortened, depending on its compatibility with national interests in light of internal circumstances of the state and the surrounding international reality. The

⁵⁰ Ibid. p: 6.

⁵¹ Najdawi, Mohamed Hadi, (2014). *Muqtarabat Dirasat Sinaeat Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Lilduwal Alearabia* [Approaches To Foreign Policy Making Of Arab States]. *Public Policy Journal*, Voll. 12, Moroccan Ministry Of Cultural. Rabat. p: 44.

⁵² Hudson, V. M., & Vore, C. S. (1995). *Foreign Policy Analysis Yesterday, Today, And Tomorrow*. Mershon International Studies Review, 39(Supplement_2), 209-238. p: 226.

⁵³ Smith, S., Hadfield, A., & Dunne, T. (Eds.). (2016). *Foreign Policy: Theories, Actors, Cases*. Oxford University Press. p: 27.

orientation of a state's foreign policy may differ based on its strategic location, importance to other countries, and its level of effectiveness at both regional and international levels.⁵⁴ The orientation of the foreign policy of a state can be controlled by its geographical sphere. There are countries that orient their foreign policy towards their regional space and pay no attention to issues far from their territory. Countries that follow this trend include Egypt, which has oriented its foreign policy to the Middle East, and Brazil, whose foreign policy is directed toward Latin America. The regional orientation can also be in line with the global orientation. In this case, the state directs its foreign policy towards international units outside its region. The interests of such states are distributed throughout the world.⁵⁵ An important example is the US, especially since the end of the Second World War. Its foreign policy is directed towards many regions of the world, and is active in the Middle East, Africa, Asia, and Europe.

2.4 Part Four: Crisis and Crisis Management

2.4.1 Concept of Crisis:

A crisis, politically and militarily, is the defining moment between peace and war, when relations between states and their limits are challenged. Crisis arises in a state of tension, lack of confidence, and instability; it accumulates and derives its causes from past conflicts moving to the present and future.

From an administrative perspective, crisis is a "situation in which the decision maker loses the ability to control the present situations and the future directions, in which the events

⁵⁴ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p: 6.

⁵⁵ Ibid. p: 7.

are intertwined and the causes are mixed with the results,”⁵⁶ wherein causes and events continually move in a perpetual cycle, in an abnormal situation that threatens an institution as a whole, including the audience.⁵⁷

Thus, crisis represents an “unusual” and unpredictable situation, extremely dangerous and rapid, with successive events, in which the results and their causes are mixed up, threatening the survival ability of individuals, organizations, or societies. Crisis presents with the difficulty of making an unusual decision in a state of absence of information, uncertainty, and an uncertain future. However, a crisis not only includes threats, but also presents an opportunity to make changes, making it a complex, rich, and a dialectical concept with two opposite extremes. Simply put, crisis is a decisive moment, a turning point for better or worse.

Organizational crisis is described by Pearson and Clair as “a low-probability, high-impact event that threatens the viability of the organization and is characterized by ambiguity of cause, effect, and means of resolution, as well as by a belief that decisions must be made swiftly.”⁵⁸ Also, crisis is a social construction, as Drennan and McConnell make it clear:⁵⁹ individuals see crises from different point of views depending on their own experiences, beliefs, interpretations, etc.

⁵⁶ Al-Khudery, M, Ahmed. (1993). *'Idarat Alazmat: Munhaj Aiqtisadiun 'Idariin Lihali Al'azamat Ealaa Mustawaa Alaiqtisad Alqawmii Walwahdat Alaiqtisadia. [Crisis Management: Economic Administrative Approach To Solve Crises In The Level Of Unified National Economy]*. Cairo: Madbouly Library. p: 53.

⁵⁷ Falkheimer, J. & Heide, M. (2006). Multicultural Crisis Communication: Towards A Social Constructionist Perspective. *Journal Of Contingencies & Crisis Management*. Vol. (14) No.(4). p: 181.

⁵⁸ Pearson, C. M., & Clair, J. A. (1998). Reframing Crisis Management. *Academy Of Management Review*, 23(1), pp: 59-76..

⁵⁹ Drennan, L. T. And A. Mcconnell (2007). *Risk And Crisis Management In The Public Sector*. London: Routledge.p: 164.

Crisis management is the process of identifying a crisis and organizing administrative or inter-organizational response as needed. With respect to the management of crises, a key point to have emerged from literature and international practice is that even though crisis actions are unpredictable, they are not unexpected.

Crisis is an unexpected change, sudden or gradual, which results in a critical problem with a high level of uncertainty that must be solved immediately. Crises may either occur or disappear relatively rapidly with unexpected arrival and conclusion, or may be slower to rise, giving more time to respond, and slower to conclude, producing longer-term issues.⁶⁰

2.4.2 Crisis Management:

Crisis management is divided into three phases.⁶¹

1. Preparation phase: targeting issues such as planning, simulations, and training.
2. Management phase: targeting issues such as allocation and deployment of resources, command systems, and communications.
3. Evaluation phase: targeting issues such as post-crisis lesson learning, debriefing, and accountability.

Other Concepts:

Any action of foreign policy must deal with two main concepts: national interest and national security, accorded in the foreign policies by decisions makers.

2.4.3.1 National Interests:

The term “national interest” is one of the most common terms used by politicians and

⁶⁰ Efficiency, Unit. (2009). Crisis Management - An International Overview. Hong Kong. Retrieved from https://www.effo.gov.hk/en/reference/publications/crisis_management.pdf p: 8.

⁶¹ Ibid. p: 10.

political dictionaries. It is also widely used by decision-makers, and is hastily called to justify actions and decisions, regardless of their legitimacy, whether institutional or constitutional.⁶²

The Merriam Webster dictionary defines National Interest as “the interest of a nation as a whole, held to be an independent entity separate from the interests of subordinate areas or groups, and also of other nations or supranational groups.”⁶³

2.4.3.2 National Security:

The concept of security refers to the ability of the state to secure its internal and external economic and military resources in various fields in the face of threats at home and abroad, in times of peace and war. The security of these resources must be sustained at present and in the future to achieve planned targets.⁶⁴

National security has five dimensions:⁶⁵ 1) the political dimension, centered on maintaining the political entity of the state in both internal and external environments; 2) the economic dimension that aims to provide appropriate conditions to meet the needs of people and provide them with the means of progress and prosperity; 3) the military dimension, where the demands of the state’s defense, security, and prestige are met by building a military force capable of meeting the needs of strategic military balance and deterrence defense at the regional level, to protect the state from external

⁶² Azzam, Abdulmuhsin, (2014, December 4). *Maqhum"Almaslihat Alwtny"* [The Concept Of National Interest].

Retrieved from <http://www.albosala.com/news/articles>.

⁶³ Merriam Webster Dictionary. (2017). National Interest. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/national%20interest>

⁶⁴ Zaki, Abdulmo'ti. (2016). *Al'amn Alqumy: Qura'at Fi Almaqhum Wal'abead* [The National Security: Concept And Dimensions]. *The Egyptian Institution For Political Studies And Strategies*. p: 3.

⁶⁵ Ibid. pp: 4-5.

aggression; 4) the social dimension, aimed at providing security to citizens to the extent that it fosters a sense of belonging and loyalty, through social justice and by narrowing differences between classes; 5) the cultural dimension, based on the protection of thoughts and beliefs, and preservation of customs, traditions, and values, which ensures availability of resources in all fields in the face of external threats and internal challenges.

National security is the state of being protected or being safe from harm, and refers to actions taken to make people and places safe.⁶⁶ National security thus prevents all aspects of life in a nation from being exposed to threats.

⁶⁶ Merriam Webster Dictionary: (2017). National Security. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/legal/national%20security>

Chapter Two

Delineating the Determinants of the Jordanian Foreign Policy

Chapter Two: Delineating the Determinants of the Jordanian Foreign Policy

This chapter is divided into three main parts. Part one traces the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy. Part two discusses the institutions involved in making the Jordanian foreign policy. Part three analyzes the process of decision-making in foreign policies with regard to the interests of Jordan.

The determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy are divided into internal and external determinants. The internal determinants include the geographical location which exposes and connects Jordan heavily to political, economic, demographic, and security events, in surrounding countries. The population determinants might also put decision makers in Jordan under pressure to choose the most appropriate alternative given the current conditions. Military power is another determinant that will be addressed, to show its effect on the Jordanian external policy. Other internal determinants affecting foreign policy decisions are: natural resources, social structure, public opinion, political system, and the personalities of leaders. The external determinants affecting the Jordanian foreign policy include international power structure, international organizations, reaction of other states, world public opinion, and alliances and treaties (bilateral and multilateral). These factors will be discussed to reveal their connection to Jordan's foreign affairs policy.

The second part of this chapter addresses the institutions that are involved in foreign policy making in Jordan. The structure of the Jordanian political system determines the institutions that are authorized to make decisions regarding, and implementing the foreign policy. These institutions include the King of Jordan, the Royal Court, Cabinet, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates, the Legislative authority, and the Security Institution.

The third part of this explains the process decision-making for Jordanian foreign policies. This part highlights the fundamental principles and the objectives of the Jordanian foreign policy. Then, it tackles the mechanism of the Jordanian foreign policy decisions and what factors are taken into consideration regarding political decisions.

The chapter will ends with a conclusion summing up the whole discussion.

3.1 Determinants of Jordanian Foreign Policy

The foreign policy of any country is not only determined or changed in response to external or internal actions, but also depending on a group of variables that interact with each other taking into account the characteristics of the international unit in a way that can be understood.¹ These are the determinants that affect foreign policy directly. Determinants here means the possible level of potentials and capabilities of any country, whether geographic or national, and depend on the interaction between the amount of possible resources and the level of modernity.²

The possible resources of any international unit are divided into two types: 1) permanent resources, of which geographic location is the most important one;³ 2) changing resources related to population, economy, and military power. Population, economy, and military power can be analyzed to assess if the various choices of foreign policy would strengthen or weaken the state.

¹ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 137.

² Cunningham, J. Karla. (1998) The Causes And Effects Of Foreign Policy Decision Making: An Analysis Of Jordanian Peace With Israel. *World Affairs*. Vol. 160, No. 4 (SPRING 1998), pp: 192-201. pp: 193-196.

³ Mohammed, Arabi. (2016). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat: Drrasat Fi Almafahim ,Altawajuhat Walmuhadadat* [Foreign Policy: A Study Of Concepts, Trends And Determinants]. *Dirassat & Abhath. The Arabic Journal Of Human And Social Sciences*. 2016, December Voll 25. ISSN: 1112-9751. Algeria. p: 8.

Foreign policy is defined as an organized activity related to the state's relations with others in regard to its determinants,⁴ and as a group of actions and procedures taken by the state towards other states, in order to achieve national interest as the first priority.⁵ Jordan, like other small countries, has a foreign policy that is directly affected by various determinants. Jordan's geographical location imposed on it the need for a certain policy with neighboring countries, especially with countries that have much stronger military and economic power. In addition, the economic situation forced Jordan to deal with a wide spectrum of issues by keeping policies stable to ensure stability of its economy, because the weaker the state, the more its vulnerability to the changing dynamics of the international order in general, and to the Syrian crisis in particular.⁶

3.2 The Internal Determinants

3.2.1 Geographical Location:

There is consensus among political science experts on the importance of geographical space as a variable affecting the political system, and hence its role cannot be ignored by the decision makers while developing any foreign strategy. Since the geographical location of any country is fixed, it is the primary characteristic of the geographic environment that affects the level of effectiveness of any foreign policy, as opposed to other conditions that

⁴ Ghalii, Butros And Mahmoud Issa (1979). *Almadkhal Fi Eilm Alsiyasa [Introduction For Political Sciences]*. Egyptian Anglo Library. Cairo. p: 309.

⁵ Al-Bazar Meh, Mohammad. (1994). *Alaydywlywja Walsiyasat Alkharijiat: Dirasat Mqarn [Ideology And Foreign Policy: Comparative Study]*. (Phd Thesis / Unpublished). Tunisia: Faculty Of Law And Political Sciences. University Of Tunis El Manar. p: 13.

⁶ Abdellateef, A. W. (2014) *Jordan Diplomacy Towards Syria And The 2011 Syrian Crisis (2011–2013)*. Adam Mickiewicz University. Poland. p: 303.

might be changed at will.⁷ An example is the Suez Canal, which enriched its surrounding regions, while other regions lost their prominence.

In case of Jordan, its geographical location is important as it links Syria, Turkey, Palestine, and Lebanon with the Arab Gulf countries mainly Saudi Arabia. It also links Iraq in the Levant with North Africa. Jordan's northern part is densely populated, and the population keeps drifting into the Syrian territories, on account of its northern borders with Syria, which extend to about 375 kilometers.⁸ The area is interconnected demographically through tribal bonds and shared historical and cultural heritage.

Jordan is a landlocked country, surrounded by four regional countries, each of which has a source of power greater than Jordan. In the north there is Syria, in the east Iraq and Saudi Arabia, the Gulf of Aqaba in the south and Israel including Palestine (occupied) on the western borders. The marine borders are just in the short coast Gulf of Aqaba and the Dead Sea, which is a salty lake on the borders of Israel and Palestine.⁹ This geographical location forces Jordan to build positive relations with neighboring countries to facilitate marine access to international waters. Thus, the geopolitical factor plays an important role in the formulation of Jordan's foreign policy regarding international trade with surrounding countries. Transit trade is a crucial support for Jordan's economy. Jordan's location put it in the heart of Arab-Israeli conflict, wherein it bore the burdens and consequences of Israel's occupation of Palestine, more than any other Arab country. The Palestinian question became of high interest for Jordan politically, demographically, economically,

⁷ Hazaymeh, Mohammad. (2000). *Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Al'urduniyat Bayn Alnazariat Waltatbiq [Jordan's Foreign Policy: Theory And Practice]*. Amman. Dar Ammar. p: 51.

⁸ Moqatel From Desert Encyclopedia. (2016) *Almamlakat Al'urduniyat Alhashmy [Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan]*. Retrieved from: http://www.moqatel.com/openshare/behoth/dwal-modn1/jordan/sec02.doc_cvt.htm

⁹ Ibid: Geography.

and military, at the internal and external levels, and cannot be isolated from the public matters of Jordan.¹⁰

The sensitivity of the Jordanian foreign policy not only comes from its influence on the strategic balance, but also because Jordan's location holds contradictions that simultaneously create stability and deprivation for the country. The shortage of natural resources in Jordan is a challenge that limits its ability to be stable without the support of external factors or without a fixed continuous policy to maintain associations with all strong surrounding countries in the area, namely Syria, Iraq, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, and Israel.¹¹ This reality has forced Jordan to follow a policy that is built on balance and on strong alliances (the United Kingdom & the United States of America), to not be threatened by external powers in the region.

Thus, the geographical location of Jordan highly influences its foreign policy, to maintain security through committing to the unipolar policy put forth by the US. The Jordanian foreign policy goes along with the American policy in the region on account of its strategic alliances.

Jordan's geographical location forces its decision-makers to be considerate of the following factors:

1. The geographical location of Jordan forms an entrance into the Mediterranean Sea.
2. The area is landlocked with limited access to territorial and international waters.
3. The existence of ruins, and holy and sacred places.

¹⁰ Quteshat, Yaser. (2009). *Ealaqat Alsiyasiat Al'urduniyat - Alearabiat Fi Zili Mutaghayirat Alnizam Al'iiqlimii Alearabii [The Jordanian-Arab Political Relations In The Shadow Of Changings In The Arab Regional System]*. 1st Edition. Dar Yafa Scientific Publishing And Distribution. Jordan. p: 67.

¹¹ Abu Odeh, Adnan. (1999) *Ashkaliah Alsalam Fi Alshrq Al'awsat Ruyatan Min Alddakhil [Problems Of Peace In The Middle East: An Internal Vision]*. 1st Edition. The Arab Foundation For Studies And Publishing. Beirut. p: 110.

4. The proximity of Jordan to Palestine, and being surrounded by six countries.
5. Jordan does not have strategic depth.

3.2.2 Population:

Population is an important factor in determining the strength and status of the state. The state's population provides a human base for economic growth and building military power, especially if natural resources are provided in addition to other capabilities.¹² The population size might not mean much when it comes to the external policy of the state, unless it is connected to other factors. Anthropology scientists say that the best size of population for any country is when a balance is achieved between its population and existing natural resources.¹³

The population of the Emirate of Trans-Jordan, when it was established in 1921, was 600,000. After the occupation of Palestine and the Arab-Israeli wars in 1948 and 1967, the population increased because of addition of the Palestinian refugees who had fled to Jordan.¹⁴ The second gulf war 1990/1991 caused further growth in the population. This was abnormal growth as Palestinian refugees formed 50% of Jordan's population. This demographic change created pressure in terms of Jordanian foreign policy, especially towards the Palestinian issue, as Palestinians accounted for half the country's population.¹⁵

¹² Sinding, Steven W. (2009). Population, Poverty And Economic Development. PMCID. Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci. 364(1532). . p: 3

¹³ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 154.

¹⁴ Hazaymeh, Mohammad. (2000). *Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Al'urduniyat Bayn Alnazariat Waltatbiq [Jordan's Foreign Policy: Theory And Practice]*. Amman. Dar Ammar. p: 58.

¹⁵ Abu Dayeh, Saad. (1990). *Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Siasat Al'urduni Alkharijia. [The Decision-Making Process In Jordan's Foreign Policy]*. Centre For Arab Unity Studies. Beirut. Lebanon. p: 159

In the year 2000, the population of Jordan was 5 million, which rose to 9 million in 2016. This growth, however, did not shift Jordan from weakness to power because of other economic and regional factors.¹⁶ The reason for this population escalation was that after the American invasion of Iraq in 2003, an estimated 200,000 Iraqis moved to Jordan, comprising approximately 4-5% of Jordan's total population. Jordanian officials initially viewed this as a security and economic issue and not a humanitarian concern. They feared that an emphasis on the crisis narrative would lead to Iraqis becoming like the millions of Palestinian refugees already in Jordan. For this reason, the Government of Jordan argued that the displaced Iraqis were not refugees, but "guests" who would return to Iraq.¹⁷

In November 2016, the initial results of the national census revealed that Syrians constituted 46% of the non-Jordanians living in Jordan, and comprised 13.2% of the kingdom's overall population.¹⁸ Of Jordan's 9.5 million population, Jordanians constitute around 6.6 million, while the other 2.9 million are non-Jordanians living in the kingdom. Syrians form 1.265 million of the total non-Jordanian population, followed by 636,270 Egyptians representing 6.68% of the population. The 634,182 Palestinians who do not possess national identity card form 6.65% of the total population. 1.3% of the population, about 130,911 are Iraqi nationals. Yemenis are 31,163 representing 0.33% of the

¹⁶ Worldometers Population (2018). *Jordan Population*. Retrieved from: <http://www.worldometers.info/world-population/jordan-population/>

¹⁷ Seeley, Nicholas. (2010). *The Politics Of Aid To Iraqi Refugees In Jordan*. Middle East Research And Information Project. University Of Richmond. USA. p: 3.

¹⁸ Ghazal, Mohammad. (2016 January 30). *Population Stands At Around 9.5 Million, Including 2.9 Million Guests*. The Jordan Times. Retrieved from <http://www.jordantimes.com/news/local/population-stands-around-95-million-including-29-million-guests>

population, while Libyans were counted to be 22,700 representing 0.24%. Around 197,385 people from several other nationalities also reside in the kingdom, and cumulatively account for 2.07% of Jordan's population.

The population is unevenly distributed in Jordan. Majority of the people reside in big cities due to the domestic migration for jobs, studies, and governmental services. The country's population distribution shows that about 4 million people, or 42%, reside in the capital city Amman, 1.770 million in Irbid, 1.364 million in Zarqa, 549,948 in Mafraq, 491,709 in Balqa, 316,629 in Karak, 237,059 in Jerash, 189,192 in Madaba, 188,160 in Aqaba, 176,080 in Ajloun, 144,083 in Maan, and 96,291 in Tafileh.¹⁹ Of the Syrians residing in Jordan, about 435,578 live in Amman, 343,479 in Irbid, 207,903 in Mafraq, and 175,280 in Zarqa governorate, while the rest of them are spread across the kingdom's other governorates.²⁰ Arabs form 98% of the country's population with two main sects: Muslims (92%) and Christians (8%).²¹

Over 1.977 million families were covered in the census, which indicated that the greatest growth in inhabitants was in 2011. The annual population increase during 2004-2015 stood at 5.3%, the census related the rise of in population to the waves of Arab refugees into the kingdom.²² The average size of families decreased from 6.7 people in 1979 to 4.8 people in 2015. Statistics showed that half of Jordan's population is protected by healthcare insurance.

¹⁹ Ibid. p: 3.

²⁰ Dos Report. (2016). *Jordan In Figures*. Department Of Statistics. Jordan. p: 6.

²¹ Quteshat, Yaser. (2009). *Ealaqat Alsiyasiat Al'urduniyat - Alearabiat Fi Zili Mutaghayirat Alnizam Al'iiqlimii Alearabii [The Jordanian-Arab Political Relations In The Shadow Of Changings In The Arab Regional System]*. 1st Edition. Dar Yafa Scientific Publishing And Distribution. Jordan: p: 70.

²² Ibid.

The population structure of Jordan affected its political position toward various issues locally, regionally, and internationally. During the second gulf crisis, the political discourse focused on national unity on the interior front, and King Hussein used to repeat the phrase “Jordanians from all origins”.²³ This philosophy in the political discourse frequently surfaced in all major crises that Jordan went through. The Jordanian society is described as an ideal model for religious pluralism since the time of its establishment; it boasts of multi-ethnicity and a diversity of religions, controlled by consistency, interspersed with peaceful coexistence and homogeneous community.²⁴

The refugees who had fled to Jordan brought vocational and scientific experiences with them, and so they contributed to the development of the Jordanian society which was dominated by the Bedouin²⁵ culture with very naïve behaviors and traditions. The refugees participated in education, healthcare, services, and private sector investments. Moreover, the Palestinian refugees set foot in all public sectors occupying the positions of Prime Minister, ministers, parliament members, and in security agencies.²⁶ These refugees are considered Jordanians on the basis of Jordanian laws dominating Palestine before its occupation.

²³ Ibid. p: 71.

²⁴ Khattab, M. A. (2010). Religious Pluralism In Jordan. *Research On Humanities And Social Sciences. Technology And Education* (IISTE). Vol 2, ISSN 2222-1719. p: 118.

²⁵ The Bedouin Are A Grouping Of Nomadic Arab Peoples Who Have Historically Inhabited The Desert Regions In North Africa, The Arabian Peninsula, Iraq, And The Levant. They Are Traditionally Divided Into Tribes, Or Clans And Share A Common Culture Of Herding Camels And Goats. See: Encyclopedia Britannica. (2017) Bedouin People. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/bedouin>.

²⁶ Gabbay, Shaul M. (2014) The Status Of Palestinians In Jordan And The Anomaly Of Holding A Jordanian Passport. *Political Sciences & Public Affairs*. ISSN: 2332-0761. USA. p: 6.

3.2.3 Social Structure:

The social structure of Jordan exercises clear influence on its foreign policy. Originally, before 1948, the Jordanian society was a Bedouin society; the tribalism still dominates a large portion of the Jordanian society in rural and urban areas where tribes are an important tribute to the Jordanian official institutions.

After 1948 war, this sociocultural structure was affected by the huge number of Palestinians who settled in villages, town, and cities. Many of them were literate and well educated. The simple society and economy of the native Trans-Jordanians managed to assimilate them. Later on, the second wave of Palestinian refugees came after the 1967 war. By the 1970s, Palestinians had established a cultural dominance over the East Bank, and by the 1980s, Palestinians had extended considerable cultural and economic influence on the country.²⁷

The constitutional framework for the government and society dates back to the 1950s. The community started participating in politics officially owing to the 1952 constitution. The constitution declared the kingdom to be a constitutional monarchy with a parliamentary form of government. Islam is the official religion, and the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan was declared a part of the Arab nation. The King has since retained ultimate authority and wields power over the legislative, judicial, and executive authorities. There is one central government in Jordan which is led by the Prime Minister who must be appointed by the king; the Prime Minister selects the cabinet members. According to the constitution, a parliamentary approval must be given to the cabinet.²⁸

²⁷ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. p: 76.

²⁸ Encyclopædia Britannica Online: Jordan (2017). Government And Society. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/place/jordan/government-and-society>

Civil society organizations in Jordan are increasingly demanding involvement in policy making. There was recently a widespread debate about the key role played by civil society institutions in the implementation of policies formulated by the government, particularly those relating to sustainable development, the refugee crisis, and poverty alleviation. The bottom line is that civil society organizations believe that their participation in policy-making alongside the government is absolutely necessary, as they are able to provide information through their work on the ground, and this information can support policymakers to formulate policies that mimic reality and meet the needs of groups that work with them. Civil society organizations, as observers, can pressure the government to ensure the implementation of appropriate policies that have already been enacted by law.²⁹ The involvement of civil society institutions in policy formulation will allow them to design programs that complement government policies instead of contradicting them, thus contributing to propelling the achievements of the government.

Participation in policy formulation is linked to giving non-governmental organizations room to work independently, so non-governmental organizations and community-based organizations can measure the success of such policies in actuality.³⁰ However, countries often interpret constructive criticism as an attack on their sovereignty, and if this concept persists, the role of civil society in Jordan will remain limited.

As a result of demographic changes in Jordan, the refugees have become part of Jordanian policy. Since the end of 2012, hundreds of thousands of Syrians have entered into Jordan in a relatively short period of time. Upon showing their passports, refugees were registered

²⁹ ARDD Report. (2016). The Impact Of Jordanian Civil Society On National And Regional Policies. ARDD. p: 2

³⁰ Ibid: p: 3.

and could stay six months without a visa. In order to secure the basic needs of the Syrians, Jordan has borne enormous burdens as these people need water as well as medical care.

However, since the end of 2013, when Jordan's northern border was closed, Jordan has gained geostrategic importance. The country is in a very troubled region, but is a stable country by itself, being heavily courted and financially supported as Israel needed a buffer zone in a crisis zone and Saudi Arabia needed another stable monarchy. Jordan also became an important partner for the EU and the US.³¹ In the event of destabilization in Jordan, serious action will likely be taken to stabilize the country.

3.2.4 Public Opinion

Public opinion is formed through relative consensus on pressing issues that concern a broad social group. Usually, public opinion is stimulated by the press; it is the result of the cumulative views of citizens on a certain subject to achieve goals that extend to the future. The desired solutions necessarily lead to a unified action and a crucial decision that stems from the citizens' awareness of past experiences and lessons learned.³²

The Jordanian public opinion has been united on most issues on the ground, most important of which is the emphasis on democratic approach as a system of life on the basis of free parliamentary elections. Jordan witnesses the contribution and existence of a legislative institution that plays an important role in broadening participation in decision-making at internal and external levels. The Jordanians also agree on a comprehensive reform process

³¹ Bank, Andre. (2016, May 9). *The Refugees Are Part Of Jordanian Politics*. GIGA German Institute Of Global And Area Studies Qantara. Germany. p: 3.

³² Al-Zuaby, Kh. Ghazi. (2009, July 31). *Alraay Aleamu Al'urduniyi* [The Jordanian Public Opinion]. Alrai Newspaper. Articles. Jordan. p: 1.

as the only gateway to a safe future for the country,^{33,34} beginning with transferring citizens to a modern society, to achieving equal opportunities and social justice in order to consolidate social security that will bring stability in its different dimensions for withstanding the demands of stressful life.

The external pressures on Jordan have influenced the conviction and senses of the Jordanian people. The Jordanians have repeatedly reconsidered their positions in order to attain the means to gain sufficient flexibility, to overcome the difficulties arising from the Arab-Israeli conflict, the American policy, and other crises that resulted in security, economic, and demographic consequences.³⁵

The Jordanian experiences have cast a shadow over the public opinion in the country, as it has suffered and endured a lot. The Jordanian public opinion has transformed in that it can now affect the internal and external policies of the country.

3.2.5 Economy:

Economic resources comprise of human and non-human resources (including natural resources), which provide the base for economic development of a state. Being abundant in economic resources helps the state to establish stronger external relations that enable it to acquire suitable arm systems. On the contrary, a shortage of resources may lead to wars. This basic fact has been proven many times since the beginning of the industrial revolution and it explains the presence of American forces in the Arab Gulf, to ensure constant flow of oil.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Dalacoura, K. (2012). The 2011 Uprisings In The Arab Middle East: Political Change And Geopolitical Implications. *International Affairs*. 88(1), 63-79. p: 79.

³⁵ Abu Halalah, Yaser. (2009, May 12). *Harkiat Alraay Aleami Al'urduniyi Tujah 'Awbama* [The Dynamics Of Jordanian Public Opinion Towards Obama]. Alghad Newspaper. Articles. Jordan. p: 1.

Jordan has a shortage of natural resources which translates into an insecure future for the economy, hence Jordan's weak position in the field of economic competition and exchanged economic interests in the open international market. Although, Jordan has natural resources such as potash, phosphate, and limited amounts of natural gas, the agricultural production meets below 15% of Jordan's food need.³⁶

Thus, the economic factor was always a point of weakness for Jordan, affecting its external relations significantly. The British, American, and Arab aids came in exchange for various political pressures on Jordan. The Arab oil that had been pumped into Jordan as an aid during 1964-1991 played a major role in the development of the Jordanian economy.

The second gulf war resulted in the greatest risk for the Jordanian decision makers because of Jordan's supporting position on Iraq. During that time, Iraq was almost the only country that provided Jordan with economic assistance, including oil at very low prices, and in return, Iraq was importing goods from Jordan.³⁷

Jordan's weak economy limited its ability to stay unbiased to either the Western or Eastern blocks. The economic assistance to Jordan was connected directly to promote political positions against the Soviet Union in the 1960s. Economic assistance was used to pressurize the Jordanian government in this same direction in 1975, when Jordan decided to initiate relations with the Soviet Union.³⁸ The United States cut part of its economic assistance to Jordan and pressed to it follow the American policy regarding solving the Arab-Israeli conflict in the region.

³⁶ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. pp: 128-129.

³⁷ Ibid. p: 162.

³⁸ Hajjaj, Khalil. (2009). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'amrikiat Dirasat Tarikhiatan Fi Aleawamil Alsiyasiat Walathar Altanmawiat 1975-1985* [The Jordanian-American Relations: A Historical Study Of The Political And Development Factors 1975-1985]. Humanities And Social Studies. Jordan University. Vol: 36. No. 1. p: 5.

The Jordanian decision makers recognized the dire economic situation that Jordan was in because of a shortage of natural resources. So when the value of the Jordanian Dinar dropped down, the Jordanian leadership took important economic and political decisions. As a result, the decision was made to follow economic reform policies that supported the political reforms.³⁹ The clearest policy was the privatization policy and increasing American assistance, after signing the peace agreement with Israel. In addition to this, Jordan focused on attracting foreign investment in technology, building industrial cities and free zones, and drawing educational plans to provide the local market with trained and skilled cadres, among other such measures. However, even all of the aforementioned efforts could not help it gain independence of political decisions. By 2016, the public debt in Jordan had become huge and reached USD 26.5 billion,⁴⁰ and the payback dissolved all its plans to achieve real development.

The fragility of the Jordanian economy being a constant source of pressure for the foreign policy decision makers, majorly affected its interior and external policy. The Jordanian economy still faces a shortage of minerals, water, energy, and agricultural resources. In the absence of a general lack of economic integration, political instability in the Arab area further worsened the situation. So, the decision makers had to ensure a balance between the internal needs and the policies imposed due to regional and international circumstances. All of the above stated factors led to a decrease in the self-sufficiency of Jordan making it dependent economy. The Jordanian policies became exceedingly linked to other countries'

³⁹ Mkrtchyan, Aghassi. (2013) *Jordan-Implementation Of Economic Reform And Development Program*. (Report Number: ICRR14019). World Bank. Jordan. Documents & Reports. p: 4.

⁴⁰ Economic Editor. (2016, 19 February). *Siton Wa Ishron Wa Nwisf Mlyar Dular Aldiyn Alkharijii Nihayat Aleam* [26.5 Billion \$ Foreign Debt At The End Of The Year]. Alrai Newspaper, Jordan. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/769496.html>

policies, so as to secure constant supply of food and goods to the Jordanian market. Jordan became so close with capitalistic markets that encouraged the government to take more and more loans and assistance to implement economic development plans.⁴¹ The Jordanian government established the “Ministry of Planning” in 1984 which became “The Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation” in 2003, to ensure the best possible investments of loans and assistance.⁴²

3.2.6 Natural Resources:

The possession of natural resources plays a major role in designing the foreign policy of any country, as availability of natural resources increases the ability to establish a strong economy and empowers the country in front of other countries. The kingdom’s mineral resources have been the main source of gross production as well as of the total value added in the economy. These resources constitute an important part of the exports of Jordan.⁴³

The report of Jordan's Ministry of Energy and Mineral Resources in 2016 shows the distribution of mineral resources in Jordan as follows:⁴⁴

Phosphates: The Jordanian Natural Resources Authority estimates that phosphate formations cover about 60% of the total area in Jordan, especially over a 300 km wide track from the north to the south of the country.

Natural Gas: Gas was discovered in Jordan in 1987. Its estimated reserves stand at about 230 billion cubic feet.

⁴¹ Qandah, Adly. (2011, May 18). 'Athara Almusaeadat Alaiqtisadiat Ealaa Alqarar Alsiyasi Al'urduniyi [The Impact Of Economic Aid On The Jordanian Political Decision]. Retrieved from <http://ar.ammannet.net/news/107782>

⁴² MOPIC (2017). The Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation Of Jordan. Retrieved From <Http://Www.Mop.Gov.Jo/Pages/Viewpage.aspx?Pageid=95>

⁴³ MEMR Report: (2016). *Altharawat Almaedaniat Fi Al'urdun* [Mineral Resources In Jordan]. Ministry Of Energy And Mineral Resources. Jordan. p: 2-3.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

Shale Oil: Jordan is one of the richest countries in the world with shale oil stock. The proven reserves of shale oil in Jordan amount to 40 billion tons, containing more than 4 billion tons of oil.

Uranium: The estimated reserves of uranium in Jordan are around 65 thousand tons. According to the Jordanian Atomic Energy Commission, the volume of Uranium production at the central mines site is expected to reach about 2000 tons per year at a value of about \$ 1.250 billion annually.

Silica: Silica is found in Jordan in large quantities, and it is easy to mine and close to the roads as well as the port of Aqaba. According to the Natural Resources Authority in Jordan, the country's silica sands are estimated at 13 billion tons and are characterized by excellent specifications.

Potash: Jordan is one of the lowest-cost producers of potash in the world because it uses solar evaporation. There were however apprehensions regarding intensive manufacturing in Israel, which could make extractions far more expensive.

Petroleum: Jordan relies heavily on imported energy resources, including crude oil and its derivatives, which constitute 95% of the commercial energy consumed in Jordan. The cost of imported fuels is a major burden on the Jordanian economy, as the steady rise in world oil prices leads to an increase in the value of the oil bill, which increases the burden on the state's budget through the value of subsidies for oil derivatives. To meet the increasing need for energy sources, the Jordanian government gradually increases the subsidy and that means the prices of oil derivatives will be released permanently. The government may also have plans to privatize the Jordan Petroleum Refinery Company.⁴⁵

⁴⁵ Dos Report. (2007). *Energy In Jordan: Numbers And Indicators*. Department Of Statistics. Jordan. p: 13.

Water: Jordan is classified as arid and semi-arid land. It is considered one of the four poorest countries in the world with an annual per capita water quota of less than 150 mm. Naturally, Jordan has 12 aquifers that supply water in varying quantities. The government has also built 10 dams, while another 5 are under construction.⁴⁶ Jordan's water resources include groundwater sources with an annual rate of safe extraction of 275 million cubic square. The annual rate of groundwater supply is 54 million cubic square. The total quantity of renewable groundwater available for extraction was 410 million cubic square in 2009. Of the surface water sources, the long-term annual rate of runoff and flood water is 713 million cubic square, while the annual rate of exploitation is 535 million cubic square, of which dams can store over 325 million cubic square.⁴⁷

The adverse effects of water deficit for Jordan⁴⁸ are:

- 1) Social effects: The lack of adequate water supply for domestic use leads to the spread of diseases and epidemics, raising the cost of health treatment while reducing productivity, which in turn negatively impacts national output.
- 2) Economic effects: The water deficit leads to an inability to achieve the goals of the development plans set by the government, negatively affecting the social and economic growth of the kingdom.
- 3) Impact on investment: The water deficit leads to a decline in industrial, commercial, agricultural, and tourism investments, thus wasting the efforts put in at the highest levels to bring in these investments.

⁴⁶ MWI Report: (2009). *The Water Situation In Jordan*. Ministry Of Water And Irrigation. Ministry Of Water And Irrigation .Jordan. p: 3.

⁴⁷ Ibid. p: 6.

⁴⁸ Ibid. p: 13.

3.2.7 Military Power:

Military power refers to the resources and technologies that enable a state to be prepared for an armed conflict reaching comprehensive war, in case such a situation arises. This preparation includes forming armies, and training and equipping them with suitable weapons. Experts believe that possessing military power may encourage a state to use it or to threaten to use it. It could also be used as a tool to deter other states.⁴⁹ Anthropologists found in their studies of states that possession of military machines will encourage states to use power while dealing with others.

Jordan is surrounded by countries much stronger than itself in military power and economy as well as demographically, and the entire region is filled with ideological conflict and competition. Moreover, Jordan is located next to Palestine which is under Israeli occupation. All these factors put Jordan's security under threat.⁵⁰ The Jordanian leadership having recognized this weakness, worked hard to overcome this situation by forming a strong army and special security agencies. The Jordanian leadership followed the policy of empowering the interior front, with the help of western allies- Britain and the United States. The policy of building strong military power cost Jordan a large amount of money. Between 1967 and 1973, Jordanian military expenses reached 40% of the general expenses, consuming around 16% of the country's GDP. Such high military expenditures affected the country's growth and development. So, Jordan sought much financial assistance in the form of loans from the western powers to keep up with its military expenses. Although all

⁴⁹ Waltz, K. N. (1981). *The Spread Of Nuclear Weapons: More May Be Better: Introduction*. Adelphi Papers, Number 171 (London: International Institute For Strategic Studies. p: 28.

⁵⁰ Hazaymeh, Mohammad. (2000). *Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Al'urduniyat Bayn Alnazariat Waltatbiq [Jordan's Foreign Policy: Theory And Practice]*. Amman. Dar Ammar. p: 50.

assistance came with various conditions being imposed on Jordanian military power, Jordan concentrated on empowering its land forces because it is a landlocked country with weak air and naval force capabilities.

Jordan's military expenditures during 2011 – 2016:⁵¹

- 1) 5.53% of GDP (2011).
- 2) 4.76% of GDP (2012).
- 3) 4.30% of GDP (2013).
- 4) 4.32% of GDP (2014).
- 5) 4.31% of GDP (2015).
- 6) 4.58% of GDP (2016).

Since Jordan's military capabilities were largely dependent on foreign aid and external funding,⁵² it led to further restrictions on Jordan's foreign policy, the effectiveness of its military capability, and the reduction of its defense alternatives.

In the shadow of variables and factors which resulted from the New World Order, Jordan managed to secure its national stability. The Jordanian military powers recognized that Jordan will not be able to stand any external invasion, which exerted pressure on the political decision makers. The Jordanian leadership, however, was able to choose an alternative that managed to achieve balance in the face of threats from Israel and Iraq.⁵³

The power criteria considered by Jordanian decision makers can be summarized as:

⁵¹ World Bank Data. Indicator. (2016) *Military Expenditure (% Of GDP). Jordan. (1965-2016)*. Retrieved from <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/ms.mil.xpnd.gd.zs?locations=jo>

⁵² Jordan Armed Forces- Arab Army. (2017) *Jordanian Armed Forces*. Retrieved from <https://www.jaf.mil.jo/default.aspx>

⁵³ Bligh, A. (2001). The Jordanian Army: Between Domestic And External Challenges. *Middle East Review Of International Affairs*. 5(2), 13-20. pp: 14-15.

1. The dependency of the Jordanian army on imported weapons due to lack of weapon manufacturing within the country.
2. The shortage of funds to ensure the desired quality and quantity of weapons; the thing that forced the Jordanian government to seek military assistance from western countries, especially the United States.
3. Any decisions related to the development of the army were subject to the exporters' opinions and interests.
4. According to strategic balance categories, the Jordanian army ranked eighth among the armies of the surrounding countries. This classification includes annual expenses of the security institution, personnel, and weapons' quantity and quality.⁵⁴

3.2.8 The Political System:

The Jordanian constitution of 1952 defines the nature of regime in Jordan as a constitutional monarchy, with a parliamentary system based on two councils representing the nation. The first is the Council of Representatives formed as a result of general elections according to constituencies, and divided on the basis of demography, representation of minorities, and the quota system for women (according to the 2003 amended electoral law). The second is the Senate, whose members are appointed by the King, with no more than half the members of the Council of Representatives. The Council of Nation is the legislative authority, responsible for issuing, amending, and repealing laws, monitoring the performance of the government, and approving the state budget. The will of the King to

⁵⁴ Business Insider. (2014, December 12) *The 15 Most Powerful Militaries In The Middle East*. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.in/the-15-most-powerful-militaries-in-the-middle-east/articleshow/45499289.cms> p: 2.

appoint a Prime minister is constitutionally accompanied by the given trust of the Parliament.⁵⁵

Based on the 1952 Constitution, the three basic pillars of the political system in Jordan are the Executive Authority, the Legislative Authority, and the Judiciary Authority.

3.2.8.1 The Executive Authority:

The executive authority in the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan has two arms: the King, and the Cabinet.

3.2.8.1.1. The King:

Under the Constitution, the King exercises his authority through the ministers, and is protected and immune from consequence or responsibility. His decisions are ultimate and no any Prime minister can compete against or gain his authority.⁵⁶

3.2.8.1.2. The Cabinet:

The Cabinet consists of the Prime Minister and his ministerial team, and they are represented in their entirety. According to article 35 of the Constitution, it is the King who appoints the Prime Minister, dismisses him, and accepts his resignation, and also appoints ministers, dismisses them, and accepts their resignations, on the basis of the recommendation of the Prime Minister.⁵⁷

⁵⁵ Moqdad, Mohamed. (2007). *'Ususa Althwwul Aldymqraty Fi Alwatan Alerby Wamurtakazatih (Alardn: Halat Aldras)* [The Foundations Of Democratic Transformation In The Arab World And Its Foundations (Jordan: Case Study)]. Al-Manara. Vol. 13. No. 7. p: 124.

⁵⁶ Abu Dayeh, Saad. (1990). *Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Siasat Al'urduni Alkharjia. [The Decision-Making Process In Jordan's Foreign Policy]*. Centre For Arab Unity Studies. Beirut. Lebanon. p: 129

⁵⁷ Thannoon, Fawaz Mwaffaq. (2007). *Hikliat Alnizam Alsiyasii Fi Almamlakat Al'urduniyat Alhashmy* [Structure Of The Political System In The Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan]. Regional Studies Center (RSC). ISSN: 18134610. pp: 151-174. Mosul University. Iraq. p: 13.

3.2.8.2. The Legislative Authority (The Parliament)

The Parliament is the second pillar of the Jordanian political system. The legislative authority rests in the hands of the King who reserves the right to ratify issued laws by the Parliament after been suggested by the government. The Parliament, which is called the Council of the Nation, consists of the Senates and the Council of Representatives, each of which has specific powers and duties set by the Constitution, for the administration of the country's affairs.

3.2.8.2.1. The Senate:

The Senate consists of no more than half the number of members in the Council of Representatives. The order to appoint this Council comes directly from the King every four years, signed by the Prime Minister and the Minister of the Internal Affairs.

3.2.8.2.2. The Council of Representatives:

The Council of Representatives consists of members elected for a four-year term by the people in accordance with the Election Law.⁵⁸

3.2.8.3. The Judiciary Authority:

The third pillar of the political system in Jordan, the Judiciary Authority is regarded by the Constitution as an independent authority with no authority other than the law. The judges are independent persons appointed by Royal Decree in accordance with the provisions of the relevant laws.⁵⁹

⁵⁸ Ibid. pp: 14-15.

⁵⁹ Ibid. p: 16.

3.2.9 Leadership and the Personalities of Leaders:

Since Foreign Policy is made and implemented by leaders of the country, the values, experiences, talents and personalities, ideas, attitudes, knowledge, skill orientations, and the world-view of the decision-makers significantly influence the various characteristics of foreign policy. The differences among decision makers also impact formulation and implementation of foreign policy.⁶⁰

As for Jordan, the real power rests in the hands of the King who heads the three authorities. The King is the internal and external political decision maker, based on absolute constitutional powers. The King's constitutional rights make him superior to any law. The role of the legislature is limited to providing advice to the executive authority and to approving decisions taken in advance, in addition to the fact that its authority is not mandatory.⁶¹ The legislative authority is further marginalized by the Senate appointed by the King, who always influence the Council of Representatives elected by the people; the Council of Representatives cannot object or approve any legislation or law without a clear indication from the Senate. This increases the hegemony of the executive authority.

3.3 The External Determinants

Several external factors influence the Jordanian foreign policy. These are:

3.3.1 The International Order:

The changes in the form and nature of the international public order affect the foreign policy of Jordan as one of the constituent units of this system. Jordan being a small country,

⁶⁰ Smith, C. (2013). *Personality In Foreign Policy Decision-Making*. E-International Relation Student. Retrieved from <http://www.e-ir.info/2012/10/16/personality-in-foreign-policy-decision-making/> p: 2.

⁶¹ Thannoon, Fawaz Mwaffaq. (2007). *Hikliat Alnizam Alsiyasii Fi Almamlakat Al'urduniyat Alhashmy* [Structure Of The Political System In The Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan]. Regional Studies Center (RSC). ISSN: 18134610. pp: 151-174. Mosul University. Iraq. p: 20.

has less ability to maneuver abroad, join a particular alliance, or withdraw from an organization.

The changes in the current Arab regional order and the international order posed an obvious challenge to the Arab world, including Jordan. The changes greatly influenced its intellectual, political, and social structure, as well as its security and integrity. Recent developments point to an important fact: the Arab reality is no longer limited to the conditions of the Arab region alone, or to the Middle East, but extends to other regions too. The Arab regional system is very sensitive to new variables, in terms of economy and geography, but on account of various international factors, it could greatly affect the global balance of power.

After the demise of the Soviet Union, several events brought about the change in the international order, especially, the Gulf War, the beginning of the peace process post Arab-Israeli conflict, the emergence of international economic blocs, the growing influence of political movements of Islam, the rise of ethnic, religious, and national conflicts in the world, and the sharp crack in the structure of the existing Arab system as a result of increasing international intervention in the system ⁶².

The structure of the international system, the current world order with all its organizations, has become an important factor influencing the Jordanian foreign policy and the extent of its implementation.

3.3.2 International Organizations:

Jordan's participation in a large number of international organizations further increases the

⁶² Da'aja. Haiel. (2004, November 10). *Alnizam Al'iiqlimiu Alearabiu Walnizam Alduwaliu Alrrahin* [The Arab Regional System And The Contemporary International Order]. Al-Rai Newspaper. Article. Jordan. p: 1.

country's responsibility. The organizations are:⁶³ ABEDA, AFESD, AMF, CAEU, CD, CICA, EBRD, FAO, G-11, G-77, IAEA, IBRD, ICAO, ICC (national committees), ICCT, ICRM, IDA, IDB, IFAD, IFC, IFRCs, ILO, IMF, IMO, IMSO, Interpol, IOC, IOM, IPU, ISO, ITSO, ITU, ITUC (NGOs), LAS, MIGA, MINUSTAH, MINUSMA, MONUSCO, NAM, OIC, OPCW, OSCE (partner), PCA, UN, UN Security Council (temporary), UNAMID, UNCTAD, UNESCO, UNHCR, UNIDO, UNMIL, UNMISS, UNOCI, UNRWA, UNWTO, UPU, WCO, WFTU (NGOs), WHO, WIPO, WMO, WTO. These 62 organizations, especially the United Nations, human rights organizations, and civil society organizations, impose certain policy directives on Jordan, as part of the country's obligations to these organizations; these directives encompass not only policies oriented to the external environment but also internal policies. The contemporary economic and military blocks also affect foreign policy decision-making in Jordan. Amidst all this, the big concern is how to gain economic prosperity for Jordan without dragging the kingdom into predicted consequences.

3.3.3 World Public Opinion:

Along with the internal public opinion, it is also very important to take into consideration the world public opinion as it shows the way the other states think. The international and worldwide values cannot be denied or neglected by any country, unless it is totally out of the international community and functioning in complete solitude, and Jordan, being at center of an unstable region, is definitely not one. With the advent of new technologies, especially social media channels, every major issue now spreads all over the world in a few

⁶³ Index Mundi (2018). *Jordan International Organization Participation*. Retrieved from https://www.indexmundi.com/jordan/international_organization_participation.html

minutes. The Jordanian government recognizes that the more extreme it is in its opinion, the more isolated it would be, and hence internal public opinion is sometimes suppressed in favor of the world public opinion.

3.3.4 The Jordanian Diplomatic Relations:

Jordan has established diplomatic relations with 53 countries all over the world. The importance of each relation depends on the basis the interdependence.⁶⁴ The basis of its relations with any country depends on the mutual concerns of Jordan and the other country, and could be political, economic, or cultural. In fact, such bases can be found in every bilateral relation. To act independently is risky, and in each relationship while the Jordanian government works through fundamental principles to achieve its own external objectives, the other state does the same for its own prosperity.

3.3.5 Alliances and Treaties (Bilateral and Multilateral):

Strategic alliances are an important tool in implementing foreign policies. Alliances were mandatory during the Cold War 1945-90, wherein both the United States of America and the Soviet Union competed against each other to gain more allies. These alliances impacted the foreign policies of all newly independent countries. Jordan was one of them and chose the Western block, still maintaining bilateral relations with USA.⁶⁵

As any other country, the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan adopted the policy of forming alliances and treaties with other countries, as part of which Jordan has signed agreements that have an important impact on Jordan's foreign policies. At an economic level, many

⁶⁴ Ministry Of Foreign Affairs And Expatriates. (2014). *Strategic Plan Of The Ministry Of Foreign Affairs And Expatriates For 2015-2017*. Amman. Jordan. p: 4.

⁶⁵ Al-Tarawneh, Anas. (2016, June 5). *Altahadiyat Alddakhiliat Walkharijiat Lil'urduni* [Internal And External Challenges To Jordan]. Ammon. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.ammonnews.net/article/271388> p: 2.

bilateral and multilateral agreements were signed to achieve economic development in Jordan, the most important being the European-Jordanian partnership and the World Trade Organization. Politically, the alliance with USA is the most important to the Jordanian leadership. Jordan and Israel have also had official relations since 1994, when Jordan signed a non-hostility agreement with Israel (the Washington Declaration) on 25 July, followed by the signing of a historic peace treaty between Jordan and Israel on 26 October. All the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy are inter-related and interdependent, and none of these act independently. They act in combination to affect the decision-making and implementation of foreign policy in Jordan.

3.4 Jordanian Foreign Policy Institutions:

While the King sits on the top of the pyramid of foreign policymaking and takes all the important decisions, there are other institutions play a supporting, administrative role. Although these institutions do not take any decision, they provide consultancy. The King receives the world leaders and conducts external visits to present the Jordanian point of view in the international arena. On the other hand, the other institutions help to formulate and implement foreign policy decisions.

3.4.1 The King of Jordan:

Foreign policy making in Jordan is considered ‘semi dominant’, as one person possesses the authority of making choices, while others in the government play a supporting role, marginalizing the role of opposition. Per the 1952 Constitution, the King of Jordan is the head of the executive, legislative, and judiciary authorities, wherein he implements his wills through the ministers’ council responsible for administering all of the country’s

internal and external affairs.⁶⁶ The supremacy of the King is confronted with many economic, political, and social development challenges, which he has to deal with.⁶⁷

The King ratifies and validates and declares all the laws, and the orders to implement them. The King is the high leader of the armed forces with all of its branches; only he has the authority to declare wars and contract peace treaties. Based on his own discretion, the King might also send special envoys from outside the governmental institutions.

King Abdullah II has been in charge since 7 February 1999, and the constitution grants him all rights and duties of the King. He takes foreign policy related decisions by himself, and supervises several issues through his repeated formal visits to various states and international organizations.⁶⁸

3.4.2 The Royal Court:

The royal court is the institution closest to the king, and there is no constitutional act that clarifies its authority or defines its responsibilities. The role of the royal court is to discharge consultation duties. The head of the royal court is the link between the King and the Prime Minister, and accompanies the King on all of his internal and external visits, being well aware of the King's attitudes and opinions on various issues. The royal court consisting of the chairman and a number of consultants,⁶⁹ is considered the closest to the King in the decision-making process, because of the nature of its daily work with the King. The royal courts also includes the Crown Prince, who practices his authority in the

⁶⁶ Jordan Parliament. (2017). *Jordan's Constitution Of 1952*. Jordan. Article: 45.

⁶⁷ Rashdan, A. A. (1991). *Foreign Policy-Making In Jordan: The Role Of King Hussein's Leadership In Decision-Making*. (Ph.D. Dissertation). Denton, University Of North Texas. p: 71.

⁶⁸ Saeed, Fouad (1988). *Siasat Al'urdun Alkharjiat: Dirasat Fi Almutaghayirat [Jordanian Foreign Policy: Study Of Variables]*. (Master Degree Thesis / Unpublished). Baghdad, Institute Of National And Communist Studies. p: 155.

⁶⁹ Mashaqbah, Ameen. (2012). *Alnizam Alsiyasiu Al'urduniyi [Jordanian Political Regime]*. Addustor Press. 2nd Edition. Amman. p: 130.

King's absence or in case any other constitutional conditions deprive the King from exercising his authority. Although the Crown Prince does not hold an official position, he can formulate and influence the foreign policy, on orders from the King.

3.4.3 Cabinet of Jordan:

The Cabinet in Jordan consists of the Prime Minister and a number of the ministers as needed for public interest. The Prime Minister is selected assigned directly by the King on the basis of a number of considerations and qualifications that make him able to plan the general policy for ministers. The Prime Minister selects the other ministers and finally, the King approves the selected ministerial formation.

The cabinet is responsible for the management of internal and external issues, except issues which are entrusted by the constitution to another body.⁷⁰ The role of the Prime minister in the external decision making process is predetermined and is to provide non-binding advice to the King. The role of the cabinet in directing and implementing foreign policy is derived from the constitution. The constitution gives the cabinet, the authority and responsibility to administer all internal and external affairs. The Prime Minister and the Minister of Foreign Affairs are in charge of the external affairs of Jordan. Both of them participate in conferences and other external issues, beside the King. The Prime Minister receives the heads of diplomatic missions in Jordan, if necessary.⁷¹

The authorities of the Prime Minister have undergone drastic changes during the history of Jordan. In the fifties, the Prime Minister was given a wide range of authority in directing the foreign policy. However, the King used his authority over the government, formed a

⁷⁰ Jordan Parliament. (2017). *Jordan's Constitution Of 1952*. Jordan. Article 45.

⁷¹ Ibid. Article 41.

new government, dissolved the Parliament, and called for new parliamentary elections, keen to the Prime Minister's role in foreign policy limited to giving non-binding consultations to the King.

3.4.4 The Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates:

In 2013, the name of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs was changed to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates is an executive body of the foreign policy of the state,⁷² and is considered the window through which Jordan can look to the world. It works on gathering information through embassies, consulates and attaché offices, and provides this information to the state's institutions according to the disciplines.

Headed by the Minister of Foreign Affairs, the main duty of the staff of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates is to strengthen relations with the world. The Jordanian diplomatic missions are charged with pursuing the interests of its citizens and of course the interests of the government. The role of the Minister of Foreign Affairs in directing and implementing foreign policy is limited to giving non-binding consultations to the Prime Minister and the King.⁷³

3.4.5 The Legislative Authority:

The articles of the Jordanian constitution stipulate that the legislative authority has some specialty in foreign affairs such as ratifying the agreements that affect the public and private rights of the Jordanian citizens. The agreements would not be valid unless ratified by the

⁷² Mashaqbah, Ameen. (2012). *Alnizam Alsiyasiu Al'urduniyi [Jordanian Political Regime]*. Addustor Press. 2nd Edition. Amman. p: 131.

⁷³ Abu Dayeh, Saad. (1990). *Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Siasat Al'urduni Alkharijia. [The Decision-Making Process In Jordan's Foreign Policy]*. Centre For Arab Unity Studies. Beirut. Lebanon. p: 179

parliament. Foreign policy is discussed with the foreign and international affairs committee in the Parliament, and these discussions form the basis for the non-binding recommendations to the government and the King on all issues related to the agreements and treaties that affect the homeland and its treasuries.⁷⁴

The articles of the Constitution give the Parliament some authorities, such as the right to form a committee of external affairs that aims to supervise the work of the government, and to vote against the government on the recommendation of the external affairs committee. Still the King has greater authorities. As a matter of fact, the Parliament's authorities are determined by the royal will. Thus, its role in the foreign policy is limited to consultation, rather than drawing it. In fact, the actual power of all internal and external affairs of Jordan rests in the hands of the executive authority.

3.4.6 The Security Institution:

The King is the supreme commander of the Jordan Armed Forces, while the Prime Minister occupies the Defense Ministry and must provide advice at the moment of decision-making. The Jordanian Armed Forces role in foreign policy is very important as the King consults the Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff of the Jordanian Armed Forces, for issues related to military power and security.⁷⁵

The security institution plays a significant role in the political life of Jordan. The army forms a core component to the internal stability of Jordan and against external threats⁷⁶.

The Jordanian army gives the King the power to face challenges and make internal and

⁷⁴ Mashaqbah, Ameen. (2012). *Alnizam Alsiyasiu Al'urduniyi [Jordanian Political Regime]*. Addustor Press. 2nd Edition. Amman. p: 131.

⁷⁵ Ibid. p: 131.

⁷⁶ Abu Dayeh, Saad. (1990). *Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Siasat Al'urduni Alkharjia. [The Decision-Making Process In Jordan's Foreign Policy]*. Centre For Arab Unity Studies. Beirut. Lebanon. p: 170.

external policy decisions. Through the army, the King can solve problems for which the civil authorities are not able to find solutions. So, the King pays great attention to the security institutions. Similarly, loyalty for the King is a core feature of the Jordanian army. The Jordanian army leadership was transferred to the King in 1956,⁷⁷ and since then there is no opportunity for possible military disobedience in the Jordanian army. In return for the care of the King towards the army and all troops, the army extends complete loyalty to the King. In 1970-1971, the army was the King's primary tool to exile the Palestinian fighters from Jordan.⁷⁸ But, despite the significant role of the army in securing Jordan and implementing the King's policies and decisions, it still retains only a non-binding consultation to the King.

3.5 The Fundamental Principles of the Jordanian Foreign Policy:

Jordan initiated a number of fundamental principles for forming the country's foreign policy, since Jordan's establishment in 1921. All of the surrounding variables, circumstances, and events in the international order had been taken into consideration. Islam, the common Arab work, and the Palestinian issue are main considerations of the Jordanian foreign policy. Jordan aims to maintain Arab national security, and to find a fair solution for the Palestinian people that guarantees their legitimate rights. Jordan always deemed the Palestinian issue to be a Jordanian issue as well, because the second majority

⁷⁷ 2. Arab Army Forum. (2013, October 21) *Taerib Aljaysh Al'urduniyi Al'idhaeat Al'urduniyat 1956 (Khtab Nadir Jda)* [Arabization Of The Jordanian Army Radio Jordan 1956 (Very Rare Speech)]. Retrieved from <http://www.arab-army.com/t84213-topic>

⁷⁸ Moqatel From Desert Encyclopedia. (2016) Ean 'Ahdath "Aylul Alaswd" Sibtambar 'Alf Watiseumiayat Wasabeun. [About The Black September Events September 1970]. Retrieved From: Http://Www.Moqatel.Com/Openshare/Behoth/Sirzatia17/Jordan/Mol002.Doc_Cvt.Htm

of Jordan's population is of Palestinian origin, and this fact has highly affected the Jordanian political behavior.⁷⁹

The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan is a part of the Arab World based on the concept of the One United Arab State. The Jordanian political system inherited the Great Arab Revolution 1916, which aimed to liberate the Arab Levant from the Ottoman hegemony to create the Great Arab State. Since the moment of its establishment, Jordan was firmly linked to the issues of the Arab Nation, and this link is apparent in Jordan's position towards the Arab Nation's issues. Jordan has been supporting the Palestinian people since 1948; it also supported Egypt during the Suez crisis in 1956, and contributed to the Arab armies against Israel in the 1967 war. In 1973, Jordan supported Syria on the Syrian front, and was with Iraq during the Iraqi-Iranian war which lasted 8 years.⁸⁰ Moreover, Jordan was a shelter for Arab Liberation Movements against prosecution in some Arab countries.

Political considerations also played a major part in directing the Jordanian external policy through stability and legitimacy. The Jordanian political system was built on the roots of Hashemite's origins of the first founder of Jordan, Hussein Bin Ali, going all the way back to Prophet Mohammed. The last Khalif who was given Baia was Hussein Bin Ali in 1916. The Arab National vision, reflected in the Great Arab Revolution, aimed to attain Islamic and National goals in Mecca, the center of the Islamic World; this vision stayed with the successive Jordanian political systems. Add to that the Bedouin and tribal dimension, as

⁷⁹ Al-Horani, Yousif. (2008). *Siasat Al'urdun Alkharijia* [The Jordanian Foreign Policy]. Alrai Center For Studies. Amman. Retrieved from http://www.alraicenter.com/alraicenter.com/user_site/site/view_article.asp?type=2&id=296

⁸⁰ Arab Army Forum. (2012, February 10). *Almaearik Walhurub Alty Khadaha Aljaysh Alearabiu Al'urduniyi* [Battles And Wars Fought By The Jordanian Arab Army]. Retrieved from <http://www.arab-army.com/t41748-topic>

the family of the Hashemites is a Bedouin family that goes along with the Bedouin tribes in Jordan, which are a fundamental part of the current political system.

From the above mentioned points, four basic fundamental principles of the Jordanian political system can be derived:⁸¹

1. Concentrating on the principals and goals of the Great Arab Revolution based on liberty, independence, and unity among Arabs.
2. Concentrating on the principals, values, and beliefs of Islam.
3. Continuing political development operations, building constitutional establishments, and increasing political participation.
4. Full commitment to the Palestinian Issue as the central issue of Jordan.

3.6 The Objectives of the Jordanian Foreign Policy

The Jordanian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates works constantly to achieve these objectives:⁸²

1. Standing by the principles of the Constitution, national values, tolerant Islamic values and the principles of the Great Arab Revolution.
2. Adhering to the international conventions and norms, the principles of international legitimacy, respect for human rights, and building relations with states and powers throughout the world, within the framework of common interests and mutual respect.

⁸¹ Al-Horani, Yousif. (2008). *Siasat Al'urdun Alkharijia* [The Jordanian Foreign Policy]. Alrai Center For Studies. Amman. Retrieved from

http://www.alraicenter.com/alraicenter.com/user_site/site/view_article.aspx?type=2&id=296

⁸² Almadina News. (2010, March 1). *Jawdat Yuakid Althawabat Alwataniat Walqawmiat Fi Alsiyasih Alkharijiat Al'urduniya* [Judeh Emphasizes On The National Fundamental Principles Of The Jordanian Foreign Policy]. Retrieved from <http://www.almadenahnews.com/article/35793-جودة-يؤكد-الثوابت-الوطنية-والقومية-في-السياسة-الخارجية-الاردني>

3. Adhering to the principle of non-interference in the internal affairs of other states and not allowing any external party to interfere in Jordan's internal affairs.
4. Resolving the regional and international disputes and conflicts through peaceful, diplomatic, and dialogue methods, and refrain from resorting to force.
5. Standing for national responsibilities towards the Palestinian issue, which is the central issue of Jordan and the basis of conflict in the region.
6. Continuing its efforts to end the Israeli occupation of all Arab territories.
7. Continuing with the role and responsibility in the protection and care of Islamic and Christian holy sites in occupied Jerusalem.
8. Exercising its humanitarian role in the maintenance of international peace and security, and contribute to stability in the troubled places of the world and to the provision of relief assistance, through various frameworks, including contribution to the United Nations peacekeeping forces.
9. Fulfilling the primary duty of preserving the security of Jordanian people, homeland, institutions, and national interests, and condemning terrorism and fighting it.⁸³
10. Working towards establishing understanding and dialogue, between religions and civilizations, as a starting point for contributing to a global dialogue that leads humanity to future horizons away from blind fanaticism and terrorism.
11. Clarifying the true nature of Islam and call for peaceful coexistence of all human beings.

⁸³ Al-Kilani, S. (2014). *A Duty And A Burden On Jordan*. Forced Migration Review, (47), 30. p: 30.

3.7 The Duties of Foreign Policy Makers

The duties of Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates of Jordan are:⁸⁴

1. Contribute to the drawing up and implementation of foreign policy in accordance with the directions issued by concerned authorities.
2. Represent the kingdom among other countries and international and regional organizations, and participate in international conferences.
3. Organize the kingdom's ties with other countries and international and regional organizations, and foster political, economic, cultural, and other relations with them and follow up on their implementation.
4. Organize the relations of foreign missions accredited to the kingdom with the official and concerned authorities of Jordan.
5. Protect the interests and rights of the kingdom and its citizens abroad, and enhance communication and participation with Jordanians abroad.
6. Enter into treaties and agreements with other countries and international and regional organizations, and contribute to the implementation of their decisions and their preservation, in cooperation and coordination with relevant parties.
7. Conduct negotiations and discussions with other countries and international and regional organizations, in cooperation and coordination with relevant parties, in accordance with the kingdom's policies and interests.
8. Facilitate coordination between international and regional organizations and national human rights institutions, to promote human rights concepts and values through the

⁸⁴ Ministry Of Foreign Affairs And Expatriates. (2014). *Strategic Plan Of The Ministry Of Foreign Affairs And Expatriates For 2015-2017*. Amman. Jordan. p: 5.

studying of international standards contained in relevant international conventions and protocols, and to consider ratifying them and/or incorporating them into national legislation and laws.

9. Explain the objectives and bases of Jordan's foreign policy by maintaining contact with various media.
10. Coordinate with accredited missions and Jordanian authorities regarding foreign communities within the kingdom.

3.8 Decision-Making for Jordan's Foreign Policy

Decision-making in foreign policy decides the destiny of a country. Suitable decisions through the times of crises are of utmost importance, in order to lead the country on a path of action that brings about the accomplishment of its national interests and helps it deal with important international units. Although the foreign policy determines the relations of a state with other states, it is the decision-making process which recognizes the problems, discovers the alternatives, and takes the final call to resolve the unresolved issues. Consequently, foreign policy decision-making is the main tool to evade negative consequences and realize national interests, while achieving positive consequences that benefit the people.⁸⁵

Jordan's foreign policy decision-making includes analysis and evaluation of past experiences to learn lessons for the present. While the current data may have different values than before, past experiences enable decision-makers to avoid mistakes in similar

⁸⁵ Salim. M. Al-Said. (1998). *Tahlil Alsiyasat Alkharijia [Foreign Policy Analysis]*. Cairo: Egyptian Nahda Library. p: 16.

situations by identifying the needs and accessible choices of action currently and in future, for protection and promotion of the Jordanian national interests.

Political decisions in Jordan might be taken by one person, or a group of individuals, or through a strict system via special protocols, or by a parliamentary institution. Each decision-making structure is different from the other.⁸⁶ These differences lead to different paradigms of operations regarding decision-making among different institutions.

3.9 The Role of Authorities in Jordan's Foreign Policy Decision Making

The actors of Jordanians foreign policy are divided into primary and secondary actors, based on their power and authorities, which are guided and controlled by the 1952 Constitution. The Jordanian political system is strictly restricted by the articles of the Constitution. In another words, the real power of decision making lies in the hands of the King. By himself, the King leads and controls all boundaries of the kingdom's foreign policy.

There are four models of decision making in Jordan that follow four types of issues. The four models outline the decision-making mechanism for issues and who is authorized to take such decisions. The decision-making process in any of the four types is not carried out according to any criterion of a Western or democratic political system. This means that it is a process that is not subject to the principle of popular participation and public opinion in some way, and is not based on studies and research conducted by specialized institutions, and presented with perceptions, results, and scenarios. Also, none of them is based on political programs of partisan or elected governments. It is a process neither institutionalized nor based on collective

⁸⁶ Abu Dayeh, Saad. (1990). *Eamaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Siasat Al'urduni Alkharijia. [The Decision-Making Process In Jordan's Foreign Policy]*. Centre For Arab Unity Studies. Beirut. Lebanon. p: 159.

responsibility or even popular choice. Of course, the nature, features, monopolies, determinants, and objectives of foreign policy do not allow anything else.⁸⁷

Therefore, decision-makers in Jordan adopted a special approach based on four patterns depending on the type of decision, three of which have an impact on international affairs which necessarily serve the objectives of foreign policy or do not contradict them, and the fourth relates to internal administrative affairs in various fields.

The First Type: Decisions of a political/economic, military or security nature that relate to or affect the objectives of foreign policy, either negatively or positively, or serve them, without directly or indirectly affecting citizens through their implementation. These decisions usually do not affect people's livelihood priorities. Such decisions are confidential, whether they are related to Western allies, or Israel, or the issues of Jordan, or the Arab region. These decisions are taken by the King alone and he orders the government to execute the request, through direct or indirect means. So, the government or the implementing agency does not understand the background and the objective of the decision, and does not discuss the matter as a royal order.

The Second Type: Decisions related to the objectives of foreign policy, which are non-confidential and known to the citizens, and whose implementation can result in unfavorable or controversial circumstances internally.⁸⁸ These decisions are taken mainly by the King, with the involvement of a select group of state officials, whose role is not to take decisions or provide consultation or discuss the decisions, but to ensure and facilitate their implementation. State

⁸⁷ Adwan, Mousa. (2017, June 7). Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Al'urdun [Decision-Making In Jordan]. Sawaleif. Jordan.

Retrieved from <http://sawaleif.com/249610-اتخاذ-القرار-في-الأردن-موسى-العدوان> p: 1.

⁸⁸ Ibid. p: 2.

officials are also responsible for overcoming difficulties of citizens' acceptance internally due to their adverse effects, along with overcoming those adverse effects.

The Third Type: Decisions related to international issues which are isolated from the goals of foreign policy. For example, initiating bilateral agreements between Jordan and other countries, with regard to economic and cultural cooperation and other international affairs.⁸⁹ These decisions are also taken by the King.

The Fourth Type: Internal decisions, unless they involve military or security matters, or have direct or indirect impacts on foreign policy or its objectives. Such decisions are practically entrusted to the Prime Minister and theoretically to the Cabinet. The Prime Minister consults with the King only if the decision to be taken directly affects the general public and internal stability, such as decisions to lift subsidies on goods, to liberalize prices and to impose taxes, or privatization. These decisions are taken only by the Prime Minister, after consultation with or orders from the King. There is no doubt that the King agrees to these decisions to serve, partially, the objectives of foreign policy, and financial and political requirements.

3.10 Stages of Policy Making

The Jordanian foreign policy decision-making process goes into four stages:⁹⁰

Stage One- Assessment of the domestic political and international environment: Jordan's foreign policy is made and implemented within domestic and international political context, which needs to be understood by decision-makers to determine and decide the most suitable foreign policy choice.

⁸⁹ Al-Bataineh, Fuad. (2014, September 28). *Alhalqat Alththaminuh Min Kitab Albitayinih: Emaliat Aitikhadh Alqarar Fi Al'urdun [The Jordanian Foreign Policy And Its Development. All Of Jordan]*. Dar Ibn Al-Jawzy For Publications. p: 13.

⁹⁰ Dabor, Ameen. (2015). *Alsiyasiat Alkharijiat [The Foreign Policy]*. Gaza: The Islamic University. pp:10-15.

Stage Two- Goal setting: Jordan has various foreign policy objectives, which are affected by the domestic and international political environment. In addition, achieving the policy objectives involves encountering problems and obstacles, mandating constant reviews of the country's external priorities.

Stage Three- Formal decision-making: Foreign policy decisions are formally taken at various levels within the government. Decisions are typically made by the King, the highest executive authority in the Jordanian political system. Other secondary actors, such as the Prime Minister, the Parliament, other ministers, and the security institutions, take decisions on a very low level which have no vital effect either on the Jordanian people or the kingdom as a whole.

Stage Four- Implementation of foreign policy decisions: Once foreign policy decisions are made, they must be executed. Usually, foreign policy decisions are implemented by special authorized departments in the Jordanian Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates.⁹¹ However, other departments of other ministries in the government, such as departments of defense, commerce, and security agencies, may also sometimes play a part in implementing specific foreign policy decisions.

3.11 Conclusion

The discussion in this chapter can be concluded as follows:

1. A number of internal and international political, economic, social, and security factors affect Jordan's foreign policy directly and indirectly. Internal factors include geographical location, population, social structure, economy, natural resources,

⁹¹ Al-Bukhari, Mohammad. (2009, August 7). Aitikhadh Qararat Alsiyasat Alkharjia [Decision-Making In Foreign Policy]. Retrieved from http://bukharimailru.blogspot.in/2009/08/blog-post_17.html p: 3.

military power, public opinion, political system, and leadership and the personalities of leaders. The Jordanian foreign policy is affected by external determinants such as the International Order, and alliances and treaties (bilateral and multilateral). Since these factors are linked with international and regional environments, they might threaten the stability and security of Jordan.

2. The geographical location of Jordan has a great impact on its foreign policy with other countries with whom it shares its borders, and may share ethnographic factors such as religion, language, and history. Jordan decided on its regional and international foreign policy by realizing the features of its own geographic location; it is a landlocked area, with limited natural resources and water, and with very limited access to the Red Sea.
3. The population and social structure of the country were affected by the successive waves of refugees from Palestine, Iraq, Syria, and other Arab states, influencing many aspects of life in Jordan. The Jordanian society was not economically ready for these quick demographic changes and so the prices of goods and properties went up gradually. Refugee waves resulted in changes in intellectual and religious beliefs and ideologies in different sections of the Jordanian society.
4. Lack of natural resources and water shortage in Jordan are constant hurdles to achieving sustainable economic development in the country. This economic challenge significantly affects the Jordanian foreign policy as the country is dependent on external aid for economic prosperity and stability. The high cost of energy further adds to the burden on public budget, causing high inflation, poverty, and unemployment. The population distribution, economic deficiency, and the shortage of natural resources

- create an inconvenient internal situation urging the Jordanian leadership to follow a cautious foreign policy with regard to other regional and international units.
5. Jordan's dependence on western economic and military assistance, to build and keep its security institutions working also affects its external policy. Jordan has thus maintained strong and distinguished relations with Western military powers in general, and the US, in particular, to ensure continued military assistance. Jordan is also required to maintain cordial relations with the surrounding Arab countries, based on tolerance and objective policies, in order to solve any bilateral issues peacefully.
 6. Within the Jordanian political system, six institutions are constitutionally authorized to deal with foreign policy issues. They are classified into two types: 1) the primary authority, i.e., the King, and 2) the secondary institutions, including the Royal Court, the Cabinet, the Parliament, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates Affairs, and the Security Institution. These institutions work constantly to achieve the various objectives of the Jordanian foreign policy.
 7. The power of decision-making with regard to Jordan's foreign policy, rests with the King. Foreign policy in Jordan is, almost exclusively, controlled by the King. The King maneuvers the foreign policy with minimal intervention from other institutions. No other institution can influence foreign policy decisions, except in some constitutional cases, which are rare and have no real effect on the King's power.
 8. The process of foreign policy decision-making in Jordan involves four stages: assessment of domestic and international political environment, goal setting, formal decision-making, and implementation of decision.

9. There are four models of decision-making in Jordan that deal with four types of issues: 1) Decisions of a political, political-economic, military, or security nature that affect the objectives of foreign policy are taken by the King alone and implemented by the government. 2) Decisions related to the objectives of external affairs, which are non-confidential, and their implementation results in controversial effects, are mainly taken by the King, with the involvement of a select group of state officials that facilitates implementation. 3) Decisions related to international issues which are isolated from the goals of foreign policy are also taken by the King. 4) Internal decisions that affect the general public and internal stability are taken by the Prime Minister and the Cabinet, unless they are military or security issues, and have direct or indirect impact on foreign policy, in which case, the Prime Minister takes decisions in consultation with the King.

Chapter Three

The Jordanian Regional Policy

Chapter Three: The Jordanian Regional Policy

4.1 Introduction:

As discussed in the previous chapter, the Jordanian foreign policy, like any other country, is the result of the overlapping of internal and external variables that directly and indirectly direct the external political behavior of the country, and the surrounding circumstances. It is also a product of the interaction between the elements of internal and external environments, whether regional or international.

The external variables were mostly characterized by a common factor that was threatened by the weakening of Jordan's own capabilities in terms of its size and geography, the scarcity of natural resources, and the disparity between the capabilities of Jordan and the neighboring countries. Thus, the nature of the Jordanian foreign policy in its regional and international relations is affected by external reactions.

The external economic aid, which Jordan eagerly accepted because of limited resources, created economic dependency, which affected Jordan's international relations and weakened its political decision-making power. This restricted the flexibility of Jordan's foreign policy and created pressure for decision-makers, preventing the kingdom from choosing alternatives most suitable for pursuing Jordan's interests and achieving its external goals.

In general, successfully implementing a foreign policy involves working out a program of ideas that express the state's goals clearly. The program is built by decision makers and is based on their personal vision¹ Jordan created a clear regional and international external policy by building up on the following basic ideologies:

¹ Badawi, Mohammad. (1986). *Madkhal 'Ilaa Eilm Alealaqat Alduwalia [Introduction To International Relation Science]*. Dar Alnahda. Bairut. Lebanon. p: 90.

1. Orientation to a United Arab stance that gathers the Arab powers, through the Arab League and the Gulf Cooperation Council.
2. Power cannot be attained unless economic dependence is eliminated with the help of national movements against colonialism.
3. Arab power directed towards maintaining Arab National Security against any threats.
4. Foreign policy based on mutual respect between countries, cordial relations with Arab friends, and antagonizing Arabs enemies.²
5. Orientation to Jordanian special responsibility regarding Palestine, and mobilizing duties in order to acquire power to support Arab rights.
6. Building the Jordanian economy on the right bases, in order to promote economic development and increase GDP.
7. Allowing political parties to work freely according to the Jordanian Constitution which stipulates that people are the source of authority. There is also the National Charter, which was written by the national powers as a frame for political work. It is considered an Honor Code to build Jordan's power in isolation from any external intervention. The National Charter was followed by the Law of Political Parties, which legitimized all Jordanian political parties after being canceled due to the Martial Law. The Political Parties Law was issued as a result of the efforts of political parties in the democratic struggle, and for the will of King Hussein in 1992.³

This chapter will address two main parts: 1) Changes in the Jordanian foreign policy from King Hussein to King Abdullah II; 2) Jordan's regional policy with Arab and surrounding

² Aldaher, Naeem. (2008). *Siasat Bina' Alquat Fi Al'urdun* [The Policy Of Power Building In Jordan]. 2nd Edition. Majdalawi Books. Bairut. p: 30

³ *Ibid.* p: 30.

countries, in addition to issues like the Palestinian-Israeli conflict, the Arab Spring revolutions, and terrorism.

4.2 Part One: Changes in Jordan's Foreign Policy under King Abdullah II

4.2.1 Jordan's Foreign Policy from King Hussein to under King Abdullah II:

Most of the studies on Jordan's foreign affairs concentrate on the kingdom's small area, geographical characteristics, and its location, and how these affect and determine the country's foreign policy. While this is still relevant, previous research neglected the economic, political, and personal components like the personality of the leadership.

Jordan has been seen as a state full of weaknesses that are reflected in its positions on regional and international issues, as it is easily affected by external factors. So, the Jordanian leadership followed a conservative foreign affair policy. Circumstances led Jordan to depend heavily on international allies to preserve its independence and to be immune from conflicts.⁴ The country's internal and external weaknesses were seen as the key to justify its foreign policies.

As a result of its location, Jordan is a poor state caught amongst more grounded and forceful neighbors like Israel, Iraq, Egypt, Saudi Arabia, and Syria. There is also the internal issue of a vast Palestinian population in Jordan that does not consider themselves to be totally Jordanians.⁵ Together, both local and external issues and their political and economic culminations were a major consideration for policy decision makers in Jordan.

⁴ Ryan, C. R. (2003). *Jordan: The Politics Of Alliance And Foreign Policy. Small States In World Politics: Explaining Foreign Policy Behavior.* (Boulder: Lynne Rienner, 2003). p: 135.

⁵ Inbar, E., & Sandler, S. (1997). The Risks Of Palestinian Statehood. *Survival.* Volume 39, 1997 - Issue 2. p: 33.

The primary policymaker has undisputedly been the King, from Amir Abdullah I, through King Talal the son, to King Hussein the builder of Jordan, to King Abdullah II. As a result of this individual approach to legislative issues, and in view of geostrategic variables, Jordan felt it was obligated to play in regional political affairs,⁶ especially as they identify with the Arab-Israeli connections. Along these lines, the kingdom's interests and aspirations have had a tendency to surpass its assets, which has fundamentally controlled foreign policy affairs in Jordan.

4.2.2 Jordan's Domestic Concerns:

While Jordan's primary objective has been the continuation of monarchical rule, lately, strengthening the economy has also become critical. Both these objectives help understand Jordan's external policy, which is formulated keeping in mind the country's dependency on different states for its local stability and monetary prosperity.⁷

The absence of a strong ethnic base in the kingdom also causes political and economic problems. Although this is the standard in the region and not the exception, the kingdom is especially helpless against having a fragmented populace comprising individuals who distinguish themselves chiefly as Jordanians and those who identify themselves as Palestinians who escaped to Jordan in 1948 and 1967. This separation is apparent in every economic, social, and political field, and creates fundamental pressure between the two sections. The Palestinians have had a tendency to overwhelm the economic sector, while the Trans-Jordanians control the legislature and armed forces.⁸

⁶ Sasley, B. E. (2002). Changes And Continuities In Jordanian Foreign Policy. *MERIA Journal*. p: 2.

⁷ Samaan, J. L. (2012). Jordan's New Geopolitics. *Survival*, 54(2), 15-26. p: 7.

⁸ Zahran, M. (2012, January 1). Jordan Is Palestinian. *Middle East Quarterly*. Retrieved from <https://www.meforum.org/articles/2011/jordan-is-palestinian> pp: 2-4.

The Jordanian leadership fears that political insecurity of liberals or Palestinian patriot thoughts might incite Palestinians to rebel against the government. The Jordanian-Palestinian event in 1970 was a clear case of this worry; another was the Kuwait crisis in 1990-1991, when the Palestinians obviously supported the Iraqi government requesting activity to help Iraq. At the time, King Hussein put the kingdom's political solidarity at stake and joined the counter-Iraq coalition.

After the Islamic Revolution in Iran in 1979, the Jordanian leadership expected that Islamist thought would affect the country and would have a great impact its own people. This had not been an issue in the past, since the biggest Islamist party in Jordan, the Muslim Brotherhood, which presented the greatest threats to the regime as a radical power,^{9,10} had legally joined the political field a long time ago. The party became very popular in 1945 and for the most part maintained amicable association with the kingdom. Still, in the 1990s, the authorities became progressively worried about the Brotherhood's tactics and attempted to constrict its activity through repression.¹¹ The issue was not just radical Islamism itself, but that such developments could exploit Islam to trigger thoughts against the kingdom in distanced Palestinians.

Jordan's economy has also been a real cause for worry for the country, especially since the Gulf War in 1991. On account of shortage of natural resources, Jordan had been compelled to depend on external help to maintain economic sustainability.¹² The hike in

⁹ Leonard, J. (1995). *National Threat Perceptions In The Middle East*. (No. 37). UNIDIR United Nations Institute For Disarmament Research Geneva.

¹⁰ Satloff, R., & Schenker, D. (2013). *Political Instability In Jordan*. New York: Council On Foreign Relations Press, pp: 16, 14.

¹¹ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. pp: 56-57.

¹² Swaidan, Z., & Nica, M. (2002). The 1991 Gulf War And Jordan's Economy. *Middle East*, 6(2), 71. p: 2.

oil prices in the 1970s resulted in rapid increment in the wealth of oil exporting states, which allowed Jordan greater external assistance. Also, a huge number of Jordanians were pulled into the Gulf area and their wages proved to be of great help as well. However, in the beginning of the 1980s, when the oil prices went down, the external aid dropped, and opportunities for foreign labor in the Gulf reduced with Jordanians confronting reduction in wages. The government's spending did not complement the reduction in assistance, and unemployment and a break in development hit the kingdom hard. By 1988, the country started to payback its external debts.¹³

Later on, Iraqis invaded Kuwait, resulting in a war. Due to internal political contemplations, King Hussein recognized that he needed to support Saddam's regime. While this decision brought him the appreciation of a huge number of Palestinians inside Jordan, the King and Jordan as a whole was subjected to the rage of Saudi Arabia and Kuwait, putting an end to all aid as Saudi Arabia shut its borders. Moreover, around 350,000 Jordanian and Palestinian labors were expelled from Kuwait to Jordan. The United States also withheld its aid to Jordan, as a result of which, most of the kingdom's income sources were lost or diminished. Despite the fact that this decision facilitated to some degree King Hussein's policy towards the West and peace with Israel, the economy still confronted numerous issues like unemployment, mal-administration, and a shortage of external investments.¹⁴ In addition, the populace's depression with its financial circumstance transformed into an antagonistic vibe towards the administration that could not mitigate such situations, further impacting the country's central objectives of survival. The choices in any event were made keeping

¹³ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. pp: 128.

¹⁴ Swaidan, Z., & Nica, M. (2002). The 1991 Gulf War And Jordan's Economy. *Middle East*, 6(2), 71. p: 4.

in mind the financial plans and to protect against potential economic difficulties in future, like those endured due to Jordan's position during the 1990 Iraqi attack of Kuwait and the consequent Gulf War in 1991.

Thus, the domestic concerns that affected Jordan's external objectives and its political economy were natural resources shortage, size and area of the nation, Jordan dependency on foreign aid for subsidizing its administration, and keeping up with expectations regarding its regular work. First England, then the US, and then the Arab countries were the main support suppliers.¹⁵ Commercial trade exchange with Iraq has also now turned into a factor with political implications.

4.2.3 External Security Interests:

Changing power structures, security threats from neighbors, and King's supremacy are viewed as the prime reasons behind the kingdom's regional policy. Jordan was under the rule of King Hussein from 1952 to 1999. He had been in charge of all foreign affairs and policies during that period, and so it is assumed that he was always involved in setting up, managing, and directing the country's policies.

As the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan is considered a traditional Arab state, it is accustomed to be on the "moderate" side which relates to its monarchical nature, pro-Western preferences, and inclination to avoid radical Arab politics in light of pan-Arabism, nationalism, or Islamism. However, geopolitical features have limited the country's ability to keep up good relations with one of the radical states, Syria. Besides, it is not necessary

¹⁵ Sasley, B. E. (2002). Changes And Continuities In Jordanian Foreign Policy. *MERIA Journal*. p: 3.

that all radical states share similar interests or strategies; in fact, they deviate from each other quite often.¹⁶

In a multipolar system, going through alliances is less robust than in a bipolar system. There are more choices for a country which means more dynamic movement and this makes it hard for countries to recognize the greatest threats to their security; suspicion and dependence on utilization of power plague the Middle East countries. This clarifies the strength of realist ideas of between states.¹⁷ Competition, antagonism, hostility, and a large group of geopolitical arguments describe state relations, instead of participation and agreement. International structure of power has been the main external factor guiding the King.

King Hussein had to deal with several issues- the Arab-Israeli conflict; the Palestinian question; Syria-Iraq dispute; Syrian and Iraqi motivations to take over Jordan; the Iran-Iraq war; and the sanctions over Iraq from international isolation after the Kuwait war. In each case, Jordan had to balance its internal and external policies. At times, it did not happen, because hostility between its neighbors continuously pushed King Hussein to make the best choice of whatever alternatives were available.

Jordan and Syria did witness a short era of peaceful coexistence, mainly during the mid-1970s. The basis for such good relation was Jordan's disappointment with the Arab world's recognition of the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) as the "sole legitimate representative of the Palestinian people," at the expense of Jordan, in the 1974

¹⁶ Ibid. p: 3.

¹⁷ Walt, S. M. (1997). Why Alliances Endure Or Collapse. *Survival*. 39(1), p: 163.

Rabat Summit.¹⁸ Nonetheless, these relations soon turned into hostility, and Iraq quickly became a far more active ally.

This change could have occurred due to several reasons: the isolation of Egypt among the Arab countries after its peace treaty with Israel, which left Syria and Iraq as the strongest Arabian powers in the area; fear of an Israeli attack on the kingdom; and fear of being pulled into Syria-Israel war. Iraq was supposed to be a guardian against Syria and Israel, as this alliance would be less provoking to Israel and Syria, than cooperating with either of them. Also, in its war against Iran, Iraq defended Jordan from the spread of Islamic Revolution in Iran.¹⁹

From the end of 1970s till the 1980s, King Hussein led his kingdom ever more close to Iraq, a consequence of Syria's constant animosity (demonstrated by the unsuccessful Syrian attack of Jordan in 1970). This alliance was strengthened by the inexpensive oil from Iraq and export of goods to the same. By 1989 and 1990, King Hussein was becoming progressively afraid that Israel might push a huge number of Palestinians refugees into Jordan, thereby threatening the kingdom, risking it turning into Palestine. Similarly, when human rights and political liberalization movements started, it led to weakening socio-economic circumstances and rising national unrest and irritation.²⁰ Also, there was sincere panic regarding Iranian intervention if The Islamic Republic of Iran won the war against Iraq. Thus, at the beginning of the 1990s, Iraq was Jordan's most valuable ally.²¹

¹⁸ Amatzia, Baram (1991). Baathi Iraq And Hashemite Jordan: From Hostility To Alignment. *The Middle East Journal*. 45(1) 51-70. p: 55.

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ Lesch, A. M. (1991). Contrasting Reactions To The Persian Gulf Crisis: Egypt, Syria, Jordan, And The Palestinians. *Middle East Journal*. 45(1), 30-50. p: 33.

²¹ Reed, S. (1990). Jordan And The Gulf Crisis. *Foreign Affairs*. Essay. Winter 1990/91 Issue, 69(5). p: 25.

Moreover, the relations between Syria and Iraq had deteriorated quickly in the 1970s, and by 1976 Syria had cut off all land and air borders with Iraq. Thus, Iraq looked towards Jordan as a passage to the Red Sea. In the end, the kingdom economically reliant on Iraq as a source of inexpensive oil, and for import and export, and transport trade both overland and via the Gulf of Aqaba.

King Hussein was one of the founders of the Arab Cooperation Council (ACC) in 1990. He believed this alliance could help to achieve Jordan's interests of security and balance against countless threats which might occur. The inclusion of Iraq and Egypt, two of the powerful and more dominant powers in the Middle East, provided Jordan the chance to have supporters if a peace treaty with Israel was signed, or use them as guardians in case it was not. The ACC also aided the kingdom more efficiently against its long-time rival, Syria. Although, circumstances changed when Iraq invaded Kuwait shortly afterward, compelling a shift in the region's policies and finally forcing King Hussein to the West.

The Kuwait crisis in 1990 unified the Jordanians, but not in a way safe for Jordan's survival. King Hussein rode the waves of public opinion to provide support to Iraq.²² Public rallies glorified their hero 'Saddam Hussein' across Jordan. But after Iraq lost the war, this policy turned catastrophic. While Jordan was hit with severe economic consequences, it could have been worse if Iraq had won the war.

At the beginning of the 1990s, the Jordanian external policy shifted from Iraq to USA, Israel and Turkey: King Hussein agreed to join the Madrid peace negotiations, and in 1994 signed a full official peace treaty with Israel. Jordan also contributed as an observer

²² Swaidan, Z., & Nica, M. (2002). The 1991 Gulf War And Jordan's Economy. *Middle East*, 6(2), 71. p: 1.

to the Reliant Mermaid military maneuvers in 1997, which included the US, Turkey, and Israel in naval search-and-rescue maneuvers.

As a result of changing policy, the kingdom reaped quick benefits. In 1994, more than 800 million dollars of the country's external debt was written off, especially by the US. Between 1989 and 1997, international official creditors rearranged the debt payments of the kingdom four times. Jordan entered into an economic partnership with the European Union in 1997, considered as the first step to opening a Jordanian-EU free trade zone by 2010. Furthermore, Amman also started the procedure to join the World Trade Organization, that same year.²³ The new policy assisted Jordan's own security agencies a lot. The peace treaty with Israel was used to gain progress in possessing American weapons and ammunition, and initiate updated modern military program.²⁴

Any discussion regarding the external affairs of King Hussein must recognize that he had a personal will to play a key role in both the Palestinian-Israeli conflict and the pan-Arab policies. The personality of the King and his efficiency in collaborating reasonable policies, along with his nonstop interactions with Arab leaders and Western powers, made him far more dominant in the scene than Jordan itself.²⁵

4.2.4 King Abdullah II: Different External Policy

After the death of King Hussein, his eldest son Amir Abdullah swore in as the new king of Jordan, in front of the Parliament. King Abdullah was named an heir just two weeks

²³ Ryan, C. (2001, February). *Alliances And Jordanian Foreign Policy*. In Annual Meeting Of The International Studies Association, Chicago, Illinois p: 21.

²⁴ Inbar, E., & Sandler, S. (1997). The Risks Of Palestinian Statehood. *Survival*. Volume 39, 1997 - Issue 2. p: 1.

²⁵ Miller, A. D. (1986). Jordan And The Arab-Israeli Conflict-The Hashemite Predicament. *Orbis-A Journal Of World Affairs*, 29(4), p: 796.

before the death of his father in 1999. King Abdullah II, one of the youngest Arab leaders, studied in Britain and the United States, and is well known for being moderate and careful like his father.

King Abdullah II has the benefit of support within the kingdom, which comes from three key sections in Jordan. First, the security institution, wherein the army is the most important. The army gave King Abdullah II its support, as an outcome of its traditional faithfulness to the kingdom and because of Abdullah's previous occupation as leader of the Special Forces and other army units. In 1998, King Abdullah was promoted to be Major General.²⁶ Second, the good relations that the royal family had initiated it with the Bedouin tribes play an important role in protecting the regime. Finally, the Jordanians of Palestinian origin saw that King Abdullah married a Jordanian-Palestinian woman (Queen Rania) in 1993 and has four children with her, meaning that King Abdullah's supposed successor might be half Palestinian, possibly a major emotional and political moment for the future of Jordan. It was supposed that these three elements would secure King Abdullah's domestic stability, as it is conditioned on maintaining the goodwill of these parts, especially the Palestinians. This appears to be the case so far. Although there have been protests by pro-Palestinian since the burst of the second Intifada in 2000, and the non-governmental links to Israel are frozen and reduced due to popular hostility against Israel. Nevertheless, there have not been any main threats to the Jordanian regime.

In addition to his ancestor's legacy, King Abdullah II also inherited a number of problems and security issues. The two main issues the King is obligatory to deal with immediately

²⁶ Bligh, A. (2001). The Jordanian Army: Between Domestic And External Challenges. *Middle East Review Of International Affairs*.5(2), p: 14..

without hesitation, are the internal socio-economic circumstances and preserving domestic balance amidst numerous regional and international problems. On the domestic level, King Abdullah seems to be aware of his economic duties and the need to be easy with the Palestinians. He often has dialogues regarding these issues but does not have a certain plan for curing it. He promoted some government statements of Palestinian origin, and reduced some of the honorifics, traditions, and customs related with Jordanian royalty in an effort to raise its popularity.

On the foreign policy affairs front, King Abdullah II followed his father's tracks in thinking and adopting strategies regarding major concerns, sometimes going beyond the limits that his father had gotten to. King Hussein brought Jordan much closer to Israel through the Jordanian-Israeli peace treaty and got involved in multiple mutual economic initiatives. He put much work into getting Jordan back in a good position with the West as an ally, particularly with the United States. It is in these two fields that King Abdullah II has strictly followed his father's way. King Abdullah II made conscious effort to not put responsibility for Arab-Israeli or Palestinian-Israeli conflict and violence. In fact, the King even succeeded in speaking well of Ariel Sharon after he was elected as the Prime Minister of Israel.

The burst of the second Intifada in 2000 did not push the King to act in the same way as other Arab state leaders that pointed the finger at Israel as the sole reason of the violence and the problem hindering its resolution.²⁷ The King, alongside Egyptian President Hosni

²⁷ Fa'ouri, S. Rakan. (2013) *Emlyt Atkhadh Alqrar Fy Alsyast Alkharjyt Alardnyt Tjah Almufawadat Alearabiat Alasrayly (1991-2012) [Decision Making Process In The Jordanian Foreign Policy Toward The Arab Israeli Negotiations (1991-2012)]*. (Master Thesis). Middle East University. Jordan. p: 66.

Mubarak, worked to reduce the rhetoric of the meetings in the Arab summits, especially the Arab League meeting which was held in Jordan in 2001. This put Jordan in a rather difficult position. The continuity of violence aroused common and tough criticism of Israel and support for the Palestinians through the Jordanian political range. This formed wide movements in the region to sever ties with and to adopt economic boycott against Israel. Though the government managed to reduce some of this rhetoric, it was under a lot of pressure to go along with the regional inclinations.

King Abdullah II has been very careful and balanced in discussing the Palestinian-Israeli peace process and its violence. The words ‘friends in Israel’ are frequently repeated in the King’s speech regarding this issue. Furthermore, he has made vocal efforts to clear his emotional stance that Israel should be joined by surrounding countries and not stay an outsider. Maybe one of his most obvious signals was his description of Israel as being a target for terrorism, a thing that the rest of the Arab nations would refuse to say. Rather, only describing Palestinian armed groups as freedom fighters. When asked what his definition of a terrorist was, King Abdullah II said that it is “anybody who takes the lives of innocent people - if somebody puts a backpack of explosives and goes to a pizza restaurant and blows himself up and kills innocent people, that is a terrorist.”²⁸

King Abdullah II also contends that there is no possibility of peace and stability in the region until the Palestinians regain their state. The King continues to announce that Jordanian support for the Palestinians has no limits till they get their full rights and that

²⁸ BBC NEWS. (2003, February 19). *King Abdullah: Talking Point Special*. BBC.NEWS. Retrieved from http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/talking_point/forum/1632372.stm

Jordan stands behind them with all its capabilities. The King, however, does not categorize Israel as Jordan's enemy, and refuses to fault Israel as being solely responsible for the violence. He warns that continuance of the Arab-Israeli dispute is a severe threat to the region's development.²⁹ The King always keeps announcing that the Arab countries need to deal with Israel's security needs and accept Israel as a member of the neighborhood.

Like his father King Hussein, King Abdullah II calls for a more dynamic American part in the Arab-Israeli peace process, and in the Middle East generally. In April 2001, the King traveled to meet the American president George W. Bush, urging him to play a bigger role in calming the region. The King's idea is that a greater role of USA would help bring peace and stability to the region, which is important for Jordan, both to improve its economy and for security reasons because an unestablished regional environment may make Jordan a target for ambitious and more powerful neighbors.³⁰ This would mean instability for the kingdom, putting it in the situation of having to select between different wings, and this is the kind of situation the King wants to avoid, as the lessons from the consequences of the Kuwait Crisis of 1991 are still strong in his mind.

King Abdullah II has been very aware of empowering Jordan's relations with the United States, as part of Jordan's effort to have a bigger role in the region. In September 2001, the kingdom signed a free trade agreement with America, and became the fourth country to sign such agreement with USA, after Israel, Mexico, and Canada.³¹ The King of Jordan

²⁹ Podolsky, Philip. (2012, September 26): *Jordan's King Urges Israel To Accept Arab Peace Initiative*. The Times Of Israel. Retrieved from <https://www.timesofisrael.com/jordans-king-urges-peace-between-israel-and-palestinians/>

³⁰ Schneider, Howard. (2001). *Jordan's Abdallah To Ask For U.S. Help,* ". The Washington Post, 4 April 2001. p: 2.

³¹ See: USTR. (2009). *Jordan Free Trade Agreement*. The Office Of The U.S. Trade Representative. USA.

was one of the first Arab leaders to visit the United States after the 9/11 attacks. He declared Jordan's complete support in combating global terrorism with the United States. The King has made it clear on all occasions that he fully supports the American actions in Afghanistan, Iraq, and Syria, and its efforts to eliminate terrorism. Furthermore, he has been forthcoming about including Jews in his list of people who suffer from terrorism. While the other Arab leaders differentiate between the terrorism of 9/11 and the suicide bombers of Hamas, seeing them as legitimate fight efforts, the King has made it very clear that he will not repeat the mistakes of 1991. Osama Bin Laden, who had earlier tried to attack Jordan was classified as an opponent of Jordan, and the King announced that the kingdom would take all necessary actions to join the international coalition against terrorism. Nevertheless, it is not clear exactly what he is ready to do.

There are numerous reasons for Abdullah's eagerness to maintain goodwill with America. He needs to contain any domestic Islamists reproducing Bin Laden's thought and actions. On the economic front, Jordan became a member of the World Trade Organization in 2000. To be in line with the world economic order, King Abdullah II expressed his desire to maintain economic growth and development in Jordan. He attempts to shift Jordanian dependence on the weak economies of the Middle East countries towards the West, and the American-Jordanian free trade agreement is a step in this direction.

Regionally, Jordan has been worried about the Iraq-Syria truce underway since 1997, and this has further propelled the kingdom to encourage American activity in the region and even forge relations with Israel. The reopening of the Syria-Iraq oil pipeline and serious debates about construction of a larger one have left Jordan concerned. The Iraqi-Syrian

hostility enabled the kingdom to stand with one side, against the other, and mainly with Iraq. The Iraq-Syria compromise would unite Jordan's strongest Arab neighbors and pose a real danger, leaving Jordan in a difficult situation and pushing it towards a non-Arab country for protection.

There are also indications of faltering of the Iraqi-Jordanian relations. In 1999, Iraq sold oil to Jordan at higher prices. In addition, Iraq's threats to Jordan made the country all the more keen on adopting closer external relations with America and Israel. Saddam Hussein's confidence that the sanctions on Iraq had come to an end, led the Iraqi leadership to think that it could go ahead with programs of mass destruction weapons and the surrounding states were prepared to accept Iraq. These issues weighed heavily on Jordan.

Although the new Jordanian foreign and security policies led by King Abdullah II, followed the tracks of King Hussein, changes were seen in some directions. While the old relations remained unchanged, the new policy opened doors to new avenues that King Hussein was not willing to explore.

The most noteworthy example of changes in Jordan's external policy can be seen in the regional initiatives of King Abdullah II, including political settlements with neighbors of Jordan, especially Kuwait and Syria, with whom King Hussein had stressed relations. King Abdullah II initiated state visits with Syrian president Bashar Al-Assad, who became the President after the death of his father Hafiz Al-Assad in 2000.³² King Abdullah II has also been vigilant in restoring relationships with Arab countries which

³² Ryan, C. R. (2004). Jordan First": Jordan's Inter-Arab Relations And Foreign Policy Under King Abdullah II. *Arab Studies Quarterly*, 43-62. p: 8.

collapsed due to the 1990 Kuwait Crisis. Diplomatic relationships with the Gulf countries were established quickly after he became king, Saudi Arabia being the most important among these countries. The Saudi Kingdom extended financial assistance to Jordan, which helped stabilize the Jordanian Dinar. Another indication of the changes in Jordanian diplomacy came when King Abdullah II, within the first few months after ascending the throne, received high-level delegations from most of the Arab and Islamic world, including the Gulf States, Turkey, Egypt, Iraq, and Iran; he also visited most of them later.

At the beginning of 2000, Jordan took steps to improve its relationship with Iraq. The former Jordanian Prime Minister, Ali Abu Al-Ragheb, was the first Arab Prime Minister to fly to Iraq since 1991. King Abdullah II emphasized in his speech to the Arab leaders in the Arab Summit in 2000, that Jordan would no longer take the international sanctions against Iraq.³³

King Abdullah II had his reasons for not playing any direct part in Palestine-Israel negotiations, and so the King's influence remained far from the core of the process, although Jordan's diplomacy retained its support towards the peace process, especially for the Palestinians. This could be due to the new dynamics in the region and to some extent the occasional pressure from the United States. Nevertheless, the King always offered all the kingdom's capabilities to all parts; he never delayed taking actions towards the Israeli policies against Islamic places in the Holy City of Jerusalem, owing to the direct responsibility of the Hashemite Family to these sites.³⁴

³³ Abdulati, Mohammad. (2004, October 3). *Juhud Rafe Alhisar Bayn Eajiz Alshueub Waturadid Alhukumat* [Efforts To Lift The Blockade Between The Inability Of Peoples And The Reluctance Of Governments]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/specialfiles/pages/98334bab-5925-457c-994c-aaeb2e0a5c11>

³⁴ Al Dakhil, Zayed. (2016, December 31). *Alquds Wamuqadasatiha Qurat Eayan Almalik Walhashimiyya. Wjhw d Mutawasilat Lihimaya "Al'aqsa"* [Jerusalem And Its Sanctities In The Eyes Of The King And The Hashemites And

King Abdullah II also came up with elaborate security plans to keep the border with Israel quiet. The offices of Hamas in Amman were shut, as a result of a policy that was radically different from his father's, who approached the Islamic organization. The King rejected the demands of Hamas and other Islamist groups to cut relationship with Israel. By October 1999, the Jordanian government had locked the offices of Hamas in Jordan and expelled some of its leaders. This policy was criticized by professional associations dominated by Jordanian Islamists. Though such steps did not form any direct threats to the Jordanian regime, King Abdullah II kept the door open for closer relations with Islamic organizations inside Jordan.

4.3 Part Two: Jordan's Regional Policy

4.3.1 Jordan-Arab Relations:

Jordan's external relations with its surrounding Arab states and other nations depend on a number of elements. The first being Jordanian official institutions led by the King, which always seek to initiate relations to have more united Arab stances that gather the Arab powers through the Arab League and the Gulf Cooperation Council. The elimination of economic dependence with the help of national movements against colonialism is another element. Arab power is directed to maintain Arab National Security against any threats. Mutual respect between countries, the friendship of Arab friends, and antagonism of enemies. Another special task for Jordan is the special responsibility regarding Palestine and mobilization duties of building power to support Arab rights. These are the ideal declared principals of the Jordanian foreign relations with Arabs.

القدس--917676/articles/917676]. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/917676>
ومقدساتهاقرة-عين-الملك-والهاتشميين-وجهود-متواصلة-لحماية-الأقصى

4.3.1.1 Jordan-Syria Relations:

Jordan and Syria have a relationship that dates back to the time when Jordan was the southern part of Syria. The two states were created after World War I from former Ottoman dominations by way of a secret bilateral agreement between Britain and France.

In 1921, the founder of the Emirate of Transjordan, King Abdullah I, desired advance to Syria, from which his brother had been evacuated by the French, and which he regarded as part of the promised Hashemite Kingdom. Even as late as 1946, when both countries had gained independence, King Abdullah I did not abandon his plan to become King of Syria. Syria considered Abdullah's schemes for an expanded Hashemite Kingdom as an intervention in its domestic affairs and officially complained to the Arab League.³⁵ Thereafter, Syria witnessed several military coups.³⁶ Ever since Hafez al-Assad became the President in March 1970, the Syrian state went through drastic changes socially, politically, and culturally. The Syrian state adopted Pan-Arabism, socialism, and secularism, which were the main formal ideologies of the only ruling Ba'th-party under both Hafez al-Assad the father and Bashar al-Assad his son.³⁷

Jordanian-Syrian tensions exacerbated in the late 1960s, following the rift between Jordan and the PLO, with Syria supporting the Palestinians against Jordan. In September 1970, before Hafiz Al Assad took power, Syria sent an armored division into Jordan to reinforce the Palestinian forces under attack by Hussein's army.³⁸ By July 1971, Syria had broken off

³⁵ Jawhar, Shahir. (2011, March 13). *Alealaqat Alsuwriuh Alairdunih ...Bin Md Wajuzur* [The Jordanian-Syrian Relations Between Tides]. Retrieved from <https://pulpit.alwatanvoice.com/articles/2011/03/13/222654.html> p: 3-4.

³⁶ Stacher, J. A. (2007). *Adapting Authoritarianism: Institutions And Co-Optation In Egypt And Syria*. (Doctoral Dissertation). University Of St Andrews. p: 171.

³⁷ Vaessen, Eline. (2014). *The Syrian Civil War*. (Master Thesis) Erasmus University Rotterdam. p: 63.

³⁸ Yassin-Kassab, R., & Al-Shami, L. (2016). *Burning Country: Syrians In Revolution And War*. Pluto Press. p: 11.

diplomatic relations with Jordan over the issue. The relation kept swinging between stability and diplomatic tension because of the October 1973 War and the Syrian intervention in Lebanon in 1976 where Jordan supported Syria. Disagreements also cropped up between the two countries when the Syrian leadership accused Jordan of supporting the Muslim Brotherhood in Syria in 1977, which Jordan denied³⁹. This pattern of relations went on till the 1990s. The period between 1999 and 2010 marked a kind of balance, improvement, and development in the relationship. There was clear influence of a set of internal and external factors, both regional and international, that led to rapprochement between the two countries. The economic factor was the most important factor leading to convergence and improvement in bilateral relations at the political, economic, and security levels, during this period. The new leadership in both countries – King Abdullah II (1999) and Bashar Al-Assad (2000) – had a clear positive impact on relations between the two countries⁴⁰ until 2011, when the Syrian crisis started.⁴¹

The Syrian conflict, which became ‘a sectarianism war’ according to some scholars,^{42,43} began in March 2011 with anti-government demonstrations as part of the Arab Spring, but the peaceful protests quickly escalated after the government's violent crackdown, and armed opposition groups began fighting back. By July, army defectors had loosely

³⁹ Wier Jr, J. S., & Al Reshoud, F. M. A. (2014). *Syrian Civil War: Solving The Prisoner's Dilemma*. (Doctoral Dissertation). Monterey, California: Naval Postgraduate School. p: 27.

⁴⁰ Ryan, C. R. (2004). "Jordan First": Jordan's Inter-Arab Relations And Foreign Policy Under King Abdullah II. *Arab Studies Quarterly*, 43-62. pp: 48-49.

⁴¹ Vaessen, Eline. (2014). *The Syrian Civil War*. (Master Thesis). Erasmus University Rotterdam. p: 63.

⁴² Davis, K. L. (2015). *The Expanding Nature Of The Syrian Civil War: From Poor Policy To Regional Conflict*. (Doctoral Dissertation). Johns Hopkins University. pp: 64-67.

⁴³ Hokayem, E. (2017). *Syria's Uprising And The Fracturing Of The Levant*. Routledge. p: 9.

organized the Free Syrian Army⁴⁴ and many civilian Syrians took up arms to join the opposition. By the end of 2016, more than 4.5 million Syrian refugees had crossed the borders to neighboring countries including Turkey, Iraq, Lebanon, and Jordan. Divisions between secular and religious fighters, and between ethnic groups, continued to complicate the politics of the conflict.⁴⁵

Since the beginning of violence in Daraa province in the south of Syria next to Jordan, Assad accused Jordan of rousing troubles in his country.⁴⁶ However, Jordan's actions towards the situation in Syria were guided by several points that determined its foreign policy in this regard: 1) interests of the kingdom; 2) shortage of resources and poor economy; 3) dealing with the crisis as an internal matter of Syria and not requiring much interference; 4) obligation to host refugees, based on international conventions and laws regarding rescuing and hosting refugees; 5) impact of the crisis on Jordan's security, demography, society, economy, and policy; and lastly 6) the generally changing dynamics in the West Asia region (the alliance policy). Jordan opened 5 camps for Syrian refugees in order to contain the huge number of refugees, with the help of U.N. special agencies and other humanitarian NGOs.⁴⁷

⁴⁴ Haj Omar, H. (2016). *Ideology, Media And Conflict In Political Discourse And Its Translation During The Arab Spring: Syria As A Case Study*. (Doctoral Dissertation). University Of Leeds. p: 58.

⁴⁵ Vaessen, Eline. (2014). *The Syrian Civil War*. (Master Thesis). Erasmus University Rotterdam. p: 63.

⁴⁶ El-Shamayleh, Nisreen. (2013, April 19). *Why Syria's Assad Is Worried About Jordan*. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.com/blogs/middleeast/2013/04/68301.html>

⁴⁷ Al-Horani, Yousif. (2008). *Siasat Al'urdun Alkharijia* [The Jordanian Foreign Policy]. Alrai Center For Studies. Amman. Retrieved from http://www.alraicenter.com/alraicenter.com/user_site/site/view_article.asp?type=2&id=296

As a result of the crisis, Jordan-Syria relations became tensed. The official stance of Jordan was to stand against any Jordanian military intervention, although Jordan officially evicted the Syrian ambassador in 2014. The public also opposed the possibility of the Jordanian government granting any facilities or outposts to any foreign military within its territory. The ambiguous political current in Jordan seeks a balanced policy to avoid an Islamist takeover in Syria. At the same time, Amman retains alignment with Riyadh and must keep playing its role in training and giving logistical services, especially services related to security efforts in intelligence and fighting ISIS.⁴⁸ Jordan has always supported the peace efforts led by international and internal actors of the conflict, and wants to prevent the possibility of Syria being split into a variety of extreme sectarian groups.

4.3.1.2 Jordan's Relations with the Gulf States:

The Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries differ in terms of the nature of their regimes. There are two Kingdoms (Saudi Arabia and Bahrain), two Emirate Principalities (Qatar and Kuwait), one Sultanate (Oman) and one presidential regime (United Arab Emirates). The difference is also found in terms of diversity in political and social growth. There are very conservative countries, and then less conservative countries that have made important progress in terms of social liberation and the principle of political participation. These countries differ in terms of area and population diversity, development and military capabilities, political growth, and political experience. There is also disparity between political elites that no longer belong to one generation.⁴⁹

⁴⁸ Wier Jr, J. S., & Al Reshoud, F. M. A. (2014). *Syrian Civil War: Solving The Prisoner's Dilemma*. (Doctoral Dissertation) Monterey, California: Naval Postgraduate School. p: 30.

⁴⁹ Al-Suwaidi, Jamal Sundus. (1999). *Majlis Altaeawun Alkhalijii Fi Alqarn Alwahid Waleashrun* [GCC Cooperation Council The 21st Century]. The Emirates Center For Studies And Research Strategy. Abu Dhabi. p: 5.

There exist distinguished historical relations between Jordan and the GCC countries. These relations are based on mutual respect, common interests, close cooperation, constant clarity, and continuous coordination among leaders. The Jordanian political experience was the conjunction of Gulf attitudes with the benefit of many of their outlooks.

Due to its geographic location, Jordan has contributed to enhancing the security and stability of all the Gulf States; Jordan has been the first line of defense as a buffer state between the GCC and Israel, serving as a deterrent against the ambitions of Israeli expansion. Jordan constitutes the strategic depth of the Gulf States and vice versa. It has the longest border with Saudi Arabia, along with unity of religion, land, language, history, common interests, and similarity of social structures and political systems.⁵⁰

In the context of the Arab dimension in Jordanian politics, Jordan's approach to its foreign policy was clear and based on the establishment of balanced relations with most of the Arab Gulf countries. Consequently, Jordan contributed to the stability and security of Kuwait in 1962, Bahrain in 1970, and Oman in 1972. Jordan has continued to provide the Gulf States with trained human resources and military training missions that have contributed to the development of military and security forces in most of the GCC countries. This cooperation has created a high level of mutual trust, reflected in Jordan's financial and economic assistance and the development of areas of cooperation in political, economic, and cultural fields.

Ever since King Abdullah II took up his constitutional powers, he sought to strengthen and enhance relations with all the GCC countries. He was able to restore confidence in the lukewarm relations between the two parties affected by the events of the 1991 Gulf War, by visiting these

⁵⁰ Mashaqbah, Ameen. (2003). *Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Al'urduniyat Wadual Majlis Altaeawun Alkhalijii [The Jordanian Foreign Policy And The Gulf Corporation Countries]*. Alhamid Press. Amman. p: 14.

countries. These visits proved successful in restoring confidence, strengthening political, economic, and social relations, and continuing consultation on relevant issues. This diplomacy contributed to increasing the volume of trade exchange, and economic and development cooperation with the GCC countries, as the Jordanian decision-makers took the economic factor into account in directing their relationships with the neighboring countries in general, and the Gulf States in particular.

The issue of Jordan's accession to the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) is very ambiguous. The officials in Jordan and the Gulf rarely speak of that idea, and it is still in debate. It seems that the increasing number of joint agreements between Jordan and the Gulf States is pushing the issue forward. The military, security, and economic contracts, are helping in completion of the process in a manner that satisfies all parties.^{51,52}

4.3.1.3 Jordan-Saudi Arabia Relations:

Jordan is one of the most prominent countries connected to Saudi Arabia, and an excellent ally as it forms the gateway to the north of Saudi Arabia. Jordan is not hesitant of aligning itself with Saudi Arabia and the Gulf, effectively and strongly, especially now that Saudi Arabia stands with the Kingdom of Jordan at all levels.

The relations between the two countries are characterized by the highest level of political and economic; consensus and the maximum extent of interconnectedness, which is not surprising,

⁵¹ Political Editor. (2016, December 3). *Alqimat Alkhalijiat Tuhyi Alniqash Hawl Aindimam Al'urdun Limajlis Altaeawun* [The Gulf Summit Revives The Debate On Jordan's Accession To The GCC]. Alkhaleej Online. Retrieved from <http://alkhaleejonline.net/articles/1480767774947601800/>

⁵² Helfont, S., & Helfont, T. (2012). *Jordan: Between The Arab Spring And The Gulf Cooperation Council*. Orbis, 56(1), 82-95. pp: 82-83.

especially as the Jordanian-Saudi relationship is at its peak.

Data regarding trade exchange between Jordan and Saudi Arabia reveals that their relations are distinct and deep-rooted, and the policies of the two countries are compatible. Saudi Arabia's exports to Jordan in 2015 were valued at about 10 million dollar, while Jordan's exports to Saudi increased from 1.9 billion dollar in 2005 to 3 billion dollar in 2015.⁵³ Saudi's investments in Jordan amounted to about 10 billion dollar, signifying the strength of their relation and status. Besides that, more than 4,000 Saudi students are enrolled in various Jordanian universities. The tourist count from Saudi to Jordan reached about one million and 500 thousand in 2015, on account of security and stability of Jordan which made it a favorite tourist destination.

The Jordan-Saudi Coordinating Council, was formed in April 2016, as part of promising economic alliances between the two countries and is capable of containing crises in the region. In addition to developing and deepening the strategic relations between the two countries, the establishment of the Coordinating Council was aimed at consulting and coordinating on important issues in bilateral, regional, and international politics.

Since 2015, Jordan has been contributing to the Saudi-led intervention in Yemen, along with nine Arab countries, showing its support for Saudi decisions in the operations aimed at maintaining security and stability in Yemen.⁵⁴ The Saudi-Gulf military campaign on the Huthis in Yemen is reshaping some of the most sensitive situations for Jordan. It may serve as a basis

⁵³ Al-Abadi Salah. (2016, September 25). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alsewdy. Namudhaj Farid Lilitaeawun* [The Jordanian - Saudi Relations. A Unique Model For Cooperation] Al-Rai Newspaper. Article. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/1014631>

⁵⁴ Albadarin, Basam. (2015, March 27). *Al'urdunu Bihamas Mae Alsewdyt Fi "Easifat Alhizm" Watawaqueat Bi'iinkhifad Watirat Al'iinfatih Ealaa Tiran Baed Alhamla* [Jordan With Enthusiasm In Saudi Arabia In The War In Yemen, Expectations Of Openness To Iran After The Campaign]. Al-Quds Al-Arabi Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.alquds.co.uk/?p=316992>

for considering the strategic alliance between the Gulf states and the Egyptian regime, where the Yemen crisis is in line with the expression of Jordanian institutions as a tactical "field maneuver" that illustrates the security and strategic cooperation between the Gulf system led by Saudi Arabia.

For the Jordanians, the sudden Saudi campaign against the Huthis in Yemen was an opportunity to review the importance of Jordan to the Gulf system- the international coalition against terrorism, the battle against the organization of ISIS in Iraq and Syria, and devoted military cooperation, specifically in the field of fighter aircrafts between Jordan and Bahrain. The importance of the campaign against the Huthis in terms of the Jordanian situation is that logistically and geographically Jordanian expertise is always available for use when it comes to issues of national security in the Gulf, especially since Jordan has recently been active in calling for military alliances, specifically with the Egyptian regime.

The Gulf military campaign has been widely welcomed in Jordan by various sectors. The welcome from Islamic groups in the country followed the kingdom's experience with terrorist organizations targeting the region, especially the ISIS, which killed a Jordanian pilot. The Jordanian citizens are counting on the country's internal and external security and Arab national security to eliminate terrorism, and stand against any attempts to destabilize the country, especially in light of the difficult circumstances in the region.⁵⁵ Thus, Jordan rushed without hesitation in announcing its participation in air forces formed by Saudi Arabia to prevent the Huthis from taking control of southern Yemen. The Jordanian enthusiasm for the Saudi military

⁵⁵ Al-Manaseer, Nader. (2015, March 30). *Tarhib Shaebiin Wasie Bimusharakat Al'urdun Fi Easifat Alhizm* [A Wide Public Welcome With Jordan's Participation Of Jordan The Saudi Campaign On Yemen]. Retrieved from <https://www.alarabiya.net/ar/arab-and-world/yemen/2015/03/30/عاصفة-الحزم-الأردن-في-عاصفة-الحزم>.Html

program in Yemen appeared to be closer to a “rehearsal” for an Arab-Islamic alliance to counter terrorism, which has openly been called for by King Abdullah II.

4.3.1.4 Jordan-Egypt Relations:

The Egyptian-Jordanian relationship has been balanced over the last few decades, especially after the independence of Jordan in 1946, although it did become mildly disturbed in the 1960s and 1970s. Jordan, with an Egyptian population of 636,000, is one of the largest Egyptian communities in the world, and the number of Jordanians living in Egypt is about 12,000. There are no land borders between the two countries, separated by the Gulf of Aqaba and the Negev desert.⁵⁶ The closest distance between two cities in the two countries is 11 km, the maritime distance between Aqaba and Taba.

Politically, the relationship between the two countries went into some tension and was broken twice in 1972 and 1979 but returned strong, thanks to the revolution of 25 January 2011.

Militarily, Jordan and Egypt fought several wars together against Israel, the most important being the wars of 1948 and 1967. The two countries are connected through several political and military agreements, the most important of which is the Joint Defense Agreement signed on 30 May 1967.⁵⁷ Jordan was one of the first countries to recognize the 30 June revolution, and the Jordanian monarch has visited Cairo nine times since the Sisi came into power.

Jordan and Egypt also participated in the peace process in the Middle East. Several summits and meetings, including the 2005 Sharm Al-Sheikh summit, were held in both countries during the

⁵⁶ Abu Ali, Aldeeb. (2017, February 21). Ishron Maelumat Ean *Alealaqat Almisriat - Al'urduniya* [20 Information About Egyptian-Jordanian Relations]. Elbalad. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.elbalad.news/2635477>. p: 1.

⁵⁷ Ibid: p: 2.

1990s and beyond, with the aim of achieving a settlement of the Palestinian issue. Culturally, the two countries share language, heritage, architecture, cuisine. Aqaba is the most affected by the Egyptian Bedouin culture in Jordan, because of its location on the coast of the sea, and mixing of its people with Egyptian fishermen and traders as well as matrimonial alliances.

Economically, the two countries are bound by several bilateral and regional trade agreements, the most important of which are the Greater Arab Free Trade Area (GAFTA) in 1997, the Bilateral Free Trade Agreement of 1998 that reached full liberalization in early 2005, Agadir in 2004, and others. The bilateral trade exchange is supervised by a joint Jordanian-Egyptian High Committee.⁵⁸ Trade exchange between the two countries was valued at about 656 million dollars in 2015.

Jordan's investments in Egypt amount to more than two billion dollars in various sectors, while Egypt's investments in Jordan amount to one billion dollars. Joint investments between the two countries were valued at about 850 million dollars in 2014, of which about 500 million for Egypt and 350 million for Jordan. In terms of agricultural exchange, Jordan imports several Egyptian agricultural products, mainly rice, potato, onion, guava, and mango. Egypt, on the other hand, imports from Jordan products such as olive oil. The two governments established the Arab Bridge Shipping Company in 1985, along with the Iraqi government, with equal share of the three countries. Individual passage as well as shipping through the Gulf of Aqaba and Nuweiba are continuous. The capital of the company increased several times to reach about 100 million dollars in 2013.

The maritime shipping line is a major entrance for the general imports of Jordan. Export and import by sea freight constitute the largest share of the Jordanian economic balance. In 2004,

⁵⁸ Ibid.

Jordan signed an agreement with Egypt for the supply of 250 million cubic feet of natural gas per day for a period of 15 years, and relied on 80% of the Egyptian gas to generate electricity. Recently, Egypt supported Jordan in consolidating relations with the Group of Common Market for Eastern and Southern Africa (COMESA), which allowed for increased Jordanian exports to the African market through Egypt.

Mutual scholarships are among the most prominent aspects of cooperation between the two sides. Jordanian students in Egyptian universities receive 10 free scholarships in medical school, 15 free scholarships for postgraduate studies in different disciplines, and 15 seats in human medicine each year. The Egyptian students receive 100 scholarships annually, including 20 free scholarships, at various Jordanian public universities. The number of Jordanian students in Egypt is 4,000, including university students, more than 700 students studying advanced courses, while in Jordan there are about 7,000 Egyptian students in different stages of education.⁵⁹ There are no entry visas for Jordanians entering into Egypt, nor is there a visa for Egyptians to enter into Jordan, since the original exempts citizens of both countries from this requirement. Although, there exist controls for the entry of Egyptians into Jordan for certain categories, especially employment.

There are several issues on which the two sides cooperate, especially the Palestinian issue, of which Cairo and Amman are a key party. According to international reference points, they are still seeking to resume the Palestinian-Israeli negotiations to implement the two-state solution and establish a Palestinian state on the borders, with East Jerusalem as its capital. Another issue

⁵⁹ Abu Ali, Aldeeb. (2017, February 21). *Ishron Maelumat Ean Alealaqat Almisriat - Al'urduniya* [20 Information About Egyptian-Jordanian Relations]. Elbalad. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.elbalad.news/2635477>. p: 3.

is terrorism - the two countries share the vision that the efforts of the international community and the Arab and Islamic countries, should be united to deal firmly with the threat of terrorism, extremism, and terrorist organizations, while defending Islam against those who distort its tolerant image. Egypt and Jordan aim to finally renounce violence and extremism and promote tolerance, moderation and acceptance of the other, and stress the centrality of the role of Al-Azhar as a beacon of Islamic thought center.

The third issue concerns the situation in Syria. Egypt and Jordan hold the same view of reaching a comprehensive political solution to the crisis that ends human suffering, preserves unity and territorial integrity of Syria, and prevents the spread of violence.⁶⁰ Bilateral relations between the two countries have witnessed great momentum with meetings of the Joint High Committee, which is the oldest among the Arab committees and the most regular in its successive sessions between Cairo and Amman.

4.3.1.5 Jordan-Iraq Relations:

The Jordanian-Iraqi relations date back to the beginning of the two countries. The Iraqi revolution 1920 brought to the Jordanian leadership the formula of the semi-independent state very early. This was 25 years before the Syrian and Lebanese independence. A joint project between the two countries was hindered by Saudi Arabia and Egypt in the Arab League in 1945.⁶¹ After that, treaty of brotherhood and alliance between the two kingdoms was signed in 1947.

⁶⁰Allam, Mohamad. (2016). *Alealaqat Almisriat - Al'urduniya* [The Egyptian-Jordanian Relations]. Ahram.Org. Egypt. Retrieved from <http://www.ahram.org.eg/news/192009/4/548650/الأردنية-العلاقات-المصرية-قضايا-واراء>.aspx . p: 1.

⁶¹ Khammas. Uday Asaad. (2011). *Alahtlal Alamryky Lleraq Wathrh Ely Alelaqat Aleraqt – Alardnyt* [The American Occupation Of Iraq And Its Impact On The Iraqi - Jordanian Relations 2003-2010]. (Master Thesis). Middle East University. Jordan. p: 22.

The special relationship between Jordan and Iraq was defined by the boundaries of division of the Fertile Crescent region, through the link between the two countries. The British were aiming to secure communication between their areas of influence from Baghdad to Amman to Haifa.⁶²

The geographical, political, and economic connection between the two countries has become an integral part of their history as two states.

The Jordanian-Iraqi relations witnessed phases of tension between 1968 and 1978 but they still involved a fundamental understanding. At a pivotal point for Jordan in 1970, Ba'athist Baghdad took a strategic decision to neutralize the existing Iraqi forces in Jordanian territory, under the Joint Defense Agreement on the conflict between the Jordanian army and the Palestinian organizations. The Ba'athists of Baghdad justified this decision, which stemmed from a deep understanding, particularly by Saddam Hussein, of the supreme interests of the Iraqi state.

Between 1979 and early 2003, Jordanian-Iraqi relation grew like a snowball and went beyond daily politics and its complexities. This relation challenged all pressures exerted by the West and the Gulf States on Amman to reduce its ties with Baghdad. In these two decades, the Jordanian economy relied on cheap Iraqi oil (half a grant and half at a preferential price) financed by Jordanian exports, creating opportunities of employment in industry, agriculture, maritime, land and air transport, trade, financial services, and others. During the Iraq-Iran war and during the siege of the 1990s, Jordan became a vital and the only outlet for Iraq.⁶³ Beyond the economic factor, Jordan and Iraq are also involved a geopolitical alliance that was directed against Iran on

⁶² Ibid: p: 23.

⁶³ Ibid: pp: 39-41.

the Iraqi front and towards Israel from the Jordanian front. For Jordan, Iraq had the strategic depth to withstand Israeli pressure.⁶⁴

Renewing the Iraqi oil grant to Jordan and opening the gate of economic cooperation on preferential bases always saved Jordan, when stuck in bad economic and financial situations. The Iraqi leadership recognized that the recovery of Iraq always came through Jordan by activating the bilateral economic links in several areas of reconstruction in Iraq, and easy and profitable investments in the Jordanian economy. Iraqi investments in Jordan reached about 12 billion dollar in 2013. The economic relations between the two countries are organized on the basis of mutual benefit, but the basic gain for both is the geopolitical context. It is important to renew bilateral relations in a geopolitical context that preserves the peaceful nature of political conflict in Jordan, freeing it from the pressures of neighboring states, solidifying its positive neutrality towards the conflict in Syria, and enhancing its ability to meet the renewed Israeli challenge of Arab fragmentation and weakness, and by saving Jordan and renewing strategic relations with it, Iraq may emerge from the turmoil of local politics.

Regarding the Jordanian stance on the 2003 American invasion, King Abdullah II had advised Washington that invading Iraq would be a ‘tremendous mistake’ that could “throw the whole area into turmoil,”⁶⁵ but the war happened and Jordan received thousands of Iraqi refugees during the invasion, especially families affiliated with the Saddam regime.

⁶⁴ Al-Rawashda, Ali. Alfaza, Ala'a (2013, July 26). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Aleiraqiat: Min Tijarat Alhurub 'Tilaa Sinaeat Almustaqbal* [Jordanian-Iraqi Relations: From Wars's Trade To The Future Making]. Al-Akhbar Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://www.al-akhbar.com/opinion/54835/العلاقات-الأردنية-العراقية-من-تجارة-الحروب-إلى-صناعة-المستقبل>

⁶⁵ Hinnebusch, R., & Quilliam, N. (2006). Contrary Siblings: Syria, Jordan And The Iraq War. *Cambridge Review Of International Affairs*. 19(3), 513-528. p: 518.

In 2004, the Jordanian government started training the Iraqi Police, and in 2005 the relations between the two countries witnessed steady improvement at the level of trade exchange.⁶⁶ For the first time since the war, Jordanian exports to Iraq reached 1.3 billion dollars in 2008; the most important exports included food and raw material. In contrast, Jordan imports chemicals, chemical fertilizers, iron, and aluminum, from Iraq.

The increase in Jordanian-Iraqi trade, has been attributed by economists, to a number of reasons including geographical proximity, facilitation of imports for Iraq through the port of Aqaba, and the unstable situation in southern Iraq in the port of Basra. The presence of a large Iraqi community in Jordan is seen as another reason. The free trade agreement between Iraq and Jordan brought the value of trade exchange to about 1.3 billion dollars in 2012, with Jordanian exports to Iraq accounting for a billion dollars, compared to 268 million dollars worth of imports.⁶⁷ In addition, the memorandum of understanding signed between the two countries in 2008 allowed Jordan to import oil from Iraq at 18 dollars below the world price.

4.3.2 Jordan's Relations with Non-Arab Regional Countries:

4.3.2.1 Jordan-Turkey Relations:

Jordanian-Turkish relations date back to the 1930s, when the founder of Jordan King Abdullah I visited the Turkish Republic in 1937, the first Arab leader to do so after the end of World War I. The Turkish President Mustafa Kemal Atatürk received King Abdullah I to begin the process of building bilateral relations between the two countries.⁶⁸

⁶⁶ Garamone, Jim. (2005). *Jordan Aids In Iraqi Police Training*. The US Department Of Defense. USA p: 1.

⁶⁷ Hatar, Nahid. (2012, June 19). *Aleiraq Wal'urduna... Ruyat Jadidat Lihilf Qadim* [Iraq And Jordan ... A New Vision For An Old Alliance]. Al-Akhbar Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://al-akhbar.com/opinion/71175>

⁶⁸ Oglu, Mohammad. (2017, December 6). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alturkiata. 'Asasiha Almadi Waeunwanuha Almustaqbal* [The Jordanian-Turkish Relations: Based On The Past And Looking For Future]. Raialyoum Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/العلاقات-الأردنية-التركية-أساسها-الم>

The first Turkish embassy in Amman was opened after an agreement was signed between the leaders of the two countries, King Abdullah I and President İsmet İnönü, in 1947. The relations between the two countries have a strategic strength, with history and shared values that have contributed to maintaining strong bilateral relations. These relations witnessed remarkable development during the time of the Justice and Development Party (AK Parti), which was characterized by mutual respect, interspersed with visits between officials of both countries.

In December 2009, former Turkish President Abdullah Gul visited Jordan and later on King Abdullah II visited Turkey in March 2013. The two leaders discussed regional and international affairs, in addition to the bilateral relations between their own countries. In 2014, activities and areas of joint cooperation between the two countries increased, and hundreds of Jordanian military officers received military training in Turkey.⁶⁹ Both Jordan and Turkey share Arab military alliances led by Saudi Arabia. The two countries are working under the umbrella of the Washington-led international coalition to strike in Iraq and Syria.^{70,71}

According to official figures, the value of Turkish investments that flowed into the Hashemite Kingdom stood at 283 million dollar in 2015, concentrated in services, information technology, food industries, and infrastructure.⁷² Jordan wants its economic relationship with Turkey to be a partnership and not a competitive relationship due to instability in the region. A free trade

⁶⁹ Ibid. p: 2.

⁷⁰ Editorial Team. (2016, March 28). *Khmsat 'Asyilat Tashrah Lak Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alturkia* [Five Questions Explain Jordanian-Turkish Relations]. Noonpost.Org. Jordan. p: 2.

⁷¹ Aloudah, H. S. (2016). *Understanding The Sources Of Turkish Foreign Policy Change Towards The Middle East During The Justice And Development Party (AKP) Era: An Empirical Examination*. (Phd Theis In Politics). University Of Exeter. UK. p: 185.

⁷² Turkish Ministry Of Foreign Affairs. (2015). *Turkey-Jordan Economic And Trade Relations*. Retrieved from http://www.mfa.gov.tr/turkey_s-commercial-and-economic-relations-with-jordan.en.mfa

agreement, signed between the two countries in 2009 and enforced in March 2011, played a strategic role in boosting relations and pushing both the economies forward.

Jordan is experiencing difficult economic conditions, exacerbated by the region's crises, especially since the kingdom is in close proximity with the most troubled countries and this has repercussions for the economic situation. Jordan seeks to strengthen economic relations with the Muslim world. The Kingdom believes that Turkey can contribute effectively to the economic growth process by involving its companies in the process of construction and development, as well as investors' contributions in supporting and developing infrastructure and increasing trade exchange between the two countries. In line with this perspective, the former Turkish Prime Minister Ahmet Davutoğlu visited Jordan in 2016 to discuss prospects of cooperation between the two countries in various fields. During the visit a package of joint agreements was signed, which contributed to enhancing joint cooperation.⁷³

The Turks look forward to the partnership with Jordan to achieve stability in the region as well as to open trade routes that pass through the Jordanian territories and ports, towards the Arab Gulf States. Jordan is also looking forward to opening trade between Jordan and the Balkans and the EU through the ports and Turkish territories.⁷⁴ Amman and Ankara are seeking to activate

⁷³ Jordan News Agency, Petra. (2016, March 27). *Jordan, Turkey Sign Dozen Agreements To Enhance Ties*. Retrieved from http://www.petra.gov.jo/public_news/nws_newsdetails.aspx?site_id=1&lang=2&newsid=245493&catid=13&type=home>ype=1

⁷⁴ Oglu, Mohammad. (2017, December 6). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alturkiata. 'Asasiha Almadi Waeunwanuha Almustaqbal* [The Jordanian-Turkish Relations: Based On The Past And Looking For Future]. Raialyoum Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/العلاقات-الأردنية-التركية-أساسها-الم/>

the RO-RO shipping line⁷⁵ between the Jordanian cities of Aqaba and Scandinavia, based on the agreement between the two countries in March 2016.

Apart from the volume of trade exchange between the two countries, regional issues remain at the top of all the discussions between the two countries' officials. Given Turkey's position in the Muslim and Middle East countries, Jordan sees Turkey's political stability as support for the security and political stability of the region.⁷⁶ The failed coup attempt in Turkey in July 2016, further reinforced the interdependence of the two countries.

The official position of Jordan is no different from its populace. The Jordanian government expressed its concern about the unrest in Turkey, and stressed that the stability of Turkey is an important factor in the stability and security of the region and has a positive role in consolidating efforts to strengthen cooperation between its countries and people.

In terms of regional affairs, especially Syrian crisis, Turkey and Jordan, being Syria's neighbors, are most affected by what is happening there. Jordan hosts about 1.3 million Syrian refugees, while Turkey has about 3 million.

There is a difference in the point of view of Jordan and Turkey regarding the Syrian crisis. Both Jordan and Turkey have long borders with Syria,⁷⁷ and the armed opposition controls the border crossings. Turkey faces a threat to Kurdish forces that have declared federalism on the territory it controls, and is trying to expand the annexation of the city of Aleppo. Jordan, on the other hand,

⁷⁵ RORO Shipping Linst Is A Term For Roll-On Roll-Off Cargo Which Is Driven On And Off A Vessel. RORO Cargo Consists Of Items Such As Tractors, Buses And Trucks, Or Oversized Cargo Loaded On Special Flatbed, Mafi Or Lowboy Trailers. Source Retrieved from <https://www.shipit.com/our-services/ocean-freight/ro-ro-shipping/>.

⁷⁶ Political Editor. (2017, August 19). *Jordan Visit: Erdogan In New Push For Syria Peace*. Arab News. Retrieved from <http://www.arabnews.com/node/1147186/middle-east>

⁷⁷ Siddiq, Hadeel. (2016, March 27). *'Uwghlu Fi Emman Li'iidhabat Aljalid Bayn Al'urdun Waturkia* [Oglu In Amman To Melt The Ice Between Jordan And Turkey]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/reportsandinterviews/2016/3/27/أوغلو-في-عمان-لإذابة-الجليد-بين-الأردن-وتركيا>

is afraid of the control of ISIS or its supporters of armed opposition factions. Turkey, which had great influence on the opposition powers in the north of Syria,⁷⁸ had suspended diplomatic relations with Damascus in 2012, and the ambassadors of the two countries were withdrawn due to the hostility in Turkey-Syria relations.⁷⁹ Both, Jordan and Turkey have emphasized on stopping the bloodshed in Syria, with Jordan still calling for resolution of the crisis peacefully with a transitional phase involving all parties.

4.3.2.2 Jordan-Iran Relations:

The Jordanian-Iranian relations go back to 1949 when a diplomatic exchange took place between the two countries. The relationship, which was characterized by cooperation, understanding, and partnership, was greatly influenced by regional events after the Iranian revolution.⁸⁰ The relations between Jordan and Iran have fluctuated quite often, and the early 1990s witnessed the best situation between the two countries. Triggered by the regional policies and wars, the positions of these two countries kept swinging politically and strategically based on specific situations.⁸¹ Jordan is part of the axis of moderation because of the peace treaty with Israel, and recognizes the Palestinian Authority and the PLO as a legitimate representative of the Palestinians. Jordan also has an alliance with the United States. Iran, on the other hand, is in contradiction with the West in general and

⁷⁸ Mahfoud, Akil. (2012). *Syria-Turkey: Turning Point Or Historical Bet*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Studies. Doha Institute. pp: 58-59.

⁷⁹ Hinnebusch, R. (2015). Back To Enmity: Turkey-Syria Relations Since The Syrian Uprising. *Orient, Journal Of German Orient Institute*. pp: 19-20.

⁸⁰ Thannoon, Fawaz Mwaffaq. (2007). *Alelaqat Al'urdunyat Al'irania* [The Jordanian-Iranian Relations 1980-2003]. Regional Studies Center (RSC). . Mosul University. Iraq. ISSN: 18134610. Vol: 32. p: 191.

⁸¹ Al-Mobidien, Mohannad. (2016, December 27). *Jordan-Iran Relations: History And Future*. International Institute For Iranian Studies. p: 1

recognizes Hamas as a legitimate representative of Palestine, which put Iran in the axis of opposition. So, regional conflicts have had a major role in influencing Jordan-Iran relations.⁸²

Historically, Jordan and Iran signed several treaties, notably the Cultural Cooperation Agreement in 1960, the Trade Cooperation in 1963, the Cooperation in Financial Issues in 1973, and the Tourism Cooperation Convention in 1975, which were not implemented as a result of the 1979 revolution. The Palestinian-Israeli conflict affected the relations between Jordan and Iran, and it seems that the relations were disrupted by regional policies at the time because of Iran's recognition of the State of Israel during the Shah's reign in 1960.⁸³ The relations between the two countries have returned to normal in an atmosphere of cooperation. The Shah affirmed his full support for Jordan in the process of restoring peace and the return of the Palestinian territories to its owners. This positivity endured until the success of the Iranian revolution on 12 February 1979. With the fall of Shah Mohammad Reza Pahlavi and the establishment of the Islamic Republic, King Hussein sent a cable of congratulations to the new system on the anniversary of the revolution, recognized the Islamic system and the new Islamic Republic.⁸⁴

In 1980, when the Iran-Iraq war broke out, relations between Jordan and Iran deteriorated again and were brought to a rupture. One of the most important motives for Jordan lending its support to Iraq in its war against Iran, was that Jordan saw this war as a barrier to

⁸² Ibid.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Abu Talib, Hassan. (1979, February). Ealaa Hamish Alhurb: Altaqarub Aleiraq Al'urduny. [On The Sidelines Of The War: The Jordanian-Iraqi Rapprochement.] *The International Politics Magazine*, Cairo, Vol: 63, p: 114.

exporting the Iranian revolution to the region. The Islamic Republic of Iran supported resistance factions such as Hezbollah in southern Lebanon and later Hamas in Palestine, which nullified the political role of Jordan on the Palestinian issue. Syria's position of supporting Iran in its war on Iraq, was seen by Jordan as a move to impose control of Iran on the whole region. Jordan was in the middle of this mess between the two biggest threats: Israel and Iran, which led to its stance of supporting Iraq to secure its borders and territorial integrity from any possible hegemony.⁸⁵

After the death of Khomeini in 1989, Iran's foreign policy under the rule of Hashemi Rafsanjani began to change, with improving foreign relations with many countries, and the idea of exporting the revolution seemed to have ended. This led Jordan to re-establish relations with Iran. The Gulf war in 1991 had a major impact on the restoration of Iranian-Jordanian relations. Jordan's representative at the United Nations, Marwan al-Qasim, continued with the Iranian side to find a common position on the Gulf War.⁸⁶ Jordan closed the offices of "MKO" in opposition to Iran, and ended any privileges and facilities given to them. The Jordanian-Iranian relations witnessed another sharp deterioration with the signing of the Wadi Araba Treaty with Israel. Later, in 2003, King Abdullah II met with Mohammad Khatami in Tehran; this visit was seen as a Jordanian mediation between Iran and the United States to restore relations and ways of dialogue on the Iranian nuclear file.

⁸⁵ Salma, Adnan. et al. (2011) *Mawqif Alduwal Alerbyat Min Alharb Aleiraqyat Al'iiraniati*. [The Position Of The Arab Countries On The Iraqi-Iranian War.] *Journal Of Art, Dhi Qar*, Vol. 3. p: 183.

⁸⁶ Al-Qur'an, Saleh. (1993). *Almawqif Alurduni Min Azmit Alkhalij*. [The Jordanian Stance From The Gulf Crisis]. (Master Thesis). The Jordanian University. p: 55.

Since the restoration of relations, the Iranian influence had no chance of growing in Jordan due to Jordan's concern over security and internal peace. However, the US invasion of Iraq greatly affected the increase in Shiites. Most of the refugee families in Jordan are known to be Shiites, and this is affecting the indigenous population. Statistics reveal that 30 families from Baqa'a camp have been converted to Shiite sect, as well as some families in Irbid and Madaba Salt and Zarqa.⁸⁷ This sect has always favored separation as a rule. Jordan passed the permissible line and began to ring alarms, especially after 2005.

After the events of the Arab Spring, which began in 2011, Jordan has become very concerned about the role of Iran in Damascus, Baghdad, Beirut, and Sana'a. After a break of seven years, in an effort to restore the relationship between the two countries, Iranian Foreign Minister Mohammed Jawad Zarif visited Jordan in 2014. On the other hand, in 2015, Jordanian Foreign Minister Nasser Judeh visited Tehran to meet with President Hassan Rowhani to discuss ways to combat terrorism and extremism.⁸⁸ In the same year, Jordan welcomed the nuclear agreement which Iran had signed with the West in Vienna in July 2015⁸⁹.

⁸⁷ Al-Hantoli, Amer. (2010, February 10). *Al'ardunn: Tamadud Shiaeiuun Siasium Wadiniun. Wal'aedad Mutadaribatan*. [Jordan: Shiite Political And Religious Expansion. Conflicting Numbers]. Retrieved from <http://elaph.com/web/news/2010/2/533563.html>

⁸⁸ Aljazeera. Net. (2016, April 19). *Al'urduniyat Al'iiraniata..Mahattat Min Altawatur Walhidhr*. [The Jordanian-Iranian Relations. Stations Of Tension And Caution]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/encyclopedia/events/2016/4/19/العلاقات-الأردنية-الإيرانية-محطات-من-التوتر-والحذر>

⁸⁹ Ammonnews.Net. (2015, July 20). *Al'urdun Yurahib Bialaitifaq Alnawawii Bayn 'Tiran Walduwal Alkubraa*. [Jordan Welcomes Nuclear Agreement Between Iran And Great Powers]. Retrieved from <http://www.ammonnews.net/article/236926>

There are of course some differences between the two countries and their political perspective on what is happening in the region, especially the Syrian crisis, the Palestinian issue and the Israeli-Arab conflict. Jordan was very cautious about Iran's attempts to impose its influence in the region after Lebanon, Syria, Iraq, and Yemen. The Jordanian-Iranian relations remain cordial, while some tension and estrangement remain on account of a number of reasons including different interests, regional and international relations, and the support of different parties. While King Abdullah II warned of the danger of Iran's expansion in the Arab region,⁹⁰ Jordan did not deviate from the Arab vision led by Saudi Arabia for Arab national security, as the kingdom is an important ally of Arab Sunni Alliance led by Saudi Arabia against the Shiite alliance led by Iran.^{91,92} In fact, it is the second strongest ally to Syria after Russia, and works with other allies to ensure that the Syrian regime is not be toppled.⁹³

4.3.2.3 Jordan-Israel Relations:

The official diplomatic relations between Jordan and Israel first commenced in 1994 when the peace treaty between the two countries was signed. Prior to this treaty, their relations were not public⁹⁴. The signing of the Jordanian-Israeli peace treaty was preceded by a meeting in

⁹⁰ Noonpost.Org. (2016, November 29). Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'iiraniata.. 'Ayn Taltaqi Wa'ayn Takhtafi?. [The Jordanian-Iranian Relations: Where To Meet And Disappear?]. Retrieved From <https://www.noonpost.org/content/15352>

⁹¹ Ryan, C. (2012). *The New Arab Cold War And The Struggle For Syria*. Middle East Report, 262, 28-31. p: 1-3.

⁹² Gause III, F. G. (2014). *Beyond Sectarianism: The New Middle East Cold War*. Brookings Doha Center Analysis Paper, 11, 1-27. pp: 12-15.

⁹³ Goodarzi, J. M. (2013). *Syria And Iran: Alliance Cooperation In A Changing Regional Environment*. OrtadoğU EtüTleri, 4(2). p: 52.

⁹⁴ Shtewi, Bothaina. (2016, November 29). 'Iisrayiyl Walerb: Sifarat Rasmiat Wamakatib Qunsuliat Tabadul Tijariin [Israel And The Arabs: Official Embassies, Consular Offices And Commercial Exchanges]. Sasapost. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.sasapost.com/israel-has-diplomatic-ties-with-arabs/> p: 1.

Washington three months prior, between the late King Hussein and Prime Minister Yitzhak Rabin, where the two leaders announced the end of the status of war between their countries.

Jordan believes that Israel and Palestine should continue to negotiate with a view to reaching a just and lasting agreement that will lead to the establishment of a Palestinian state, and will deal with the suffering of the Palestinian people, alongside Israel.⁹⁵ On the other hand, Jordan stresses the need for Israel to take concrete steps to improve the living and economic situation of Palestinians, and to remove the obstacles to the peace process, notably settlement activity in the West Bank including East Jerusalem and the siege of Gaza.

Jordan-Israel relations are affected by the Palestinian-Israeli conflict and the issue of refugees, the Israeli separation wall, the Arab peace initiative, the settlements, and Jordan's position on Jerusalem. Jordan regards Jerusalem as occupied territory,⁹⁶ and due to Wadi Araba agreement, Israel must respect the special role of Jordan in Jerusalem.

The treaty between Jordan and Israel marked the beginning of a new era of peaceful relations between the two countries; it has brought economic, academic, and agricultural, peace and cooperation between the two countries. These relations alternated between tense, unstable, better, stable and then tense again. The problems in the bilateral relations between Amman and Tel Aviv arose from the Jordanian popular position opposed to normalization with Israel, and the latter's failure to respond to the Arab peace initiative adopted by the Arabs at the Beirut Summit in 2002. Jordan supported the roadmap and urges Israel as well as Palestine to take necessary steps to meet their commitments outlined in the road map.

⁹⁵ Al-Alaf, Ibrahim. (2008). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat -Alasrayylyt :Insha'atuha Watatawuruha* [Jordanian-Israeli Relations: The Origins And Development]. *Elhewar*. Issue: 2206 - 2008/2/29. p: 2.

⁹⁶Ibid: p: 3.

At this point, the final status negotiations failed. The Al-Aqsa intifada broke out as a result of Ariel Sharon's visit to the holy shrine, which soon ignited bloody confrontations between the Palestinians and the Israelis.⁹⁷ As a result of the failure of the understanding with Israel, Jordan announced the suspension of procedures for the appointment of a new Jordanian ambassador to Israel, and Israel reduced the number of diplomats at its embassies in Jordan.

Israel has so far failed to respond to the Arab peace initiative adopted by all Arab countries in 2002; Israel carried out two military operations that year, during which Israel reoccupied the cities of the West Bank. The peace treaty was breached in more than one area, including the articles which emphasized the role of Jordan in Jerusalem, and the processes of changing the features of Jerusalem and the displacement of its Arab population. All of these pulled down the Jordanian-Israeli relations.

Jordan calls for Israel to accept the peace initiative presented by the Arab states as Jordan believes that the initiative addresses the Israeli concerns, especially security, ending the conflict and ending all claims from all sides.⁹⁸ This initiative calls for Israel's withdrawal from the Palestinian, Syrian, and Lebanese territories to the borders of 1967, in addition to the establishment of an independent Palestinian state with East Jerusalem as its capital, and a just solution to the question of Palestinian refugees on the basis of relevant United Nations resolutions. Jordan believes that normal relations with Israel can be established and that a peace agreement can be achieved, thus achieving security for all countries in the region.

⁹⁷ Al-Kilani, Mahmoud. (2015, August 23). *Hal Tantazie Dawlat Alaihtilal Alwisayat Ealaa Al'aqsa Min Al'ardin?* [Will The Occupation State Take Over Al-Aqsa From Jordan?] *Noonpost.Org*. Jordan. p: 1.

⁹⁸ Podolsky, Philip. (2012, September 26): *Jordan's King Urges Israel To Accept Arab Peace Initiative*. The Times Of Israel. Retrieved from <https://www.timesofisrael.com/jordans-king-urges-peace-between-israel-and-palestinians/>

In addition to the popular movement that rejects normalization, the Islamists who lead most of the opposition forces from parties and unions in the peace treaty see a threat to Jordan. The rejection of normalization with Israel in Jordan takes an organized form through the anti-normalization committees of trade unions that impose a comprehensive boycott of Israel politically, economically and culturally.⁹⁹

4.3.2.4 Jordan-US Relations:

The roots of the Jordanian-American relations go back to 1945 when the United States emerged as a superpower after its victory in World War II. It presented itself as the leader of the free world and saw that the limits of its national security extend to the whole world. The most important goal was to prevent the Soviet tide from reaching the Middle East and the oil-rich Arabian Peninsula, where the US had the conviction that those that controlled the region could control the European continent.¹⁰⁰

Jordanian-American relations began with Jordan's rejection of the communist rule. Jordan was opposing the influence of the Soviet Union for ideological reasons and the US interest in Jordan was built over strategic reasons. The geographical location of Jordan gave US the benefit to implement its foreign policy in the region. The relations between Jordan and America have achieved undeniable benefits. American aid has enabled Jordan to overcome its economic crises, and helped it to develop its infrastructure and armed forces, while also helping Jordan to manage its response to pressure from political and geostrategic factors.

⁹⁹ Al-Alaf, Ibrahim. (2008). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat -Alasrayylyt: Insha'atuha Watatawuruha* [Jordanian-Israeli Relations: The Origins And Development], *Elhewar*. Issue: 2206 - 2008/2/29. p: 3.

¹⁰⁰ Hajjaj, Khalil. (2009). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'amrikiat Dirasat Tarikhiatan Fi Aleawamil Alsiyasiat Walathar Altanmawiat 1975-1985* [The Jordanian-American Relations: A Historical Study Of The Political And Development Factors 1975-1985]. *Humanities And Social Studies*. Jordan University. Vol: 36. No. 1. p: 3.

The US viewed Jordan as an asset, given its interests in the region, especially since the two countries expressed their opposition to the Soviet ideology. In the mid-1950s, even though a group of Arab states linked themselves with the Soviet Union, Jordan continued to maintain its alliance with the West. King Hussein always rejected communism, and believed that the only way to preserve and defend his country was by alliances. He also took a positive view of the Eisenhower Doctrine and the accompanying economic project; he found it to be an important factor that would improve the economic situation of Jordan. It also helped reduce the influence of the Communists and quell the political turmoil that accompanied the resignation of the government of Suleiman Al-Nabulsi in 1957.

So King Hussein stayed pro-American, and Jordan received financial and military assistance as part of this alliance, and practiced joint exercises and mutual training.¹⁰¹ Although the relations between Jordan and America did go through disturbances several times, especially during the Arab-Israel wars and the 1991 Kuwait liberation war, when the US left Jordan as payback for standing with Iraq,¹⁰² in the early 1990s Jordan had declared its neutrality in the Gulf War and maintained relations with Iraq. Now though, there exists substantial military cooperation between the two countries, especially against terrorism.¹⁰³ This Jordanian-American alliance can be summed up as an attempt to prevent the spread of the Soviet Union's influence in the region and to bring about peace after the end of the Arab-Israel conflict.

¹⁰¹ Sharp, J. M. (2013). *Jordan: Background And US Relations*. Congressional Research Service. p: 14.

¹⁰² Gani, J. K. (2011). *Understanding And Explaining US-Syrian Relations: Conflict And Cooperation, And The Role Of Ideology*. (Doctoral Dissertation). The London School Of Economics And Political Science (LSE). p: 279.

¹⁰³ Xinhua. (2016, May 15). *Jordan, U.S. Discusses Cooperation In Fight Against Islamic State*. Retrieved from http://news.xinhuanet.com/english/2016-05/15/c_135360924.htm

Despite the political pressure on Jordan, it could abandon foreign aid if there was an Arab alternative. However, the unavailability of such alternative and the interruption of Arab assistance when needed, obligated Jordan to maintain a positive and ideal relationship with the US. Considering the Arab-Israel conflict and the joint efforts to resolve it, this relationship was stable and intimate.

The Jordanian-American relations system were based on complementing political trajectories. The Jordanian political discourse that Jordan, along with the Arab and Islamic nations, sought to resolve its issues, and build its strength and self in order to defend itself against future risks and challenges. Jordan seeks political and diplomatic moves that can achieve just, comprehensive, and balanced peace that guarantees justice for people and security of states, on the basis of the principles of justice in accordance with the provisions and resolutions of international law.¹⁰⁴

The Palestinian case has taken absolute priority on its foreign policy agenda, especially with the United States. The alliance was built on the basis of the Jordanian assessment of the support that the US as a superpower, can provide to international efforts of bringing peace and ending the suffering of the Palestinian people.¹⁰⁵ Jordan viewed the US administration's policy in the Middle East as moving towards its objectives through constructive cooperation with the Arab world.

Based on what the US can offer in terms of political, military, and economic assistance, Jordan's relations with the country are of great significance, but were not serious until the British role

¹⁰⁴ Alorani, Abdelraheem. (2012, May 3). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'amirkiat Fi Eahad Almlk Eibad Allah Althaany 1999-2012* [Jordanian - American Relations In The Era Of King Abdullah II 1999-2012]. Alrai Newspaper. Jordan. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/507983/2012-1999---عبد-الله-الثاني>

¹⁰⁵ Ibid: p: 8.

declined and then completely subsided. Jordan has been a key US partner in the Middle East since the 1960s when the US considered Jordan to be one of the countries that followed the pattern of free trade and appreciated the GATT agreement. The Jordanian-American relations took a new direction in 1985, which was also a milestone for Jordan's foreign policy as King Hussein, on the United Nations' panel, announced his will to hold direct talks with Israel.¹⁰⁶

Since then, relations between the US and Jordan have been strong. The United States annually allocates 360 million dollar of its budget to Jordan, and an additional 100 million since the events of the Arab Spring in 2011. The two countries entered into an agreement to turn Jordan into a major non-NATO ally.¹⁰⁷ Recently, Jordan also signed a free trade agreement with the US.

The decisions and policy of Jordan depend on economic assistance from America, Europe, and the Gulf States; the kingdom's foreign policy is guided by the desire to maintain good relations with these countries to keep the aid coming in. As it does not enjoy complete sovereignty, Jordan's foreign policy is entering a very complicated domain, with changes in the regional and international environment amidst a state of divisions and alliances. Nevertheless, foreign policy decisions are made with the goal of maintaining stability in the face of these challenges.

The United States' commitment to peace has kept Jordan afloat in the American orbit. The country has initiated financial aid to Jordan more than once in order to prevent it from collapsing, which might lead to a series of events that would destroy the prospects for peace in the region. It has also recently invested in the relationship with Jordan for direct or indirect involvement in the

¹⁰⁶ Editorial Team. (2016, December 3). *Al'urdunu Walwilayat Almutahida .. Almasalih Almutaqatiea* [Jordan And The United States. Cross-Cutting Interests]. Levant Research Institute. Montreal-Canada. p: 1.

¹⁰⁷ Ibid. p: 1.

Syrian crisis; United States' real interest and concern in the Syria conflict is preserving the security of Israel.¹⁰⁸

King Abdullah II, for the most part, followed the same policies that were created by King Hussein. The relations between Jordan and the US during the reign of King Abdullah II, are based on mutual interests.¹⁰⁹ The dialogues and meetings held by the leaders of the two countries from time to time in Washington and Amman, are focused on aligning their vision, and on constructive debate, ideas, and proposals that can translate the hopes and aspirations of people to build a human society with peace, security, and stability. The King also relied on United States' support to create the Palestinian national territory.¹¹⁰

4.3.2.5 Jordan-Russia Relations:

The diplomatic relations between Jordan and the Soviet Union were initiated by Jordan in 1963. On 16 February 1992, Jordan recognized Russia as the successor to the Soviet Union. The two countries have established friendly relations and cooperation over many years.¹¹¹ Their political relations are identical to their respective positions on most international issues, especially on the issue of the settlement of the crisis in the Middle East region.

The Jordanian-Russian political relations were at their peak during the last ten years. For Jordan's leadership, the Russian military presence in Syria works in their interest of keeping Jordan safe.

¹⁰⁸ Aarts, J. A. (2015). *Saving The Libyans And Skipping The Syrians, What's The Deal With That?* (Master Thesis). University Leiden, The Netherlands. p: 32.

¹⁰⁹ Alorani, Abdelraheem. (2012, May 3). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'amirkiat Fi Eahad Almlk Eibad Allah Althaany 1999-2012* [Jordanian - American Relations In The Era Of King Abdullah II 1999-2012]. Alrai Newspaper. Jordan. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/507983/2012-1999>---عهد-الملك-عبد-الله-الثاني-العلاقات-الأردنية-الأميركية-في-عهد-الملك-عبد-الله-الثاني

¹¹⁰ Al-Faiz, Thiab. (2013). *Alealaqat Al'urdunit-Al'amrikiat Wafaquha Almustaqbalia [Jordanian – American Relations And Its Future Prospects]*. (Master Thesis). Middle East University. p: 78.

¹¹¹ Kreutz, A. (2007). *Russia In The Middle East: Friend Or Foe?* Greenwood Publishing Group. p: 40.

The leaders of the two countries, the King of Jordan and the Russian president, have exchanged several diplomatic visits, and their view of the two main issues in the region, i.e., the Palestinian-Israeli conflict and the Syrian Crisis, is nearly identical. This similarity of thought is a result of the longstanding historical relations between the two countries.

Jordan and Russia agree that the best solution for the Palestinian issue is finding a secure way through the two-state solution.¹¹² They concur on the right of Palestinian refugees to returning back and seeking compensation, the freezing of settlements, the release of detainees, the adoption of East Jerusalem as the capital of the State of Palestine, and the adoption of Security Council resolution 242.

During the Syrian crisis, Jordan was chosen by the participants at the Vienna Conference to prepare a list of terrorist organizations in Syria because of Jordan's ability to maintain security and stability despite its complex population structure and increasing complexity due to the influx of hundreds of thousands of refugees from Iraq and Syria. Having been subjected to the occupation of Iraq, and the Syrian crisis and its transformation into war,¹¹³ Jordan security services hold huge amount of intelligence information on account of direct contact with regional issues in Iraq, Syria, Palestine, and Lebanon, in addition to receiving refugees and politicians from these countries and being the gateway for the Gulf countries towards southern Syria.

Jordan remained very conservative for the Syrian government and Bashar al-Assad; Jordan serves as the backyard for the work of military formations operating in southern Syria. There

¹¹² Ibid. p: 3.

¹¹³ Editorial Team. (2015, November 17). *Limadha Aukhtir Al'urdunu Munasiqaan Liqayimat Almunazamat Al'iirhabiat Fi Suria?* [Why Were Jordan Chosen As Coordinator Of The List Of Terrorist Organizations In Syria?] Arabic.Rt.Com. Retrieved from [https://arabic.rt.com/news/800646-الأردن-منسقا-للقائمة-المنظمات-الإرهابية-سوريا/](https://arabic.rt.com/news/800646-الأردن-منسقا-للقائمة-المنظمات-الإرهابية-سوريا)

were reports of Jordan preventing the control of Al-Nusra Front and the Free Syrian Army at the northern border with Syria. Jordan's participation in the US-led international coalition in order to strike at Damascus and against ISIS,¹¹⁴ does not object the Russian air strikes and has joint coordination centers.

Jordan and Russia also share strategic military relations, reflected in Jadra Equipment and Defense Systems, a subsidiary of the Cadbury Investment Group of the King Abdullah II Center for Design and Development. The company is a Jordanian-Russian joint project, for the development and manufacture of anti-armor rockets. The company was opened in 2013, and its first product was NESAB 32, an RPG weapon. Prior to that, military-technical cooperation between Russia and Jordan focused on the production of rocket-propelled grenade RPG-3 (Hashim). Jadra Company also sought to purchase eight Sukhawi SuperJet aircrafts from Russian civil aircraft company.¹¹⁵

Economically, the Jordanian-Russian relations focus on partnership in the areas of nuclear energy, food security projects, and the promotion of Russian tourism. Jordan relies on Russian expertise in nuclear energy, to build the Jordan reactor due to be completed in 2018. The peaceful nuclear reactor is being developed for the purpose of supplying electricity and desalinating water, with assistance amounting to 7 billion dollars from Russia and other international parties.¹¹⁶ The company that bought the reactor, Rosatom State Nuclear Power Company, is based in Moscow

¹¹⁴ Ibid. p: 2.

¹¹⁵ Abu Hamad, Ahmad. (2015). *Jordan And Russia: An Economic Consensus Before Politics*. Ammanet.Net. Amman. p: 1.

¹¹⁶ Alotom, Hosam. (2017, September 30). Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alruwsiat Waeumq Almustaqbal [Jordanian-Russian Relations And The Depth Of The Future]. Retrieved from <https://www.ammonnews.net/article/333831>

and will contribute 49.9% of the total cost of the project, while the Government of Jordan will contribute 50.1% of the cost of the plant to build two reactors, each with a capacity of producing 1000 MW of electricity.

During the Jordanian-Russian Higher Committee meeting in Moscow, a customs agreement was signed between the two sides, under which they agreed on facilitating customs exchange between the two countries. Russia also seeks passage to Jordan through its national carrier, to reduce the high cost of transportation through Royal Jordanian Airlines which operates three weekly flights from Moscow to Jordan.¹¹⁷ Jordan, on the other hand, is keen on increasing in the number of Russian tourists entering the kingdom; official data indicate that Russia's share of the total flow of tourism to Jordan is 5%.

4.3.3 Jordan's Policies to Main Issues:

4.3.3.1 Jordan's Policy towards the Palestinian-Israeli Conflict:

The Jordanian diplomacy had several issues with the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. As a fixed principle of Jordan's foreign policy with Israel, Jordan believes that the Palestinian Liberation Organization (PLO) represented by the Palestinian National Authority is the legitimate representative of the Palestinian people, and it will continue to support Palestinians until the establishment of their state on the 1967 borders. Jordan continues to call on the international community, especially the donor countries, to support the Palestinian National Authority's efforts to establish a state on Palestinian soil. It also call upon the Israeli government to take necessary actions to facilitate the work of Palestinian National Authority in implementing and maintaining

¹¹⁷ Abu Hamad, Ahmad. (2015). *Jordan And Russia: An Economic Consensus Before Politics*. Ammannet.Net. Amman. p: 1.

the road map obligations. Jordan strongly rejects the alternative homeland theory, and stresses the right of refugees to return and to compensation. This stance has proven detrimental to Jordan-Israel relations.

Jordan rejects all forms of targeting civilians in Palestine and emphasizes the cessation of all such operations. It continues to condemn these operations as a moral and political mistake. Jordan believes that security cannot be used as a pretext for collective punishment policies, and that Israel must realize that resorting to military and security approaches will only deepen hatred and generate violence in the West Bank, Gaza and East Jerusalem.¹¹⁸

Jordan considers the land of Jerusalem occupied in 1967 to be Arab territory and affirms that Israel's occupation of the West Bank is illegal under international law, and in particular under Security Council resolutions 242 and 338. Also, Israel's control and annexation of East Jerusalem is contrary to international law. Jordan affirms its historic responsibility to preserve Islamic holy sites and is wholly committed to it.¹¹⁹ Jordan holds the opinion that any violation of Arab and Islamic identity and any attempt to change this identity is totally unacceptable, and the rights of the three monotheistic religions must be respected equally.

Jordan hosts the largest percentage of Palestinian refugees, a total of 1.8 million (UNRWA estimates), that is 90% of the total displaced population.¹²⁰ The issue of Palestinian refugees, is

¹¹⁸ MEE Staff. (2014, July 9). Mixed International Responses To Escalating Israel-Gaza Tensions. Retrieved from <http://www.middleeasteye.net/news/international-reaction-escalating-israeli-gazan-battle-1687358451>

¹¹⁹ See: Full Text Of The *Jordanian-Palestinian Agreement On Holy Places In Jerusalem*. Latin Patriarchate Of Jerusalem. (2003, April. 4). *Jordanian-Palestinian Agreement On Holy Places In Jerusalem*. Retrieved from <http://en.lpj.org/2013/04/04/full-text-of-the-jordanian-palestinian-agreement-on-holy-places-in-jerusalem/>

¹²⁰ Beinun, J., & Hajjar, L. (2009). *Palestine, Israel And The Arab-Israeli Conflict*. The Middle East Research And Information Project, 11, 2009. p: 5.

one of the most important issues for Jordan, on account of which it is involved in the final negotiations between Palestine and Israel. A vast majority of refugees and displaced persons are now Jordanian citizens with historical and legitimate rights in the places where they were displaced. The granting of Jordanian nationality, as a result of the declaration of unity between the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan and the West Bank in 1950, does not nullify or diminish the rights of refugees in their country of origin. Jordanian nationality has not been imposed on refugees and has never been granted in lieu of the loss of their rights as refugees.¹²¹

Jordan deems that refugees and displaced persons have the right to return and to receive appropriate compensation,¹²² and that it incurred significant economic difficulties as a result of the refugee problem and its absorptive capacity has been depleted. Jordan would, therefore, not allow any additional refugees to be accommodated and would not grant citizenship to any new refugees.

Article 8 of the Jordanian-Israeli Peace Treaty refers to the bilateral refugee solution between Jordan and Israel,¹²³ wherein the Jordanian position is that the right of return should be exercised in accordance with United Nations resolutions, particularly resolution 194, which provides for the return of refugees to their homes. On the basis of international law, the same article also provides the solution to the problem of displaced persons, and states that the issue of refugees is legally based on Security Council resolution 237, which stipulates that Israel facilitate their return.

¹²¹ Bid. p: 6.

¹²² Abu Omar, Yasmeen. (2010). *Qadiat Allajiiyn Alfilastiniyn Wa'athariha Ealaa Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Alfilastiniat 2009-1948 [The Influence Of The Palestinian Refugee Question On Palestinian-Jordanian Relations]*. (Master Thesis). Birzeit University. p: 66

¹²³ United Nations. (1994). *Treaty Of Peace Between The State Of Israel And The Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan*. Peacemaker.Un.Org. Volume 2042, 1-35325.

Jordan strongly calls for complete and direct cessation of all Israeli settlement activity in the West Bank and East Jerusalem, including the natural growth of existing settlements.¹²⁴ Jordan believes that these settlements hinder the possibility of formation of a viable Palestinian state, thus threatening the prospects of a peaceful solution to the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. The settlements obstruct the movement of the Palestinians, cut off their state, and prevent them from accessing important land and water sources, and so Israel must dismantle these settlements.

Jordan holds the view that all settlement activities in Jerusalem and the West Bank are illegal and constitute a violation of the relevant resolutions of the UN Security Council and the UN General Assembly. They also violate the international humanitarian law and the Fourth Geneva Convention, as affirmed by the International Court of Justice in the advisory opinion on the issue of the separation wall. The illegality of settlements in the occupied territories further warrants their removal.

As the Jordanian-Israeli cooperation in the framework of the Jordan-Israel peace treaty continues to slow down, the conflict remains dependent on Israeli escalation, developments on the ground, and the Palestinian-Israeli scene. Still, Jordan stands by its belief that the wall which is penetrating deep into the Palestinian territories, is illegal and must be removed as it threatens the peace process and Jordanian national security.¹²⁵ The decision of the International Court of Justice which declared the separation wall on the West Bank illegal, was a welcome move and Jordan believes that Israel cannot ignore this important legal decision.

¹²⁴ Gold, Dore. (2010). *Untenable Linkages: Tying A Cessation Of Palestinian Violence To An Israeli Settlement Freeze*. Jerusalem Center For Public Affairs. Jerusalem. p: 1.

¹²⁵ Editor Of Arabic Issues. (2011, May 8). *Al'urdunu Walqadiat Alfistyny.. Risalat Wamawaqif* [Jordan And The Palestinian Issue: A Message And Positions]. Addustour Newspaper. Jordan. Retrieved from <http://www.addustour.com/articles/757067-الأردن-والقضية-الغلسطينية-رسالة-ومواقف>

4.3.3.2 Jordan's Policy towards the Arab Spring:

Based on the principle of no interference in Arab internal issues, the Jordanian diplomacy remained very cautious while dealing with the Arab Spring revolution in Tunisia, Libya, Yemen, and Syria.^{126,127} The Jordanian leadership opines that that Jordan has nothing to do with what happens in the neighboring countries, and that it respects the choices and decisions of the concerned nations. This view stemmed from the fear that the effects of these revolutions will extend to Jordan, which did eventually happen.

Jordan's diplomacy was experienced in managing situations of internal crises in the Arab countries.¹²⁸ In many cases, it succeeded in taking balanced positions, avoiding any bias towards one side at the expense of the other, which proved useful for the future of Jordan's relations with its Arab neighbors. Jordan was not required to adopt the speech of former Turkish Prime Minister Recep Tayyip Erdoğan; it had to distance itself from the positions of some of the Gulf States, and not rush behind them.¹²⁹

However, like any other Arab country, Jordan did experience the effects of the Arab Spring. Several governments followed thousands of demonstrations that broke all edges, and resulted security services being changed (police, gendarmerie, and intelligence to a lesser

¹²⁶ Editorial Team. (2011, February 11). *Tasalsul Zamani: Al'asida' Warudud Alfiel Alduwaliat Ealaa 'Ahdath Misr* [Timeline: Echoes And International Reactions To The Events Of Egypt]. Bbc.Com/Arabic. Retrieved from http://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast/2011/02/110203_egypt_reactions

¹²⁷ Ahmed, A., & Capoccia, G. (2014). The Study Of Democratization And The Arab Spring. *Middle East Law And Governance*. 6(1), 1-31. pp: 30-31.

¹²⁸ Allagui, I., & Kuebler, J. (2011). The Arab Spring And The Role Of Ict| Introduction. *International Journal Of Communication*. 5, 8. p: 1-2.

¹²⁹ Alkhetan, Fahad. (2013). *Alhudu' Al'urduniyi Tujah Altatawurat Fi Misr* [Jordanian Silence Towards Developments In Egypt]. Retrieved from <http://http://www.alghad.com/articles/524458>

degree) and parliaments being dissolved.¹³⁰ New community leadership aimed at fighting corruption as the masses wanted, and the leaders of the opposition ended up in the hands of the government. The growing violence and instability in the neighboring countries enhanced the value and legitimacy of Jordanian rule in the minds of the Jordanian public.¹³¹ The Muslim Brotherhood movement provided the kingdom with the largest mass mobility in the movement that began with the 2010 teachers' uprising.¹³² The Jordanian Prime Ministers were questioned in the parliament, but King Abdullah II was very clever in dealing with the whole issue. The husband of one of the princesses was accused, tried to prove his innocence, but was sentenced to a fine of hundreds of millions. The King did not interfere with the court, and was clear in his instruction to hold all corrupted people, going to the extent of saying “even if it was my son.”¹³³

Through all this, the King was aware of everything that was happening and even watched recordings of people burning his pictures.¹³⁴ He pardoned those who did this, and knew well that the Brotherhood movement intended to make one of the south provinces a hot spot. The protests demanded amendment of the Jordanian Constitution of 1952 and a

¹³⁰ Mobaideen, Mohanad. (2015, December 28). *Khuruj Al'urduni Min "Alrbie Alearabi"* [Jordan's Exit From The Arab Spring]. Alhayat. Retrived from <http://www.alhayat.com/article/719190/>

¹³¹ Yesilyurt, N. (2014). Jordan And The Arab Spring: Challenges And Opportunities. *Perceptions, Winter 2014, Volume XIX, Number 4, pp: 169-194.* p: 16.

¹³² Ibid.

¹³³ Jordan TV. (2015, August 30). *Barnamaj Mufasal Ean Liqa' Jalalat Almalik Mae Wujaha' Aleasimat Eamman.* [Detailed Program On The Meeting Of His Majesty The King With The Dignitaries Of The Capital Amman]. Retrieved from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=x7gzufyIhd8>

¹³⁴ Dodge, T. (2012). Conclusion: *The Middle East After The Arab Spring. After The Arab Spring: Power Shift In The Middle East.* The London School Of Economics And Political Science. 64-68. pp: 66-67.

constitutional court, as well as an independent body of elections.¹³⁵ All that was done; even the lands registered in the name of the King were re-seized or seized, and all this was announced by the media. It became necessary to persuade the state to reform and change its policies based on temporary containment of some powers or giving privileges or support to some dignitaries in return for loyalty.¹³⁶

The Jordanian governments pursued several policies during the Arab Spring. The tools were often traditional in dealing with the movement, but to avoid slipping into chaos it was ensured that wisdom was not overshadowed. The King made a clear decision that no one would be shot or punished strictly.¹³⁷ There were minor incidents, but contrary to the wants of some parts, they did not escalate. The country was led by the opinion of the King and the security establishment, who realized that the movement would be resolved and it was not necessary to punish those who demanded change; that it was important to understand the minds, not angry hearts or voices calling for reforms.

The Jordanians returned to their homes not for fear, as they discovered the betrayal of the leadership of the opposition movement and the blocking of the political horizon of the masses. There are no political parties or symbols without personal and regional goals, but their vigilance is still present in spite of their calmness, especially as the risks of Syrian asylum increase socially and economically.¹³⁸ Also, the reform plans implemented by the

¹³⁵ Muasher, M. (2011). *Jordan's Proposed Constitutional Amendments—A First Step In The Right Direction*. Carnegie Endowment Commentary. p: 1.

¹³⁶ Ibid: p: 2.

¹³⁷ Tobin, S. A. (2012). Jordan's Arab Spring: The Middle Class And Anti-Revolution. *Middle East Policy*, 19(1), 96-109. pp: 104-105.

¹³⁸ Abdel-Hadi, A.(2016). The Arab Spring And The Mediterranean Basin: A Case Study Of Jordan. *Athens Journal Of Mediterranean Studies*. 175-185. p: 183.

government will have some negative effect, especially on the Jordanians' coping capacity, because of the severe policy adopted and constant high unemployment.¹³⁹ The lack of employment, decline in education, the spread of drugs and the growth of sub-identities, the rise in prices, inflation, debts, and unemployment continued. All this needed to be noted by the government, to gauge the consciousness of people who might not be modest in the future if they do not see solutions to problems of unemployment and low income.

4.3.3.3 Jordan's Policy towards Terrorism:

Terrorism is a global phenomenon, based on an extreme ideology, and experienced by most nations. Terrorism is used to achieve political goals, by groups of people who follow thoughts against humanity. Unfortunately, the targets of violence are innocent people who just want to live in peace. Terrorist acts often amount to killing innocent people, destroying property, damaging social infrastructure, and influencing the world in a very negative way. Although, the killing of innocent people is not limited to terrorist organizations and may be carried out by state.¹⁴⁰

Jordan, currently under ISIS attacks, played a significant role in combating extremism in multiple aspects.¹⁴¹ Jordan adopted a clear and stable policy based on an information system network, good and strong relations, cooperation, and exchange of security

¹³⁹ IRIS Analysis Study. (2016 January). *Jordan Two-Year Scenario Analysis: Deteriorating Resilience And Increasing Vulnerabilities*. Humanitarian And Development Programme. Institut De Relations Internationales Et Stratégiques. IRIS. Paris, France. p: 5.

¹⁴⁰ See: Svatoň, Petr. (2013). *An Analysis Of Main Objectives Of Selected Internal Agents Of The Civil War In Syria*. Department Of International Relations And European Studies. Faculty Of Social Studies. Masaryk University. Czech Republic. pp: (51). pp: 38-39.

¹⁴¹ Abbadi, Salim. (2015). Jordan In The Shadow Of ISIS. *Counter Terrorist Trends And Analysis*. Volume 7, Issue 2. p: 10.

information at international and regional levels. This approach allowed the Jordanian security agencies to hunt terrorists, and secure stability and security for its citizens. For its allies, Jordan enhanced its credibility by fighting terrorist groups in their territories.

King Abdullah II stressed the importance of cooperation and sharing information within specific frameworks, both through direct and bilateral exchanges or through international alliances such as the international coalition against ISIS, and the international coalition against terrorism after the 9/11 attacks. The King participated in a discussion about the efforts of the International Coalition to confront extremism and terrorism, which was hosted by US President Barack Obama in New York on 29 September 2015. The King had then said, "I thank President Obama for his leadership and determination and his efforts to discuss what we are discussing today- the efforts of the International Alliance in the face of terrorism, which may be the greatest danger in our contemporary history ... I spoke last year, and also from this platform, about the need to find what I call the 'coalition of the will-holders', which has already been done ... Although this war is going on in the battlefield, it will not be resolved except in the fields of thought"¹⁴²

Jordan focuses on Islam as a religion of faith and tolerance, equality, justice, and mercy. Islam has no any relation with terrorism and terrorism does not belong to religions or lands or races. Jordan, its citizens, officials, and interests, have become a target for terrorist actions owing to its righteous principled position, and its rejection of all forms of extremism. The Jordanian leadership continues to combat terrorism with all possible and available means. Stability and security are Jordan's top priority, with no tolerance for

¹⁴² Alsharfat, Saud. (2016, March 31). *Altaeawun Alduwaliu Watusharik Almaelumat Fi Majal Mukafahat Al'iirhab* [International Cooperation And Information Sharing In The Field Of Counter-Terrorism]. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/929383>

terrorists or terrorist organizations. Jordan believes that resorting to security and military means is not sufficient to uproot international and regional terrorism; in order to fully eliminate terrorism, the governments should be taking economic and social factors into consideration, in addition to other reasons for this phenomenon. The government in Jordan counts on the Jordanian people to stand with it in its battle. The Jordanian Jihadists are also in the strategic plan, and they have to change their attitudes and commit no actions violating the anti-terrorism law.

Jordan declared that it will remain an integral part of the international coalition against terrorism, without any intervention in the conflict over authority in Syria.¹⁴³ Jordan has regularly expressed its condemnation of all forms and practices of terrorism, and stands ready to coordinate and cooperate with the international community in the fight against this phenomenon. The Jordanian leadership is of the opinion that terrorist practices go against religious and human values of civilized human ideologies. Furthermore, Amman has underlined, time and again, the importance of fighting terrorism everywhere without any double standards.

4.4 Conclusion:

This chapter showed how Jordan has always been influenced by its surrounding geopolitical environment and its international relations, as well as by geographical, demographical, and economic factors, including national resources, foreign aid, and the ongoing social and economic changes. The Palestinian-Israeli conflict has also been a major challenge to the political

¹⁴³ Drennan, J. (2014). Who Has Contributed What In The Coalition Against The Islamic State? *Foreign Policy*. 12. p: 10.

leadership, and so the Jordanian foreign policy is formulated as a result of the amalgamation of various internal and external factors. The policy is governed by a set of objectives, wherein, maintaining stability in the country is the most fundamental concern. The scarcity of economic resources in Jordan and its constant need of assistance from abroad, has also shaped the country's foreign policy.

The frequent visits of King Abdullah II to America and England bear testimony to the country's relations with the Western world. Constant communication between the involved parties has been one of the main stabilizing factors for the Jordanian regime. Jordanian foreign policy behavior is characterized by stability and permanence.

Foreign and security policies formulated by King Abdullah II were much inspired by the ways of his father, King Hussein. For the most part, the old relations have remained unchanged, except changes in certain directions, for example, the new policy opened avenues where King Hussein was not willing to venture.

The Jordanian-Syrian relations, ever since their establishment, have swayed between peaceful, cooperative, lukewarm, tensed, and even military clashes. The reason for this inconsistency in bilateral relations is the difference in ideologies of the two countries. Syria is pro-USSR, while Jordan is pro-US. Syria's leadership is determined to stay out of the dominance of the USA despite political pressure.¹⁴⁴ The opposing alliances of the two countries led to general political tension as King Hussein and Hafiz Al-Assad did not share the same ground. The Palestinian issue was another point of contention, as the two countries moved in different directions guided by the will of associated super powers. The

¹⁴⁴ Gani, J. K. (2011). *Understanding And Explaining US-Syrian Relations: Conflict And Cooperation, And The Role Of Ideology*. (Doctoral Dissertation). The London School Of Economics And Political Science (LSE). p: 273.

new leadership tried to establish peaceful political relations, but things soon went in the wrong direction, despite the economic importance of their geographic locations for each.

With the Syrian crisis, the relations got worse but did not escalate to military involvement.

As for the policy decisions, it is believed that since the accession of King Abdullah II in 1999, decisions have been influenced primarily by two variables. The first variable is the kingdom's relationship with the United States, which has changed drastically in line with the changes in political and economic conditions. Relations with America have improved, as they are no longer based on Israel or British corridors, but direct and thus stronger.

The second variable is the relationship with Saudi Arabia. This relationship is the strongest regional alliance for Jordan, with full coordination, and excellent understanding between the two Kings. The two countries have the Taif agreement between them, which even includes joint defense.

The policy for Arab-Arab relations, in addition to the positions and policies of the superpowers and the allied parties on the region and its future, were important determinants for Jordan's foreign policies and were always to be considered by decision-makers. Hence, the continuous need of the country to balance its foreign and regional relations, in order to achieve political stability. Ever since the King took up his constitutional powers, he has been striving to strengthen Jordan's political and economic relations with other countries, by exchanging official visits.

Geographically, Jordan lies in the midst of strong Arab forces, with Saudi Arabia in the south, Iraq in the east, and Syria in the north, all of which are strategically important. Add to that the presence of Jordan on most of the eastern borders of Palestine, and Jordan's foreign policy must achieve the tough task of balancing relations with Arab, regional, and international powers.

Jordan's sense of isolation and the threats to its interests, have always led it to direct its regional policy towards forming alliances with the stronger and closer countries, especially in light of economic factors like financial and military assistance, along with political support.

For its foreign policy, Jordan has adopted an approach that is difficult to deal with but is essential, i.e., keeping a distance from sensitizing neighboring countries. For every action, this process must be carried out and a balance must be struck between regional and international environments. Over the last two decades, new regional and international powers have emerged, with each looking for better role, influence, and alliances. Jordan is aware of this development and must consider it in all its dealings. Internationally and regionally, Jordan has retained a moderate policy, and is considered one of the most committed and responsible countries in the world, having gained international respect.

One of the most important determinants of Jordan's foreign policy is the country's stance on the Palestinian question and its unwillingness to abandon the same. It is an essential component of all its external political efforts. Any analysis of the King's meetings, speeches, dialogues, and conversations, whether local or abroad, always involves this component. Jordan's relationship with Israel, despite the existence of a treaty, is more a cessation of hostilities than a peace process. Jordan is always aware of the ongoing negotiations between Palestine and Israel, with a permanent, unwavering call to end the conflict by peaceful means.

Jordan's foreign policy is dynamic. The country, through its regional policy, has always sought to encourage peaceful conflict resolution. It is trying to move from competition with other countries to influence in the region, to seeking the region's interests. In line with this goal, Jordan's regional policy has been quick to change and accommodate its changing dynamics with

not just with the surrounding Arab and Muslim countries, but also with countries such as Latin America and China, as well as the European Union.

In terms of its international policy, Jordan has always operated with the West and in support of Western projects. This has been an important factor in formulation of Jordanian foreign policy. The only periods that Jordan showed opposition to the Western policy were during Iraq's occupation of Kuwait in 1990-1991, and during the leadership of Sulaiman Nabulsi in the 1950s, which lasted several months.

As for the Syrian Crisis, Jordan has not expressed its interests in a clear and final position on the crisis, but has repeatedly expressed its concern regarding the unstable surrounding environments, the war in Syria and chaos in Iraq, in addition to the mysterious path to the peace process. Jordan has chosen the model of "moderation" to deal with utmost caution, with what is happening in Syria, exactly as the precautionary measures that the kingdom has adopted in dealing with movements in its own territories spurred by the Arab Spring, despite all local justifications.

Chapter Four

The Syrian Crisis and its Implications for Jordan

Chapter Four: The Syrian Crisis and its Implications for Jordan

5.1 Introduction:

The purpose of this chapter is to discuss the impacts of the Syrian crisis on Jordan. The chapter starts with a review of the chronology of events leading to Syrian refugee influx in Jordan between 2011 and 2016, and its negative and positive effects for Jordan, including effects on politics, economy, society, education, and security.

During this period, despite all preparations on Jordan's part, the Syrian refugees created multiple burdens for Jordan, especially the vulnerable hosting communities. The Jordanian government had created the Jordan Response Platform to the Syrian crisis (JRPSC), the refugees, and the hosting communities, empowered by 12 teams to work through special governmental institutions, and was supported by the international community and organizations for implementation. At the beginning of starting work with the UNHCR, Jordan faced some criticism for its way of leading strategies,¹ but later these obstacles were overcome to follow the strategies depending on the Jordanian humanitarian response through JRPSC, and in sync with the international community.

This chapter also discusses the advantages for the Jordanian community, through the Syrian crisis and the presence of Syrian refugee on its territories.

5.2 The Syrian Refugees from March 2011 till December 2016:

Once the Syrian Crisis began, it quickly escalated, and by 2011 Syrian refugees had started to arrive in Jordan. The country was accommodating Iraqi refugees and was worried about hosting more refugees. The previous experiences with Palestinian and

¹ Healy, Sean. Tiller, Sandrine. (2013 October). *A Review Of The Humanitarian Response To The Syrian Refugee Crisis In Jordan, 2012-13*. Doctors Without Borders (MSF). pp: (25). p: 2.

Iraqi refugees raised concerns over the existence of refugee populations and the negative implications of hosting more refugees in the middle of regional economic, political, and security challenges such as terrorism expansion from terroristic organizations through the Syrian refugees. These experiences contributed to the development of the country's policy towards the Syrian refugees.

By October 2011, a number of Syrian families had legitimately crossed the Jaber border to enter the Jordanian territory. There existed tribal extensions and social, economic, and historical relations between people in some governorates in Syria and Jordan. During the first six months of the crisis, Jordanian families hosted their relatives from Syrian families who had been displaced. At the same time, local charities rushed to provide assistance to the Syrian families residing in Jordanian cities. International relief agencies also distributed aid to Syrian families hosted in the northern Jordanian governorates.²

The year 2012 witnessed flow of hundreds of thousands of Syrian refugees into Jordan through the northern border. This massive exodus came in search of security and safety, and for treatment of people wounded in the events of the crisis. As a result, the Jordanian government opened the Zaatari refugee camp, to accommodate the growing number of Syrian refugees.³

In July 2012, upon the recommendation of the Minister of Foreign Affairs, the Jordanian Cabinet decided to approve the establishment of emergency camps for Syrian refugees in

² JHCO. (2011). *Jordan Hashemite Charity Organization. Syria*. JHCO. Retrieved from <http://www.jhco.org.jo/subdefault.aspx?pageid=186&menuid=50>.

³ Al-Bakhit, Marouf. (2013) *Altaqrir Alsanawiu Aleashir Lilmarkaz Alwatanii Lihaqawiq Al'iinsan 'Awdae Haqawiq Al'iinsan Fay Limamlakat Al'urduniyat Alhashimiat Lieam 2013* [The 10th Annual Report For Human Right In Jordan 2013]. The National Center For Human Rights. Jordan. National Library Of Jordan. No.(3141/2/4234). pp: 7-40.

the kingdom. The government decided to adopt the Jordanian Hashemite Charity Organization as the supervisor of the management of the Zaatari refugee camp, and it was responsible for reception and distribution of all assistance to refugees, from local as well as international associations. The government also signed an agreement whereby UNHCR was to bear full expenses of the camp and its requirements. The groundwork for the establishment of the refugee camp started on 17 July 2012 with an area of 7 square kilometers, and on 29 July, the UNHCR field Coordinator announced that Zaatari camp was ready to receive refugees according to international and humanitarian standards.⁴ The camp was opened on 31st July, by the Jordanian Minister of Interior, and the following day 800 refugees were transferred to the camp, including those from the camps of Ramtha and others had crossed the border.⁵ The Zaatari camp is located on the land of Al Zaatari Municipality. Zaatari is considered the fifth largest city in Jordan and has been equipped with basic infrastructure and services such as electricity, water and roads, tents, and prefabricated houses for refugees.

The northern parts of Jordan hosted the first refugee wave from Syria. By the end of 2011, about 2,000 Syrians had arrived in Jordan, which was a small number and had no severe impact on the hosting communities. Many of the refugees believed they would soon go back to their homeland,⁶ however, the following years brought in huge numbers of refugees into the kingdom. Consequently, the Jordanian government, with the help

⁴ JHCO. (2011). *Jordan Hashemite Charity Organization. Syria*. JHCO. Retrieved from <http://www.jhco.org.jo/subdefault.aspx?pageid=186&menuid=50>

⁵ Al-Bakhit, Marouf. (2013) *Altaqrir Alsanawiu Aleashir Lilmarkaz Alwatani Lihaqawiq Al'iinsan 'Awdae Haqawiq Al'iinsan Fay Limamlakat Al'urduniyat Alhashimiat Lieam 2013* [The 10th Annual Report For Human Right In Jordan 2013]. The National Center For Human Rights. Jordan. National Library Of Jordan. No.(3141/2/4234). p: 30..

⁶ UNCHR Report. (2012). *Syrians In Jordan*. UNCHR. UN. pp: 1-7.

of UNHCR, opened Zaatari refugee camp over the course of just two weeks in July 2012, because it became very clear that the refugee influx would only accelerate. The initial several hundred residents multiplied to 15,000 by August 2012.⁷ In the seventh year of the Syrian civil war, Zaatari refugee camp had grown into one of the most crowded concentrated population centers in the region, becoming the fourth-largest city in Jordan,⁸ and the second-largest refugee camp in the world.

The impact of the Syria crisis on Jordan is multifaceted, spanning almost all sectors of the economy and affecting – with varying degrees of intensity – all geographic areas. At the macroeconomic level, the crisis continues to aggravate economic difficulties and exacerbate existing vulnerabilities, thereby casting a shadow over public financial performance. The crisis has placed a significant burden on budgets, and is overstressing services across all affected sectors. While some sectors may have benefited from the population increase, the overall impact of the crisis on the economy has been detrimental. Although the influx of some 630,000 Syrian refugees — in addition to other 750,000 Syrians who were in Jordan before the crisis — is an important component of this impact, it represents only part of the picture. Another important destabilizing economic factor has been the regional trade distortions caused by the crisis, which is directly linked to increasing levels of national debt and worsening trade deficit.

⁷ Remnick, D. (2013, August 26). City Of The Lost. *The New Yorker*.

⁸ Weston, P. (2015, August 5). *Inside Zaatari Refugee Camp: The Fourth Largest City In Jordan*. Retrieved from <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/middleeast/jordan/11782770/what-is-life-like-inside-the-largest-syrian-refugee-camp-zaatari-in-jordan.html>

According to UNHCR statistics, in August 2014, around 621,997 registered Syrian were living across Jordan.⁹ By December 2016, this number had grown to 655,344, making Jordan the sixth highest refugee-hosting country in the world, with world's second highest number (87) of refugees per 1,000 inhabitants.¹⁰

The Jordanian government developed response strategies and plans to deal with the impact of increasing refugee population, partnering with the UNHCR and other international organizations. Of all neighboring host countries, Jordan has proved to be the most sophisticated in terms of its reaction to the Syrian refugee crisis. Led by the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, Jordan demonstrated its willingness and readiness to use the Syrian population as a lever to garner international development aid through the JRPSC, which is described as “the first nationally-led response of its kind, joining refugee and development responses in one complete national plan targeting the Syrian refugees and the affected Jordanian, as well.”¹¹

5.3 Implications of the Syrian Refugee Crisis on Jordan:

5.3.1 The Political Implications:

The political impact of the Syrian Crisis on Jordan had two dimensions – internal impact on the country and its citizens, and external impact on its relations with other countries. Early on during the crisis in 2011, the Jordanian government looked at it as an internal issue of Syria. The Jordanian leadership feared the possibility of the fall of the Syrian

⁹ UNHCR. (2014). *Syria Regional Refugees Response*. Retrieved from <http://data.unhcr.org/syrianrefugees/regional.php>

¹⁰ UNHCR. (2017). *Jordan, Factsheet. January 2017*. United Nations High Commissioner For Refugees (UNHCR). p: 1.

¹¹ JRPSC. (2013). *Jordan Response Platform For The Syria Crisis (2013/2014)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 5.

regime, which could create confusion in the internal political scene in Jordan, if Jordan got too involved with the crisis.¹² But as the Syrians started to flee to Jordan and the government began facing difficulties in social and economic sectors, the crisis could not be ignored anymore. At the same time, international intervention led by the United Nations, Russia, the US, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and other regional countries, in addition to the Syrian actors of the crisis, resulted in a series of negotiations between the Syrian government and the opposing parties- from Arab League peace plans in 2011–2012, to the Geneva peace talks on Syria in 2016 supervised by Staffan de Mistura, UN Special Envoy for Syria.

Jordan was more open to the Syrian opposition and its support after the armed conflict broke out in Daraa, and maintained channels of communication with the regime of President Bashar al-Assad. But after Geneva 1, with supervision of Lakhdar Brahimi, UN Special Envoy for Syria, Amman took a firm stand on the political solution to the crisis and warned of the dangers of the spread of “radical Islamic groups” in the region. The challenge for Jordan was to not slip into war with either side, while maintaining the ability to build on any political development in favor of any of the conflicting parties, to satisfy the allies in Saudi Arabia and the United States, and depending on what the Syrian regime or its allies could tolerate. This policy confounded Jordan’s political discourse and made the Jordanian position ambiguous, which was described as positive, given its priority to emerge safely from the Syrian crisis and its challenges.

¹² Abed Alhamed, Al-Kayali. (2014, January 14). *Tadaeiat Al'azmat Alsuwriat Ealaa Al'urdun*. [The Consequences Of Syrian Crisis On Jordan]. *Middle East Studies Journal*. Amman. Jordan. Vol. 65. p: 13.

Jordan did not express its interests in a clear and final position on the crisis, but repeatedly expressed its concern regarding the unstable surrounding environments, the war in Syria and chaos in Iraq, in addition to the mysterious path to the peace process. Jordan chose the model of “moderation” to deal with utmost caution, with what is happening in Syria, exactly as the precautionary measures that the kingdom adopted in dealing with movements in its own territories spurred by the Arab Spring, despite all local justifications.¹³ The Jordanian leadership was convinced that a political solution is the best way to resolve the Syrian crisis, with a transitional stage and agreement of the Syrians, in order to preserve Syria's unity and safeguard its institutions.

Later however, the Jordanian leadership did change its ways in dealing with the Syrian crisis and the refugees issue. Jordan declared it would not take on the burden of refugees at the expense of its national interests and the Jordanian people. Jordan had formulated its own policy and plans to meet the challenges of the crisis. Nevertheless, it was very important for the government to get financial assistance from the international community, and at the same time be a part of the Syrian peace process.

The Jordanian diplomacy worked towards raising funds to support the public budget, to meet the increasing demands of Jordanians as well as the refugees. In March 2016, the World Bank decided to offer Jordan 100 million dollars at low rates, a type of loan usually reserved for the poorest countries, for the purpose of financing the creation of job opportunities for Jordanians and the Syrian refugees in Jordan.¹⁴

¹³ Shuqer, Shafeeq. (2014, February 10). *Mawqif Al'urduni Min Al'azmat Alsuwriat: Ghumud Bnna' 'Am Tanaqd?* [Jordan's Position On The Syrian Crisis: Ambiguity Or Contradiction?] AL Jazeera Centre For Studies.. p: 2.

¹⁴ Seeberg, P. (2016). Jordan's Migration Diplomacy And The Syrian Refugees. *Videnscenter Om Det Moderne Mellemøsten*. p: 2.

The refugee population created political difficulties for Jordan, being highly concentrated in Jordan's most weak communities and affecting the marginalized Jordanians. As public frustration increased, political conflict gradually moved towards being a struggle against feeling unjust. This attitude was in contrast to Jordan's conventional political disputes, which were mainly categorized as conflicts between the monarchy and elite interest groups. The quick growth of the Syrian refugee population in Jordan, enhanced development of the marginalized in the political domain and carried the possibility of threatening the stability of the country's political structure.¹⁵ So the Jordanian leadership and the government worked hard to get out of these potential troubles by seeking external assistance.

The Syrian asylum in Jordan, which lasted for more than five years, represented growing political pressure for the Jordanian leadership, the government, the political parties, and other actors in the society, on account of the adverse effects on services and infrastructure, in addition to the social cost of increasing crime, poverty, and unemployment, in a country already struggling to meet the needs of its population. While the number of registered Syrian refugees in Jordan stands at over 600 thousand, with another 700 thousand unregistered migrants, even the international support towards hosting such a large number of refugees, was insufficient to meet the real, escalating costs,¹⁶ resulting in multidimensional effects within Jordanian society.

¹⁵ Francis, A. (2015). *Jordan's Refugee Crisis* (Vol. 21). Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. p: 3.

¹⁶ Amnesty International. (2016). *Living On The Margins*. Amnesty International. 23 March 2016, Index Number: MDE 16/3628/2016. p: 5.

As for the influence of Syrian asylum on political issues at the domestic level, the government had two concerns.¹⁷ The first concern was the fear of the influence of the Syrian crisis on its populace, similar to the Arab Spring revolution. Syria being the closest country to Jordan a transfer of ideologies was a very real possibility, especially given the large number of Syrian refugees living in Jordan. The presence of Syrians among the Jordanians could incite revolutionary ideas, sparking a revolution within the Jordanian territory itself, against the monarch regime, particularly when the Islamic parties including the Muslim Brotherhood and the Salafist parties were ready to work to make changes to the political system. New community leadership aimed at fighting corruption as the masses wanted, and the leaders of the opposition ended up in the hands of the government. The growing violence and instability in the neighboring countries enhanced the value and legitimacy of Jordanian rule in the minds of the Jordanian public. The Muslim Brotherhood movement provided the kingdom with the largest mass mobility in the movement that began with the 2010 teachers' uprising. The Jordanian Prime Ministers were questioned in the parliament, but King Abdullah II was very clever in dealing with the whole issue. He did not interfere with the court, and was clear in his instruction to hold all corrupted people, going to the extent of saying “even if it was my son.”

The second concern of the government was that Jordanians by themselves could revolt against the government, following the adverse impact of the Syrian refugee influx on all aspects of life of its own people. The flow of refugees affected the political system, the economy, education, energy, environment, health, justice, livelihood and food security,

¹⁷ Sevilla Sendarrubias, L. (2016). *Social, Economic And Political Impact Of Syrian Refugees In Jordan*. Facultad De Ciencias Sociales Y De La Comunicación Universidad Europea. p: 17.

local governance and municipalities, shelter, social protection, transport, wash, and security. For example, in 2016, the Syrian were extended over 200 thousand labor opportunities,¹⁸ to compensate for the limited access to the labor market, education and other services, as well as the uncertainty of their legal status and the jeopardy of more turmoil in the area.¹⁹ However, the benefits extended to Syrians resulted in loss of opportunities for Jordanians. The crowded classes in public school reduced the opportunity for better education of the Jordanian students. Similar circumstances prevailed in other fields as well, including healthcare and waste management. Syrian refugees also benefitted from government subsidies for water, bread, and gas. According to government estimates, the total financial impact of the Syrian crisis on Jordan reached 2.99 billion dollars in 2015.²⁰ The Jordanian people voiced their complaints regarding the shortage in services in various service sectors, and the rise of crimes in the Jordanian community. The state was no longer able to justify to its citizens all the economic decline, unemployment, recession, and the inability to fulfill the promises of favorable economic activity made by the government time and again.

The government realized that any further pressure on the Jordanians would manifest itself as undesirable, widespread discontent, and so it was very important that the concerns of citizens be addressed through the JRPSC response plans aimed at meeting the needs of the hosting communities and the Syrians.

¹⁸ Alkhatatbeh, Mahmoud. (2016, February 17). *Me'ata 'Alf Fursat Eamal Lilsuwayiyina?! [200 Thousand Jobs For The Syrians?!]*. Al-Ghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://alghad.com/articles/920946>

¹⁹ Lenner, K., & Schmelter, S. (2016). *Syrian Refugees In Jordan And Lebanon: Between Refuge And Ongoing Deprivation*. Institut Europeu De La Mediterrània (Hrsg.), Iemed Mediterranean Yearbook. p: 125.

²⁰ JRPSC. (2015). *Jordan Response Platform For The Syria Crisis (2015)*. Executive Summary. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 16.

Regarding the settlement of the Syrian refugees, a study showed that if Jordan becomes more open to integration and a pathway to citizenship for Syrian refugees, it will surely ameliorate some of the challenges that the Syrian refugees in Jordan currently face as well as the challenges that Jordanian nationals and supporting organizations face.²¹ But the Jordanian politicians reduced the concerns about the resettlement of Syrian refugees in Jordan, which could happen if the refugee crisis and Syrian political peace process were prolonged. However, this did not prevent them from emphasizing that the extension of the conflict in Syria posed significant political and developmental challenges to the kingdom. As of the current situation, Jordan still working on three basic issues: 1) integrating refugees into the Jordanian community; 2) covering the costs that the Treasury was expected to pay; 3) manner of spending and means of financing projects on refugees.²² Former Interior Minister Samir Habashneh had said that, “the concern of Syrian refugees’ settlement in Jordan is ‘absolutely unthinkable’, and that the chances of settling them are “zero percent” compared to the Iraqi refugee crisis that lasted from 1991 to 2003 when the same perceptions were raised at the time and proven wrong”. He added that, “As far as Syrian asylum is concerned, it is not far from the Iraqis, when the situation changed and became easy, the Iraqis returned even the poor to Iraq.”²³

5.3.2 Economic Implications:

Jordan, as a resource-poor country that depends on external support for economic stability, has an economy very vulnerable to external economic shocks. Just before the

²¹ Mayer, R. (2016). *The Right To No Longer Be A Refugee: The Legal Empowerment Of Syrian Refugees In Jordan*. (Master Thesis). Columbia University. USA. p: 88.

²² Political Editor. (2016, February 14). *Syasywn: La Makhawif Haqiqiyan Min Tawtin Allajiyyn Alswryyn* [Politicians: There Are No Real Fears Of Settling Syrian Refugees]. AL-Ghad Newspaper. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://alghad.com/articles/920347>

²³ Ibid.

arrival of Syrian refugees, Jordan's economy was facing an important period of shrinkage on account of two such shocks: 1) waves from the international financial crisis of 2008 shook the foundations of Jordan's economy, leading to a notable reduction in foreign direct investment and private capital flows to Jordan;²⁴ 2) the Arab Spring caused a regional economic decline and weakened several of Jordan's key trading partners. For example, disturbances to the flow of natural gas from Egypt, generated instability in the regional oil supply and prices. Deteriorating global commodity values, limited exports, and reduced transmittals negatively triggered Jordan's economy during this period.²⁵ The precipitous drop had negative consequences in the form of unemployment and rising product prices in Jordan.

The International Labor Organization reported that unemployment among Jordanians grew from 14.5% in March 2011 to 22% by 2014.²⁶ Many Jordanians blame the influx of Syrian refugees for increasing levels of unemployment in the country. According to a survey published by ILO, 96% of Jordanians believed that Syrians were seizing their jobs. Although Syrians can't legally work in Jordan, ILO estimated that around 160,000 Syrians are working in the informal job sector, mainly in construction services, and agricultural jobs.

In contrast with the ILO, a study conducted in January 2016 showed that the Syrian refugees' presence does not have any significant impact on the Jordanian labor market.

²⁴ Ahid, M., & Augustine, A. (2012). The Impact Of Global Financial Crisis On Jordan. *International Journal Of Business And Management*. p: 110.

²⁵ Warlop, Sophie W. Sayed, Haneen. (2009). *The Financial Crisis: Impact On The Middle East*. Horizons Development. The World Bank Group. pp: 28-31.

²⁶ Stave, S. E., & Hillesund, S. (2015). *Impact Of Syrian Refugees On The Jordanian Labour Market*. Geneva: ILO. pp: 17-19.

The study gave following explanations for their claim: 1) Jordan took additional measures to prohibit companies from hiring Syrian refugees; 2) the refugees were forced to work in informal sectors, where no work permits are required; 3) the Jordanian authorities forced the Syrian refugees to remain in border areas and camps with restrictions on movement; 4) many refugees have low skills, meaning they are not suited to the available jobs.²⁷ Thus, despite Syrian presence, it is more likely that the regional and international economic crisis, along with Jordan's preexisting structural economic issues, is responsible for the increase in unemployment in the country.²⁸

Reports propose that the salary decline in Jordan's informal economic sector represents the most concrete effect of Syrian entry into the Jordanian workforce. Decreasing wages in the informal employment market threaten to make the economic situation untenable for Jordanians who rely on these jobs; around 14% of Jordanians living below poverty line, rely on wages from informal employment for half of their earnings.²⁹ Thus, slashing wages not only increases labor exploitation and deteriorates work standards as job competition in the informal sector grows, but also encourages negative coping mechanisms like child labor and intensifies poverty among the most vulnerable communities. The World Bank also contends that downward pressure on wages may be causing the decrease in the Jordanian national labor force participation rate.³⁰ The presence of Syrians in Jordanian economic sectors, informal sectors in particular, has

²⁷ Fakh, A., & Ibrahim, M. (2016). *The Impact Of Syrian Refugees On The Labor Market In Neighboring Countries: Empirical Evidence From Jordan*. Defence And Peace Economics, 27(1), 64-86. pp: 19-20.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Karasapan, O. (2015, February 25). *Jordan's Syria Refugees*, " Brookings Institution. pp: 1-3

³⁰ The World Bank. (2014). *Jordan Economic Monitor. Resilience Amid Turmoil. Poverty Reduction And Economic Management Unit. Middle East And North Africa Region. The World Bank. p: 13.*

increased marginalization in Jordan, with declining wages and rising unemployment rate, as the Jordanian market benefits from increased Syrian demand and a larger workforce.³¹

The economic sector in Jordan suffered a notable slowdown in 2015, due to increased political and social instability in the region. The financial resources of the Syrians became smaller as they exhausted their savings, thereby increasing their debt ratios, in addition to decreasing international support. During the first half of the year, 86% of the refugees in Jordan lived below poverty line, and 80% resorted to emergency or negative adjustment methods, such as reducing food supplies, begging, early marriage, child labor, and prostitution.³²

5.3.2.1 Water:

Jordan is the second water-poorest country in the world. The country is facing a continuing supply deficit of water; a large quantity of renewable surface water has been consumed and groundwater is being unsustainably exploited.³³ Therefore, the lasting usable sources are increasingly fading and leading to declining water levels.

Since 2011, the water situation has progressively worsened as national population growth surpassed predicted levels, propelled by the influx of Syrian refugees. As a result, water services became severely stressed, given the growth in demand while the supply constant. The host societies gave up portions of their available water services

³¹ Francis, A. (2015). *Jordan's Refugee Crisis* (Vol. 21). Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. p: 14.

³² Alda'ma, Mohammed. (2016, January 10). *Alluju' Alsuwriu Fi Al'urdina.. 85 % Yaeishun Taht Khati Alfaqr* [Syrian Asylum In Jordan. 85% Live Below The Poverty Line]. Retrieved from <https://aawsat.com/home/article/540311/>

³³ Namrouqa, Hana. (2014, October 22). *Jordan World's Second Water-Poorest Country*. Jordan Times Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.jordantimes.com/news/local/jordan-world%e2%80%99s-second-water-poorest-country>

and facilities to the Syrian refugees, who were out-of-camp and living among them in their neighborhoods.³⁴

Water supply was based on a revolving system, to meet the lack of resources, decrease nonrevenue water, and to guarantee just supply. In the northern governorates, which hosted around 50% of the Syrian refugees living out of camps, faced difficulties of water distribution because of the increase in population. The per capita daily share which was over 88 liters before the Syrian refugees' arrival, came down to 64.5 liters.³⁵ The Syrian refugee presence increased water demand, and gradually Jordanian citizens became more cautious, saving more water out of fear that the authorities will pump unused water resources to Syrian refugees. Therefore, competition over water between Jordanians and Syrians caused a threat to Jordan's water supplies.³⁶

Hosting of the Syrian refugees also deeply impacted Jordan's public budget, with increasing government spending on support for goods and services other than water, such as gas, electricity, and bread. More than 62% of Jordan's population was served by sewage systems, yet in specific sites, this coverage was lower. Sewage treatment could ruin the surrounding environment. Water in public places, such as schools, had been affected badly because of the crisis.³⁷ Water crisis was already a severe problem in Jordan, which was only worsened by the refugee presence. Jordan always needed developments in the water sector, but the Syrian refugee crisis has directed a lot of

³⁴ MWI. (2015). *Jordan Water Sector: Facts & Figures*. Ministry Of Water And Irrigation. Jordan. pp: 14-17.

³⁵ JRPSC. (2016). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2016/2018)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 104.

³⁶ De Châtel, F. (2014). *The Role Of Drought And Climate Change In The Syrian Uprising: Untangling The Triggers Of The Revolution*. Middle Eastern Studies. p: 521.

³⁷ Ibid.

attention to the water crisis, putting it high up on the priorities list³⁸. The refugee problem and the resulting circumstances have thus pushed for the development of the Jordanian water sector, redirecting focus towards greater awareness of this issue and practices to overcome it.

5.3.2.2 Energy:

As one of the world's most poor countries, in terms of energy resources, Jordan meets almost 97% of its energy needs via imports. Driven by the burdens of energy prices on the Jordanian economic sector, the government has tried to achieve various development goals, and sustaining these results it can count on gradually shifting to a reasonable energy future.

Till 2009, Jordan depended on natural gas from Egypt for around 86% of its electricity needs, but since 2011, a series of disturbances to this flow brought this number down to 10% in 2014. To compensate, Jordan moved to higher-cost heavy oil imports, which increased its bill of imported energy from 2.67 billion dollars in 2009 to 5.74 billion dollars in 2014. Jordan's energy imports reached about 17% of the country's GDP in 2013. In 2013, the government subsidies for fuel and electrical power products hit 2.59 billion dollars, while the collected cost for electric power production reached 4.9 billion dollars and was estimated to hit 6.72 billion dollars by December 2014.³⁹ This growth was way above estimations based on usual population growth, and so much of the increased demand could be attributed to the drastic growth in population because of the Syrian crisis.

³⁸ Francis, A. (2015). *Jordan's Refugee Crisis* (Vol. 21). Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. pp: 22-25.

³⁹ JRPS. (2015). *Jordan Response Platform For The Syria Crisis (2015)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 112.

The continuous flow of Syrian refugees to Jordan till 2016, created pressure to meet the increased energy needs in hosting societies. There was a serious demand to improve the efficiency of power production. The government tried to create and upgrade the necessary infrastructure, transmission, and distribution for additional medium-term renewable energy generation, in addition to building renewable energy stations for the hosting communities and refugees camps,^{40,41} which in turn translated to more expenses out of the public budget.

5.3.2.3 Environment:

The influx of Syrian refugees from 2011 to 2015, also affected the environmental services in the kingdom, as the increase in overgrazing, wetting, excessive collection of medicinal plants, and the abundance of agricultural activities, added pressure on fertile land. Owing to the presence of refugees, there was a noticeable increase in medical, solid, and hazardous waste. Solid waste disposal was a big concern, as most municipalities practiced solid waste in open locations. Hazardous and medical waste management was inadequate, with treatment in obsolete burners located in open in areas of high population; this was reflected in deteriorating water quality, air quality, and forests. In 2015, the cost of environmental degradation in Jordan, taking into account the immediate and long-term effects of land degradation, was estimated to be

⁴⁰ JRPS. (2017). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 20.

⁴¹ See: Grafham, Owen, et Al, (2016, April). *Refugees And Energy Resilience In Jordan*. Moving Energy Initiative, Amman. p: 5.

somewhere between 143 and 332 million Jordanian Dinars, representing 2.35% of GDP.⁴²

The United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA), the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), and the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), had organized a joint workshop in Geneva, Switzerland, on 25 January 2016, to take stock of the ongoing efforts by partners to identify, assess, and mitigate environmental consequences of the crisis in Syria and neighboring countries. Some areas of concern included protected areas in the north of Jordan encroached upon for grazing and firewood collection, increase of waste and medical waste with need for landfill upgrade, and air quality problems as a result of increased traffic.⁴³

The environmental hazard was identified as a priority in the JRPSC 2016-2018. The economic assessment of the direct and indirect impact of refugee presence on the ecosystems of host communities in Jordan, led to the drafting of an important policy document that aided the decision-making process in 2016. Earlier, there was no appropriate monitoring mechanism in place which made it problematic for the government to monitor air quality, and solid and liquid waste flow.⁴⁴ Furthermore, the Ministry of Environment had no database system for preserving minutes of all air

⁴² Al-Atiat, Farah. (2015, March 2) *Drast: Tadafuq Allajjiyn Alsuwriyn Yarfae Aldaght Ealaa Khadamat Alnizam Alaiqtisadii* [Study: The Influx Of Syrian Refugees Raises Pressure On The Services Of The Economic System]. Alghad. Jordan. p: 3.

⁴³ UNEP/OCHA/UNHCR. (2016, January 25). *Environmental Consequences Of The Syria Crisis (Coordination Workshop)*. UNEP/OCHA Environment Unit And The UNHCR Environment Unit. p: 4.

⁴⁴ JRPSC. (2015). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis (2016/2018)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 58.

parameters, and the types and quantities of solid waste and wastewater, running in the surrounding areas.

5.3.2.4 Transport:

The influx of Syrian refugees heavily impacted transport infrastructure in Jordan, mainly in areas with high refugee population. Meeting the requirements of refugees added pressure on transport infrastructure and networks, increasing the capacity of heavy-loaded goods, water supply, and solid waste disposal trucks, in addition to contributing to the quick degradation of the capacity and quality of roads. In the north, new networks of roads, as well as reconstruction and rehabilitation of roads, were needed in newly formed communities and in hosting communities across municipalities.⁴⁵

The closure of border crossings with Syria resulted in heavy losses of around 755.65 million dollars for truck transport sector in Jordan as movement of goods through trucks decreased. About 17 thousand Jordanian trucks were operating inside and outside the kingdom, including 5 thousand working externally, and 3 thousand refrigerated trucks operating in the kingdom. The border closure, however, rendered about 5-6 thousand trucks worthless, as these trucks were used to carry goods to Syria and Eastern European countries.⁴⁶

⁴⁵ JRPSC. (2015). *Jordan Response Platform For The Syria Crisis (2015)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 17.

⁴⁶ Economic Editor. (2015, December 10). *756 Mlywn Dular Khasarat Qitae Alshshahinat Al'urduniyi..Bsbb Al'azmat Alsuwria* [\$ 756 Million Loss Of The Jordanian Truck Sector Due To The Syrian Crisis]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/economy/2015/12/10/756>

Statistics reveal that the transport sector plays an important role in the Jordanian economy, with over 8.1% contribution to the gross domestic product (GDP). It was growing at a rate of 6% annually, and employed about 7% of the Jordanian labor force.⁴⁷

Following the Syrian crisis, the challenges for the transport sector grew and required it to keep up with growing demand, to support the growth of the economy.

By 2016, existing roads in the governorates of Irbid, Mafraq, and Zarqa, were in desperate need of urgent maintenance comprising rehabilitation, reconstruction, and expansion, as the sudden population growth magnified the number of commuters in these areas. As a result of the rising density in public transport and street networks, which were used by people on a daily basis, social tensions in host societies increased.⁴⁸

Moreover, Jordan had lost one of its main trade roads and the growing violence in Syria had forced Jordan to take up alternative routes, mainly through Gulf Aqaba Port, thus adding to the existing burden on road networks and transport infrastructure.⁰⁰

5.3.3 Social Implications:

5.3.3.1 Education:

As public schools became overwhelmed with Syrian refugees, the Jordanians expressed qualms regarding class timings, double-shifting, and overcrowded classrooms. Even before the arrival of the Syrian refugees, advances were required in the education sector, and this situation heightened community and government frustration over the added stress on public schools.⁴⁹

⁴⁷ JRPSC. (2017). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 128.

⁴⁸ Ibid.

⁴⁹ Achilli, L. (2015). Syrian Refugees In Jordan: A Reality Check. Migration Policy Centre EUI. P:1–12. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/34904>. p: 3.

Over half of the Syrian refugee population in Jordan is under the age of eighteen, which drives the demand for educational services.⁵⁰ The government opened 98 additional double-shifted schools to ease burdens on classrooms. As the share of students joining double-shifted schools increased from 7.6% in 2009 to 13.4% in 2014,⁵¹ the Ministry of Education is apprehensive of reducing the number of double-shifted schools in the country. Out of 656,400 Syrian refugees in Jordan, some 236,304 are school-aged children (117,306 boys; 118,998 girls). By the end of the school year 2015-16, 145,458 Syrian refugee children were enrolled in public schools in camps and host communities, an increase of 16,104 students (12%) compared to the previous academic year.⁵² In Amman and Irbid, nearly half of the schools are overloaded and have only limited capacity for more students.

The pressure on educational institutions has increased friction among host communities. An assessment by REACH, a joint initiative by two nongovernmental organizations and the United Nations Operational Satellite Applications Program, found that 55% of Syrian and Jordanian respondents reported challenges to education as ‘very’ or ‘extremely’ urgent.^{53,54} The survey found 61% of Jordanians believed that access to education caused community tensions.

⁵⁰ UNICEF. (2015). *Working Access To Education For Syrian Refugee Children And Youth In Jordan Host Communities. Joint Education Needs Assessment Report*. Education Sector Group. UNICEF. UN. p: 62.

⁵¹ Achilli, L. (2015). Syrian Refugees In Jordan: A Reality Check. *Migration Policy Centre EUI*. p: 1–12. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/34904>. p: 5.

⁵² UNESCO. (2017, Mrch 28-29). *The Regional Conference On Higher Education In Crisis Situations : “Higher Education In Crisis Situations : Synergizing Policies And UNESCO (2017). Promising Practices To Enhance Access, Equity And Quality In The Arab Region,”* UNESCO. UN. (March), pp: 28–29.

⁵³ British Embassy, A. (2014). *Education And Tensions In Jordanian Communities Hosting Syrian Refugees*. Jordan. p: 1.

⁵⁴ UNICEF. (2015). *Working Access To Education For Syrian Refugee Children And Youth In Jordan Host Communities. Joint Education Needs Assessment Report*. Education Sector Group. UNICEF. UN. pp: 64-65.

An analysis of 2014-15 and 2015-16 academic years, shows that the Syrian crisis had a major impact on the education sector in Jordan, particularly public schools. In the year 2014-15, the number of Syrian refugees were enrolled in public schools in refugee camps and other host communities was 129,354, which increased to 143,000 in 2015-16, an increase of 875% compared to the academic year 2011-12, thus exerting severe pressure on resources and infrastructure in the education sector. School space and the availability of skilled tutors were also among the primary difficulties in this field, particularly in the four main cities Amman, Irbid, Mafraq, and Zarqa.

To overcome challenges in the education sector, the Jordanian Ministry of Education was forced to recruit additional teachers, who often lacked adequate training and skills to handle the growing number of students. There were apprehensions regarding the quality of education which could be undermined.⁵⁵ The access to education services had been a constant source of stress between the Jordanians and the Syrian refugees, but Jordan was devoted to guaranteeing access to education to all refugee children. In 2013, training courses and workshops were organized by the Ministry of Education, in cooperation with the UNESCO, to formulate adequate educational strategies to absorb the Syrian children into the Jordanian public schools.⁵⁶

5.3.3.2 Healthcare:

Healthcare is a basic need, and with rise in refugee population the Jordanian healthcare system came under pressure, in terms of both finances and service capacity. According

⁵⁵ JRPS. (2017). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. pp: 61-62.

⁵⁶ UNESCO (2016 September). *Evaluation Of Unesco's Role In Education In Emergencies And Protracted Crises*. Internal Oversight Service, Evaluation Office IOS/EVS/PI/153. p: 12.

to the Ministry of Health, the number of Syrian outpatient visits to primary care centers increased from 68 in January 2012 to 15,975 in March 2013, while the number of Syrian refugee admissions to government hospitals increased from 300 to 10,330 during the same period. As a result of capacity burdens, Jordanians were increasingly directed to private centers and hospitals to receive care,⁵⁷ making healthcare less accessible and more expensive for citizens.

Jordan also witnessed the re-emergence of previously eradicated communicable diseases such as tuberculosis, polio, and measles, and so the provision of vaccinations has simultaneously been one of the most important public health missions as well as one of the costliest services provided to Syrian refugees in Jordan.⁵⁸

Community tensions escalated in response to pressure on the healthcare system. This was corroborated by the REACH survey, wherein 64% of Jordanians and 56% of Syrians reported that access to health care contributed to community tension.^{59,60}

The refugees' demand for healthcare services continued to affect the health sector in Jordan, with greater healthcare spending and growing incidence of communicable diseases. Healthcare demands came from the disabled, war-wounded, and older refugees, making the circumstances particularly challenging, as war-related injuries require expensive medical treatment and long rehabilitation. Further, more than 50% of

⁵⁷ JRPSC. (2013). *Jordan Response Platform For The Syria Crisis (2013/2014)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 5.

⁵⁸ The World Bank. (2014). *Jordan Economic Monitor. Resilience Amid Turmoil*. Poverty Reduction And Economic Management Unit. Middle East And North Africa Region. The World Bank. p: 3.

⁵⁹ REACH. (2014). *Access To Health Care And Tensions In Jordanian Communities Hosting Syrian Refugees*. Thematic Assessment Report. REACH. p: 2.

⁶⁰ El-Khatib, Z., Scales, D., Vearey, J., & Forsberg, B. C. (2013). *Syrian Refugees, Between Rocky Crisis In Syria And Hard Inaccessibility To Healthcare Services In Lebanon And Jordan*. *Conflict And Health*, 7(1), 18. p: 2.

Syrian families suffered from great health weaknesses, and around one-third of Jordanian children below five years, were anemic with severe vitamin and iron deficiency.⁶¹

This situation led to restrictions on services available to Syrian refugees. When the Syrians initially began arriving in Jordan, the government guaranteed free access to primary and secondary healthcare centers for registered Syrians. However, in November 2014, the government repealed free medical services for Syrian refugees, citing an overburdened health sector and budget. Due to financial limitations, the Ministry of Health was forced to stop permitted access to healthcare previously given to many Syrian refugees. Instead, they were pushed to pay an amount equivalent to that paid by the uninsured Jordanians. The healthcare requirements of the country's population kept changing given the changing epidemiology of diseases based on new population demographics. The increasing healthcare expenses, on both facilities as well as purchases, meant a struggle with finances, so much so, that about one-third of Jordanians did not receive comprehensive health insurance coverage.⁶²

5.3.3.3 Shelter:

The Jordanian housing market could not stay isolated from the impact of refugee flow, as over 80% of Syrians in Jordan were living outside of refugee camps,⁶³ leading to a shortage of low-income housing. The growing demand for housing drove up rental

⁶¹ JRPSC. (2017). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 86.

⁶² Ibid.

⁶³ MOPIC, (2014). *National Resilience Plan 2014/2016*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p:

prices in the northern cities and towns where average rental prices nearly tripled.⁶⁴ Stress on the housing sector moved both poor Jordanians and Syrians away from the housing market. The Jordanians could see that growth in rent and competition over shelter were causing social problems among communities. Reports reveal that mounting housing costs compelled young people to postpone their marriages, as they could not pay for new housing.⁶⁵

The Syria crisis severely strained the capacity of the Jordanian housing sector. There existed a gap of more than 100,000 housing units in the housing sector; this number was way higher than predictions based on typical demand from the Jordanians. Before the Syrian crisis, there was a surplus in terms of number of available housing units when compared with demand; the situation had now reversed with a severe shortage of inexpensive housing units, which further contributed to increasing tensions between refugees and Jordanians. Around 95% of Syrians and 87% of Jordanians linked dissatisfaction among communities to the lack of cheap housing, especially in urban cities where demand is the strongest, and increasing housing cost.⁶⁶

Providing additional, cheap residential units in the market would probably release the upward pressure on rental charges, and people would have the choice of availing better quality houses for better prices. Furthermore, this would likely decrease chances of

⁶⁴ Corps, M. (2013). *Mapping Of Host Community-Refugee Tensions In Mafraq And Ramtha, Jordan*. Mercy Corps, Portland, OR. pp: 1-3.

⁶⁵ Hamai, L., McCormack, R., Niederberger, E., & Lasap, L. (2013). *Integrated Assessment Of Syrian Refugees In Host Communities. Emergency Food Security And Livelihoods; Water, Sanitation And Hygiene; Protection*. UNICEF. United Nations Children's Fund. (March), p: 8

⁶⁶ REACH. (2015, July 23). *Comprehensive Reports Analyze Drivers Of Tensions And Satisfaction With Service Delivery Within Host Communities*. Jordan. p: 12.

mistreatment of Syrian refugees and helpless Jordanians, and ease the usage of undesirable managing tools between them.⁶⁷ The need is to devise a method that links relief and growth in Jordanian societies, such that relief and development programmes can match each other, to maximize prosperity in the residential sector.

5.3.3.4 Justice Impacts:

Before the Syrian crisis, violence and criminal levels in Jordan were generally low. However, as the crisis extended this situation gradually changed. Data from the Public Security Directorate showed that the northern part of Jordan recorded growth in criminal performances, attacks, and proliferation of small arms. As of August 2016, the Ministry of Justice had recorded over 7 thousand cases involving Syrian refugees.⁶⁸ In 2014 and 2015, there was a rise in detention cases for people working without permits, because of the reduction in resources, shortage of humanitarian support in urban areas, and administrative and financial obstacles to obtaining official work permits. The growing caseload stretched the courts in Jordan beyond their technical and working capabilities, adversely affecting their effectiveness and their capability to ensure fair trials, and problems in accessing justice directly influence protection and social consistency.

Numerous Syrian refugees in Jordan did not have basic civil documents like birth, marriage, education, craft, and death certificates, most of which were lost or damaged in their homeland, Syria. As many Syrian refugees got married informally in Syria, they

⁶⁷ JRPSC. (2017). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 49.

⁶⁸ Quaidar, Rami. (2015). *Dirasat Thilylyt Hawl 'Ihtsayyt 'Aedad Alqdaya Lil'atraf Alsuwryyn Alssadirat Ean Wizarat Aleadl* [Analytical Study For Statistics About The Number Of Lawsuits Involving Syrian Parties]. *Ministry Of Justice*. Arab Renaissance For Democracy & Development. Jordan. pp: 2-5.

had to get ratification of their marriage through special Jordanian courts, to be issued a birth certificate for their children born in Jordan. The shortage of birth certificates prevented countless Syrian refugee children from accessing health and education services. Although, the Syrian personal identity documents and the regular presence of a civil registrar in refugee camps facilitated access to birth registration to a certain extent, still it was estimated that around 30% of Syrian refugee children did not have birth certificates.⁶⁹

The Ministry of Justice indicated that, generally, the number of cases increased by 84% in Mafraq, 77% in Irbid, and 50% in Amman, all of which are densely populated areas. And as for Syrian and Palestinian refugees, the most common types of legal problems were family law cases, which accounted for 65% of all cases. Criminal law cases accounted for 15% of the cases, refugee-related problems for 13%, and civil cases for 7%. These ratios were similar to the legal issues faced by not-so-prosperous Jordanians. However, conflict and displacement often added to the strain on family structure, resulting in further problems. Within the refugee communities, there were a large number of legal problems faced by the Syrians, such as marriage, divorce, alimony, and child custody. For example, marriage in Syria does not require court documentation, while it is required in Jordan, and so it was necessary for the Syrians to prove their marriages and family ties to be able to obtain certain humanitarian relief services.⁷⁰

⁶⁹ UNHCR. (2016). *2016 Jordan Refugee Response Protection Sector Operational Strategy*. UNHCR. UN. Jordan. pp: 2-5.

⁷⁰ Prettitore, Paul. (2016m February 18). *The Legal Problems Of Refugees*. Justice Center For Legal Aid. Retrieved from <http://blogs.worldbank.org/arabvoices/ar/legal-problems-refugees>

The Shari'a courts were burdened with greater caseloads due to the crisis, to the extent that the Chief Justice had to order extension of regular working hours by two hours. The number of judges was increased by employing trained civil court judges to meet the needs of the refugees. For protection the government also added administrative institutions and practices in refugee camps by establishing two offices of the Shari'a court in Zaatari and Azraq refugee camps.⁷¹

5.3.3.5 Social Protection:

The influx of Syrian refugees had a negative impact on the local livelihood of Jordan's host communities. It increased competition among the poorest parts of hosting communities over informal charitable and relief services, employment opportunities, agriculture, and other jobs that do not require skilled labor, in addition to putting pressure on basic infrastructure in the fields of education, healthcare, and municipal services. According to Ministry of Social Development of Jordan, the influx of Syrians built pressure on the Jordanian social protection system.^{72,73} The protection challenges faced by Jordan as a whole included:⁷⁴

1. Poverty and unemployment, especially among women and youth.
2. Violence against children.
3. Sexual and gender-based violence against women and girls.

⁷¹ JRPS. (2017). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. pp: 96.

⁷² Zureiqat, Ghaith. (2015). *Social Protection And Safety Nets In Jordan*. Center For Social Protection, IDS. UK. p: 38.

⁷³ ECHO Factsheet. (2016 January). *Jordan: Syria Crisis*. European Commission's Directorate-General For European Civil Protection And Humanitarian Aid Operations. p: (2).

⁷⁴ JRPS. (2017). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 51.

4. Social security.
5. Youth engagement.
6. Access to basic services for persons with disabilities and reduced mobility.
7. Tensions within societies and danger of radicalization.

For the Syrians, their general situation in the kingdom had become more problematic because of obstacles to formalizing their placement in non-camp locations, challenges in getting legal work, inability to provide for their own basic requirements, and a decline in humanitarian aid. According to the JRPSC 2017/2019, the key protection challenges for the Syrian refugees included:⁷⁵

1. Child labor.
2. Access to international protection.
3. Registration and documentation issues.
4. Sexual and gender-based violence against women and girls.
5. Violence against children.
6. Access to services for persons with disabilities.
7. Tensions with host societies.
8. Access to sustainable livelihoods, particularly for women and youth.

In relation to unemployment, a study by ILO confirmed that between 2011 and 2014, the unemployment rate among host communities in Amman, Irbid, and Mafraq rose from 14.5% to 22.1%, with an increase of around 30-40% among women, and around 10-17% among men. The study, which was carried out in cooperation with the FAFO Institute for International Applied Studies and the Jordanian Department of Statistics,

⁷⁵ Ibid.

also revealed the impact of the influx of Syrian refugees on the Jordanian labor market, as Syrian workers were willing to accept lower wages and inferior working conditions compared to their Jordanian counterparts, which raised the number of Syrian workers in the informal sector.⁷⁶ The study pointed out that this put more pressure on the Jordanian authorities to apply labor laws, such as commitment to minimum wages, and fair working conditions and safety at work.

According to official data released by the Department of Statistics, the poverty rate in Jordan jumped from 14.4% in 2010 to 20% in 2016. Jordan's exposure to the Syrian asylum crisis and the consequent economic and social repercussions have led to a rise in the poverty rate in the country, especially in areas where refugee concentration is higher, such as the northern regions.^{77,78}

5.3.3.6 Livelihoods:

The Syria crisis had worsened existing structural challenges within Jordan's labor market and economy. According to a World Bank report, 14.4% of the Jordanians lived under the poverty line, and one-third of the people were considered transient poor. A vast majority of Syrians in Jordan were highly vulnerable with 87% living beneath the national Jordanian

⁷⁶ Editorial Team. (2015, May 20). "*Aleamal Aldwly*": *Alluju' Alsuwriu Rafae Bitalat Al'urduniyiyin Alrijal Sab'ata Ashar Bilm'a* ["International Labor Organization": Syrian Asylum Raise Unemployment Of Jordanians Men 17%]. Sarayanews Jordan. Jordan. Retrieved from <https://www.sarayanews.com/article/308433>

⁷⁷ Al-Dbesyeh, Ziad. (2018). *Alfaqr Fi Al'urduni Yaqfiz 'Ilaa 20% Qabl 'Ijra'at Rafae Aldarayib Wal'asear* [Poverty In Jordan Jumps To 20% Before Tax And Price Increases]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/economy/2018/1/20/الفقر-في-الاردن-يقفز-ل-20-قبل-رفع-الاسعار>

⁷⁸ Al-Dbesyeh, Ziad. (2015, October 17). *Nisbat Alfaqr Fi Al'urdun 'Aelaa Min Almueadilat Alhukumia* [Poverty In Jordan Is Higher Than Government Rates]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/economy/2015/10/17/-نسبة-الفقر-في-الاردن-اعلى-من-المعدلات-الحكومية>

poverty line.^{79,80,81} Though humanitarian aid had kept various urban community and camp refugee residents from dangerous levels of food insecurity and weakness, bad managing tools remained widespread, with a reported 26% out-of-camp refugees dependent on income from household members in socially worsening, unfair, high threat or illegal temporary work, to meet their basic food requirements.⁸²

Still, the Jordanian government steadily worked towards lowering unemployment rates in the kingdom, especially among women and youth. In 2016, the unemployment rate for women was double that of men. The GDP contracted from 3.1% in 2014 to 2.4% in 2015. With continuous government efforts, GDP was projected to recover somewhat to reach 3% in 2016, but this growth was inadequate to create jobs for the rising population.⁸³

As a result, at the conference in London in February 2016, the Jordanian government committed to creating 200,000 job opportunities and facilitating business development for the Syrians, with the help of the international community. An important step towards accomplishing assessable effects was the agreement signed with the EU to ease specific rules of origin. The agreement aimed to improve exports in general, stimulating the

⁷⁹ The World Bank. (2014). *Jordan Economic Monitor. Reviving A Slowing Economy*. Middle East And North Africa Region. The World Bank. pp: 2-5.

⁸⁰ Kotb,Tarek. (2016). *IFAD Report On Jordan*. IFAD. p: 1.

⁸¹ The World Bank. (2013). *Jordan Economic Monitor. Maintaining Stability And Fostering Shared Prosperity Amid Regional Turmoil*. Middle East And North Africa Region. The World Bank. p: 7.

⁸² Verme, p: (2015). *The Welfare Of Syrian Refugees: Evidence From Jordan And Lebanon*. World Bank Publications. pp: 6-8.

⁸³ JRPSC. (2017). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 101.

economy, and increasing the number of jobs for Jordanians and Syrians.⁸⁴ These economic decisions generated the possibility for refugees to sustainably accomplish their basic demands on their own, along with participating in the Jordanian economy.

5.3.3.7 Food Security:

Jordan was largely a food secure country, but hosting a large proportion of the world's refugee population affected food security. The impact of the Syrian crisis was obvious when the prevalence of malnutrition in Jordan, went up from 3.4% in 2006 to 4.2% in 2016. The average prevalence of acute food insecurity among the total population in Jordan from 2014 to 2016 was 12.7%.⁸⁵ As the crisis continued, Syrian refugees and host communities continued to struggle with food insecurity. The World Food Program studies indicated that in 2016, 12% of the families continued to be food insecure, while 60% were vulnerable to food insecurity. Also, 72% of Syrian refugee households in host communities were food insecure compared to 85% in 2015. The slight improvement was on account of food aid. The Syrian crisis affected the agriculture sector, directly impacting food security. Small farmers were challenged by the rising agricultural input prices and the disruption of traditional trade routes, as well as land and water scarcity, high temperature, inadequate rainfall, low productivity, and inadequate marketing.⁸⁶

⁸⁴ Ghazal, Mohammad. (2017, January 24). Jordan-EU Meeting On 'EU Rules Of Origin' Trade Deal Postponed Indefinitely. Retrieved from <https://www.albawaba.com/business/jordan-eu-meeting-eu-rules-origin-trade-deal-postponed-indefinitely-929208>

⁸⁵ Economic Affairs Editor. (2017, September 18). Taqir: Ithna Ashar Was Sab'a Biasharah Bilme'a Nisbat Aintishar Aineidam Al'amn Alghidhayyi Fi Al'urdun [Report: 12.7% Prevalence Of Food Insecurity In Jordan]. Al-Ghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://alghad.com/articles/1833062>

⁸⁶ Media Center. (2017, January 12). *'Iqrar Khutat Alaistijabat Lil'azmat Alsuwriat 2017 - 2019 Biqimat 6.7 Mlyar Dular* [The Response Plan To The Syrian Crisis 2017-2019 Of 7.6 Billion Dollars Is Approved]. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. Retrieved from <http://www.mop.gov.jo/detailspage/newsdetails.aspx?newsid=871>

For host communities, limited income remained the predominant reason limiting food access, compounded by increasing bills as a consequence of the increased request for food and other goods. Food security in the kingdom was connected to financial access to limited diet, illiteracy, inadequate possessions, extended family, and malnutrition habits. Family income was depleted by the growing housing cost.⁸⁷

In general, Jordanian meals comprised high intake of energy, mainly from vegetable oil, bread, meat, vegetables, and fruits. A study conducted in 2016, showed that 25.4%, over one-fourth, of the refugee population in Jordan was food insecure, resulting in changes in food habits, at times losing meals for entire days. In the capital city of Amman, circumstances of food insecurity were much worse due to greater competition for jobs and more expensive living situations. The study also found strong connections between gender and food security, wherein men were found to be less vulnerable to food insecurity as compared to women.⁸⁸

5.3.3.8 Local Governance and Municipal Services:

Before the Syrian crisis, the Jordanian government was struggling with local governance to meet service delivery shortages, encourage domestic economic development, and preserve social coherence through communities, primarily because of their previously inadequate capacity in administrative and financial matters. Meeting the requirements of Syrian refugees living in urban areas, threatened to overwhelm already overextended local administrations, especially in the northern governorates. In the refugee camps, the

⁸⁷ JRPSC. (2017). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 79.

⁸⁸ Albandak, G., Al-Smadi, A. M., Gammouh, O., Dababneh, B. F., & Shamieh, J. (2016). Cross-Sectional Survey Of Food Security Status For The Syrian Refugees Living In Hosting Communities In Jordan. *International Journal Of Food Engineering*. Vol. 2, No. 1, June 2016, 2(1). p: 5.

government and the donors funding had been used to meet minimum standards. Yet, municipality-neighboring refugee camps, for example in Mafraq Governorate, received limited financial aid to make suitable arrangements and distribute basic services and infrastructure to everyone.⁸⁹ Salary expenditure further exhausted municipalities' budget, so they were unable service their debts, and grappled with constrained revenue generation. Further, municipalities in host communities continued to have shortages in instruments, logistical tools, and capacity to accomplish the best distribution of services and utilize assets.⁹⁰

The growth in population in the northern parts of Jordan also directly impacted societal coherence as it worsened existing tension. It also brought to the front the absence of shared governance at the local level. The host societies demanded much more effective responses to their requirements from central governmental institutions and local governmental authorities, particularly in smaller populated communities.⁹¹

The municipal services of solid waste management suffered because of the growth in population and the resulting enormous waste. Pollution in soil, air, and water had increased as a result of increased amounts of waste, inadequate management of waste collection and disposal, illegal dumping sites, and unsuitable dumping and burning of solid waste. This was also a factor of tension between host communities and Syrian refugees.⁹²

⁸⁹ JRPSC. (2016). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2017/2019)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. p: 107.

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ House, C. (2015, June). *The Role Of Local Government In Addressing The Impact Of Syrian Refugees: Jordan Case Study*. In Middle East And North Africa Programme Workshop Summary, Amman. pp: 2-5.

⁹² Subh, Bashar. et al. (2016). *Analysis Of Impact Of Influx Of Syrian Refugees On Host Communities*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. pp: 40-42.

The water sector in hosting communities was also significantly affected by the increasing demand for water, which had forced the government to increase the pumping of groundwater from groundwater wells in large quantities, going beyond the capacity of these wells. The increase in pumping led to pollution and increased salinity, which in turn drove dissatisfaction of households with water quality. To overcome these challenges, the government attempted to rehabilitate and strengthen water networks, reduce water losses, immediately stop pumping water out of underground wells, compensate for shortages of water through existing dams, dig new dams, and raise awareness regarding the need to rationalize water use.⁹³

5.3.4 The Security Implications:

The Syrian conflict started with seculars and nationalists, but radical Sunni Islamist groups such as Ahrar al-Sham, the ISIS, and Jabhat al-Nusra, also emerged in the conflict, and surprisingly, became the most prominent in the armed conflict.⁹⁴ As Jordan shares a 379 kilometer long border with Syria that encompasses a portion of the north and east of the kingdom, the borders have been covered by border guards equipped with high-level technical and intelligence techniques to protect the border. Threats arise from drugs, terrorism, and accompanying infiltrators. A number of Jordan's soldiers have been killed and many wounded, while facing terrorist operations, preventing infiltration attempts, and following drug smugglers on the border.⁹⁵ The armed forces also trained

⁹³ Ibid: p: 103.

⁹⁴ Mullins, C. A. (2015). *Syria And The Rise Of Radical Islamist Groups*. (Master Thesis). Naval Postgraduate School Monterey CA. pp: 129-130.

⁹⁵ Kamal, Mwafaq. (2017, April 2). *Tahadiyat 'Amniat Waeaskariat Kabirat Tafrihuha Al'azmat Alsuwriat Ealaa Almamlaka* [Major Security And Military Challenges Imposed By The Syrian Crisis On The Kingdom]. Alghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/1528192>

their soldiers stationed at the border on how to deal with human rights and refugees, and the need to notify them, especially children and women.

Jordan not only fears terrorists among the Syrian refugees but also criminal action from newcomers. Terrorist flow is a major challenge for Jordanian security agencies; terrorists now have the opportunity to steer clear of the eyes of security agencies. This situation has forced Jordan to take vital steps in order to avoid being hit again.⁹⁶

As a matter of fact, Jordanian fighters who join terrorist groups have links with individuals from the Syrian refugee population. It is estimated that since the beginning of the crisis in 2011, more than 30,000 foreign fighters had joined terrorist groups such as al-Qaeda and ISIS in Iraq and Syria, of which 3,000 were Jordanian fighters.⁹⁷ These fighters are generally provoked by frustrations with governance, unemployment, unequal opportunities, in addition to the spread of militant jihad beliefs.^{98,99} The increasing number of attacks carried out by ISIS members of Jordanian nationality, along with the rising numbers of Syrian refugees and Jordanians jumping into Salafi-jihadi groups existing in Iraq and Syria, have raise major concerns for the kingdom.¹⁰⁰

The security effects of terrorist actions on Jordan's economy, have been direct as well as indirect. It is noted that as the government spends a lot on security as businesses have

⁹⁶ Malkawi, S. (2015, December 9). Muearidun Suriwn: Daeishiun Yuhawilun Biaistimrar Dukhul Al'urdun Bayn Allajjiyn [Syrian Opponents: ISIS Members Are Constantly Trying To Enter Jordan Among The Refugees]. [Www.24.Ae](https://24.ae/article/205558/). Retrieved from <https://24.ae/article/205558/>

⁹⁷ Wagemakers, J. (2018). *Jihadi-Salafism In Jordan And The Syrian Conflict: Divisions Overcome Unity*. *Studies In Conflict & Terrorism*, 41(3), 191-212. p: 200.

⁹⁸ Schenker, D. (2014). Jordan Not Out Of The Woods Yet. *The Washington Institute*. p: 2

⁹⁹ Dunne, M., & Wehrey, F. (2014). *US-Arab Counterterrorism Cooperation In A Region Ripe For Extremism*. Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. (Vol. 23). p: 7.

¹⁰⁰ Harel, Z. (2017, May 3). *Hundreds Of Thousands Of Young Jordanians Support ISIS*. Memri.Org/Reports. pp: 1-7.

become vulnerable to terrorist assaults, creating apprehensions among foreign investors and multinational firms. Any probability of terrorist actions affects the sensitive economic and business elements in the kingdom, leading to significant socioeconomic consequences.¹⁰¹

Owing to high crime rate in 2016, security services in Jordan have increased their efforts in dealing with Syrian refugees. According to a security expert, crimes against morality, drug issues, and the proliferation of weapons in the kingdom have increased since 2011.¹⁰² The Directorate of Public Security has also established the Directorate of Syrian Refugee Affairs, and provided the same with qualified personnel to deal with Syrian refugee camps as per international standards. According to experts, one of the most prominent security concerns facing Jordan were sleeper cells that could be located in refugee camps or in residential areas, waiting to carry out their operations.

The security bill was enforced by the Jordanian government in its dealings with the Syrian refugees, introducing iris and fingerprint scanners for security checks of refugees entering Jordan, in order to prevent security breaches. The biggest military threats come from inside Syria but not from Syrian refugees.¹⁰³ Security sources pointed out that security in Syrian territories had been compromised as a result of the crisis, which also then reflected on security in Jordan. High, commercial quantities of drugs and weapons

¹⁰¹ Aly, A. M. S., & F. (2015). *Saving The Middle East. Middle East Brief*. Crown Center For Middle East Studies. pp: 1-8.

¹⁰² Kamal, Mwafaq. (2017, April 2). *Tahadiyat 'Amniat Waeaskariat Kabirat Tafriduha Al'azmat Alsuwriat Ealaa Almamlaka* [Major Security And Military Challenges Imposed By The Syrian Crisis On The Kingdom]. Alghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/1528192>

¹⁰³ Szparaga, A. E. (2014). *The Effect Of The Syrian Crisis On Jordanian Internal Security*. Indiana University Bloomington. p: 20.

flow in via the border with Syria, and the armed forces and the security services deal with these issues daily.¹⁰⁴

The rise of terrorism and criminal actions in Jordan has been strongly linked with the sudden influx of Syrian refugees. The international alliance in the Middle East plays a vital role in this regard as the chaos exists in any country extends to neighboring, stable countries.¹⁰⁵ The Syrian crisis yielded four main security threats for Jordan:

1. Islamic Terrorist Group Threats to Jordan: The chaos caused by the Syrian crisis contributed to the rise and strengthening of fundamental terrorism. Jordan suffered violent attacks and threats from ISIS; this went against the Jordanian interest of keeping the Jordanian society stable.

The Jordanian military agencies have adopted the approach of counterterrorism. The detention of ISIS supporters by Jordanian security services exhibits how Jordan is seriously acting against threats of extremism and terrorism. The government is putting in great efforts in campaigns to promote moderation and tolerance of Islam against the extremist radical ideologies in the minds of the ISIS and Al Qaeda affiliates.¹⁰⁶

2. Terrorism amidst the Syrian Refugees Influx: Jordan fears terrorists hiding among refugees. On account of movement of a large number of refugees into the kingdom,

¹⁰⁴ Kamal, Mwafaq. (2017, April 2). *Tahadiyat 'Amnat Waeaskariat Kabirat Tafrihuha Al'azmat Alsuwriat Ealaa Almamlaka* [Major Security And Military Challenges Imposed By The Syrian Crisis On The Kingdom]. Alghad Newspaper. retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/1528192>

¹⁰⁵ Abbadi, Salim. (2015). Jordan In The Shadow Of ISIS. *Counter Terrorist Trends And Analyti*. Volume 7, Issue 2. p: 8.

¹⁰⁶ Ibid: p: 9.

the terrorists have gained an opportunity to stay away from the eyes of security, forcing Jordan to take some important steps to avoid being hit again.¹⁰⁷

Over the past six years, Jordan received over 600 thousand refugees seeking asylum, pushed by the violence in Syria. Five camps for refugees were opened including Zaatari, Azraq, Marjeb Al Fhood, Rukban, and Hadallat. Some of the refugees can move from one location to another or to isolated remote areas in Jordan. It is believed that the refugees' crisis had an adverse impact on Jordan's economic, social and security dimensions. Jordan, with its limited economic and natural resources under critical pressure, is trying to host refugees creating another threat for Jordan.¹⁰⁸

3. Jordanian Fighters Join Terrorist Groups: Since the beginning of the Syrian Crisis in 2011, more than 30,000 foreign fighters had joined terrorist groups such as al-Qaeda and ISIS, of which an estimated 3,000 were Jordanian fighters. The fighters are people frustrated with governance, unemployment, and unequal opportunities, and influenced by militant jihadi beliefs. Jordan is an active supplier of fighters to Iraq and Syria. Al Zarqawi Jihadist gave a clear example of what could happen from a regular individual citizen.^{109,110} The violent extremists succeeded in awakening the Jihadists inside

¹⁰⁷ Malkawi, S. (2015, December 9). Muearidun Suriwn: Daeishiun Yuhawilun Biaistimrar Dukhul Al'urdun Bayn Allajjiyn [Syrian Opponents: ISIS Members Are Constantly Trying To Enter Jordan Among The Refugees]. [Www.24.Ae](https://24.ae/article/205558/). Retrieved from <https://24.ae/article/205558/>

¹⁰⁸ JRPSC. (2015). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis 2015*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. p: 20.

¹⁰⁹ Gulmohamad, Z. K. (2014). *The Rise And Fall Of The Islamic State Of Iraq And Al-Sham (Levant) ISIS*. Global Security Studies, 5(2). pp: 1-2.

¹¹⁰ Bosch, K. M. (2015). *How The Expansion Of The Islamic State Influences The Peace Process Between Turkey And The PKK And How It Affects The Prospects Of An Independent Kurdish State*. (Master Thesis). Utrecht University. p: 18.

Jordan, motivating them to launch attacks within the kingdom. Regardless of whether the fighters stay or go home, they create a threat to the kingdom.¹¹¹

4. Rise of Criminal Actions: The rise of criminal actions in Jordan due to bad economic situation for refugees as well as for the hosting community. The increasing demand for sources of income has made it hard for Jordanians and refugees to handle their daily life. As a result, security agencies recorded high crime rates, in addition to violent actions in the country. The spread of violence, thugs, drugs, and gangs in Jordan, cannot be denied. The Jordanian authority is trying its best to not only contain this impact, but also to find a solution through plans formulated by the government and special international organizations. Actions like fighting unemployment, women care, and anything that empowers the communities, are directed towards both refugees and the hosting communities.

5.3.4.1 Jordan under Threat from ISIS:

The situation in West Asia has become more complicated given the expansion of the Islamic State in Iraq, Syria, Egypt and Libya. Heavyweight terrorist groups, supported by an army, form a real risk for the neighboring Jordan. The power of ISIS cannot be underestimated as it was growing, supported with suitable funding from known and unknown sources.^{112,113,114} This had been proven clearly in Mosul when in 2014, the whole city fell into their hands with a blink of an eye. Other terrorist organizations that pose a

¹¹¹ Speckhard, Anne. (2017). *The Jihad In Jordan: Drivers Of Radicalization Into Violent Extremism In Jordan*. International Center For The Study Of Violent Extremism. p: 15.

¹¹² Windrem, R. (2014). *Who's Funding ISIS? Wealthy Gulf 'Angel Investors,' Officials Say*. NBC News, 21. pp: 1-2.

¹¹³ Dickinson, E. (2013). *Playing With Fire: Why Private Gulf Financing For Syria's Extremist Rebels Risks Igniting Sectarian Conflict At Home*. Saban Center At Brookings. pp: 1-2.

¹¹⁴ See: Warrick, J. (2013). *Private Money Pours Into Syrian Conflict As Rich Donors Pick Sides*. Washington Post, 16.

threat to Jordan include Al-Nusra Front, Ajnad al-Sham, Khalid Ibn Al-Walid Army, Nour al-Din al-Zenki Movement, Tawhid Army, Muhajirin wa-Ansar Alliance, and Jund al-Aqsa.¹¹⁵

For Jordan, being at the edge of the cliff is not a comfortable matter. As the Jordanian society is conservative, it has some tendency toward Islamism. It is no secret that 3,000 of Jordanians who had gone to fight in Syria had joined ISIS. The Jordanians who are fighting with the ISIS and other Salafist-jihadist organizations will remain a big security concern for the Jordanian authorities in the future, within Jordan and outside.¹¹⁶ The Islamic Parties in Jordan are active in the Jordanian streets. The Islamic Action Front (Muslims Brothers Islamic party) is the most active. These Islamic parties do not follow the Salafists thoughts, yet majority of the Jordanian society members consider ISIS and Al Qaeda terrorist groups. Jordan has been a part of the strategic goals of ISIS. The Islamic States propaganda published a primary imagined map of the future State of Islamic Khilafah, which was to later include Iraq and Syria, then Jordan and Kuwait, reaching Palestine. The Islamic State managed to challenge the transponder of the states that had been in Sykes–Picot colonial Agreement, which encouraged it to expand its appetite for nationalism and act on religious duties to reshape the Islamic Empire.¹¹⁷

¹¹⁵ Editorial Team. (2015, December 15). *Tasrib Qayimat Al'urdun Lilmunazamat Al'iirhabiat Baynaha Ahrar Alshsham Walzunki, Watahdid Binisf Mutamar Alriyad* [Leaked List Of Jordan's Black List Of Terrorist Organizations, Including Ahrar Al-Sham And Al-Zanki, And Threatened To Blow Up The Riyadh Conference]. Souriat E-Newspaper. Retrieved From: [Http://Www.Souriat.Com/2015/12/15411.Html](http://www.souriat.com/2015/12/15411.html)

¹¹⁶ IRIS Analysis Study. (2016 January). *Jordan Two-Year Scenario Analysis: Deteriorating Resilience And Increasing Vulnerabilities*. Humanitarian And Development Programme. Institut De Relations Internationales Et Stratégiques. IRIS. Paris, France. p: 2.

¹¹⁷ Editorial Team. (2016, December 2). Jordan In The Shadow Of Salafism. Retrieved from <http://strelok-analysis.com/analysis/jordan-shadow-salafism>

During the last three years, wide geographic and demographic developments were noticed in Jordanian jihadists' activities. The numbers of Jihadists reached over 7000, in addition to the supporters, distributed in all cities and governorates and found in all classes. However, they are concentrated more in cities like Zarqa and Rusayfeh where the population is already high. Prevalence is also high in poor areas in Amman, Salt city, Ma'an city and in Palestinian refugee camps, as these areas are characterized by feelings of being marginalized, that cause a sense of deprivation, poverty, and unfairness, thus breeding jihadists. Such societies act as incubators of terrorism, especially in Zarqa and Ma'an. Jihadists in Jordan are all set to work, they only need time and orders.¹¹⁸

The burning of the Jordanian pilot by ISIS in 2015 provoked anger and hatred against the Islamic State in Jordan, which consequently led the government to execute by death sentence, ISIS members judged on 2005 bomb attacks in Amman.¹¹⁹

Recently, Jordan became a target of several terror attacks. The latest attack in December 2016, where a group of four Jordanian nationals struck a number of targets in Karak city, south of Jordan. The fight resulted in killing of four security men, other civilians and one Canadian tourist. The Islamic State (ISIS) owned responsibility for the incident. Later on, investigations revealed that the attackers were in prison at the time, attempting to join ISIS.¹²⁰ The increasing number of deadly attacks carried out by ISIS members of Jordanian

¹¹⁸ Schenker, D. (2014). Jordan Not Out Of The Woods Yet. *The Washington Institute*. p: 3.

¹¹⁹ Gadarian, S. K. (2010). The Politics Of Threat: How Terrorism News Shapes Foreign Policy Attitudes. *The Journal Of Politics*. 72(2), 469-483. p: 481.

¹²⁰ Bremmer, Ian. (2017, April 14). The Top 5 Countries Where ISIS Gets Its Foreign Recruits. Retrieved from <http://time.com/4739488/the-top-5-countries-where-isis-gets-its-foreign-recruits/>

nationality, along with the worrying numbers of Jordanians jumping into Salafi-jihadi groups in Iraq and Syria, are cause for concern for the kingdom.¹²¹

The governmental campaigns in media against terrorism were served a lot by the pilot's killing. A big wave of shock and feelings of horror flowed through the Jordanians, when citizens felt the real danger from ISIS.¹²²

While incident occurrence in Jordan is still low, there are reasons to believe that terrorists are present in Jordan, looking to launch more attacks. ISIS members in the kingdom have issued statements targeting the King Abdullah II regime; hundreds of fighters who have deep roots in Jordan and have traveled to fight for ISIS and other militants may return, whether as part of an ISIS plan or in reaction to big losses in Syria and Iraq. In addition, repeated assaults in Europe have proved that there is danger from lonely self-radicalized individuals who are fascinated by the ideology of ISIS to attack their countries. These could be normal citizens or even armed forces members with access to extraneous military or inhabitant personnel. Indeed, ISIS has specifically encouraged violence through its several propaganda platforms. The Jordanian security agencies remain alert to the danger and are prepared to counter such challenges, but as the 18 December Karak city incident and other incidents through 2016 have showed, the security agencies cannot entirely eradicate the threat or stay immune to attacks.

ISIS attack methods regionally have constituted primarily sole attackers, and then multiple militants deployed against both hard and soft targets. Given the high security in Jordan,

¹²¹ Harel, Z. (2017, May 3). *Hundreds Of Thousands Of Young Jordanians Support ISIS*. Memri.Org/Reports. p: 5..

¹²² Abu Roman, Samer. (2015) *(Daesh) Tanzim Aldawlat Fi Euyun Alshueub [The Islamic State In The Eyes Of People]*. *Albayan Center For Researches And Studies*. Jordan. p: (20).

public casualty and complex assaults including gun and bomb attacks, are more prevalent near the borders with Iraq and Syria, compared to the main urban areas. There exist noticeable security and political vacuums in western Iraq and southern Syria, which enable ISIS movement and operation. In Jordan, attacks are focused on soft targets, executed by small groups, singular suicide bombers, or gunmen. Patrols, checkpoints, and less secured state institutions are likely the easy targets. Western interests, including businesses and diplomatic facilities, are the prime targets, so are areas where Westerners gather, such as hotels, restaurants and tourist areas. The problem is that as the time and place of attacks is mostly unknown, they require rapid deployment of trained forces to counter terrorism.¹²³

The sense of danger increased further on account of existence of Islamic Militants that follow ISIS in south Syria at the Jordanian-Syrian border, in addition to the series of ISIS and Al Qaeda attacks in Jordan. Jordan holds that it will not be the backyard for Syrian fighting parties, especially for terrorist groups that had fled from the war in Syria. Instead, the country believes in peaceful solutions.¹²⁴

Terrorism tries to achieve its political objectives through violence and terror, thus ISIS terrorist activities are a clear violation of local human rights, international law and legal norms on the one hand, and of traditions and religious norms on the other. Terrorism in Jordan has created a new situation of horror, fear, and panic among the public. This poses a threat to international peace and security of societies, and disturbs internal and international stability and friendly relations between nations. Terrorist groups have become

¹²³ Susser, A. (2015). *Jordan Facing Up To The ISIS Challenge: A Net Assessment*. Brandeis University, Crown Center For Middle East Studies, 92, pp: 6.7..

¹²⁴ AFP. (2016, June 21). *Jordan Declares Syria Border 'Military Zone' After Bombing*. Al-Monitor. Retrieved from <https://www.al-monitor.com/pulse/afp/2016/06/jordan-unrest-syria.html> pp:1-2.

a weapon used by some countries as alternatives to conventional wars in their pursuit of personal strategic interests and objectives, regardless of the legitimacy of the means leading to it, thus directly and indirectly resorting to terrorist acts to achieve those objectives.¹²⁵

International terrorism appears to be a fundamental indicator of the violation of many of the original human rights guaranteed by religions, conventions, and charters through international human rights law. Jordan joined the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, as well as the Covenants on Civil and Political Rights.¹²⁶ The country does not want to get tangled in terrorism like Syria, Iraq, and Libya, where civilians are easy targets for all kinds of attacks and weapons, and fear and panic are everywhere. The resulting destruction occurs in various forms causing destruction of homes, burning of property, and all kinds of material losses. Yemen is another good example of an insecure state, where the government is unable to secure its citizens, borders, and economy. Syria, Iraq, Libya, and Yemen seem to have turned into terror lands, from where people are fleeing to neighboring countries including Jordan. Even so, the Jordanian authorities recognize that some of the refugees might hold the seeds of terrorism and create an insecure environment in the country.

5.3.5 The Positive Implications of the Syrian Crisis for Jordan:

Despite the fact that Syrian crisis had huge negative implications for Jordan; still, there were some positive implications for the country, mainly from an economic perspective. Economic experts elaborated that owing to the presence of investors among Syrian

¹²⁵ Mohammad. R. Hamdan, (2011). *Al'iirhab Alduwaliu Watadaeiatuh Ealaa Al'amn Walsilm Alealamii Dirasatan Tahlilatan Min Manzur Aijtimateiin*. [Global Terrorism And Its Consequences On Global Security And Peace. Analytical Study From Social Prospect]. *Basic Journal*, Basic Education Faculty. Al- Mousil University. p: 26.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

refugees, it became possible to provide benefits to both parties involved if provided with the right incentives and facilities. Availability of cheap labor, as a result of increasing refugee population, was another advantage to the Jordanian economy.

5.3.5.1 Syrian Investments:

According to official statistics issued by the Directorate of Companies Control in Jordan, in 2014, 485 Syrian companies were registered in the country with a total investment of around 24.6 million dinar. The total capital invested by registered Syrian companies since the outbreak of the crisis in 2011, reached 98 million dinar.¹²⁷ Syrian companies spanned to various sectors in the Jordanian economy.

Jordan Investment Commission reported that by the end of 2016, Jordan witnessed remarkable amounts of Syrian investments in various sectors, especially the industrial sector, where investments were a qualitative addition to the economy. Syrian businessmen took great interest in all sectors since Syrian labor had high skills. Earlier, Syrian investments in Jordan focused on small projects, but when the government provided better investment facilities it managed to attract more Syrian investors. These facilities have created new areas of work in Jordan, and provided employment opportunities to more than 5,000 Jordanian citizens.¹²⁸

At the opposite end of the spectrum were economists who believed that Syrian investments that entered the kingdom did not add much value to the national economy, due to the

¹²⁷ Al-Kilani, Mahmoud. (2015, June 10). Hijrat Alaiqtisad Alswry: Aineikas 'Ijabiun Ealaa Al'urdun [Syrian Economy Migration: Positive Impact On Jordan]. Noonpost.Org. Jordan. Rerieved from <http://www.noonpost.org/الوضع-الأردني/هجرة-الاقتصاد-السوري-انعكاس-إيجابي-على-الأردن> p: 1.

¹²⁸ Economic Editor. (2016, November 19). *Hayyat Al'iistithmar Al'urduniyat: AlsuwriuwN Nahduu Biqitae Alsinaeat Fi Almamlakajordan* [Investment Commission: Syrians Risen To The Industry Sector In The Kingdom]. Retrieved From <Https://Www.Akhbaralaan.Net/Business/2016/11/19/هيئة-الاستثمار-الأردنية-السوريون-نهضوا-بقطاع-الصناعة-في-المملكة>

modest size of investments when compared to the large proportions of Syrian investments which were directed to neighboring countries. Syrian investments in Jordan remained limited to 200 million dinar. However, some trades and occupations contributed to adding value to professions, in addition to helping Jordanians gain experience in professions where workers were predominantly Syrians. Syrian investments that entered the kingdom had both positive and negative consequences, as on the one hand they developed some trades and professions, while on the other they created more competition for Jordanian laborers. At the end, Syrian investments did not contribute significantly to the Jordanian GDP.¹²⁹

5.3.6 Converting Challenges into Opportunities:

The Independent Jordanian Economic Observatory issued in 2015, was an in-depth report calling for the integration of Syrians into the local economy. The report pointed out that throughout history, various refugee movements had proven productive for Jordan and had huge positive impact on the Jordanian economy. The report pointed out that the Palestinian refugees moving to Jordan in 1948 and 1967, eventually formed the backbone of the Jordanian private sector and contributed to the stimulation of the economy. Similarly, the Iraqi refugees also brought enormous amounts of foreign investment to Jordan, which supported its economic recovery at the time and continued for years after 2003. Thus, it could also be true in the case of Syrian refugees who could have a positive impact on the local economy and the economic environment.¹³⁰

¹²⁹ Al-Jinini, Saif. (2016, January 18). *Aiqtisadiun: Alaistithmarat Alsuwriat Lm Tushakil Qimatan Mudafatan Lilaiqtisad Alwatanii Litawadue Hajmiha* [Economists: Syrian Investments Did Not Add Value To The National Economy To The Modest Size]. Alrai Newspaper. Jordan. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/762278.html>

¹³⁰ Special Report. (2015, September 6). *Taqirir 'Urduniyun Yatahadath Ean 'Ahamiyat Alaistifadat Min Alwujud Alsuwrii Watahwil Allajiiyn Limuntajin "Elaa Ghirar Alfilastiniinya"*. *Wairqam Sadimat: 99% Min Alsuwriiyn Fi Al'urdun Yaemalun Fi Qitaat Ghyr Munazamata* [A Jordanian Report On The Importance Of Benefiting From The Syrian

The report stated that the primary advantage of hosting refugees is their impact on the local economy. In long-term refugee situations, refugees build up the consumer market, create new markets, and bring in new skills and employment opportunities that may not be available in the host country. The other positive influence discussed is the opportunity to improve and develop infrastructure and basic services which are often supported by donations, the value addition being that such developments would benefit both the refugee population and the host communities.¹³¹ The report added that this, however, cannot be achieved unless the government changes its vision towards refugees and works to create an appropriate legislative and investment environment. The report recommended adopting a strategy that includes tools and appropriate means to grant economic and social freedoms to refugees and to create a supportive legislative environment that increases the benefits for refugees while reducing costs. This would require a complete transformation in the government's perception of refugees.^{132,133}

5.4 Conclusion:

The Syrian refugee influx in Jordan which raised its population by at least 8%, touched almost all aspects of life in Jordan including political, economic, social, and security

Presence And The Transfer Of Refugees To Producers "Like The Palestinians" And Shocking Figures: 99% Of Syrians In Jordan Working In The Sectors Of The Organization]. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/-تقرير-اردني-يتحدث-عن-الاستفادة-م>

¹³¹ The Independent Jordanian Economic Observatory. (2015). *Al'athar Alaiqtisadiu Walaijtimaieu Lilajiiyn Alsuwriiyn Ealaa Al'urduni Tahwil Altahadiyat 'Iilaa Furas* [Economic And Social Impact Of Syrian Refugees On Jordan: Turning Challenges Into Opportunities]. Identity Center. Jordan. pp: 24-25.

¹³² Ibid.

¹³³ See: Compact, J. (2016, February). The Jordan Compact: A New Holistic Approach Between The Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan And The International Community To Deal With The Syrian Refugee Crisis. In Supporting Syrian And The Region: London Conference (Www. Gov. Uk/Government/Uploads/System/Uploads/Attachment_Data/File/498021/Supporting_Syria__The_Regions_Statement_London_2016_-_Jordan_Statement. Pdf.

aspects. The presence of thousands of refugees in urban areas raised fear of competition for resources and opportunities among Jordanians. It also affected the public financial performance, placing a significant burden on budgets and overstressing services across all affected sectors. Most affected were the already vulnerable communities, as wages went from being low to even lower, to an extent that these communities struggled for financial independence. The government, on the other hand, was concerned about the potentially serious economic effects of refugees, including effects on the labor market as the available job opportunities declined, along with wage levels, working conditions, and access to work. At the political level, the Jordanian policy followed its own plans to meet the challenges resulting from the crisis. Jordan did not clearly express its interests and its final position on the Syrian crisis, but repeatedly voiced concerns regarding the worsening surrounding environment. Although, the Jordanian leadership later changed its way of dealing with the crisis in general and the refugees issue in particular. Jordan declared it would not bear the burden of refugees at the expense of its national interests and the Jordanian people. The leadership recognized that the Syrian peace process between the Syrian government and the opposition parties will be a long course of negotiations starting from Arab League peace plans 2011–2012, then the Geneva peace talks on Syria, to the Initiation of Astana talks in 2016. Jordan made it a point to not get involved in the heart of the crisis.

As for the internal influence of Syrian asylum on political issues at the domestic level, the Jordanian government was concerned regarding the popular influence of the Syrian crisis imitating that of the Arab spring revolution. Another concern was that of Jordanians themselves revolting against the government as the Syrian influx hit severely all aspects of

life in Jordan. As for the concerns of Syrian refugees' settlement in Jordan, the government confirmed that it is not a possibility.

The Jordanian economic sector was significantly affected by flow of Syrian refugees; however, some hosting communities partly benefitted from the presence of refugees. Business owners benefitted as the refugees made for cheap skillful labor, and also increased consumer demand. Although, incomes were threatened by the downward push on informal-sector wages, which were already very low. The Jordanian government issued 200 thousand work permits for Syrian refugees in the fields of constructions and agriculture, vocational occupations and services, but they were not allowed to get into 19 roles, including administrative positions. Syrians were competing with Jordanians for work opportunities, especially in lower paid jobs, even though they possessed better experience. In terms of investment, Syrian business owners were allowed to invest, but there were some legal regulations in place.

The influx of Syrian refugees had ramifications for the education sector as well. School classrooms became overcrowded, more so than before, with many schools converting to two-shift timings wherein Jordanians were taught in the mornings and Syrians in the afternoons, resulting in teachers working overtime even while not being compensated for the same. In addition, schools needed maintenance or expansion due to the sharp increase in the number of pupil. Crowding in classes was found to be more severe in seven districts in governorates where refugee population was higher. Thus, education became a major priority for the government.

The population surge affected public services for all. The quality and availability of healthcare declined as overburdened facilities struggled to cope with the increasing number

of patients. People had to wait for long before receiving medical attention. Jordanian residents in urban areas gained from the presence of refugees as increased housing demand allowed property owners to set higher rents. The lower-income Jordanian families, on the other hand, were displaced due to higher rents.

The local water shortages also increased as majority of the Syrian refugees were not living in refugee camps, but in cities and towns. Consequently, the water supply in those hosting communities was severely hit and water portions for Jordanians declined. Intensive competition over water, forced the communities to buy water at high prices to meet their daily needs.

In terms of security, the Jordanian government feared the unknown Syrian refugees who could be inclined to radical thought or could possess terrorist ideologies. There were instances where a number of refugees either participated in violent actions or had factional relations with radical and terrorist organizations. Such people were a huge threat to the Jordanian society and to the authorities alike. Jordan recognized the risk that some refugees posed to the security, economy, society, and even culture of the country.

The JRPSC plans include both short-term humanitarian plans and short and medium term resilience interventions, needed to mitigate the impact of the Syrian crisis on Syrian refugees and the Jordanian population, chiefly through the provision of humanitarian aid and strengthening of basic services and government financing. This will ensure that emergency, short, medium and long-term interventions by the government, the UN, NGOs, and private sector are integrated, sequenced, and coordinated.

There were also some positive impacts of the crisis. The Syrian investment, though not at the desired level, supported the Jordanian economy. When compared with Syrian

investments in other neighboring countries, Syrian investors in Jordan focused on smaller projects in industrial and service sectors. Experts recommended that the government launch packages of investment facilities including but not limited to work permits, in order to attract investments and extract benefits from the crisis. Finally, the government looked at international aid as an advantage of the crisis, as the government was counting on this assistance to support the public budget to meet the growing service demands of both the host communities and the Syrians, especially regarding building and reconstruction and restoration of the basic infrastructure.

In conclusion, research suggests that the largest costs to the Jordanian economy were linked to Syrians entering the local labor market, and the pressure exerted on the infrastructure and public services of the state which needed huge investments in terms of building, restoration, and maintenance. The external aid was directed toward both helping the Syrians living in Jordan as well as helping the host communities. Benefits from the Syrian refugee crisis included contribution to economic sectors which added to the overall GDP as Syrians became a major source of foreign investment in Jordan. These advantages have contributed positively to macroeconomic indicators, including those related to public budget and foreign-exchange reserves.

Chapter Five

The Changing Dynamics of the Jordanian- Syrian Relationship the Jordanian Perspective

Chapter Five: The Changing Dynamics of the Jordanian- Syrian Relationship the Jordanian Perspective

6.1 Introduction:

In this chapter, the researcher will address the Jordanian foreign policy towards all components and actors of the Syrian crisis in order to uncover the country's stance on the crisis and its components. The chapter will showcase the position of Jordan in the context of action and interaction with internal and external variables, focusing on the Jordanian perspective towards the crisis, actors in the conflict, and consequences.

The chapter will begin with an overview of the current Jordanian foreign policy, then moving to the changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations including the Jordanian stance on the crisis during 2011-2016 and its determinants, along with regional and international influences on Jordan's position, public opinion, and internal stability. The discussion will then move to the Jordanian policy towards Syrian asylum, the country's economic policy and government plans developed in response to the crisis, and policy towards the Syrian regime and opposition. The chapter will end with explaining Jordan's policy against security issues and terrorism, and finally, its position towards the Syrian peace process strategies adopted by Jordan. The chapter will end with a conclusion.

6.2 An Overview of the Current Jordanian Foreign Policy:

The current Jordanian foreign policy is the result of a mixture of internal factors and external factors. The policy is governed by a set of objectives, the most important of which is maintaining stability in the country. The scarcity of economic resources in Jordan played an important role in shaping its foreign policy, as it is always in need of assistance from other states.

Since its establishment, the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan has adopted a foreign policy that expresses its will and public discourse according to a set of principles that shaped its policy and controlled the mechanism of political decision-making in accordance with domestic, regional, and international data, and all of this happened under the shadow of the Arab-Israeli conflict pressure. ¹The country's foreign policy is distinguished from other regional countries because Jordan enjoys the friendship and respect of all its allies as its policy is based on balancing the issues of conflict without abandoning the fundamentals and the supreme national interests. By the end of the last century, Jordanian regime's policy was swinging from confrontation to accommodation in order to go along with the regional changes to face the massive domestic and regional challenges that might be a threat to the regime's survival.²

The Jordanian foreign policy is categorized as dynamic, changing, and pragmatic, adopting a method of dialogue and discourse instead of fighting and conflict, in an attempt to avoid creating enmity with any party, and not interfering in the affairs of other states. This was evident during the regional disputes. Further, Jordan's foreign policy cannot be separated from the country's geographical reality as its location makes it prone to external environment thus affecting its political decisions. The human resources of the kingdom represented by human capabilities and capacities also influence its foreign policy. Jordan's interests are vested in countries in the Middle East as well as the superpowers of the world

¹ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. p: 209.

² Salloukh, B. F. (1996). State Strength, Permeability, And Foreign Policy Behavior: Jordan In Theoretical Perspective. *Arab Studies Quarterly*, 39-65. p: 61.

and any political decision may affect their accomplishment in the future.³ Limited economic resources also influence Jordan's political decision-making because any decision may give rise to a major internal crisis, especially if any external assistance is cut off. On account of all these factors, Jordan tries to direct its policies and efforts towards maintaining good relations with all parties.

Jordan's policy is now based on playing a competitive role in seeking and implementing the highest interests of its people without fear of financial, economic or other losses that they once supported.⁴ This means structuring foreign policy in line with the people's will and leadership because they are on the same side. Therefore, external pressures are hardly imposed on Jordan's policy and people. The political planners must move quickly to stay abreast with regional and international changes to protect national gains based on the "Jordan First" principle which was launched by King Abdullah II in November 2002.

Looking at the Jordanian political movement, it can be said that it is flexible and multifaceted. For example, relations with the European Union take priority as Jordan's relationship with the European Union dates back to 1977, which is also why Jordan has built a great deal of credibility with the EU countries. On the other hand, Jordan has built a parallel course of relations with the US, establishing strong diplomatic relations since 1949, which culminated into presidential visits including visit with former US President Richard Nixon.⁵

³ Al-Makahleh, Shehab. (2018, January 31). Albraghatyt Alsiyasiat Al'urduniyat Wasiasat Alwasatia [The Political Pragmatism Of Jordan And The Policy Of Moderation]. Retrieved from <http://geostrategicmedia.com/2018/01/31/البراهماتية-السياسية-الأردنية-وسياس>?lang=ar

⁴ Telhami, S., & Barnett, M. N. (Eds.). (2002). *Identity And Foreign Policy In The Middle East*. Cornell University Press. pp: 26-27.

⁵ Metz, H. C. (Ed.). (1989). *Jordan: A Country Study*. Library Of Congress, Federal Research Division. pp: 215-217.

Jordan is surrounded by countries that have experienced political tensions and major security crises that required vigilance and caution. The kingdom has thus formulated a foreign policy, which aims to protect its national security in accordance with security arrangements through regional and international alliances with dominant powers, led by the United States.⁶

Jordan's foreign policy is made by King Abdullah II, and there are assistants and advisers voice their opinions on several matters while adhering to the constants of moderation and the tendency of Western policy. Because Jordan lies in the heart of the Arab world, it was influenced by the geopolitical environment, its international relations, the demographical, geographical, and economic and water dimensions, which had a great impact on its social and economic transformations. The most important feature of Jordan's policy is its approach to the Palestinian issue,⁷ especially with regard to the issue of Jerusalem, which was greatly influenced by the policies of the major powers and the policy of regional axes, but Jordan is doing what it can to achieve balance in its foreign relations at all levels despite the fact that it is located between some strong Arab states like Syria, Iraq, Saudi Arabia and the West of the Kingdom of Palestine and Israel. Jordan is also following the approach of the Great Arab Revolution from an ideological point of view, which means that Jordan cannot abandon its reality and its cause which is the issue of Jerusalem, the Holy City under the Hashemite trusteeship.⁸

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ Al- Bani Nasur, Nader Ibrahim M., Al-Fawwaz, Abdulrahman. Al-Afif, Ahmad Kh. (2012). *Jordanian Foreign Policy Toward The Palestine Issue*. Research Gate. Department Of Humanities. Al-Balqa' Applied University. Jordan. pp: 11-12.

⁸ Ibid. p: 7.

With King Abdullah II as a policymaker, there are two important dimensions to the Jordanian foreign policy. The first dimension is its relationship with the United States of America which no longer has the same political and economic conditions that existed during the reign of King Hussein. Relations with America have improved, are no longer dependent on the Israel or British gates, instead it is direct and strong.⁹ The second dimension is the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which is Jordan's strongest regional alliance. There is full coordination, and an excellent relationship between the Kings of the two countries regarding the political, security, and economic aspects.¹⁰

Jordan adopts the policy of alliances whether it is Arab relations or with the Western powers. The positions and policies of the superpowers and the allied parties on the region and its future, were determinants for Jordan's foreign policies and cast their shadow over the decision-making process, which confirms Jordan's continuous need to balance its foreign and regional relations. International relations too, with a view to achieve political stability, were not absent from the King's strategy and vision. Since the King took up his constitutional powers and he has been striving to strengthen Jordan's political and economic relations with other countries, exchanging official visits with different countries.¹¹

Following a moderate policy that functions on good relations with everyone, Jordan is pursuing an approach that may be difficult to deal with but is essential, as it prevents sensitizing neighboring countries. For every action, this process must be carried out and a balance must be

⁹ Al-Faiz, Thiab. (2013). *Alealaqat Al'urdunit-Al'amrikiat Wafaquha Almustaqbalia [Jordanian – American Relations And Its Future Prospects]*. (Master Thesis). Middle East University. Jordan. pp: 34-36.

¹⁰ Editorial Team (2016, April 11). *Alsewdyt Walardun: Taeziz Altaeawun Al'amni Bitawqie Aitifaqiat Easkariat Mushtaraka* [Jordan And Saudi Arabia: Strengthen Security Cooperation By Signing Joint Military Agreements]. Retrieved from <http://sdarabia.com/?p=29317>

¹¹ Walt, S. M. (1997). Why Alliances Endure Or Collapse. *Survival*. 39(1), pp: 163-164.

struck between all regional and international environments. Over the last two decades, regional and international powers have emerged; these powers were earlier in the margins of regional politics.

Internationally and regionally, Jordan follows a moderate policy,¹² and is thus considered one of the most committed and responsible countries in the world that has gained international respect. As part of its responsibility regarding international cooperation, Jordan participates heavily, establishing hospitals in disaster areas and sending more than 40,000 soldiers to maintain peace all over the world.

Amidst the changing arena of Arab and international politics, Jordan decides on its position in the face of Arab countries' weakness, and inability to influence regional decisions. The Jordanian leadership recognizes that the Arab countries with more population density and wealth, are trying to be at the center of polarization. In addition to that, Jordan is an essential member of the Arab League, which is fighting to restore a part of the power with some new stimulations in the polarization process, with Arab countries whose economies are growing and who want to be a force of influence.¹³

6.3 The Relation of Jordan's Foreign Policy with "Jordan First":

The slogan "Jordan First" places Jordanian interests over all other considerations, and is an attempt to instill a novel societal consensus among the Jordanians and to reshape the country-

¹² Romman, Raid. (2016, February 16). Alsiyasat Alkharijiat Al'urduniya .. Sadaqat Mae Aljamie 'Am Tabeia [Jordanian Foreign Policy: A Friendship With All Or Dependence And Subordination?] Retrieved from <https://www.noonpost.org/?الوضع-الأردني/السياسة-الخارجية-الأردنية-صداقة-مع-الجميع-أم-تبعية-وخضوع>

¹³ Al-Manaser, Nader. (2016, November 2). *Kayf Sayastathmir Al'urdunu Alqimat Alearabiat Almuqabilata?* [How Will Jordan Invest The Next Arab Summit?] Retrieved from <https://www.alarabiya.net/ar/arab-and-world/2016/11/02/-كيف-سيستثمر-الأردن-القمة-العربية-المقبلة؟>

individual relationship. The slogan goes beyond being a simple thought, as it would be inculcated in all aspects of life for the Jordanian people. “Jordan First” is a means to pursue new policies and programs regarding the state’s development in various fields. The slogan also symbolizes a request to public, civil, societal, and private sector organizations, to increase their participation in structuring a modern state by concentrating on attaining political, economic, and social development, creating creative opportunities and combating unemployment and poverty, in addition to improving the values and standard of living of the citizens. In short, “Jordan First” is a new governance philosophy, founded on the principle of putting Jordan's national interest above all considerations of civil society.¹⁴

The current domestic and foreign policy under King Abdullah is best summarized by the regime's motto "Jordan First", proposing a strong nationalist outlook to foreign policy that has been used to fight back foreign influences on Jordan’s domestic politics. For example, the King has criticized the interactional relations of several of Jordan's central opposition parties, from both pro-Syrian and pro-Iraqi Baathist parties in Jordan to the Communist party, to the Islamic Action Front.¹⁵ So the tone, in nationalist simple words, applies to foreign policy and to domestic politics. In practice on the ground, the political opposition of secular left or religious right would theoretically be considered as un-Jordanian. Before the “Jordan First” campaign started, dissenting voices of journalists, activists in political parties, independent Islamists, and feminist activists, were silenced through arrests.¹⁶

¹⁴ Phenix. (2016). *Guide To Joranian Political Life*. Retrieved from <http://www.jordanpolitics.org/en/documents-view/62/jordan-first/41>

¹⁵ Ryan, C. R. (2004). "Jordan First": Jordan's Inter-Arab Relations And Foreign Policy Under King Abdullah II. *Arab Studies Quarterly*. p: 55.

¹⁶ Ibid. p: 56.

In summary, the current Jordanian foreign policy is based on, first and foremost, implementing the high interests of the Jordanian State. The roles played in the past by Jordan, regarding the Arab Nation, would not be played again at the expense of the Jordanian people. “Jordan First”, as the name rightly suggests, puts Jordan’s interest above all else. The new policy adopted by King Abdullah II matches the demands of the new world order in its political, economic, and societal aspects. During the reign of King Hussein, Jordan would regularly lend free services for the Palestinians, the Iraqis, and to other Arab states and issues; this approach was proven wrong with the argument that there must be a price for each participation, and so this policy is now being strictly put in practice regarding the Syrian issue.

Jordan has always sought to encourage peaceful conflict resolution through its foreign policy, which has been quite dynamic as the state has consciously moved from competition with other countries to influencing the region to seeking its own interests. So, Jordan’s policy has moved quickly with a stable dynamic rather than stable alliances. This movement includes not only the surrounding Arab and Muslim countries, but also Latin America and China as well as the European Union.

6.4 The Changing Dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian Relations:

The dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations during the period 2011-2016 were controlled by various variables connected firmly to the events of the Syrian crisis and their consequences. The bilateral relationship between Jordan and Syria went into deterioration with the Syrian crisis as it not only impacted Jordan, but also global and regional political dynamics.¹⁷ Jordan, as a close

¹⁷ Demir, S., & Rijnoveanu, C. (2013). *The Impact Of The Syria Crisis On The Global And Regional Political Dynamics*. Scientific Researcher, Institute For Political Studies Of Defense And Military History, Bucharest, Romania. pp: 73-74.

neighbor of Syria, was affected directly by the events and the violence of the crisis, and the effects were mostly negative. The presence of more than 1.3 million Syrians in Jordan led to a direct, negative impact on the Jordanians in hosting communities, encompassing all aspects of life including politics, economy, society, and security.

6.4.1 The Jordanian Stance on the Syrian Crisis from 2011 to 2016:

The Jordanian leadership saw the crisis in Syria as an internal issue of a neighboring Arab country; the crisis was a result of certain circumstances that belonged to Syria and Jordan had nothing to do with it. However, the situations escalated so far that the violence and consequences affected Jordan directly. The Jordanian leadership under King Abdullah II and the authorized governmental institutions repeatedly alluded to the fundamental principles that governed Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis, and that it did not affect the safety of Jordan's unity, territory, people, national interest, and security. Jordan acted in a way that helped in guarding the kingdom. Jordan's primary stance on the crisis can be summarized as follows:^{18,19,20}

1. The unity of the Syrian territories.
2. No intervention with others issues.
3. No resettlement for the Syrian refugees.
4. Priority of Jordanian interests.

¹⁸ King Abdullah II. (2014, December 6) His Majesty King Abdullah II's Interview On PBS's Charlie Rose – Transcript. 6 December 2014. Retrieved from <http://usvisit2014en.rhcjo.com/hmkiicharlierosetranscript/>

¹⁹ Political Editor. (2016, February 14). *Syasywn: La Makhawif Haqiqiyan Min Tawtin Allajiyyn Alswryyn* [Politicians: There Are No Real Fears Of Settling Syrian Refugees]. AL-Ghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/articles/920347>

²⁰ The Guardian. (2016, July 26). *Terrorist Attacks And Security Lapses Fuel Fears For Jordan's Stability*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/on-the-middle-east/2016/jul/25/terrorist-attacks-and-security-lapses-fuel-fears-for-jordan-stability>

5. Supporting the Syrian peace process.
6. No military intervention; limited involvement.
7. Jordan's national security and stability are most important.
8. No efforts to dethrone the Syrian regime.
9. Jordan calls to stop fighting and violence immediately.
10. Jordan shall not take the burdens of the Syrian Refugees alone.
11. Jordan follows the international laws regarding receiving the refugees.

Since the inception of the Syrian crisis, the Jordanian foreign policy towards it was characterized by ambiguity. Jordan continued to voice a political solution as the best option for resolving the crisis, and did not encourage promotion of any policy requiring any military intervention for solving the crisis.

When they took the leadership of their countries, both King Abdullah II and Syrian President Bashar al-Assad found themselves in struggling with tense relations between their countries, but the two leaders managed to seek a way to decrease tension to accomplish of the countries' mutual interests. In 2004, King Abdullah II spoke about the formation of Shiite crescent led by Iran in the Arab Levant, including Syrians, the thing that led to creating political tensions between Amman and Damascus as there is a threat from the presence of Iranian military forces and Iraqi Shiite militias in Syria.²¹ The difference between the axis of moderation and the axis of resistance was the main reason behind Jordanian-Syrian political dispute. Cooperation at the economic level remained, in addition to the trans-border security issues.²²

²¹ Fulton, W., Holliday, J., & Wyer, S. (2013). *Iranian Strategy In Syria*. AEI's Critical Threats Project. pp: 13-25.

²² Satik, N. (2013). *The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis Of Neighboring Countries' Stances*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Studies. p: 15.

In line with its foreign policy to not interfere in another state's internal issues, Jordan did not consider the Syrian legitimate authority or any political actor in the Syrian crisis as a rival or an enemy, except ISIS and Al-Nusra Front.²³ On 15 August 2016, King Abdullah II stressed that the only solution to the Syrian crisis was a comprehensive political solution in which all components relating to the Syrian people are agreed upon by all parties. The King stressed that this solution must end the suffering of the Syrians and preserve the unity of the Syrian territory. He added that this would contribute to the launching of broad reforms that would guarantee pluralism, democracy, reconciliation and the return of refugees to their country. "We hope that the cooperation between Russia and the United States will help stop the hostilities in Syria and resume the talks in Geneva to reach a comprehensive political solution," said King Abdullah II, in an interview with the Jordanian Al-Dustour newspaper. He stressed that sectarian conflict, in the absence of this solution, will be fueled at the regional level and encourage extremism, with criminal gangs threatening global security and stability.²⁴

King Abdullah II expressed his country's readiness to facilitate the crossing of Syrians stranded on the border to any country that accepts to host them, stressing that Jordan will not allow the formation of sites for organized ISIS terrorists near its borders. "We are committed to cooperating with the international community to find appropriate solutions

²³ Al-Masri, Abdulrahman. (2015, April 19). 'ISIS And Nusra Are One' In Yarmouk Camp. Published In: Article, Middle East, Opinion, Syria. Retrieved from <https://www.middleeastmonitor.com/20150419-isis-and-nusra-are-one-in-yarmouk-camp/>

²⁴ Petra News Agency. (2016). *Almulk Fi Muqabalat Shamilat Mae Sahifat Aldustur* [Jordan's King In A Comprehensive Interview With The Al-Dustour Newspaper]. Retrieved from http://www.petra.gov.jo/public_news/nws_newsdetails.aspx?menu_id=&site_id=2&lang=1&newsid=264855&catid=14

that will not be at our expense,”²⁵ the King said, reinforcing the fact that Jordan's security remains the foremost priority of the state.

6.4.2 An Evaluation of the Jordanian Position on the Syrian Crisis:

The Syrian crisis started off as just peaceful demonstrations in Deraa in March 2011, which then moved on to first neighboring and then to remote areas, before transforming into armed protests²⁶. The crisis soon converted into another historical milestone that would reshape the Jordanian-Syrian relations. During the first months of the crisis, the Jordanian leadership kept Jordan isolated from the blazing environment in Arab countries, especially Syria. This move stemmed from the fear of Arab Spring events entering Jordan’s domestic environment. The government believed that the demonstrations in Jordan could intensively move towards bringing down the parliamentary monarchy system. The authorities commented at various times on the events in Syria but did not offer moral or material aid either to the Syrian government or to the opposition. The first armed groups attacked the Syrian government in May 2011, to which the Syrian army replied with brutal responses,²⁷ which acted as the spark that lit the flame in Syria.²⁸ Organized rebel groups first emerged in October 2011 as the Free Syrian Army.²⁹ As the events turned more aggressive in Syria and the Syrian Army took over Hama, the position of Saudi Arabia shifted towards the Syrian rebellions, and US President Barack Obama called for Bashar al-Assad to step down

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Tokmajyan, A. (2014). *Conflict Transformation In Syria*. (Master Thesis). University Of Tampere. Finland. pp: 21-22.

²⁷ See: Verma, S. (2011). *How A 13-Year-Old Became A Symbol Of Syrian Revolution*. The Globe And Mail. Retrieved from <https://www.theglobeandmail.com/news/world/how-a-13-year-old-became-a-symbol-of-syrian-revolution/article4260803/> p: 2.

²⁸ Sterling, J. (2012). *Daraa: The Spark That Lit The Syrian Flame*. CNN.

²⁹ Tokmajyan, A. (2014). *Conflict Transformation In Syria*. (Master Thesis). University Of Tampere. Finland. pp: 23.-25.

on 15 August 2011. The Jordanian authorities expressed concern over the escalating violence and bloodshed, and the heavy and unjustified use of force by the Syrian Army. Yet, the government kept repeating that Jordan had no interest in the conflict and would not interfere in domestic affairs of Syria, and that Jordan regards the unity of Syria, its security and stability, as a red line which is not to be crossed.³⁰

Jordan supported all the Arab League's resolutions regarding the Syrian crisis, except the imposition of economic sanctions, which Jordan declared it would not adhere to. Unlike the Gulf States and some Arab countries, Jordan did not expel the ambassador of Syria, instead maintained diplomatic relations between the two sides. In November 2011, King Abdullah II stated in an interview with the BBC that, "If I were in his shoes, I would have stepped down after being certain that the person who will replace me will be capable of changing the reality that we are witnessing." The Jordanian news agency Petra, however, made sure to affirm that these statements were not a call for Assad to step down.³¹

With the escalation of armed struggle in the Syrian crisis in mid-2012, Jordan focused on issuing warnings regarding the dangers of war between the governmental forces and the opposition forces, and on the rise of Islamist fighters in the opposition armed battalions, in addition to the fear of division of Syria.³² At the same time, Jordan allowed the border crossing of Syrian refugees into the Al-Zaatari camp in northern Jordan. It also showed

³⁰ Editorial Team. (2015, August. 12) Khata Ahmar Jaded [A New Red Line]. Retrieved from <https://www.khaberni.com/news/153625-153625-خط-أحمر-جديد>

³¹ Editorial Team. (2011, November 14). Almalik Yadeu Al'asad Liltanhi [The King Calls On Assad To Step Down]. Retrieved from <http://ar.ammannet.net/news/133089>.

³² Syrian News. (2013). *Almalik Al'urduniyu Yahdhar Min "Inihiar Suria 'Aw Taqsimiha"* [The Jordanian King Warns Against The Collapse Or Division Of Syria]. Retrieved from http://syria-news.com/readnews.php?sy_seq=159584

flexibility in allowing weapons to be smuggled into Syria, especially the Croatian arms deal financed by Saudi Arabia.³³ Thus, the Jordanian government appeared to be following a selective policy of arming and supporting some armed groups with which it had established a common understanding. The integration of cross-border issues established direct security coordination with the United States, sending 200 US soldiers in April 2013, in order to be able to form a possible joint task force for military operations.³⁴ These developments led to Syrian President Bashar al-Assad warning Jordan in an interview with Syrian news channel Al-Akhbar on April 17, 2013. Following this, the Jordanian Prime Minister Abdullah Nisour, in an interview with CNN on 12 May 2013, announced “Jordan's desire to deploy Patriot missiles on the border with Syria.”³⁵ On 11 May 2013, Jordan held a conference of “Syrian Friends” and was keen to name the “Amman Ministerial Meeting on Syria” in preparation for the Geneva II Conference.

The Jordanian position calling for a political solution did not prevent the Military Operations Center (MOC)³⁶ from supporting the Syrian opposition factions in the

³³ The Guardian. (2013, April 14). *Syria: Jordan To Spearhead Saudi Arabian Arms Drive*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2013/apr/14/syria-jordan-spearhead-saudi-arms-drive>

³⁴ Sawalqa, Hisham. (2013, April 17). *Almumini Yuakid L'Eimwn" Aistiqbal Al'urduni 200 Jundiun 'Amrikiin* [Al-Moumny Confirms To Ammoun The Arrival Of 200 US Soldiers]. Retrieved from <http://www.ammonnews.net/article/150330>

³⁵ *Al-Zamil, Ayman. (2013, May 22). Alnswr: Nurid Nashr Batrywt Ealaa Alhudud Mae Suria Walan Nusharik Fi Eamal Eskry Didaha* [Al-Nusur: We Will Deploy Patriot Missiles Along Syrian Borders And We Will Not Participate In Military Operations Against It]. Retrieved from <http://elaph.com/web/news/2013/5/813556.html?entry=syria>

³⁶ The Military Operations Center (MOC Room) Is An External Military Room, Command, Coordination And Command Center Run By The United States Of America, France, Britain, Jordan And Some Gulf States. It Was Formed In 2013 And Developed In 2014. It Includes Several Factions Of The Free Army In Daraa, Quneitra, The Second MOC Room Section Is In Turkey. Almasry, Fahad. (2016. August 12). " *Almawk W Almawm " Khafaya 'Tidarat Alsirae Aleaskarii*

south, and the kingdom's involvement in training programs for the Syrian opposition, which remained secret until officially announced on 23 March 2015, as a program to train the Syrian tribes to fight the organization of the ISIS. Previously in 2013, Jordan participated in supporting opposition parties with weapons that had been paid for by Saudi Arabia.³⁷ Even before the opening of the MOC room, Jordan was a target of repeated Syrian accusations of training and arming the opposition and facilitating the transit of terrorists across its borders to join terrorist groups active in Syria. These accusations were reinforced by the accession of some 3,000 Jordanians to the Al-Nusra Front, which was denied by Jordan.³⁸

On 1 April 2014, Jordan closed the Jabir border crossing with Syria because of the clashes between the governmental forces and the armed opposition on the Syrian side of the crossing (Naseeb). The clashes ended with control of the opposition at the crossing, which remained closed after 2016 even amid endeavors to open it. The Jordanian-Syrian diplomatic relationship remained tense, until it reached a state of declared hostility when on 26 May 2014, Jordan declared the Syrian ambassador in Amman, Bahjat Suleiman, a “Persona non grata,” as the Jordanian leadership considered his actions a continuing abuse of the kingdom and its leaders, political figures, and national institutions. In return, the

Bisuria ["MOM And MOC" Hidden Management Of The Military Conflict In Syria]. Retrieved from <http://alghorab.com/?p=2109>

³⁷ White, J., Tabler, A. J., & Zelin, A. Y. (2013). *Syria's Military Opposition*. Washington Institute For Near East Policy For Near East Policy, 1-35. p: 23.

³⁸ Al-Fudelat, Mohammed. (2017, September 8). *Al'urdunu Walthawrat Alsuwriat... Khatun Lm Yanqatie Ywmaan Mae Alnizam* [Jordan And The Syrian Revolution: A Line That Never Ceased With The Regime]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/politics/2017/9/8/1-الأردن-والثورة-السورية-خط-لم-ينقطع-يوما-مع-النظام>

charge d'affaires of the Jordanian Embassy in Damascus was evicted, but the official diplomatic relations became worse.³⁹

On 10 September 2014, Jordan officially announced that it had joined other countries, USA and its allies, and Russia and its allies,⁴⁰ in the international coalition for the war on ISIS. The Jordanian Air Force participated in the bombing of Raqqa. On 24 December, a Jordanian fighter plane landed in al-Raqqa and captured its commander, Lieutenant Muath al- Kasaesbeh.⁴¹ A video of the pilot's execution was released in February 2015, which shocked not only the Jordanians but the world,⁴² as even Al-Qaeda members characterized their organization as moderate compared to ISIS.⁴³ After that, Jordan carried out repeated bombings on the sites of the organization inside Syria, amid demands of the Syrian regime to coordinate with Jordan in the war on terrorism.

However, Jordan continued to coordinate with Russia through the MOC room set up in Amman, to coordinate between the two sides, in order to preserve the stability of the Syrian south bordering on the Jordanian territory.⁴⁴ Then Jordan shift its position on the Syrian conflict. Jordan explained its contact with the Russians, who ensured Jordan's attendance

³⁹ Ibid.

⁴⁰ Arango, T. (2014). *Longtime Rivals Look To Team Up To Confront ISIS*. New York Times, 9. p: 1-4.

⁴¹ Dawber, Alistair. (2015, February 3). *ISIS Video Shows Death Of Jordanian Hostage Muath Al-Kasaesbeh*. Retrieved from <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/middle-east/isis-video-purports-to-show-jordanian-pilot-hostage-muath-al-kasasbeh-being-burned-to-death-10021462.html>

⁴² Salama, Vivian. (2015, February 6). *In Unison, Muslim Clerics Lash Out Against Islamic State*. Associated Press. Retrieved from http://old.seattletimes.com/html/nationworld/2025634464_apxislamicstate.html

⁴³ Joscelyn, T. (2015). Al-Qaeda Appears 'Moderate' compared To Islamic State, Veteran Jihadist Says. *FDD's Long War Journal*. Retrieved from <https://www.longwarjournal.org/archives/2015/10/al-qaeda-appears-moderate-compared-to-islamic-state-veteran-jihadist-says.php>. p: 1.

⁴⁴ Al-Fudelat, Mohammed. (2015, October 23). *Tansiq Eskry Bayn Rusia Wal'urduni Bishan Aljanub Alsuwrii* [Military Coordination Between Russia And Jordan On The Syrian South]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/politics/2015/10/23/بعد-سورية-والعراق-روسيا-تحاول-التحالف-مع-الأردن>

as an observer, in the discussions in Astana, along with all other parties to the Syrian crisis. The flow of Syrian refugees into Jordan continued until 21 June 2016, when Jordan declared its borders a closed military zone in the wake of a terrorist attack on a military post opposite the Rukban camp, in which six Jordanian soldiers and security personnel were killed.

The Jordanian approach to the Russians, the most important player in the Syrian conflict, made Jordanian politics more realistic in dealing with the crisis. The talk became more about the efforts to restore stability and ensure the return of Syrian refugees living in Jordan. On 30 December 2016, Jordanian Chairman of the Joint Chiefs-of-Staff, Major General Mahmoud Freihhat, in his interview with the BBC, revealed that contacts with the Syrian regime had not been interrupted throughout the conflict. The most critical criticism against Jordan was the role that Jordanian intelligence had allegedly played in freezing the southern front, and the pressure to keep it silent since the early effective Russian military intervention in the Syrian war at the end of 2015,⁴⁵ pushed by its economic and political interests in the region, especially with Syria.⁴⁶

The Jordanian policy was also influenced by the US policy under former President Barack Obama. It contributed to making Jordan cautious about taking a decisive stance on the crisis. The Syrian crisis put Jordan in a more complicated situation between its relationship with Washington and its allies, especially Saudi Arabia, and maintaining its interests and security in coordination with Moscow, which supported the Syrian army near its borders.

⁴⁵ Ibid.

⁴⁶ Gorenburg, D. (2012). *Why Russia Supports Repressive Regimes In Syria And The Middle East*. PONARS Eurasia Policy Memo, 198. Retrieved From [Http://Www.Ponarseurasia.Org/Sites/Default/Files/Policy-Memos-Pdf/Peprm198.Pdf](http://www.ponarseurasia.org/sites/default/files/policy-memos-pdf/pepm198.pdf) pp: 1-3.

At the same time, Jordan actively participated in a Washington-led coalition that struck against the organization of a terrorist Islamic State that controlled large areas of Iraq and Syria, before another contribution in the Islamic alliance was announced by Saudi Arabia at the end of 2015. Jordan has succeeded in following two lines of good relations with Washington and its allies who were reviving the Syrian government, and maintaining its relationship with Russia which supported the regime of Bashar al-Assad and formed a diplomatic shield for his rule.⁴⁷ On the one hand, Jordan could not oppose Saudi Arabia and its ally Washington, while on the other, it could not oppose Russia's will. Jordan believed that the Russian role and pressure south of Syria, and the arrival of the Syrian army to the border and regaining control, was a positive thing for Jordan and in its interest. Although the regional players' adversaries were shrinking and there were certain limits, Saudi Arabia had no free hand and was not able to move away from Washington. This allowed Jordan to maneuver and become capable of dealing with Russian and US lines.⁴⁸ Saudi Arabia and Turkey, being supporters of the Syrian opposition, revealed their willingness to send ground troops to Syria to fight the jihadists. Jordan, as one of Washington's main allies in the region, was part of a US-led international coalition that had been waging air strikes against the ISIS since 2014. During this time, the annual US aid to Jordan was over one billion dollars. In December, Riyadh, one of Jordan's biggest donors,

⁴⁷ Allison, R. (2013). Russia And Syria: Explaining Alignment With A Regime In Crisis. *International Affairs*. 89.4 (2013) 795–823. pp: 298-299.

⁴⁸ AFP. (2016, February 26). *Al'azmat Alsuwriat Tadfae Al'urdun 'Iilaa Wade Yazdad Taeqidaan Bayn Ealaqatih Biwashintun Wahulafayiha Wakhususaan Alsewdyt Walhifaz Ealaa Masalih Waminah Bialtansiq Mae Musku* [The Syrian Crisis Is Pushing Jordan Into An Increasingly Complex Situation Between Its Relationship With Washington And Its Allies, Especially Saudi Arabia, And Maintaining Its Interests And Security In Coordination With Moscow]. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/الازمة-السورية-تدفع-الأردن-إلى-وضع-يزد>

announced the formation of an Islamic military alliance of 34 mainly Sunni Arab countries, including Jordan, to fight terrorism.⁴⁹

In the security field, Jordan believed that the Syrian army's control of the border was in Jordan's interest, and the Jordanian leadership feared two things. The first was ISIS and Al-Nusra Front approaching its borders, which likely would not happen given the progress of Syrian forces strongly backed by the Russian cover in that area. The second was to find Hezbollah and Iran's Revolutionary Guard on its border, which was also a major challenge, but the close relationship with Russia allowed for the resolution of Jordan's concerns.⁵⁰

6.5 Determinants of the Jordanian Position on the Syrian Crisis:

In its foreign policy towards the Syrian crisis, Jordan has generally been influenced by its regional and international interaction, and the nature of its relationship with the US in particular, at the same time heeding its domestic environment and considerations in a way that ensure fulfillment of its vital interests, along with internal stability.

6.5.1 Regional and International Influences on Jordan's Position:

The regional and international environments, the relations between Jordan and the United States, in addition to both Saudi Arabia and Turkey which are working to find and space in a fast changing area,⁵¹ are the most important factors affecting decisions regarding Jordan's foreign policy. Actually, relations with the US are the most influential factor

⁴⁹ Ibid.

⁵⁰ Ibid.

⁵¹ Ennis, C. A., & Momani, B. (2013). Shaping The Middle East In The Midst Of The Arab Uprisings: Turkish And Saudi Foreign Policy Strategies. *Third World Quarterly*. 34(6), 1127-1144. p: 1141.

between the different external variables in the international environment, and the same is also reflected in the political decision-making in Jordan.⁵²

Washington made it possible for Jordanian diplomacy to maneuver toward alternatives to dealing with the Syrian regime, the American administration especially, kept all options open to dealing with the crisis, focusing on political settlement as one of the most fundamental solutions to deal with the Syrian predicament. It is clear that there is harmony in the Jordanian and American positions regarding non-military intervention, and shared worry of extending the influence of radical Islamic groups such as Al-Nusra Front and al-Qaeda-affiliated fighters and their impact on the stability in Syria and beyond Jordan's borders. These concerns are based on the fact that in case of collapse of the local authority in Syria, it will lead to civil war in multi-ethnic and multi-sectarian regions in Syria, especially in light of the rise of Islamists to power there, which would cause harm to the Jordanian and American interests.⁵³

There is a reason to the Jordanian position within the pro-American framework in the axis of moderation vis-a-vis the Syrian crisis. The Gulf countries, especially Saudi Arabia, were pressing Jordan to intervene in the crisis in terms of facilitating the entry of arms into Syria by pressuring Jordan's treasury and Jordanian labor forces in the Arab Gulf area.⁵⁴ At the same time, Jordan worked on new consensus and changes in terms of the Islamic

⁵² Abd Al-Hayy, Waleed. (2010). *Decision-Making In Arab Regimes*. Center For Arab Unity Studies. Doha/Beirut. 1st Edition. p: 63.

⁵³ Satik, N., & Mahmud, K. (2013). *The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis Of Neighboring Countries' Stances*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Studies. p: 23.

⁵⁴ Agencies. (2013). *Albarlaman Al'urduniyu Yadaeu Haddaan Lilkhilaf Mae Dual Alkhalij* [The Jordanian Parliament Puts An End To The Discord With The Gulf States]. Retrieved from <http://www.althawranews.net/portal/news-40634.htm>

ascendancy in the region and took practical steps to converge with countries that were not in line with its policies regarding the Muslim Brotherhood. It can be said that Jordan worked to balance regional and international interaction in such a way that it distanced itself from direct intervention in the Syrian crisis that would benefit any side. Therefore, the Jordanian position opposing the Syrian regime came under the cover of the Arab League resolutions.

On the other hand, the Jordanian-Russian relations witnessed remarkable development. Government spokesman Mohammad Momani described the military coordination with Russia, which supported the Syrian regime in the face of civil and armed opposition that came in the context of Arab Spring,⁵⁵ as “a guarantee of the kingdom's borders with its northern neighbor Syria” and that it would “prevent operational errors affecting Jordan during the implementation of Russia's air strikes in the south of Syria.”⁵⁶

However, observers underestimated the dimensions of the military deal, noting that “coordination and military cooperation between the two countries comes in the natural context between countries with common interests, even if it does not amount to a comprehensive or strategic agreement, because Jordan is a member of the International Alliance for Combating Terrorism which contradicted to Russian policy at that current stage.” Other opinions disagreed with that view and believed that “coordination and

⁵⁵ Dannreuther, R. (2015). Russia And The Arab Spring: Supporting The Counter-Revolution. *Journal Of European Integration*. 37(1), 77-94. p: 2.

⁵⁶ EREM NEWS. (2016, March 28). Alealaqat Alruwsiat Al'urdunia. Safqat Siasiat Bimadhaq Eskryin [Russian - Jordanian Relations: A Political Deal With A Military Taste]. Retrieved from <https://www.ere-news.com/news/arab-world/460461>.

cooperation between the two countries, trade in the taste of the alliance, that is, the phenomenon of trade, but within the alliance to achieve the common interests of the two sides,” while not see a contradiction with the political International alliance, because each country was looking to achieve its interests and objectives. A third voice believed that “the military coordination between the Russian and Jordan comes in the context of the latter's desire to open contacts with Russia to restore what was broken with the Syrian government in order to coordinate on some regional matters, which is understood that within the procedures of Jordan to maintain its security.”⁵⁷

After the meeting of the Russian Foreign Minister Sergey Lavrov with the Jordanian Deputy Prime Minister and Foreign Minister Nasser Judeh, in Vienna in October 2013, he declared that there was a Russian-Jordanian agreement on military coordination on Syria, while the Jordanian minister commented, “There are deep channels of coordination between Jordan and Russia on Syria.”⁵⁸

6.5.2 The Public Opinion and Internal Stability:

There were reasons for Jordanian reservation towards the Syrian crisis during the first few months, despite the peaceful nature of the demonstrations. Jordan considered factors like the Syrian government having a way to guarantee the security of the regime, and the absence of change in the Arab world in general, the preservation of Jordan from the Arab revolution, and Jordan's economic relations with Syria.

⁵⁷ Ibid: p: 2.

⁵⁸ Leep, Mathew. (2013, October 23). *Kerry, In Vienna, Seeks Diplomatic Solution To Syrian War*. Retrieved from <https://en.annahar.com/article/278046-kerry-in-vienna-seeks-diplomatic-solution-to-syrian-war>

The economic variable in Jordan's official political decision-making process has obvious importance in Jordan's interactions with the Syrian crisis. This variable is a central factor for decision-makers, in order to select from the available alternatives for a specific decision. Jordan's economic potential which does not allow it wide and unrestricted margin in its trade, makes it unable to ignore the wide network of commercial and economic interests associated with Syria. The northern borders of Jordan form a vital region, especially since it is the least expensive way for goods coming into the Jordanian market.⁵⁹ The official inflation rate in Jordan increased from 6.7% in February 2012 to 7.8% in February 2013, due to increasing number of Syrian refugees.⁶⁰ Therefore, Jordan focused on international conferences to resolve the refugees' issue, and to transfer it to the Security Council on account of its impact on economic and security in Jordan.

The issue of Syrian refugees and the rise of jihadist movements within the Syrian opposition forces, imposed on Jordan the need to control security on its northern border in order to guarantee national security. Jordan dealt with the issue of Syrian refugees with warnings and facts not apparent in its dealings with the Iraqi situation. Jordan showed concern about the Syrian opposition's control of areas adjacent to its northern border, and continued to shape its position based on the development of events in Syria, in a way that

⁵⁹ Alkhetan, Fahad. (2012). *Hal Yaqtae Al'urdun Ealaqatih Aldiblumasiat Mae Suri?* [Does Jordan Cut Its Diplomatic Relations With Syria?] Alghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://www.alghad.com/prints/529766-هل-يقطع-الأردن-علاقاته-الدبلوماسية-مع-سورية؟>

⁶⁰ Gerasa News. (2013, March 15). *Alaiqtisad Al'urduniyi Yatadahwar Bsbb Al'azmat Alsuwria* [The Jordanian Economy Is Deteriorating Due To The Syrian Crisis]. Retrieved from <http://www.gerasanews.com/index.php?page=article&id=101997>

reflected results on Jordan's economy and national security through the ability to control cross-border movements.

Jordan is able to walk a fine safety line in an environment full of mines. What makes Jordan balanced against the complex Syrian issue is that there is agreement among the majority of Jordanian public opinion regarding their vision of the Syrian crisis, and also against foreign intervention for change there. The results of the Arab Opinion Index for 2012 conducted by the Arab Center for Research and Policy Studies⁶¹ during the period from 5 to 11 July 2012, showed that the vast majority of Jordanians were biased that the solution of the Syrian crisis lied in a fundamental political change to the existing regime and responding to the demands of the Syrian people. The results reflected that almost unanimous support for the Syrian revolution (82%), while only about 3% of the Jordanian public expressed support for the Syrian state and its tools and methods in dealing with the revolution and the forces opposed to the regime there, a percentage so small that it is not statistically significant. The poll also found that four-fifth of Jordanian society felt that it would be better for Syria if President Bashar al-Assad stepped down from power, while 11% did not agree with this view. The majority of Jordanians (57%) described the Syrian crisis as a revolution against the ruling regime, while 35% of the Jordanian public believed it to be a conspiracy against Syria.

⁶¹ The Arab Opinion Index. (2012) *Arab Public Opinion Measurement Program*. Arab Center For Research And Policy Studies. December 2012. p: 302.

The attitudes of Jordanian public towards the Syrian revolution were divided and continued to change, but were not firm enough to affect the track of matters. However, the changing figures did reflect the change in attitudes. According to the Arab Opinion Index 2014, 64% strongly supported the phrase “the best for Syria today is to step down from power,” while 8% opposed the statement.⁶² According to the Arab Opinion Index 2015 statistics, respondents opinion was divided on the optimal solution of the Syrian crisis, with 79% supporting regime change, 6% condoning peaceful solution of the crisis with participation of all parties, 6% calling for the elimination of revolution and opposition, while 3% wanting elimination of ISIS first and then the approval of the political parties to resolve the crisis.⁶³ 19.4% of Jordanians agreed on intensified military effort in the war against the organization of the Islamic state, and 20.7% called for the need to stop foreign intervention in the region, while 9.4% believed in finding a solution to the Syrian crisis which suited the aspirations of the Syrian people.

Majority of the Jordanians expressed their support for the opposition in the Syrian revolution, agreed with regime change in Damascus and rejected Bashar al-Assad, but were against foreign intervention for this change.⁶⁴ The Islamic political forces, in particular, supported the Syrian revolution conducting boycotts and demonstrations against the Syrian

⁶² The Arab Opinion Index. (2014) *Arab Public Opinion Measurement Program*. Arab Center For Research And Policy Studies. September 2014. p: 282.

⁶³ The Arab Opinion Index. (2015) *Arab Public Opinion Measurement Program*. Arab Center For Research And Policy Studies. December 2015. p: 379

⁶⁴ Almasry, Mohammed. (2012). *Aitijahat Alraay Aleam Fi Almashriq Alerby Nahw Al'azmat Alsuwria* [Public Opinion Trends In The Arab Levant Towards The Syrian Crisis]. *Siyasat Arabiya Journal*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Study. Vol. 1. March 2013. pp: 132-136.

regime. They increased pressure to take more firm and clear positions on the Syrian regime. On the other hand were national and leftist political elite, who were concerned about the development of the situation in Syria. The Jordanian government warned against taking any stand on the Syrian issue in response to Western and Gulf pressure. Therefore, it was clear that the official and popular consensus in Jordan was exclusion of Jordan from any military arrangements that may involve targeting Syria, or any military presence on the Jordanian territory.

Jordan's decisions were based on political, security, and economic calculations, in the shadow of uncertain scenarios and stakes in dealing with the Syrian scene. Jordan wanted to play in accordance with a balanced policy determined by facts on the ground. The state tried to balance its interests and alliances at the lowest cost. However, the official Jordanian position towards Syria till 2016 was that there is no willingness to intervene militarily, no facilities are allowed for any foreign forces that can plan for intervention, and a solution that ensures that Islamist militants do not control the government after Assad to be a stronghold of extremist groups.⁶⁵ This was the essence of Jordan's political orientation, and is likely to remain the same as long as the United States changes its policies towards Syria.

6.5.3 Jordanian Policy towards Syrian Asylum in Jordan:

Since 2011, Jordan has been burdened with receiving a flood of Syrian refugees, and its policy has become more restrictive over time due to circumstances. Jordan's responses were shaped by growing security and demographic concerns, in addition to structural

⁶⁵ Satik, N., & Mahmud, K. (2013). *The Syrian Crisis: An Analysis Of Neighboring Countries' Stances*. Arab Center For Research & Policy Studies. p: 27.

challenges, and reflected a clear strategy early on. When the Syrians started to flee to Jordan at the beginning of the Syrian crisis, the Jordanian authorities dealt with it from a humanitarian perspective. The Syrian refugees who arrived in Jordan a few days after the crisis, the Jordanian government refused to call them refugees and considered them guests of their relatives in northern Jordan, whose families were linked and had relations with the Syrian south, but the policy of denial collapsed a few months after asylum became human waves. As a result of clear and undeniable negative impacts, Jordan's policies have had a profound impact on refugees' freedom of movement, residence, employment, housing, education and healthcare. In 2016, following an attack by ISIS, Jordan closed all remaining open border crossings with Syria and forcibly deported some of the refugees.⁶⁶

The statistics of the Jordanian government and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) showed that the number of registered refugees in Jordan reached 655,344 by December 2016, in addition to other Syrian refugees who were not registered. Some refugees may not have planned a long-term stay in Jordan or may not have known how to register, or may have claimed difficulty in accessing registration centers or may have feared expulsion and persecution by the Syrian regime. The number of refugees was relatively gender-balanced, and about half of them were under the age of 18, of which 30% were women.⁶⁷

⁶⁶ Editorial Team. (2018, May 5). *Allajiuwn Alsuwriiwn Fi Alardn: Alhuquq Walqalaq Al'ammii Walidiymughrafi* [Syrian Refugees In Jordan: Rights And Security And Demographic Concerns]. Retrieved from <http://www.alhadassonline.com/da.aspx?aid=81957>

⁶⁷ Al-Rishiq, Tagreed. (2015, October 11). *Fi Aleam Alkhamis Lil'azma.. Al'urdunu Yarzah Taht 'Aeba' Alluju' Alsuwrii* [In The Fifth Year Of The Crisis, Jordan Is Under The Burden Of Syrian Asylum]. Alghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <https://alghad.com/articles/897317-في-العام-الخامس-للأزمة-الأردن-يرزح-تحت-أعباء-اللجوء-السوري>

Definitely, the Syrian refugees brought enormous economic and social challenges to the Jordanian community, particularly in terms of shelter, education, healthcare, and employment. Even before the crisis broke out, Jordan was already facing significant development challenges, including water shortages and stagnant economic growth (estimated to be an average of 2.6% annually since 2011). The participants in the Carnegie workshops identified the high cost of living as the most important challenge they faced, and the situation was exacerbated by the lack of employment opportunities.

In accordance with the 1952 Constitution and the Memorandum of Understanding with the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) concluded in 1998, foreigners, including refugees, had to have a work permit to legally obtain a job in Jordan. However, the requirements of obtaining a work permit were to obtain a valid card from the Ministry of the Interior. In 2015, the unemployment rate among Syrian refugees was 61%, about 10% held work permit, while the rest work without official papers.⁶⁸

Many Syrians worked construction or other short-term jobs. In 2015, the monthly income of a Syrian refugee was \$296, lower than the minimum wage of \$310 in Jordan. Given the limited employment opportunities available to refugees, about 20% of financial aid from non-governmental organizations was their main source of income. It is therefore not surprising that some 82% of Syrian refugee families lived below the poverty line.⁶⁹

⁶⁸ Editorial Team. (2018, May 5). *Allajiuwn Alsuwriuwn Fi Alardn: Alhuquq Walqalaq Al'amni Waldiyughrafi* [Syrian Refugees In Jordan: Rights And Security And Demographic Concerns]. Retrieved from <http://www.alhadassonline.com/da.aspx?aid=81957>

⁶⁹ Areef, A. Mohammed. (2018, May 3). *Allajiuwn Alsuwriuwn Fi Al'uridin.. 'Azamat Aleamal Walsukan Waltaelim* [Syrian Refugees In Jordan. Work, Housing And Education Crises]. Retrieved from <http://www.almayadeen.net/articles/blog/876095/اللاجئون-السوريون-في-الأردن---أزمات-العمل-والسكن-والتعليم>

In response to this situation, as part of an understanding between Jordan and the EU, in 2016, the EU increased grants and concessional loans to the Jordanian government and facilitated its exports to the European market. The Jordanian government took steps to increase the employment opportunities for Syrian refugees and facilitate their entry into the market of formal work. These steps included abolition of labor license fees and social security proofs by employers, and even medical examination required by conditions for obtaining work permits.⁷⁰ These steps were taken to reduce the high financial cost for refugees and increase their access to certain sectors of employment; the cost of a work permit was one to two months of average income. This provided refugees with some money, but their participation in the labor force did not rise as expected, nor did they overcome further obstacles to obtaining a work permit such as high social security contributions.

6.5.3.1 Accommodation and Housing Requirements:

Jordan's open border policy between 2011 and 2014 demonstrated its commitment to providing a safe place to Syrians. At that stage, however, security concerns led to a gradual policy of closure of border transit, with restrictions on the movement of Syrian refugees. Jaber crossing was closed in 2015, following the control of militants from the Syrian side. A suicide attack at the army checkpoint in al-Rukban in June 2016, reportedly carried out by the Islamic state organization,⁷¹ led to the closure of the Rukban and Qatbal crossings too. Since then, neither has been opened to refugees, except in rare cases.

⁷⁰ Ibid.

⁷¹ Sky News Arabia. (2016, February 2). *Al'urduna. Tafasil Alhujum Ealaa Mukhayam Alrukban* [Jordan. Details Of The Attack On Al-Rikban Camp]. Retrieved from <https://www.skynewsarabia.com/middle-east/851595-الأردن-تفاصيل-الهجوم-مخيم-الركبان>

Beginning 2012, Syrian refugees who entered Jordan from official crossings were transferred to official refugee camps where they could register with UNHCR and obtain a proof of asylum. However, four groups of people were refused entry periodically, which is denied by the principle of non-refoulement: Palestinian and Iraqi refugees residing in Syria, unmarried men of combat age, and persons without identity papers. These restrictions forced many refugees to infiltrate into the country, often through human trafficking networks, which put them more at risk of exploitation and abuse.

In the meantime, refugees residing in the camps could not leave unless “sponsored” by a sponsor, specifically a Jordanian relative aged 35 and over. However, the sponsorship system was initially flexible; refugees who wanted to leave the camps without a Jordanian relative could obtain a card from the Ministry of the Interior that would bridge them to various public services, including healthcare and education.⁷² This situation continued until 2015, when the Jordanian authorities began applying the sponsorship system rigorously, before abolishing it altogether. Instead, the government initiated a “civil investigation” that required Syrian refugees to register again and apply for a new biometric card from the Ministry of the Interior.

Restrictions on who could afford the new service card led to neglect and ignorance of many. Refugees who did not obtain an asylum seeker's documents or left the camps without a sponsor were prohibited from registering. Moreover, some could not afford to obtain the card due to high cost. In addition, it was not easy for many refugees to obtain the new card as they were asked for undocumented identity documents, a sealed lease, a “residence

⁷² Shaheen, Hamzah. (2014, August 11). *Tisdar Shurut Jadidat Litakfil Allajiiyn Alswryyn* [New Conditions Issued For The Syrian Refugees]. Retrieved from <http://assabeel.net/news/2014/8/11/إصدار-شروط-جديدة-لتنكفيل-اللاجئين-السوريين>

certificate” approved by UNHCR, a health certificate and a copy of the owner's identity documents.⁷³ When entering Jordan, the Jordanian authorities confiscated some identity documents such as passports, marriage documents, and birth documents. Since 2014, some refugees have not been allowed to enter because of lack of documents⁷⁴ and security reasons.⁷⁵

As a result, by August 2016, almost one-third of the Syrian refugees registered with UNHCR and outside the camps lacked the new service card. One direct result was the inability of couples without a marriage document to register their children at birth, leaving behind thousands of infants without nationality and without documentation. This also resulted in the inability of refugees to benefit from public healthcare or enroll themselves or their children in formal education.⁷⁶

Unlike Lebanon, Jordan chose to build refugee camps for Syrians. However, of the total registered refugees in Jordan, only 21% lived in camps, most of them in the Zaatari, Al-Azraq and Al-Zarqa camps. Zaatari camp was home to about 80,000 refugees, and is often described as the fourth largest city in Jordan and one of the largest refugee camps in the world. But about 20% of the Syrians lived in garages and tents; 1% live in informal tent camping communities.⁷⁷

⁷³ Ibid.

⁷⁴ Berti, B. (2015). *The Syrian Refugee Crisis: Regional And Human Security Implications*. Strategic Assessment, INSS. The Institute For National Security Studies. Volume 17 | No. 4 | January 2015. 17(4), 41-53. p: 47.

⁷⁵ SIDA Report. (2016). *Syria Crisis: Humanitarian Crises Analysis 2016 Regional Overview*. The Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency. Stockholm Sweden. pp: (20). p: 15.

⁷⁶ Alnuaimi, K., Kassab, M., Ali, R., Mohammad, K., & Shattnawi, K. (2017). *Pregnancy Outcomes Among Syrian Refugee And Jordanian Women: A Comparative Study*. International Nursing Review, 64(4), p: 6.

⁷⁷ Weston, Phoebe. (2015, August 5). *Inside Zaatari Refugee Camp: The Fourth Largest City In Jordan*. Retrieved from <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/middleeast/jordan/11782770/what-is-life-like-inside-the-largest-syrian-refugee-camp-zaatari-in-jordan.html>

Overcrowding became a major problem in hosting communities. Half of the Syrian refugee families shared at least one housing with another family to be able to pay rent. According to UNHCR survey in 2014, Syrian refugees paid an average of \$206 a month, or two-thirds of their monthly income as rent.⁷⁸ One-third of the households lacked tenancy contracts, and about 25% of the survey respondents faced expulsion. The problem exacerbated the rise in rental rates. In northern Jordan, the rent doubled twice, following the influx of Syrian refugees. As in Lebanon, this worsened relations between Syrians and Jordanians, which were already strained on account of water scarcity and waste management. Starting 2011, water resources declined significantly, with 40% of Jordanian families and 29% of Syrian households reporting water scarcity in 2015.⁷⁹

Syrians had comparatively more access to education and health care, than shelter. Syrian refugee children could attend public schools free of charge, though required to have a proof of asylum application and a Ministry of Interior service card; the quality of education varied. In 2013, the Ministry of Education allowed some schools to stay open for additional hours to receive more Syrian refugee children,⁸⁰ but the quality of education for afternoon shifts was usually low as teachers at these shifts were less trained. Syrian refugee children who lack required documentation to attend public schools, could access education through informal programs often run by non-governmental organizations or religious charities. However, the certificates received by students in these facilities were not recognized or

⁷⁸ *ibid.*

⁷⁹ *Ibid.*

⁸⁰ Areef, A. Mohammed. (2018, May 3). *Allajiuwn Alsuwriuwn Fi Al'urdin.. 'Azamat Aleamal Walsukan Waltaelim* [Syrian Refugees In Jordan.. Work, Housing And Education Crises]. Retrieved from <http://www.almayadeen.net/articles/blog/876095/اللاجئون-السوريون-في-الأردن---أزمات-العمل-والسكن-والتعليم>

approved, which prevented them from being able to register in public schools in the future as well.

About 62% of more than 330,000 Syrian refugee children registered in Jordan, followed public school education. However, as in Lebanon, dropout rates were high; UNICEF estimated that 68% of dropouts were enrolled in schools. Overall, the high rates of absenteeism and dropout were attributed to the high cost of education, bullying, discrimination, school violence, the long distance to school, and the need to do domestic chores. As refugee children progressed, their school attendance declined. This was partly due to the fact that there was no point in seeking education at a time when they were in dire need of supporting their families economically.⁸¹ At higher education level, only 8% of refugees between the ages of 18 and 24 were enrolled in universities. Obstacles to university attendance included difficulties of passing formal secondary examinations, the high cost of university education, proficiency in English, and the acquisition of pre-university or secondary education certificates issued by formal education programs. Without a university degree, Syrian refugees faced additional barriers to employment, in addition to existing job competition, thus becoming increasingly dependent on aid and having less money to spend on healthcare and housing.

Since 2011, the Government of Jordan has made clear efforts to improve healthcare delivery. However, Syrian refugees continue to face significant challenges, notably after the 2014 healthcare policy reform,⁸² whereby a refugee with a Ministry of the Interior card

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Mazhar, M. (2015). *The Impact Of Jordanian Health Care Policy On The Maternal And Reproductive Health Care Seeking Behavior Of Syrian Refugee Women*. SIT Graduate Institute/SIT Study Abroad. pp: 5-7.

had to pay for services which were previously free, and the payment was equal to the amount paid by Jordanians without health insurance. Refugees without such cards had to bear even higher costs, equal to those paid by foreigners (in non-governmental and private enterprises). Moreover, while Ministry of Interior cards enabled refugees to obtain healthcare, this access was restricted to the areas where the cards were issued. This policy, combined with high cost of health services, hampered access to care. In 2016, 37% of households with chronic illnesses did not have access to health services, mainly because of expenditures. Indeed, this also applied to Lebanon.

Although Lebanon and Jordan dealt with the largest influx of Syrian refugees, their legal frameworks showed deep confusion in approaching this issue. At a time when both countries received large numbers of Palestinian and Iraqi refugees at different stages, neither ratified the 1951 UN Convention relating to the status of refugees or its 1967 Protocol.⁸³ The Convention defined the classification of refugees and defined the duties of host countries, to ensure their right to freedom of movement, protection, justice, and employment. The Protocol abolished geographical and temporal restrictions in accordance with the application of the Convention to displaced persons in World War II until 1951. The fundamental cornerstone of the Convention and the Protocol is the principle of non-refoulement - that is, refugees cannot be forced to return to where their lives or liberty may be threatened and their lives may be vulnerable to danger.

⁸³ Areef, A. Mohammed. (2018, May 3). *Allajiuwn Alsuwriuwn Fi Al'uridin.. 'Azamat Aleamal Walsukan Waltaelim* [Syrian Refugees In Jordan .. Work, Housing And Education Crises]. Retrieved from <http://www.almayadeen.net/articles/blog/876095/اللاجئون-السوريون-في-الأردن---أزمات-العمل-والسكن-والتعليم>

Unlike the 1951 Convention and Protocol, the Government of Jordan regarded the fugitives as non-refugees. Accordingly, neither country was bound to recognize their rights guaranteed by the Convention, unless such rights were provided for by other international treaties such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.⁸⁴ On the other hand, the welfare and interests of refugees depended solely on the generosity of host countries and international agencies. This hosting approach was intended, in part, to prevent the integration of refugees and to ensure their eventual return to the countries from which they hailed.

There is no doubt that there has been a significant change in Jordan's attitude toward dealing with the issue of Syrian refugees, in order to encourage the international community to deal more seriously with the humanitarian role played by Jordan in this regard on behalf of the international community. The costs and burdens of the refugees consumed around 25% of the Jordanian budget, in a manner that exceeded the capacity of Jordan, which soon reached the limits of its maximum endurance capacity, in light of difficult financial and economic conditions.⁸⁵ Certain factors contributed to this change in the Jordanian position, such as the possibility/indication of the Syrian crisis being prolonged for several years to come even if a political settlement was achieved, in addition to the absence of concerns regarding solving the crisis among major international actors.

6.5.3.2 The Policy of Refoulement:

Reports of human rights organization recorded that the Jordanian authorities started a new

⁸⁴ Ibid.

⁸⁵ Al-Da'aja W. Hayel. (2016, Febraury 7). *Tatawur Almawqif Al'urduniyu Min Alluju' Alsuwrii* [The Jordanian Position Evolution From Syrian Asylum]. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/766722.html>

policy of refoulement or deportation of Syrian refugees back to Syria in 2014. The reports issued by human rights monitors and aid organizations recorded refoulement of refugees registered with the UNHCR. The deported refugees included women, children, medical workers, and other injured people.⁸⁶ The Jordanian Ministry of Interior responded to these cases by declaring that the Security Committee depended for its decisions on international legislation, which excluded the right of non-response and expulsion of groups that posed a threat to national security. The contrasting policies of the Jordanian government were explained by the complex connection between security needs and encampment.⁸⁷ International legislation allowed the country to not accept fighters even if they threw their weapons as humanitarian refugees, for security and political reasons represented as the rights of the host country to maintain its security and stability.⁸⁸

Jordanian government spokesperson Mohammed al-Momani stated that there were forced deportations of Syrian refugees, which he called “cross-border deportation” in Jordan. In his words, “The deportation is subjected to international considerations and laws. We receive the refugee to protect him from exceptional circumstances. But when he transgresses the law and raises problems, we as a host country are entitled to deport him.”⁸⁹

⁸⁶ Human Right Watch. (2014). *Not Welcome Jordan's Treatment Of Palestinians Escaping Syria*. Human Right Watch. pp: 31-34.

⁸⁷ Turner, L. (2015). Explaining The (Non-) Encampment Of Syrian Refugees: Security, Class And The Labour Market In Lebanon And Jordan. *Mediterranean Politics*, 20(3), 386-404. p: 3.

⁸⁸ Al-Fudelat, Mohammed. (2014, April 26). *Alsuwriiwn Fi Al'urdun..Raeib "Alrmi Ealaa Alhdwd" Yutarid Allajiiyn Wa'atfalahum* [Syrians In Jordan ... Terror From Being "Throwing At The Border" Chasing Refugees And Their Children]. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/investigations/2015/4/26/السوريون-في-الأردن-رعب-الرمي-على-الحدود-يطارد-اللاجئين-وأطفالهم>

⁸⁹ RASD. (2014). Al'urdunu Yuqaru Bitarhil Lajiiyn Suriyyn Khalafuu Alqawanin [Jordan Admits The Deportation Of Syrian Refugees Who Violated The Laws]. Retrieved from <http://www.rasd-sy.net/language/ar/-الأردن-يقرب-بترحيل-لاجئين-السوريين-خالفو-2>

Politically, Jordan realized that the relationship between the United States and Russia was based on disagreements, and not on understanding and consensus that could create a common ground for reaching the desired political solution. This complicated the situation further and made it even worse for the Syrian people, exacerbating their sufferings and tragedies. There was also the retreat of European countries, and their idea of closing borders to refugees on the pretext of fear of terrorism, leaving this task to other countries in the region, in return for granting more aid and assistance.⁹⁰ This was what Jordan had tried to employ in order to obtain additional assistance, but in the framework of a new approach based on achieving sustainable development and offering adequate economic development and economic initiatives, by providing the required financial support, soft grants, attracting investments, access to European markets, opening up to Jordanian products, creating jobs, and developing, expanding and supporting infrastructure instead of just providing emergency or relief aid.

Otherwise, Jordan would look at things differently if they reached a critical stage, and it will not be able to receive more Syrian refugees if the world did not help the country. King Abdullah II, in an interview with BBC in February 2016, emphasized Jordan's firm stance on the entry of certain Syrian refugees at the border,⁹¹ who came from Syrian areas under the control of terrorist organizations, citing a security issue and a red line for Jordan. Jordan could not afford security risks as a result of lack of strict and rigorous security measures.

⁹⁰ Ibid.

⁹¹ BBC Arabic. (2016, February 2). *Eabdallah Althaani: Al'urduniyuwn Wasaluu 'Tilaa "Drajat Alghalyan"* [King Abdullah II: Abdullah II: Jordanians Reached The "Boiling Point"]. Retrieved from http://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast/2016/02/160202_jordanians_boiling

6.5.4 Jordan's Economic Policy in Response to the Syrian Crisis:

The Jordanian government formulated response policies, strategies, and plans to deal with the impacts of refugees.⁹² The main partners of the Jordanian government were the United Nations special agency, including the UNHCR and other international organizations. Jordan proved to be the most sophisticated among all the major neighboring host countries, in reacting to the Syrian refugee crisis. Led by the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, Jordan demonstrated its willingness and readiness to use the Syrian population as a lever to garner international development aid through JRPSC. The plan was described as “the first nationally-led response of its kind, joining refugee and development responses in one complete national plan targeting Syrian refugees, and the affected Jordanian as well.”

The Jordanian government recognized deeply that this mega plan required long-term commitments and investments to overcome isolation in funding and operations, to design and implement responses in a manner that will prove beneficial. Benefits were sought for the affected households and local economies, to strengthen national and local institutions and to promote development and pave the way for future recovery.

Given the continuation of the crisis despite ongoing efforts to reach a political settlement, Jordan will continue to be affected by the consequences of the crisis. The influx of about 1.3 million refugees from Syria, has been putting great pressure on basic services throughout the kingdom, driving social tensions. Although the government and international donors have borne huge costs of this crisis, still the needs have gone far

⁹² UNHCR. (2017). *Jordan Refugee Response Inter-Agency Coordination Briefing Kit*. Data2.Unhcr.Org. p: 1.

beyond the available assistance.⁹³ The competent authorities in Jordan recognized early on that there would be a need to adopt an effective approach that must be complementary to and built up on the extensive humanitarian and development work in the kingdom.

6.5.4.1 The Components of Jordan Response Plans to the Syrian Crisis (JRPSC):

The estimated number of people that fled Syria since 2011 has reached more than 4 million. With the Syrian crisis entering its sixth year, in 2016, Jordan was hosting about 1.3 million Syrians, of which 655,833 were registered as refugees. The government decided to work on meeting their needs without risking the Jordanian people, institutions, and systems' development gains and opportunities, by assisting the vulnerable Jordanians affected by the Syrian crisis and giving priority to the Jordanian people's requirement for development from the budget allocated for that purpose. The plan strived to be aligned with national priorities to ensure continuity, ownership, and sustainability, and was developed in coordination with national development plans.

In 2013, the Jordanian government took an active part in responding to the effects of the Syrian crisis within a flexible framework by formulating the National Resilience Plan (NRP 2014), which was concentrated mainly on host communities. Then, the JRPSC was established in September 2014, in order to coordinate, guide and oversee the preparation, implementation, and monitoring of the Jordan Response Plans, the first ever comprehensive humanitarian and resilience-based response to the Syria crisis in Jordan.⁹⁴

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ JRPSC. (2015). *Jordan Response Plan For The Syria Crisis 2015*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. p: 19.

The JRPSC brought together high-level representatives of the government, the donor community, UN agencies and the INGO community, under one planning and coordination framework. Its mission was to ensure an effective, nationally-owned, and coordinated response to the multi-faceted challenges faced by the country as a result of the Syrian crisis⁹⁵. It was chaired by the Minister of Planning and International Cooperation (MOPIC). To ensure coherence in the work of the JRPSC, 12 Task Forces were established in education, energy, food security, health, justice, livelihood, local governance & municipal services, shelter, social protection, transport, wash, and environment.⁹⁶

6.5.4.2 Purpose of the Jordan Response Plan 2016-2018:

The objective of the Jordan Response Plan 2016-2018, is to provide protection and emergency humanitarian response to Syrian refugees and to strengthen the resilience of the affected Jordanian people, communities, and institutions, while at the same time (i) mitigating the ongoing impact of the crisis; (ii) sustaining Jordan's social and economic stability, and (iii) preserving the critical development gains achieved in the last decades.⁹⁷

The response plans will include both short-term humanitarian and short and medium term resilience interventions needed to mitigate the impact of the Syrian crisis on refugees as well as the Jordanian population, including host communities and institutions, chiefly through the provision of humanitarian aid and strengthening of basic services and

⁹⁵ Ibid.

⁹⁶ JRPSC. (2016). *Comprehensive Vulnerability Assessment (2016/2018)*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. pp: 18-19.

⁹⁷ RPSC. (2016). *Jordan Response Plan 2016-2018 Guiding Framework*. Ministry Of Planning And International Cooperation. Jordan. pp: 2-3.

government financing. This will help ensure that emergency, short, medium and longer-term interventions by government, the UN, NGOs, and private sector are integrated, sequenced and joined up. In particular, the response plan will be framed under the “Jordan 2025” development blueprint, and will integrate information and lessons learned from the NRP, the RRP and the JRP2015 formulation and implementation process, as needed. Crosscutting issues will be duly taken into account during formulation.

Within a timeframe of three years, from January 2016 to December 2018 (JRP Guiding, 2015), the response plan 2016-2018 would:⁹⁸

1. Rapidly upscale critical capacities of the central, regional and local authorities to plan, program, coordinate and implement the development response, in order to manage and mitigate the impact of the crisis in a timely, efficient and effective manner.
2. Foster the resilience of:
 - a) The service delivery system, at national and local levels, and mitigate the negative impacts on health, education, water, and sanitation, in a cost-effective and sustainable manner.
 - b) Municipal services and infrastructure in areas critically affected by demographic stress, including solid waste management, housing, and energy sectors, thereby advancing more cost effective and sustainable solutions.
3. Meet the immediate needs of:
 - a) Syrian refugees on and off camps.
 - b) Vulnerable Jordanians affected by the Syrian crisis.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

4. Rapidly expand employment and livelihood opportunities, and strengthen the coping mechanism of the most vulnerable groups in the Jordanian population, which are most affected by the crisis.
5. Address social imbalances and strengthen social cohesion in Jordanian communities.
6. Support the government budget to cope with the additional financial obligations resulting from the crisis.

6.5.4.3 The Governing Principles of the Response Plans:

Jordan adopted a focused approach in responding to implications of the Syrian crisis through Jordan Response Plan for the Syria Crisis (JRPSC) based on the following set of basic principles:⁹⁹

First: Increasing synergy between investments and humanitarian and development approaches. The humanitarian work and development cooperation share a common goal: reducing vulnerability and ensuring the capability of individuals and communities to adapt to changing circumstances and meet their physical, protection, and sustainable needs. Therefore, in order to build resilience to face the crises from individuals, communities, and institutions, in Jordan, the competent authorities in the government of Jordan aimed to benefit from linkages between humanitarian and development work at the institutional level, financial arrangements, processes and programmatic approaches.

Second: Giving priority to the dignity and self-sufficiency of affected populations. Dignity lies at the core of the capacity to face crises and it must be seen as a practical necessity

⁹⁹ UNDP. (2015). *Resilience Development Forum: Integrating Responses, Expanding Partnerships*. UNDP. Dead Sea. Jordan p: 2.

rather than as a mere concept. This requires the involvement of all affected communities in all elements of program designing and implementation. More importantly, helping to create the conditions in which one can pursue self-sufficiency. Doing so is crucial not only to building a more cost-effective response but also to countering the tendency to rely on aid in case of protracted crisis.

Third: Strengthening rather than replacing the local capacity. Strengthening capacity to face the crisis, to keep up the capacity of accountable local institutions so that they are able to cope with and recover from current and future shocks. These local institutions may be governmental or private, formal or informal, and may be occupied by the affected communities themselves. This approach focuses on supporting and enabling these institutions to be able to perform their services on a continuous, transparent and efficient basis, in line with human rights and with the needs of affected women, men, and children.

Fourth: Building new and inclusive partnerships for capacity-building in response to the implications of the Syrian crisis and promoting innovation and enhancing connectivity, effectiveness, and efficiency: Strengthening resilience before the crisis requires the involvement of a broad range of stakeholders and innovative partnerships. Such partnerships could include citizen groups, political parties, private sector, civil society, governmental institutions, humanitarian and development agencies (including non-governmental organizations), donors, international financial institutions and affected communities themselves. The response plan entails some risks, but they can also pave the way for more closely linked, more efficient and cost-effective responses.¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ Ibid.

Fifth: Protecting social cohesion for joint action to promote capacity to face the crisis, and peaceful cooperation. The ability to respond to the crisis requires a strong social fabric that can adapt to change and grow stronger in difficult circumstances. However, social cohesion is weakened by feelings of discrimination, social exclusion and by tensions that should be addressed. Therefore, the response plan outlines and its mechanism reaffirms, that all internal responses to this crisis must be geared to meeting needs, addressing vulnerabilities and strengthening capacities for better life.¹⁰¹

6.5.4.4 Jordan Response Plan and International Assistance:

Jordan would be unable to implement the response plan depending solely on its budget. The total budget needed for the period 2016-2018 is \$7,990,882,501 in order to meet the needs of the vulnerable affected Jordanian communities and the Syrian refugees.¹⁰² This budget confirms that Jordan is increasingly dependent on public debt and foreign aid to prop up continued spending. The continuously increasing expenses on account of Syrian refugees led to a deficit in the Jordanian budget.

Since the beginning of the crisis in 2011, UN humanitarian appeals were launched to ensure that Syrian refugees receive international assistance and were supported with essential protection services. Jordan cooperated with about 50 NGOs that worked in different humanitarian fields, in which they either provided direct fund or implemented various projects for Syrian refugees and affected Jordanian communities.¹⁰³ As of 2015, Jordan has taken the lead in the set-up of the response plan by integrating humanitarian and

¹⁰¹ Ibid.

¹⁰² MOP, (2015). *National Resilience Plan 2014 - 2016*. Jordanian Government. p: 3

¹⁰³ UNHCR. (2017). *Jordan Refugee Response Inter-Agency Coordination Briefing Kit*. Data2.Unhcr.Org. pp: 2-3.

development responses and resources to address the needs of both Syrian refugees and host communities.

The integration of humanitarian and development aid represents the first time that United Nations development and humanitarian actors have worked so closely towards crisis response.¹⁰⁴ It is a suitable response to the difficulties of the all affected people; it is essential that both refugee and Jordanian communities receive support.

Although the international community has helped Jordan, it has fallen short of the needs and requirements defined in JRP 2016-18 and all its predecessor plans. This is emblematic of the failure of the orthodox model, according to which host countries provide protection space for refugees while the costs are borne by the international community. Yet the international community has no legal obligation to offer financial support.¹⁰⁵

6.5.5 Economic Opportunities with the Help of International Community:

Jordan believes that it can gain an economic opportunity by working with the international community and its institutions. The Jordanian government as well as the international community agreed on a new holistic approach to achieving the most adequate solution for the Syrian refugee crisis. This approach is composed of three interlinked pillars that attempt to support Jordan's growth programme while securing its resilience and economic stability:

1. Converting the Syrian refugee crisis into a practical development opportunity which attracts investments in various sectors and opens up the European Union market with

¹⁰⁴ UN, S. Rights, H., & Commission. (2016). *Year: Humanitarian Implementation Plan (Hip) Syria Regional Crisis*. UN. 1-18.

¹⁰⁵ WANA. (2015). *Forging New Strategies In Protracted Refugee Crises: Syrian Refugees And The Host State Economy Jordan Case Study*. Wanainstitute.Org. ESCWA. pp: 2-4.

simplified rules of origin for exporting, and creating jobs for both the Jordanians and Syrian refugees while supporting and improving the post-conflict Syrian economy.

2. Reconstruction of Jordanian hosting communities by sufficient financing via grants to the JRP 2016-2018.

3. Mobilizing adequate grants and easy financing to support and improve the macroeconomic framework, and targeting Jordan's financing requirements for the next three years as part of Jordan joining a new Extended Fund Facility program with the IMF.¹⁰⁶

Also, Jordan agreed to work with the World Bank Group program, which was based on the \$300 million Program for Results operation approved by the Bank's Board of Directors in September 2016, to support the Jordanian government's efforts to improve the investment climate, attract investors, reform the labor market, and allow Syrian labor to contribute to Jordan's economic growth. The project also supported trade facilitation and investment promotion, particularly in existing special economic zones, and promoted Syrian entrepreneurial activities. Under the program, in support of the implementation of the contract document with Jordan, Syrian workers will receive work permits enabling them to obtain jobs in official sectors. The Jordanian Ministry of Labor launched labor facilitation services to implement the work permit reform process.¹⁰⁷

¹⁰⁶ Compact, J. (2016, February). The Jordan Compact: A New Holistic Approach Between The Hashemite Kingdom Of Jordan And The International Community To Deal With The Syrian Refugee Crisis. In Supporting Syrian And The Region: London Conference (Www. Gov.

Uk/Government/Uploads/System/Uploads/Attachment_Data/File/498021/Supporting_Syria__The_Regions_London_2016_-_Jordan_Statement. Pdf. p: 1.

¹⁰⁷ Saade, Lara. (2016, June 28). *Economic Opportunities For Jordanians And Syrian Refugees- Questions And Answers*. The World Bank. Washington. Retrieved from <http://www.worldbank.org/en/country/jordan/brief/economic-opportunities-for-jordanians-and-syrian-refugees-questions-and-answers>

The Jordanian government had identified 11 zones, most of which are close to major population centers in Jordan. The companies that the government aims to attract to these areas employ both Jordanians and Syrians. The zones were administrated by the Jordan Investment Commission and the World Bank Group, to facilitate and encourage investment in Jordan's economy as a whole, benefiting business activities in all areas and sectors, within and outside these areas.¹⁰⁸

The Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation declared that the amount of additional assistance received by Jordan in 2016 in the form of grants to finance the JRP 2016-2018, amounted to \$1.02 billion, equivalent to only 38.4% of the value of the needs within the JRPSC. The contract with Jordan, is committed to providing additional grants of \$700 million annually over three years to the Jordanian response plan, most of which are allocated to finance priority projects targeting host communities.¹⁰⁹

This assistance comes as a result of the London Conference on Support for Syria and the Region in February 2016, and the commitment of the international community to provide additional support to Jordan within a comprehensive framework to deal with the Syrian crisis, including adequate funding to support the JRP development projects, outside of the regular annual aid provided to Jordan through bilateral and signed agreements to support the general budget.¹¹⁰ Adequate funding from the international community will remain a challenge to the humanitarian response plans of the government. Any cuts definitely will

¹⁰⁸ Ibid.

¹⁰⁹ Media Center. (2016, December 5). Alfakhury: Ithnen Wa Thamanyeh Mlyar Dular Hajm Almusaeadat Alkharijiat Li 2016 [Al-Fakhouri: (2.8) Billion Dollars In The Size Of The Foreign Aid For The Year 2016]. Retrieved from <http://www.ammonnews.net/article/291614>

¹¹⁰ Ibid.

exacerbate vulnerabilities for Syrian refugees in most of the host communities in various vital sectors such as water, housing, healthcare and food security.¹¹¹

6.6 The Jordanian Policy towards the Syrian State and Opposition:

The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan embraced opponents of Syria at the beginning of the Syrian crisis, and gave them freedom of expression and allowed the opposition movements to practice on the Jordanian land. The most prominent of these movements was the Free Syrian Army.¹¹² Jordan's dialogue with the Syrian opposition factions came in accordance with international legitimacy. Jordan's relationship with the Syrian opposition has been subject to profound changes and has remained in place for temporary functional considerations. Mainly, the Syrian oppositional parties are classified into five categories: 1) Armed rebellious groups and revolutionaries; 2) Oppositional groups; 3) Various governmental forces and groups; 4) Foreign Salafists, Jihadist groups, and Al Qaeda-affiliated groups; 5) Pro-government foreign armed rebel groups.¹¹³

Even so, still there is debate among the actors in the Syrian conflict about the nature, goals, and loyalty of some organizations such as the “White Helmets” organization which works as a civil defense organization. The NATO classified it as terrorist-linked imposters¹¹⁴,

¹¹¹ IRIS Analysis Study. (2016 January). *Jordan Two-Year Scenario Analysis: Deteriorating Resilience And Increasing Vulnerabilities*. Humanitarian And Development Programme. Institut De Relations Internationales Et Stratégiques. IRIS. Paris, France. p: 9.

¹¹² Niana, Abdalnaser. (2012). *Almawqif Alearabiu Min Althawrat Alsuwria* [The Arab Position Of The Syrian Revolution]. Umayya Center For Research & Strategic Studies. p: 8.

¹¹³ Rafizadeh, M. (2014). *The Syrian Civil War: Four Concentric Circles Of Tensions*. (Ph.D. Thesis). University Of South Florida. p: 58.

¹¹⁴ Beeley, Vanessa. (2016, September 23). The REAL Syria Civil Defence Exposes NATO's 'White Helmets' As Terrorist-Linked Imposters. Retrieved from <https://www.mondialisation.ca/the-real-syria-civil-defence-exposes-natos-white-helmets-as-terrorist-linked-imposters/5547528>

while the Syrian army attacked them in Aleppo¹¹⁵ and classified as clients for the NATO. The Jordanian perspective to the opposition parties and fractions is similar to the American perspective. Jordan was more open to the Syrian opposition and its support, after the armed conflict broke out in Daraa, and maintained channels of communication with President Bashar al-Assad's regime. However, following Geneva I, Jordan stressed the political solution to the crisis and warned of the dangers of the spread of “radical Islamic groups” in the region. The challenge for Jordan was not to slip into war with either side while maintaining the ability to build on any field or political development in favor of any of the conflicting parties, allowing it to satisfy the allies in Riyadh and Washington, and what the Syrian government or its allies could tolerate.

In September 2012, senior official sources in Jordan told Al-Hayat newspaper that “the Jordanian authorities entered in an undisclosed manner on the line of the arrangement of the internal house of the Syrian opposition. This decision was translated in practice following the secret visit by the dissident Syrian Brigadier General Manaf Tlass to Jordan for two days.” During the visit, Talas met with former Syrian dissident Prime Minister Riyad Hijab, who Jordan had decided to host earlier on the condition that his supposed activities would be frozen on the local scene. There were reports of a meeting between Manaf Tlass and King Abdullah II, accompanied by dissident Prime Minister Riyad Hijab, which was neither confirmed nor denied by the Jordanian government at the time.¹¹⁶

¹¹⁵ Malsin, Jared. (2016, September 25) How The White Helmets Of Syria Are Being Hunted In A Devastated Aleppo. Retrieved from <http://time.com/4507009/aleppo-offensive-syria-white-helmets-attack/> p: 2.

¹¹⁶ Al-Kilani, Mahmoud. (2015, March 30). *Khilal 4 'Aewam Min Althwrt: Ma Hi Ealaqat Al'urdun Bialmuearada* [During 4 Years Of Revolution: What Is Jordan's Relationship With The Syrian Opposition?] Retrieved from <https://www.noonpost.org/content/6060>

Jordan recognizes the National Coalition for Syrian Revolutionary and Opposition Forces as a legitimate representative of the Syrian people. The representative of the coalition Mohammed Al-Marouh told Arabic CNN that “the political body in the coalition decided to appoint him as a ‘political representative’ of the coalition in Jordan, who has nothing to do with the relief office of the coalition located in Amman.”¹¹⁷

A senior official in the Jordanian government told Al-Quds Al-Arabi newspaper that the training of the Free Syrian Army soldiers on Jordanian territory is not new, and does not constitute a program related to further training in the future. Al-Quds Al-Arabi newspaper quoted the official as saying that the exercises were linked to security relations and agreements signed by the Jordanian government several times to protect its borders with Syria following the refugee exodus and the border tension, as well as an emergency Jordanian-Israeli emergency plan,¹¹⁸ in case of chaos and use of chemical weapons.

Jordan had a direct role in arming the Syrian opposition, training hundreds of its members in camps near the capital city Amman, supervised by trainers from the United States. German magazine Der Spiegel reported that US experts were participating in the secret training of Syrian opposition fighters in Jordan. In March 2013, The Times reported that Washington and its allies were training "moderate groups" fighting to overthrow the Syrian regime, meaning the Free Syrian Army, on Jordanian land. The New York Times, also revealed Washington's support for the Syrian opposition, by training fighters from the

¹¹⁷ Arabic CNN. (2014, May 26). *Almuruh Li CNN: Taeyin Mumathilin Limakatib Alaitilaf Bial'urduni Muqadimatan Litaslim Sifarat Suria Lilmuearada* [CNN: Appointment Of Representatives Of The Coalition Offices In Jordan Introduction To Hand Over The Syrian Embassy To The Opposition]. Retrieved from <https://arabic.cnn.com/middleeast/2014/05/26/jordan-syria-diplomacy-update2>

¹¹⁸ Ibid. p: 2.

opposition to rule in the region.¹¹⁹

The army of the “Free Tribes”, which was one of the most important pillars of the Jordanian regime, included about 4000 soldiers deployed between the port of Naseeb and the governorates of Suweida and Syrian Daraa. The job of the Free Tribes Army was securing the region through material and moral support from Jordan. “There are undeclared military plans, we continue our coordination with Jordan”, said Mohammed Adnan, a spokesperson for the Free Tribes Army.¹²⁰

By analyzing Jordan’s attitudes towards the Syrian opposition and the Syrian regime, it can be said that Jordan accompanied the regional and international developments as well as the changes in the conflict in Syria since its outbreak in 2011 until the end of 2016. Jordan played a role in all situations for strategic and geographical dimensions on the one hand, and on the other, for Jordan's relationship with various influential actors in the crisis. The declarations and announcements of the Jordanian officials showed that Jordan maintained a minimum level of relations with the Syrian regime, while also receiving Syrian opposition parties as part of a policy that tried, as far as possible, to achieve a balanced equation that guaranteed the security of the Hashemite Kingdom first.¹²¹

The relations between Jordan and Syria tend to return towards positivity at the end more than six years of stagnation. It is a conditional return imposed by variables in Syria and the

¹¹⁹ Ibid. p: 3.

¹²⁰ Sadiq, Hadeel. (2017, January 26). *Khutat 'Urduniyat Litaqyid Khatar Tanzim Aldawlat Fi Badiat Alshsham* [Jordanian Plans To Limit The Risk Of State Organization In The Desert Of The Levant]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/reportsandinterviews/2017/1/26/خطط-أردنية-لتقييد-خطر-تنظيم-الدولة-في-بادية-الشام>

¹²¹ Asharq Al-Awsat Newspaper. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

regional arena. Also, it comes within the framework of a "new vision" for resolving the crisis in Syria, the future of Assad, and cooperation with the opposition parties.

Jordan was one of the first countries to receive the leaders of the Free Army and the political opposition who broke away from the Syrian regime. They were received in the MOC room formed by the United States, France, Britain, Jordan, and some Gulf States in 2013, and developed further in 2014. It also included several factions of the Free Army in Daraa, Quneitra, Damascus, and Aleppo Area. But with increasing complexity in Syria,¹²² after the emergence of radical Islamic organizations and the entry of Iran with its multinational militias, Jordan reviewed its accounts and began to open back lines with the Syrian government on a security level. The Syrian Embassy remained open, but in return, it stepped up its cooperation with the Syrian opposition within positions imposed by strategic and geographical proximity between Jordan and Syria. Experts believe that the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis is not new, as it is a reproduction of a previous policy pursued by Jordan during the war in Iraq. In that period Jordan had strong ties with former Iraqi president Saddam Hussein.¹²³ At the same time, it also hosted Iraqi opposition and coordinated with countries that wanted to topple the former Iraqi regime. As for the Syrian crisis, Jordan maintained balance in its relations between the opposition and the regime in Syria.

The Jordanian writer Amer al-Sabaila said that "The Jordanian-Syrian messages clearly indicate the beginning of a new stage that creates understandings between the two parties

¹²² Ibid.

¹²³ Ibid.

and can be easily monitored in Jordanian statements. The most important messages were in the statements of the government spokesman Mohammad Momani.”¹²⁴ Al-Momani said that “relations with the Syrian regime are likely to move in a positive direction”. He considered that the truce agreement between the opposition and the Syrian government in the south as a sign of support for Russian action in these agreements. He added that this makes way for “further steps that will establish stability in southern Syria.” He emphasized that the authorities of his country look forward to the next phase to consolidate this agreement.¹²⁵ The government spokesman said that “our relationship with the brothers in Syria is likely to take a positive course,” adding “we recall that when the Arab League decided to close the Syrian embassies, we asked for exception in this matter because of the special relationship between us and Syria”. At the same time, he stressed that the presence of any sectarian militia on the borders of the Hashemite Kingdom is unacceptable, and Amman will take the necessary steps to ensure security and stability of the border.¹²⁶

Jordanian writer Sameh al-Mahariq alluded to Jordan's attempt to normalize relations with Syria. And there is a supportive view within the structure of the Jordanian state, which views Syria as part of a traditional equation that the adversary has certain limits that must not be overcome. He added in a statement to the Arab Newspaper that “in contrast, other

¹²⁴ Al-Sabaila, Amer. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://alarab.co.uk/>-الأردن-يضيبط-علاقاته-مع-سوريا-تطبيع-مع-النظام-وتعاون-مع-المعارضة

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ Ibid.

limits draw the maximum relationship and adhere to the Jordanian side and requires that Amman not become a mere planet in the orbit of Damascus and its own complex calculations"¹²⁷.

Al-Mahariq believed that there were two opinions for Jordan for dealing with Syria: the first opinion saw the need for accelerating normalization with Syria, folding the page of recent years and taking an additional boost in recent developments in Syria and what appeared in the Syrian issue as an early declaration of victory by Damascus. The second opinion was that Jordan take a cautious stance on Syria and slow down.¹²⁸

Jordanian stance became clear when the Chairman of the Joint Chiefs-of-Staff, Major General Mahmoud Freihat, said, "We have not acted against the Damascus regime. We support the border tribes to fight terrorism". Freihat revealed the reasons for the return of the Hashemite Kingdom to assess its position on Syria by saying: "We are concerned and warn of the path prepared by Iran to penetrate Iraq to connect with Lebanon through northern Syria."¹²⁹

The Jordanian political analyst Zaid al-Nuwaisah explains the rapprochement between Jordan and Syria as a result of the Syrian regime's military progress on the opposition and extremist organizations backed by Russia. "Jordan is aware today of the rapid strategic developments that took place after the return of Aleppo to the Syrian sovereignty and the

¹²⁷ Al-Mahariq, Sameh. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹²⁸ Ibid.

¹²⁹ Ibid.

defeats of the successive supporters of Palmyra, Al-Kalmon, and the Aleppo parties,”¹³⁰ he said.

Jordan did not cut off its relations with Syria totally but kept on the verge through ongoing security services ongoing. Notable, the strong security man in Damascus, Ali Mamluk, visited Amman twice.¹³¹ According to Zaid al-Nuwaisah, Jordan, since the beginning of the conflict in Syria, recognized the danger of the expansion of the crisis and its elongation, for fear of the arrival of its effects to the geographically and archaeologically overlapping Jordanian arena. In addition to that, the importance of Syria as an economic crossing land that paves the way for nearly a third of Jordan’s exports, especially agricultural exports to Europe through the crossings of Jaber and Daraa.¹³² At the same time Jordan imports through the port of Tartus on account of shortest distance and thus less cost. Therefore, Jordan was keen to exclude itself from the decisions of the boycott imposed by the Arab League.

Amer al-Sabaila in his reading, focuses on the economic aspect of Jordan maintaining a fine line of contact with Syria, and restoring relations with a new vision different from the one adopted at the beginning of the crisis. “For Jordan, Syria is now an important economic

¹³⁰ Al-Nuwaisah, Zaid. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://alarab.co.uk/> الأردن-يضيظ-علاقته-مع-سور-يا-تطبيع-مع-النظام-وتعاون-مع-المعارضة

¹³¹ Political Editor. (2016, October 17). Arbe Dual Zaraha "Rjal Al'asda" Ealia Mamluk.. Wamisr Muhatatih Alkhamisa [Al-Assad's Man "Ali Mamlouk" Visits Four Countries... Egypt And Hid Fifth Station]. Retrieved from <https://www.enabbaladi.net/archives/109649>

¹³² Economical Editor. (2011, December 11). *Tujjar Yuakidun: Bidayil Alaistirad Waltasdir Eabr Turuq Ghyr Suriat Mukalifa* [Dealers Confirm: Alternatives To Import And Export Via Non-Syrian Routes Expensive]. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/7253/اقتصاد-تجار-يؤكدون-بدائل-الاستيراد-والتصدير-عبر-طرق-غير-سورية-مكلفة>

gateway, particularly in terms of trade, traffic and the reconstruction of Syria. For Syria, this comes at a time when Syria is trying to achieve a political victory outside the geographical borders by opening the border and restoring relations, in addition to security cooperation, which affects both the parties especially after the fall of ISIS¹³³”.

Sameh Al-Mahariq agrees with Amer al-Sabaila. According to him, Jordan considers the opening of the border crossings with Syria and Iraq at the same time as a safety cushion in a negative economic situation, bearing the consequences of Jordanian citizens forming pressure towards acceptance of solutions and positions that can be translated into economic gains in the foreseeable future, even if negative effects are seen later. However, the strong economic dimension does not eliminate the political goals, especially since the openness of Jordan to Syria, according to the Arab diplomatic circles in Amman, comes within the new regional position, which is keen primarily on maintaining the Syrian state and its various institutions.

Al-Mahariq believes that “Jordan's good relations with Damascus could give it at least better negotiating options by appearing in a formula that would ease the pressure on its northern border. The stability of the situation in Syria, as envisaged by Amman at this stage will contribute even indirectly to better management of the negotiations on the Palestinian

¹³³ Al-Sabaila, Amer. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://alarab.co.uk/> -الأردن يضبط علاقاته مع سوريا تطبيع مع النظام وتعاون مع المعارضة

situation of relatively importance for Jordan.”¹³⁴

Jordanian security expert Omar al-Raddad stresses that Jordan's interests in normalization are far from being economic only. He said that “There are interests for Jordan in making Syria independent, because the most dangerous scenario for Jordan is for Syria to become a failure state. This failure will lead to security and military burdens on Jordan. This normalization would contribute to the lifting of the blockade on Jordan, where we must not forget that Jordan also closed its borders with Iraq for the same reasons that led to the closure of its borders with Syria.”¹³⁵

Al-Raddad does not believe that normalization between the two countries will take longer than what many observers expect. The first is a conciliatory approach represented in the statements of the chancellor Buthaina Shaaban on future relations between the two countries. The second is the harsh statements made by former Syrian ambassador to Amman Bahjat Suleiman, but it is clear that the approach of Shaaban is the closest to the future approach of the Syrian government.¹³⁶

The former member of the Jordanian parliament, Mohammad al-Hajjuj shared his thoughts on the geographical dimension between the two countries, with Arab Newspaper, saying that "the border between Jordan and Syria is more than 370 kilometers, so the Jordanian

¹³⁴ Al-Mahariq, Sameh. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹³⁵ Al-Raddad, Omar. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹³⁶ Ibid.

state has maintained the stability of its position on the Syrian file since its inception. Jordan wants Syria to be a unified, stable state free of terrorism and chaos, and it wants to deal with the stable Syrian state and not with a country that is engaged in conflicts and wars because this is harmful to Jordan, which Amman has suffered in recent years"¹³⁷.

Al-Hujjuz emphasized on the constructive role of Jordan in the Syrian affairs. He pointed out that "in the light of the truce in southern Syria, the Amman Center for Monitoring Ceasefire in southern Syria (Daraa and Suweida Countryside and Kenitra) began its work with the participation of representatives of Russia and the United States."¹³⁸

As for Jordan's relations with the Syrian opposition, al-Nuwaisah does not believe that Jordan relies heavily on it. It needs a strong body that guarantees its interests and the Syrian opposition today, in the event of exposure and raising regional and international cover. Jordan believes in this behavior that there is a tendency to the Egyptian approach. While, Al-Mahariq believes that the Syrian opposition missed many great opportunities in the past years, making it the weakest party in the current equation regarding the future of Syria. He said, "But it is customary in Jordan to deal sensitively with the file of political opponents and undesirable personalities. For example, as happened with the daughter of former Iraqi President Saddam Hussein, with a big difference from the situation compared to the situation of the Syrian opposition. Damascus may realize that it cannot push to embarrass Jordan in this stage of the opposition file, but will develop its own list, which is linked to

¹³⁷ Al-Hajjuz, Mohammad. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition]. Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹³⁸ Ibid: p: 8.

red lines relating to the Syrian opposition residing in Jordan.”¹³⁹ He added that “Jordan plays a role in rehabilitating the opposition associated with it on the grounds that it is part of the opposition, which could be re-integrated in the next phase in Damascus, even for the purpose of completing the protocol form for future arrangements in Syria”.

Jordan can reconcile its relations with the Syrian opposition militarily and politically and with the Syrian government. Omar al-Raddad explains that this can be done “by providing protection to the opposition until the final solution is clarified.” Jordan exerted pressure on the opposition to accept future solutions, especially since Jordan has historically distanced itself from the use of opposition.¹⁴⁰

Regarding the Iranian militia on the border,^{141,142} al-Nawaseh said that “the nature of the relations Jordan has built with Moscow regarding the Syrian crisis and the south of Syria, included Jordan's unequivocal guarantee of removing the threat of Iranian forces on its borders of perhaps more than 50 kilometers. Amman is pleased with the results of these understandings. The frequency of news and leaks in Amman about the Jordanian

¹³⁹Al-Mahariq, Sameh. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹⁴⁰ Al-Raddad, Omar. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://s3.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/alarabuk.prod/pdf/2017/09/05-09/p1000.pdf#page=7>

¹⁴¹ I24NEWS (2015, January 26) Fighters From Syria Army, Hezbollah, Iran Capture Town Close To Jordan Border. Retrieved from <https://www.i24news.tv/en/news/international/middle-east/100568-160126-fighters-from-syria-army-hezbollah-iran-capture-key-town-close-to-jordan-border>

¹⁴² See: Al Jazeera English. (2014, May 2) 'The Role Of Hezbollah In Syria's War'. retrieved from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=j5uyjh5b498>

ambassadors to Tehran, Abdullah Aburman, returning to the embassy may coming soon.”¹⁴³

The Jordanian-Syrian relations may tend strongly towards positive developments. “However, the real activation by the Jordanian authorities of the diplomatic and political sides will be gradual until the end of the Gulf-Russian negotiations. The Jordanian government is primarily concerned that there is a guarantee on its border and I think Russian security is the best option”, he said.¹⁴⁴

6.7 The Jordanian Policy against Security Issues and Terrorism:

6.7.1 Security Policy Regarding Jordan’s Concerns on Northern Borders:

In the shadow of the disintegration and fragmentation that hit Arab countries after the Arab Spring revolutions, Jordan maintained the unity of its people and overcame cracks within the various components. It also adopted a more neutral official policy toward Syria, despite the presence of some sources which confirmed that it was training ground for the Syrian opposition. For this reason, since the beginning of the conflict in Syria, the Jordanian position has been vague. For almost two years after the events, Jordan tried to distance itself as much as possible from involvement in the conflict, providing only letters of advice and receiving the influx of refugees on its northern border.¹⁴⁵ Politically, Jordan, along

¹⁴³Al-Nuwaisah, Zaid. (2017, September 5). *Fi Alomq: Al'urdunu Yadbut Ealaqatih Mae Suria: Tatbie Mae Alnizam Wataeawun Mae Almuearada* [In Depth: Jordan Controls Relations With Syria: Normalization With The Regime And Cooperation With The Opposition] Retrieved from <https://alarab.co.uk/> -الأردن-يضيبط-علاقاته-مع-سوريا-بالتطبيع-مع-النظام-وتعاون-مع-المعارضة

¹⁴⁴ Ibid.

¹⁴⁵ Mahmoud, Kh. Waleed. (2013, September 10). 'Ayn Yaqif Al'urdunu Min Mujrayat Al'azmat Alsuwria? [Where Does Jordan Stand In The Course Of The Syrian Crisis?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/knowledgegate/opinions/2013/9/10/أين-يقف-الأردن-من-مجريات-الأزمة-السورية/>

with other neighboring countries such as Iraq and Israel, and the United States and its allies, realized that “the regime in Syria will not come out easily.”¹⁴⁶

According to the UNHCR, the number of Syrian refugees in Jordan reached 620,000 in 2015, with 84% living in cities and villages, especially in the northern border,¹⁴⁷ which exacerbated Jordan's security, political, and economic challenges. By the end of the sixth year of the crisis, Jordan began changing its policy of “open borders” used at the beginning of the conflict, to a policy of “limitation” of its humanitarian response. This change was expressed by the Minister of Information, the spokesperson for the Jordanian government, on 25 July 2016 when he said that “Jordanian government ready to use the Royal Jordanian Airlines to transport Syrian refugees to their destination as desired by the international organizations.”¹⁴⁸ This was considered a new development.

It can be said that until mid-2012, there was conviction among Jordanian decision-makers that “the survival of the Syrian regime is better than the dominance of radical Islamic groups in Damascus because it will affect the balance of power in Jordan. There were fears of transfer of dominance of rule to the hands of Salafist jihadist and the organization of al-Qaeda in Syria or at least in the northern borders till Anbar in Iraq, where these organizations were flourishing.”¹⁴⁹

¹⁴⁶ Kinninmont, Jan. (2014).The Syrian Conflict And The Geopolitical Situation Of The Region. Retrieved from <http://www.iemed.org/observatori/arees-danalisi/arxiusadjunts/anuari/anuari-2014>

¹⁴⁷ Alexandra, Francis. (2015). *Jordan's Refugee Crisis*. Carnegie Endowment For International Peace. Washington DC. p: 6.

¹⁴⁸ Alrai Newspaper. (2016, July 25). *Almumani: Sananqil Allajiiyn Bitayiratina Liman Yuriduhum* [Al-Momani: We Will Transfer Refugees By Our Planes To Those Who Want Them]. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/1001456>

¹⁴⁹ Kinninmont, Jan. (2014).The Syrian Conflict And The Geopolitical Situation Of The Region. Retrieved from <http://www.iemed.org/observatori/arees-danalisi/arxiusadjunts/anuari/anuari-2014>

Jordan is one of the countries mainly and directly involved in the Syrian conflict because of the threat posed by Jordanians fighting by the side of ISIS.¹⁵⁰ The northern borders of Jordan of 375 kilometers are considered an important place for those who wish to join the fighting organizations in Syria since Jordan is the third port for them after Turkey and Lebanon.

A report published by the US Congress in 2017 shows that “there are about 4,000 Jordanians who have joined ISIS in Syria and Iraq since 2011.” According to the report, Jordan became the second largest foreign volunteer in ISIS after Tunisia.¹⁵¹ The report mentioned that “not only did the volunteers come from Ma’an city in the south of the kingdom, but extended to include northern cities such as Irbid and Salt.”¹⁵²

Apparently, the Jordanian security vision at the beginning of the conflict, was based on the idea that the “Syrian refugee problem” on its northern border was a “temporary problem”. However, the kingdom’s political and security decisions shifted to more restricted policies due to the security threats occurring on its northern border. The concerns arise due to increase in the number of refugees¹⁵³ as a result of the growing gravity of the conflict. Most of the refugees, particularly from the southern governorate of Syria, came through the

¹⁵⁰ Special Media Report. (2017, January 1). *Hal Yubadid Aitifaq Alhudnat Fi Suria Makhawif Al'urdumi Al'ammia?* [Will The Truce Agreement In Syria Dispel Jordan's Security Concerns?] Retrieved From [Http://Alkhaleejonline.Net/Articles/1483212895116114900](http://Alkhaleejonline.Net/Articles/1483212895116114900)

¹⁵¹ Russia Today Arabic. (2017, April 2). *Al'urdumu Thany 'Akbar Masdar Lildawaeish Baed Tunis* [Jordan Is The Second Largest Source Of ISIS Fighters After Tunisia]. Retrieved from https://arabic.rt.com/middle_east/871204--الأردن-ثاني--أكبر-مساهم-بالمطو-عين-الأجانب-إلى-داعش-بعد-تونس

¹⁵² Ibid.

¹⁵³ Younes, Ilham. (2014). Jordan Facing The Syrian Crisis. The Keys Of The Middle East. Retrieved from <http://www.lesclesdumoyenorient.com/la-jordanie-face-a-la-crisesyrienne.html> p: 4.

border between Jordan and Syria, and the number of refugees reached 1.4 million in 2015, of whom 80% of lived outside the camps set up for this purpose.

The security and military situation on the borders of northern Jordan, especially the province of Daraa, came under the influence of the Islamic fighters who were very close to Jordan's borders. Missiles were launched on some Jordan territories in the north.¹⁵⁴ In early 2014, Jordan joined the International Coalition against Terrorism.

In response to the imminent terrorist threat on its northern and eastern borders, Jordan intervened in the war against the organization of the Islamic state. On 22 September 2014, Jordan launched a number of air strikes against ISIS sites in Syria. The incident of Jordanian pilot Moaz al-Kassaba being captured and killed led Jordan to launch retaliatory condensed raids on ISIS sites in Syria and Iraq between 5 and 7 February 2015. The military media release pointed out that 20% of the military capabilities of the Islamic State had been destroyed.¹⁵⁵

After Russia's effective intervention in 2015¹⁵⁶ and the empowering of the Syrian government in the face of the terrorists of ISIS, Al-Nusra Front and other opponents, a rapprochement between Russia and Turkey resulted in the signing of the cease-fire

¹⁵⁴ Mahmoud, Kh. Waleed. (2013, September 10). 'Ayn Yaqif Al'urdunu Min Mujrayat Al'azmat Alsuwria? [Where Does Jordan Stand In The Course Of The Syrian Crisis?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/knowledgagate/opinions/2013/9/10/أين-يقف-الأردن-من-مجرىات-الأزمة-السورية/>

¹⁵⁵ Ibid.

¹⁵⁶ Frihat, Ibrahim. (2016, March 28). *Madha Haqaq Altadakhul Alruwsiu Fi Swrya?* [What Did The Russian Intervention Achieve In Syria?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/knowledgagate/opinions/2016/3/28/ماذا-حقق-التدخل-الروسي-في-سوريا>

agreement throughout Syria on 28 December 2016.¹⁵⁷ The agreement allowed for the creation of a ground for negotiations between the regime and the opposition in Astana, the capital of Kazakhstan. Jordan welcomed this agreement based on its desire to solve the crisis by a “political solution” that brings permanent stability to Syria and protects it from the consequences of the crisis that loom on the economic, social, and security reality of Jordan.

Despite Jordan's welcome of the Russian-Turkish agreement, the security and political decision-makers were surprised by the fact that Jordan began to re-review its security policy as a result of the Karak terrorist attack of 19 December 2016 by the Islamic State. Jordan felt that this agreement will give the Islamic State time to direct its strikes to the targeted countries on the list of ISIS.¹⁵⁸

On the other hand, it must be clear that Jordanian fears, according to the Jordanian security mind, did not come only from the presence of a security threat from Islamic terrorist groups or other emanations from the Syrian arena. Other fears stemmed from the presence of Iranian or Shiite forces that supported and helped the Syrian regime in its fight against the Takfiri communities on northern border of Jordan. It is therefore not surprising that the

¹⁵⁷ BBC Arabic. (2016, December 28). *Turkia Warusia Taedan Wathiqatayn Lilhali Alsiyasiy Walhudnat Fi Suria* [Turkey And Russia Are Preparing Documents For The Political Solution And A Truce In Syria]. Retrieved from <http://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast-38449521>

¹⁵⁸ Special Media Report. (2017, January 1). *Hal Yubadid Aitifaq Alhudnat Fi Suria Makhawif Al'urduni Al'ammia?* [Will The Truce Agreement In Syria Dispel Jordan's Security Concerns?] Retrieved From <Http://Alkhaleejonline.Net/Articles/1483212895116114900>

Chairman of the Joint Chiefs-of-Staff Major General Mahmoud Freihat, appeared on media to warn of a “land belt” that Iran aspires to achieve to link it with Lebanon.¹⁵⁹

The security situation in Jordan appeared to be very dangerous, as a large number of Islamic fighters who held Jordanian nationality entered Syria to fight within the Islamic terrorist organizations, especially the Al-Nusra Front.¹⁶⁰ Jordan was concerned of serious security problems when these fighters returned back home to Jordan. Mahmoud Ardesat, director of the Center for Strategic Studies at the King Abdullah II Academy for Defense Studies in Amman, said that “this is the last thing we want to see; the presence of extremist groups in Syria will lead to many problems in the near future.”¹⁶¹

The strategy of Jordan determined to not allow the Islamic State to approach the northern borders of Jordan. On this basis, the intensity of Jordanian fire continued to counter any attempts to penetrate the Jordanian border from any armed or unarmed side on the Syrian side. Activists working in coordination committees with Al-Nusra Front from the Jordanian security side were warned that the Jordanian border authorities would deal with any element in Al-Nusra Front that try to flee to Jordan or approach the border as “infiltrator”, and they will be dealt with directly by military means, even if they are willing to cease fighting with ISIS.¹⁶²

¹⁵⁹ Ibid.

¹⁶⁰ Al-Shalabi, Jamal. (2017). *'Athara Alluju' Alsuwriu Min Alhudud Alshamaliat Ealaa Al'amn Alqawmii Al'urduniyi* [The Impact Of Syrian Asylum On The Northern Border On Jordanian National Security]. *Dafater Al-Syasa Wa Al-Qanon*. Université Kasdi Merbah - Ouargla. Algeria. p: 4.

¹⁶¹ Gatehouse, Gabriel. (2013, April 26). *The West Trains Syrian Militants In Jordan*. Retrieved from http://www.bbc.com/arabic/middleeast/2013/04/130426_jordan_trains_syrian_rebels

¹⁶² Raialyoum. (2016, July 5). *Risaltan Min Al'urdun Lijanub Swryt...Alawla Limuqatili Alnusrat Bieunwan"La Taqtaribuu Bihujat Alfirar Min Daesh".. Walththaniat Liljaysh Alhuri : Nudaeimukum Fi Muajahat Tanzim Aldawlat Waghiab Jaysh "Alnzam"* [Two Messages From Jordan To The South Of Syria. The First Of The Fighters Of Al-Nusra Entitled "Do Not Approach The Pretext Of Escape From The Daash". The Second Free Army: We Support You In The

In general, Jordan faced intense pressure from the Syrian war, but compared to Syria's neighboring countries, Jordan is the most effective in the face of instability. Jordan adopted a policy to quickly strengthen control over its northern border and prevent the flow of arms. The Julien Barnes-Dacey report confirms that there have been no large-scale attacks in Jordan as a result of what was happening in Syria, despite the presence of nearly two thousand Jordanian fighters within ISIS, concerns about the security situation in southern Syria and the extent of the ability of the Jordanian security services to address them. To address these security risks near the northern border, the Jordanian parliament gave the security services greater power.¹⁶³

6.7.2 Confronting Terrorism:

The Jordanian authorities recognized that Jordan is not far from the dangers that the Islamic State formed. The warnings of coming from of ISIS toward Jordan, stimulated the kingdom to respond and react in the way it deemed proper, before it was too late. The Salafist groups' members still support ISIS and other similar terrorist organizations; the thing that makes the situation worse. The declaration of ISIS of establishing base in Jordan in order to start providing it with logistics made the kingdom take preventive measures to face threats through deployment of Jordanian troops on the borders with Syria and Iraq with more forces, in addition to enforcement of internal policies, laws, regulations, and measures to have more discipline which leads to detaining terrorist supporters.¹⁶⁴

Face Of Islamic State And The Absence Of The "Regime"}. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/رسالتان-من-الأردن-لجنوب-سورية-الاولى/>

¹⁶³ Barnes-Dacey, Julien. (2016). *The War Next Door: Syria And The Erosion Of Stability In Lebanon, Jordan And Turkey*. London: European Council On Foreign Relations. p: 3-4.

¹⁶⁴ Schenker, D. (2014). Countering The ISIS Threat To Jordan. *Wall Street Journal*. p: 1..

From Jordan's perspective, there are three major motivations which encourage ISIS to look eagerly to Jordan:

First: The Jordanian contribution to the international coalition against ISIS. Jordan is in a strategic alliance with the United States in its war against terrorism and regional threats. This was apparent as Jordan provided logistics and intelligence services to the international coalition. Jordan also opened the Jordanian airspace to launch fighting aircraft and drones for the international coalition to conduct airstrikes on ISIS locations. The Jordanian Salafist extremists opposed that and condemned it.

Second: The geographic expansion of ISIS in Jordan would strongly provide the Islamic State with vital crossing points. ISIS captured area in Iraq is 60 kilometers away from Jordan and closer to the borders. As ISIS leader Abu Bakr Al Baghdadi sees it, Jordan's land can also be used to reach Sinai in Egypt.

Third: Thought expansion through the supporters in Jordan. The expansion of jihadist and religious thoughts facilitates moving into neighboring land. Demonstrations calling for Jihad were carried out in the streets in Ma'an south of Jordan. Many of the Salafi jihadists in Jordan were in battlefields in Afghanistan, Iraq, and Syria.¹⁶⁵

Legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law: The parliament of Jordan ratified the legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law in 2014. The government and the security agencies were extended great authorities. New concepts of terrorism issue were added or modified. The Muslim Brothers and the human right organizations criticized this move, as it was followed by wide detention campaigns for whomever showed sympathy with ISIS in public, resulting in detention of 300 persons. Meanwhile, 25 Imams were prohibited

¹⁶⁵ Ibid.

from preaching in mosques for violating the law and promoting intellectual and religious extremism.

High ministerial committee for facing terrorism: This committee was formed as a result of increasing Salafist movements in cities and villages of Jordan. The goal of the committee was to face hardliners politically, socially, intellectually, and if necessary, even with security means. The representatives of the committee were found to observe extremists closely all over Jordanian establishments.

The deployment of Jordanian troops across the border with Iraq and Syria, came after the controlling of ISIS land on shared borders of Jordan with Syria and Iraq. The United States supported Jordan with military assistance. During 2016, Jordan kept on strengthening its long border with Iraq and Syria to reduce its proximity danger, specifically, to stop access by terrorists and to control large influx of refugees. In June 2016, possibly infiltrating men were killed when an ISIS suicide man exploded along the Jordan-Syria border at Rukban refugee camp, killing six Jordanian security men. Later on, Jordan's counterterrorism services recognized and stopped several threats. In March 2016, security attack at a Palestinian refugee camp in the north of Jordan caused the death of seven assumed ISIS men. Officials showed that the suspects were preparing for attacks on the kingdom. Other important events during the year were the June 2016 killing of five state personnel in the Palestinian Baqaa refugee camp near the capital city of Amman, and the November 2016 killing of three US security members in al-Jafr at the King Faisal Air Base. Both incidents, committed by lone gunmen, were measured at the time as lying within the baseline risk assessment of medium. The two incidents were followed by a big attack in Karak on 18 December 2016.

Having joined the international coalition against terrorism, along with other 62 countries, Jordan military bases contain operations rooms for collecting, analyzing, and exchanging data, and coordinating action, in addition to observing.¹⁶⁶ The Jordanian government launched campaigns to promote tolerance thoughts of Islam instead of extremist thoughts. Promoting peaceful ways in progressive debate and expressing moderate thoughts, the campaigns were organized by official social establishments, media, schools, universities, and social media.¹⁶⁷

6.7.3 Jordan's Policy to Combat Terrorism:

As the danger of terrorism has increased because of the Syrian crisis and the threat posed by ISIS, Jordan has initiated some new strategies and policies, and revised old laws with modifications. The Jordanian government's response to present threats formed by extremist organizations and groups, has become much greater than what it was in the past, mostly because of the complexity and severity of the situation.¹⁶⁸ King Abdullah II called the war against ISIS a critical fight for the kingdom, despite popular uncertainty to Jordan's contribution in the international coalition to combat ISIS till the death of Jordanian pilot Lt. Kasasbeh at the hands of ISIS.¹⁶⁹ The King stated in an interview that he considered the

¹⁶⁶ Drennan, J. (2014). Who Has Contributed What In The Coalition Against The Islamic State? *Foreign Policy*. 12. p: 11.

¹⁶⁷ Altarawneh, Mahmoud. (2016, June 16). *Maswuwulun: Alkhutat Alwataniaat Limukafahat Altataruf Mutabaqatan Bijadawul Zamania* [Officials: The National Plan To Combat Extremism Is In Place With Timetables]. Alghad Newspaper. Retrieved from <http://alghad.com/articles/953512>

¹⁶⁸ Monti, Elyse. Patterson, Sarah. (2015). *Jordan's Counterterrorism Policies: Response To Complex Threats*. The Institute For Middle East Studies. p: 31.

¹⁶⁹ Hassan, Hassan. (2015, February 4). Jordan's Battle Against ISIL No Longer 'Someone Else's War. Retrieved from <http://www.thenational.ae/world/middle-east/jordans-battle-against-isil-no-longer-someone-elseswar>

war against ISIS to be more of Jordan's fight than of the United States.¹⁷⁰ In an interview with Charlie Rose in December 2014, the King called the Islamic world to take the lead in combating Islamic extremism. He said that a "strategic, holistic approach" is essential throughout the Middle East region, and Muslims indeed need to "take ownership" and "start fighting back".¹⁷¹ Furthermore, the King has been the dynamic force that pushed the authorities to enhance counterterrorism strategies and policies, which consisted of legislative, military and security, and public and social measures. The role of King Abdullah II in Jordanian policymaking cannot be overstated.¹⁷²

6.7.3.1 Legal Measures:

Despite the fact that Jordan had been facing terrorist threats for a long time, its laws related to counterterrorism were mostly new. Before 2016, Jordan did not have anti-terrorism laws, and used its penal code to manage terrorism-related issues.¹⁷³ The first anti-terrorism law in Jordan was passed in 2006. The law was stated by the government as a necessity to avoid attacks on Jordanian territories and in response to Al-Qaida's hotel bombing attacks in Amman in 2005, which resulted in the killing of 60 people.¹⁷⁴ The government also passed the Fatwa Law, under which the State gave only Islamic religion sheiks the authorization

¹⁷⁰ Ibid.

¹⁷¹ King Abdullah II. (2014, December 6) His Majesty King Abdullah II's Interview On PBS's Charlie Rose – Transcript. 6 December 2014. Retrieved from <http://usvisit2014en.rhcjo.com/hmkiicharlierosetranscript/>

¹⁷² Fishman, B. (2014). Jordan: Caught In The Middle Again. *Adelphi Papers*.54(447-448), 123-134. p: 131.

¹⁷³ The Associated Press. (2006, August 28). *Jordan's Parliament Approves Country's First Anti-Terrorism Law*. Retrieved from <http://www.kcchronicle.com/2006/08/28/jordansparliament-approves-countrys-first-anti-terrorismlaw/aqrp5s7/archive-749698290320.txt>.

¹⁷⁴ Gambrell, Jon. (2014, June 1). *Jordan Amends, Widens Its Anti-Terrorism Laws*. Retrieved from <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2014/jun/1/jordan-amends-widens-its-anti-terrorism-laws/>

to issue fatwas.¹⁷⁵ The 2006 law was amended in June 2014 to widen the government's authority to combat terrorism. There was wide acceptance for the new amendments, passed largely because of the growing numbers of Jordanians and foreigners who traveled to join the fighting opponents in Syria. The new amendments criminalized any speech that was deemed disparaging to the King or government officials or institutions or to Islam, and speech that may be interpreted and understood as defamatory of others. The definition of terrorism was amended to include "disturbing Jordan's relations with a foreign state."¹⁷⁶ So, the Jordanian authorities could legally charge any networks or individuals supporting and helping terrorist groups or facilitating spread of thoughts inciting terrorist actions. Media outlets and websites were also subject to the new laws.¹⁷⁷

The amendments came at a time when the government was under pressure and anxiety because of ISIS and the war in Syria. Before 2014, the fighters returning from Syria were not arrested on the border immediately when crossing back into Jordan, particularly if these fighters were first-time offenders and showed their regret for their actions.¹⁷⁸ Later on however, the Jordanian authorities closed many border crossings with Syria due to security concerns. The government also began forcing Syrians refugees to settle down in camps set

¹⁷⁵ Hearne, Ellie. Laiq, Nur. (2010). *A New Approach?: Deradicalization Programs And Counterterrorism*. International Peace Institute (IPI). p: 6.

¹⁷⁶ Human Rights Watch. (2015). *World Report 2015: Events Of 2014*. Policy Press. p: 333.

¹⁷⁷ Gambrell, Jon. (2014, June 1). *Jordan Amends, Widens Its Anti-Terrorism Laws*. Retrieved from <https://www.washingtontimes.com/news/2014/jun/1/jordan-amends-widens-its-anti-terrorism-laws/>

¹⁷⁸ Al-Khalidi, Suleiman. (2014, October 27). *Jordan Arrests Influential Al Qaeda Scholar For 'Incitement'*. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com/article/us-jordan-islamist/jordan-arrests-influential-al-qaeda-scholar-for-incitement-iduskbn0ig1vs20141027>

up for them, instead of residing in already crowded cities.¹⁷⁹ The government would not have taken those actions unless it sensed the growing security concerns on the ground that could no more be denied or neglected.

As per the new anti-terrorism law, several individuals were prosecuted in Jordan. The Jordanians returning from fighting in Syria were detained and charged with “disturbing relations with a friendly nation.”¹⁸⁰ At least 60 individuals were detained for participating in jihadi activities in a security force campaign during the period between September and October 2014; the activities included using social media to promote videos and messages sympathetic with ISIS,¹⁸¹ and the Judiciary Authority announced various sentences for those convicted. In December 2014, the State Security Court gave one to two years in prison, to five youths who were arrested in August, for “either using the internet to promote the thoughts of the group or joining ISIS”. A judicial source noted that the court had decreased the original sentences from three years to give the defendants an opportunity to reform themselves as they were still young.¹⁸² In contrast, in February 2015, the same court gave a number of Jordanian individuals, five to fifteen years for recruiting for joining terrorist groups or for importing weapons and ammunition in favor of these groups.¹⁸³

¹⁷⁹ Black, Ian. (2014, December 1). *Patience Running Out In Jordan After Influx Of Syrian Refugees*. Retrieved from <http://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/dec/01/jordan-syrian-refugees-patience-running-out>

¹⁸⁰ Anjarini, Suhaib. (2015, January 16). Alardnywn Fi “Jbihat Alnsr”: Husat Almalik [Jordanians In Jabhat Al-Nusra: The King’s Share]. Retrieved from <http://www.al-akhbar.com/node/223939>

¹⁸¹ Reed, John. (2014). *Jordan Tackles Homegrown Islamists As It Joins Attacks On ISIS*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/08fc027c-4a29-11e4-bc07-00144feab7de.html>

¹⁸² Middle East Online. (2014, December 8). *Alsijn Li Kamsat 'Urduniyyn 'Udinuu Bialailtihaq Waltarwij Litanzim Daeish* [Prison For 5 Jordanians Convicted Of Joining And Promoting ISIS]. Retrieved from <https://aawsat.com/home/article/238871/السجن-ل-5-أردنيين-أدينوا-بالالتحاق-والترويج-لتنظيم-داعش>

¹⁸³ Al-Da‘Ma, Muhammad. (2015, February 17). *Alardun: 'Ahkam Bialsajn Ealaa Eadad Min 'Ansar “Daesh”* [Jordan: High Prison Sentences For A Number Of ISIS Members]. Retrieved from <https://aawsat.com/home/article/291491/الأردن-أحكام-بالسجن-على-عدد-من-أنصار-«داعش»>

6.7.3.2 Military and Security Changes

In order to assist the increasing legal actions of the government against terrorism, the Jordanian government initiated military operations and an intensified security campaign in response to the threats created by ISIS. The government made a vital contribution for the military element to clamp down terrorism, where it previously used security services. Jordan recognized that it was a two-pronged move including an enhanced security campaign and the Jordanian Army for military action.¹⁸⁴ The military response of Jordan consisted of various plans and actions such as increasing border security, training moderate opposition forces which were anti-Assad, and participating in the international coalition to combat ISIS by participating in direct military actions. Jordan was encountering terrorism on domestic, regional, and international levels.¹⁸⁵

Jordan managed to increase security on its long border with Syria to stop extremists from crossing in, by establishing the Jordan Border Security Program. The program involved high technology sensors to avoid infiltration, and used Special Operations Forces, for example, the 71st Counterterrorism Battalion, which was widely known to be the best in the area.^{186,187} In addition to enhancing security, the counterterrorism forces in Jordan were

¹⁸⁴ Reed, John. (2014). *Jordan Tackles Homegrown Islamists As It Joins Attacks On ISIS*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/08fc027c-4a29-11e4-bc07-00144feab7de.html>

¹⁸⁵ Abu Rumman, Mohammad Suliman et Al. (2016). *Methods Of Preventing And Combatting Terrorism In The MENA Region And The West*. Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung Jordan And Iraq. pp: 96-97.

¹⁸⁶ Terrill, W. A. (2008). *Jordanian National Security And The Future Of Middle East Stability*. Army War Coll Strategic Studies Inst Carlisle Barracks Pa. p: 56.

¹⁸⁷ The Soufan Group. (2013). *Intelbrief: Jordan's Counterterrorism Program*. The Soufan Group. Counterterrorism-Program. p: 6.

pressuring high intellectuals such as educators, clerics, and others to condemn ISIS and its thought and actions.¹⁸⁸

Jordan had a big role in assisting and training on the Jordanian territories, moderate opposition of anti-Assad groups. The Jordanian military institution had a reputation for expertise in training other states' police and Special Forces troops in the past.¹⁸⁹ Leaders of the Free Syrian Army (FSA) mentioned they received from Jordan military equipment including light arms, in addition to modest financial aid, for more than a whole year. The FSA took communications equipment, weapons, and money from the Amman operations center. The center included several advisors from the international coalition, mainly from the US, the UAE, and some European countries.¹⁹⁰ The Jordanian front against ISIS expanded to include Iraq. Mohammed al-Momani, the government spokesperson, officially confirmed in March 2015, that Jordan will train forces from Syrian and Iraqi tribes in addition to Iraqi Kurdish forces, to fight against ISIS.¹⁹¹

The Jordanian military also participated in the international air coalition, which began airstrikes in Syria and Iraq in September 2014. Beyond its pilots directly engaging in airstrikes, it allowed the US-led coalition to use Jordanian training centers, airfields, and its state security services to fight ISIL;¹⁹² this came as no surprise since the US provided

¹⁸⁸ Reed, John. (2014). *Jordan Tackles Homegrown Islamists As It Joins Attacks On ISIS*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/08fc027c-4a29-11e4-bc07-00144feab7de.html>

¹⁸⁹ Ryan, C. R. (2014). Jordanian Foreign Policy And The Arab Spring. *Middle East Policy*, 21(1), 144-153. p: 148.

¹⁹⁰ Ibid.

¹⁹¹ Sultan, Jamal. (2015m March 23). Al'urdunu Yudarib Eashayir Suriatan Waeiraqiatan Wakaradiatan Limujaha "Daesh" [Jordan Trains Syrian And Iraqi Tribes And Kurdish Forces To Confront 'Daesh]. Almesryoon.Com. Retrieved from <https://www.almesryoon.com/story/698989/الأردن-يدرب-عشائر-سورية-وعراقية-وكردية-لمواجهة-داعش>

¹⁹² Reed, John. (2014). *Jordan Tackles Homegrown Islamists As It Joins Attacks On ISIS*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/08fc027c-4a29-11e4-bc07-00144feab7de.html>

Jordan's armed forces with approximately \$300 million annually. The Jordanian government also allowed the US to train moderate Syrian rebels inside Jordan.¹⁹³

The turning point that made Jordan significantly escalate its military activities against ISIS was after the latter released a shocking video of burning alive Jordanian pilot Lieutenant Moaz al-Kasasbeh. ISIS captured the pilot when his plane crashed in Syria in December 2014. The death of Lieutenant Kasasbeh was considered in many ways the turning point for Jordan in its combat against ISIS operations. Public outrage against the incident gave the government and the Jordanian leadership a rally around the flag. Jordan increased its air raids against ISIS in both Syria and Iraq. King Abdullah II called the fight against ISIS as a third world war,¹⁹⁴ and public opinion boosted the authorities to carry out more military and counterterrorism operations.¹⁹⁵

6.7.3.3 Social Messaging Measures:

In addition to legal, security, and military procedures, Jordan was also countering terrorism through social and public messaging platforms which were not used in the past. The government found it extremely necessary to use these platforms as technologies, thinking, and attitudes evolved. Jordanian security agencies declared that they were trying to control the ways in which religion was understood and practiced, by trying to counteract ISIS thought and practice on social media via lectures, preaches, and sermons. Jordanian

¹⁹³ Schenker, D. (2014) Preventing ISIS Inroads In Jordan. *The Washington Institute*. pp: (2)

¹⁹⁴ Mohseni, P. (2015). *Disrupting The Chessboard: Perspectives On The Russian Intervention In Syria*. Massachusetts: Belfer Center For Science And International Affairs, Harvard Kennedy School. p: 26.

¹⁹⁵ King Abdullah II Interview With Fareed Zakaria. (2015, March 1). *Jordan's King Abdullah "This Is A Third World War By Other Means*. Retrieved from <http://cnnpressroom.blogs.cnn.com/2015/03/01/jordans-king-abdullah-this-is-a-third-world-war-by-other-means/>

Information Minister, Mohammad al-Momani said, “We continue to ask the clerics, the academics, the educators to speak about the true nature of Islam.”¹⁹⁶ In June 2014, the Jordanian authorities released the Salafi ideologue “Abu Mohammad al-Maqdisi” and in September dropped terrorism charges against the radical preacher “Abu Qatada” after he condemned and denounced ISIS in prison.^{197,198}

In addition to a huge public relations campaign to fight the thoughts of ISIS, the Jordanian government intensified its efforts of spreading messages at mosques. Unauthorized imams in mosques and illegal mosque constructions were clamped down.¹⁹⁹ Of approximately 8,600 mosques in the kingdom, most were built illegally and around 4,500 imams leading them were not government-appointed. The government established great control over the religious aspect of people’s lives and was apprehensive that the unauthorized imams were preaching violence. The government expected that the selected imams who received salaries from the government at legal mosques should support the monarchy and condemn and renounce jihadist salafi ideology.²⁰⁰ The government even gave the imams weekly suggestions for Friday sermons, and instructions on main topics to preach and discuss and the ones to avoid in mosques and public gatherings.

Jordan thus tried to gain control of the messages given in authorized and unauthorized mosques. Efforts were particularly directed towards poverty-ridden areas such as Zarqa,

¹⁹⁶ Reed, John. (2014). *Jordan Tackles Homegrown Islamists As It Joins Attacks On ISIS*. Retrieved from <http://www.ft.com/intl/cms/s/0/08fc027c-4a29-11e4-bc07-00144feab7de.html>

¹⁹⁷ Ibid.

¹⁹⁸ Wood, G. (2015). What ISIS Really Wants. *The Atlantic*. 315(2), 78-94. pp: 83-90.

¹⁹⁹ Abi-Habib, M. (2014). Jordan Plans Crackdown On Unauthorized Mosques To Combat Radical Islam. *Wall Street Journal*, 19.

²⁰⁰ Ibid.

which were known for an extremist stronghold. In the governorate of Zarqa, there were about 300 mosques, 80% of which were illegal, and lack of funds was the main obstacle to the government assigning imams in these mosques. According to Ministry of Religious Affairs in Jordan, government plan for this purpose needed \$70 million to be effective, which gave rise to funding problems to achieve the goals of the anti-radicalization program. Some Jordanians were upset and believed that the government should have put such efforts to regulate anti-radicalization in all mosques after the bombings in three hotels in Amman in 2005.²⁰¹

These plans also raised questions from citizens about why the Jordanian authorities did not implement more such programs for anti-radicalization sooner; at the same time, as the government started implementing the programs it began receiving even more threats from ISIS as well as the Jordanians returning from Iraq and Syria.

In addition to anti-radicalization projects, prisoners were also subjected to a religion-based deradicalization program. The program aimed at re-engaging extremist prisoners towards moderate Islam.²⁰² It suited the private needs of the prisoners and included employment, treatment, literacy classes, and religious instruction.²⁰³ Moreover, in January 2015, Jordan's prison authorities started separating Islamist extremist prisoners from regular prisoners, as the extremist prisoners had the ability to radicalize regular prisoners and recruit them to join groups like ISIS.²⁰⁴ For example, the Jordanian prisoner Ibn Ibrahim

²⁰¹ Ibid.

²⁰² United States Department Of State. (2013, April 30). *Country Reports On Terrorism 2013 – Jordan*. Retrieved from <http://www.refworld.org/docid/536229e3d.html>

²⁰³ Ibid.

²⁰⁴ Frenkel, Sheera. (2015). *Jordan's Jails Are Now Ground Zero In Its Fight Against ISIS*. Retrieved [Http://www.buzzfeed.com/sheerafrenkel/jordans-jails-are-now-ground-zero-in-its-fight-against-isis](http://www.buzzfeed.com/sheerafrenkel/jordans-jails-are-now-ground-zero-in-its-fight-against-isis)

was charged and imprisoned in 2012-2013 under a drugs case, and during that period the man was indoctrinated with militant Islam by extremist prisoners. By 2014, he was heading to Syria to join ISIS.²⁰⁵ Furthermore, some jihadi Jordanian sheiks such as Abu Qatada and Abu Sayyaf, recognized the importance of radicalization process and the strong impact it had on their own thoughts and beliefs as well as on that of other prisoners.²⁰⁶

A major problem faced by the government's counter-messaging program were recruits of ISIS and other extremist organizations like Al-Nusra Front, who saw moderate imams as illegitimate, particularly if they were appointed and paid by the government or working under government-sanctioned projects. The government had little control over how moderates and extremists were being perceived on the ground.²⁰⁷ In Jordan, even less extreme Islamists who were powerful voices against ISIS and Al-Nusra Front ideologies such as Maqdisi, were seen by supporters as illegitimate people and infidels.²⁰⁸ Therefore, the general impact of the counter-messaging program was minimal.

6.8 The Jordanian Political Position towards the Syrian Peace Process

6.8.1 Contradictions in the Jordanian Position:

Since the beginning of the Syrian crisis, Jordan received refugees on its territory and allowed them to present their claim condemning the Syrian actions, especially the people of Daraa, who launched the first spark of conflict. Some Syrian people had close ties in other areas in Jordan. There were multiple incidents of clashes between the Syrian and

²⁰⁵ Ibid.

²⁰⁶ Ibid.

²⁰⁷ Chowdhury, A., & Krebs, R. R. (2009). *Making And Mobilizing Moderates: Rhetorical Strategy, Political Networks, And Counterterrorism*. *Security Studies*, 18(3), 371-399. p: 6.

²⁰⁸ Sowell, K. H. (2015). *Jordanian Salafism And The Jihad In Syria*. *Current Trends In Islamist Ideology*, Hudson Institue. 18, 41. p: 41.

Jordanian armies²⁰⁹ because of the presence of armed men either according to the Syrian claim, or because of attempts by refugees or deserters of the regime including military personnel, to flee to Jordan. The refugees included a Syrian pilot²¹⁰ as well as the former Syrian Prime Minister Riyad Hijab.²¹¹ King Abdullah II himself called on President Assad to step down.²¹² On more than one occasion, Syria accused Jordan of sheltering, training and arming insurgents with the support and patronage of Saudi Arabia and the US, so that they could control all border crossings between the two countries except for the Naseeb crossing. This raised fear that Daraa would be a point to launch an attack.²¹³

The Syrian President Bashar al-Assad received a Jordanian delegation that declared its support without a denial from the Jordanian state.²¹⁴ The Jordanian security services prosecuted Jordanian fighters who attempted to infiltrate or return to Syria, as well as

²⁰⁹ Al-Najjar, Mohammed. (2012, August 2). *Aishtibak Eanif Bayn Aljyshyn Al'urduniyi Walsuwrii* [Violent Clash Between The Jordanian And Syrian Armies]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/pages/2ed7e471-853f-4c0d-83d8-e1425f0d42ee>

²¹⁰ Asharq Al-Awsat Newspaper. (2012, June 22). *Ainshiqaq Tayar Suriin Wafararih Batayiratih Alharbiat 'Ilaa Al'urduni Hayth Manh Alluju' Alsiyasiu* [A Syrian Pilot Defected And Flew To Jordan Granted Him An Asylum]. Retrieved from <http://archive.aawsat.com/details.asp?section=4&article=683013&issueno=12260#.wygawkifpiu>

²¹¹ Asharq Al-Awsat Newspaper. (2012, August 9). *Hijab Yazhar Lilmarat Al'uwlaa Baed Ainshiqaqih.. Wal'urdun Yuelan Rasmiaan Dukhulih 'Ilaa 'Aradih* [Hijab Appears For The First Time After Its Split. Jordan Officially Announces Its Entry Into Its Territory]. Retrieved from <http://archive.aawsat.com/details.asp?section=4&article=690100&issueno=12308#.wygdluifpiu>

²¹² Middle East Panorama. (2011, November 15). *Malik Al'urdun: Law Kunt Makan Al'asad Litanhiat* [KING OF JORDAN: If I Were The Place Of Assad, I Would Leave Power]. Retrieved from <http://www.mepanorama.net/43873/ملكالأردن-لو-كنت-مكان-الأسد-لتنحيت>

²¹³ Asharq Al-Awsat Newspaper. (2013, March 31). *Almuearadat Alsuwriat Taseaa 'Ilaa 'Iitbaq "Fky Alkmash" Ealaa Alnizam Tamhidaan Limaerakat Dimashq* [The Syrian Opposition Tries To Close The "Pliers" On The Regime In Preparation For The Damascus Battle]. Retrieved from <http://archive.aawsat.com/details.asp?section=4&issueno=12542&article=722897&feature#.wygft0ifpiu>

²¹⁴ Al-Najjar, Mohammed. (2013, February 14) *Aietisam Bial'urduni Dida Ziarat Wafd Lil'asad* [A Sit-In In Jordan Against A Visit By A Delegation To Assad]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/pages/d2d2f010-183e-4261-893e-7bc8e455406e>

worked towards preventing the infiltration of Syrian fighters.²¹⁵ The Jordanian authorities restricted the movements of Syrian dissidents on its territory, even though it was keen on giving them freedom of movement and expression at the beginning of the crisis.

These two facets of the Jordanian position, in favor of or against the Syrian regime, and in favor of or against the opposition, were not necessarily distinctly temporal, but sometimes overlapping. This led Jordanian political and popular forces to accuse their government of contradicting its own position.²¹⁶ This reflected how careful the Jordanian decision makers had to be of any wrong calculations that may reflect negatively on domestic or regional situation.

All of the political, existential and strategic fears of Jordan hail from Syria and there are no easy options to be relied upon. The absolute stand by the side of the Syrian opposition without an absolute victory or failure of the latter, will bring Jordan into a cycle of enmity and confrontation with parties in the new system under the old regime or the same old regime if it is able to withstand or prove its ability to last long. In reducing the importance of the Syrian opposition, in the event of their victory and formation of a new regime under new conditions, Jordan will be expose to the dangers of formation of a Syrian government that does not take into account the interests of Jordan.

Assad's survival in power, or the continuation of the Syrian crisis without him, places Jordan at a high security and economic risk. Jordan cannot endure the Syrian refugees cost,

²¹⁵ Swiss Info. (2013). Alsijn Khmst 'Aewam Lisalafi 'Urduniyun Qatal Fi Sufuf Jabhat Alnasrat Fi Suria [Five Years Imprisonment For A Jordanian Who Fought In Al-Nusra Front In Syria]. Retrieved from <http://www.swissinfo.ch/ara/detail/content.html?cid=37606008>

²¹⁶ Qandeel, Khaleel. (2013, September 7). Hrakywn: Almawqif Alrasmiu Min Darbat Suria Mutanaqid Mae Alshsharie [Activists: The Official Position Of Syria's Strike Is Contradictory To The Street]. Retrieved from <http://assabeel.net/news/2013/09/07/حراكيون-الموقف-الرسمي-من-ضربة-سوريا-متناقض-مع-الشارع>

and the numbers are growing, steadily increasing as the conflict intensifies or escalates unresolved. The continuation of the conflict without a reasonable international ceiling would allow the “religious militancy” leaking from Syria to sweep Jordan like the rest of the region.

Jordan is also concerned with other existential or structural concerns, such as those related to changes that may arise in the Syrian geopolitics as a consequence of the conflict or its solution.²¹⁷ Jordan will then be concerned with either the threats of disintegration of the Syrian state or dealing with some of its repercussions. As for the structure of the regime in future, Jordan played its role by conciliating and assimilating the Islamic trend in return for giving up a calculated share of it. Any victory recorded of any kind for the moderate Islamists in Syria in terms of building the state, will roll back and strengthen the Islamic opposition on the Jordanian soil, i.e., the Muslim Brotherhood.

It is not surprising that Jordan considers the growth of “political Islam” a threat to its stability after the active participation of the Muslim Brotherhood in the Jordanian protests. The protests increased to some extent demanding constitutional monarchy. This explains Jordan's eagerness to limit the influence of Islamists within the parties of the Syrian revolution or in the field, and perhaps in other Arab countries.²¹⁸ These fears cannot be ignored in any review of the Jordanian position and its tracks. The Syrian crisis put weight

²¹⁷ See: Asseburg, M. (2013). *Syria's Civil War: Geopolitical Implications And Scenarios*. European Institute Of Mediterranean, pp: 14-16.

²¹⁸ Alsoudi, A. (2015). *The Impact Of The Arab Spring On The Political Future Of The Muslim Brotherhood In The Middle East: Jordan As A Case Study*. Middle East Review Of International Affairs (Online), 19(3), 41. p: 8.

on Jordan and made it subject to the influence of the positions of major regional and international players, and to the changing dynamics of the Syrian war and its daily realities.

6.8.2 The Jordanian Political Position towards the Syrian Crisis

It is possible to establish major milestones that illustrate the Jordanian position and the pressures that it was exposed to in its interaction with the Syrian crisis, bearing in mind all of Jordan's strategic concerns presented at all stages:

Prior to Geneva I: Jordan was still living under the influence of daily events in Syria, especially with the beginning of events in Daraa. It was still under pressure from the Arab Spring, which encompassed a number of Arab countries as well as the movements in Jordan. Jordan was more open to the Syrian opposition, but it was still committed to continuing limited channels of dialogue with the regime of President Bashar al-Assad. At this stage, King Abdullah II called to President al-Assad to step down.

Post-Geneva I: In June 2012, the Geneva I Conference culminated in a statement calling for a “political transition” in Syria to end the war. The statement was based on the Jordanian position, but was somewhat puzzled by the ambiguity surrounding the US position. On the one hand, there was a solely American-Russian roadmap for a political solution to the crisis in Syria,²¹⁹ but the American stance against the regime remained intact until it reached the brink of a military strike against Damascus because of the use of chemical weapons.²²⁰ The pressure on the opposition pushed it to agree to join Geneva II, and to fight “terrorism” as the American characterization of hardline groups such as ISIS and Al-Nusra Front. At this

²¹⁹ BBC. (2016). *Syria: The Story Of The Conflict*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc./news/world-middle-east-26116868>

²²⁰ Albayan, Agencies. (2013, March 20). 'Awal Aistikhdam Lilsilah Alkimawii Fi Suria. [The First Use Of Chemical Weapons In Syria]. retrieved from <https://www.albayan.ae/one-world/arabs/2013-03-20-1.1845513>

stage, Jordan was insisting that it did not intervene in the Syrian affairs,²²¹ while supporting the political solution. But the opposition was still strengthening its control over most of the border areas between Syria and Jordan.²²²

Post-retreat of the US strike on Syria (14 September 2013) Jordan became more ²²³,) confident of the political solution and called for it. As a matter of fact, military intervention was not allowed in Syria by the Russians. Both Russia and China stood firmly and vetoed four draft resolutions in the Security Council, condemning the Syrian regime and taking forcible measures in response to the Syrian conflict. Russia repeatedly alerted its Western rivals led by the United States about its deep doubts regarding the effectiveness of military intervention in Syria.^{224,225} Jordan affirmed its rejection of any foreign military intervention to end the Syrian crisis, while stressing on the importance of the Syrian opposition joining the political process. This position was confirmed by Jordan at the Friends of Syria Conference and reiterated at Geneva.²²⁶

²²¹ Mahmoud, Kh. Waleed. (2013, September 10). 'Ayn Yaqif Al'urdunu Min Mujrayat Al'azmat Alsuwria? [Where Does Jordan Stand In The Course Of The Syrian Crisis?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/knowledgegate/opinions/2013/9/10/أين-يقف-الأردن-من-مجرىات-الأزمة-السورية>

²²² Darweesh, Ibrahim. (2013, October 4). 'Sy 'Aya Ayh' Tusae Barnamaj Tadrib Muqatili Almuearadat Alsuwriiyn Fi Al'urdun [CIA Expanded Its Training Program For Syrian Opposition Fighters In Jordan]. Al-Quds Al-Arabi Newspaper. UK. Retrieved from <http://www.alquds.co.uk/?p=90247>

²²³ Aljazeera. (2013, September 14). Aitifaq 'Amirkiun Rwsyun Ealaa Tadmira Kimiayiyin Suria [American-Russian Agreement To Destroy Syrian Chemicals]. Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/arabic/2013/9/14/اتفاق-أميركي-روسي-على-تدمير-كيميائي-سوريا>

²²⁴ Huang, S. (2015). *The Legality And Legitimacy Of Using Armed Force For The Protection Of Strangers: From Humanitarian Intervention To The Responsibility To Protect*. (Master Thesis). Uit Norges Arktiske Universitet. p: 82.

²²⁵ POMEPS Studies. (2013, December 18). *The Political Science Of Syria's War*. The Project On Middle East Political Science (POMEPS: 22), George Washington University. pp: (77). p: 26.

²²⁶ Petra News Agency. (2014, January 22). *Judeh: Alhalu Alsiasu Fi Suria Bialtawafuq Ealaa Hayyat Alhukm Alaintiqalia* [Judeh: The Political Solution In Syria In Accordance With The Transitional Government]. Retrieved from <http://alrai.com/article/628160.html>

It is clear that Jordan has stabilized on its preference for a political solution. At the same time, Jordan is still involved in military options related to the Syrian crisis while the political solution requires deep involvement. There is a conviction that the Syria would be able to survive. At this stage, the position of Jordan is settled clearly on the rejection of some of the Syrian Islamic opposition. The Jordanian political and security apparatuses have, in one voice, described the “Islamic extremism” in Syria and the region as a threat to Jordanian national security.

The most dramatic feature of the shift in the Jordanian position towards the Syrian crisis has been the change from the bias for Assad regime and accusing the revolutionaries of betrayal and unfaithfulness at the beginning of the crisis, to supporting the political opposition and preparing it to take over, to opting for gradual transition of power, to finally returning back to square one - providing support for the Russian position in backing the current system. The transformation which was described as a “coup” originally was the result of practical introductions by way of continuous events, with constant visits of King Abdullah II to the US and Russia raising questions about the reasons, motivations, and features of this transformation.

Since the outbreak of the Syrian crisis, Jordan has played a role that was described by some as “ambiguous”, while others saw it as a “seeker to satisfy all parties”. It was also characterized by “deep pragmatism”. The occasional fluctuations in the situation led the Jordanian leadership to support the Assad regime.²²⁷ The auditors of the Jordanian foreign

²²⁷ Magid, Aaron. (2016, June 13). *Assad's Acolytes In Jordan's Parliament*. Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/english/indepth/2016/6/13/assads-acolytes-in-jordans-parliament>

stations in their assessment found that Jordan's position under Abdullah II's authority had taken four different views, followed by developments in internal and external scene in Damascus.

The first was support for Bashar al-Assad's regime, which has been clear since the beginning of the crisis. Amman declared its full support for the Syrian regime and its rejection of what it called "chaos." It accused the Syrian opposition to act on behalf of foreign agendas which negatively affected Jordan's Gulf relations.²²⁸

Second, the gradual peaceful transition of power. The developments in the Syrian scene during the first three years of the crisis, compelled King Abdullah II to take a step back and a rethink Jordan's position. The Jordanian position thus shifted from absolute support of Bashar al-Assad's regime to giving him the opportunity to complete his current presidential term and holding presidential elections, followed by a peaceful transfer of power, with emphasis on refusing to support the opposition or taking part in any military action against the regime's army.²²⁹

Third, support for the political opposition after the withdrawal of Russian troops from the Syrian territories, and intensive meetings between the Russian and American sides about the fate of Al-Assad and the search for a peaceful transfer of power that ensured the participation of all parties. Jordan policy was it is better to go back another step than to declare its willingness to support the civil opposition politically, in the face of extremist

²²⁸ Aljazeera. (2011, November 14). *Madha Baed Daawat Malik Al'urdun Al'asad Liltanhi?* [What After King Of Jordan Call Al-Assad To Step Down?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/news/reportsandinterviews/2011/11/14/ماذا-بعد-دعوة-ملك-الأردن-الأسد-للتنحي>

²²⁹ Ibid.

groups and militants²³⁰ from both sects, Sunnis and Shiite, within the sectarian rivalry between Saudi Arabia and Iran.²³¹

Fourth, the return to supporting the Russian position with all details of the future of Syria and the Assad regime, especially after Moscow gained power on land accompanied by the decline of the role of US in a way that opened the field for Russians to play solo without rivals.²³²

As a result, the Jordanian leadership recognized that the Syria's stand in the face of the opposition is not based on its own strength or on the weakness of the opposition, but on the nature of the regional and international forces that fear radical changes that do not serve their vital interests and dominate the Syrian scene after the fall of Assad. These interests controlled the path of political events inside Syria and outside it.²³³ So, it was a game of interests.

The transformation of the Jordanian position towards the Syrian crisis was affected heavily by the terrorist operations that the kingdom was exposed to. It was hit at the border with south Syria, being subjected to nearly six terrorist actions during 2016, mostly targeted at Jordanian soldiers and civilians. The most prominent of these incidents were:²³⁴

²³⁰ Mahmoud, Kh. Waleed. (2013, September 10). 'Ayn Yaqif Al'urdunu Min Mujrayat Al'azmat Alsuwria? [Where Does Jordan Stand In The Course Of The Syrian Crisis?] Retrieved from <http://www.aljazeera.net/knowledgegate/opinions/2013/9/10/أين-يقف-الأردن-من-مجريات-الأزمة-السورية/>

²³¹ Abdo, G. (2017). *The New Sectarianism: The Arab Uprisings And The Rebirth Of The Shi'a-Sunni Divide*. Oxford University Press. p: 63.

²³² Alkhaleej Online. (2016, October 9). *Sahifat: Baed 'An Takhalat Ean Suria.. Ma Dawr 'Amrika Fi Alealam?* [A Newspaper: After Giving Up Syria, What Role America In The World?] Retrieved from <http://alkhaleejonline.net/articles/1475992470792779900/صحيفة-بعد-أن-تخلت-عن-سوريا-ما-دور-أمريكا-في-العالم/>

²³³ Ahmed, Hussain Mustafa. (2017). *Alsirae Fi Suriat Walquaa A'ilqlimiat Walduwalia (Draasat Tahliliat Wamustaqbalia)*. [The Conflict In Syria And The International – Regional Powers (An Analytic And Futurist Study)]. *Al-Austath Journal*. Vol. 2. No. 221. pp: 1-26. p: 22.

²³⁴ Anan, Emad. (2017, February 7). *Tahul Almawqif Al'urduniyu Hial Suria.. Limadha Alan?* [The Jordanian Attitude Shifting Towards Syria. Why Now?] Retrieved from <https://www.noonpost.org/content/16542>

1 – Karak attack (18 December 2016): gunmen attacked some of the security centers in Karak governorate in the south of the country, shot and then holed up inside the historical fortress of Karak. The operation against the attack resulted in killing 10 people including seven security men and a Canadian tourist, and injuring 28 others.

2 – Intelligence center (6 June 2016): a gunman attacked a Jordanian intelligence center near the Baqaa camp in the north of Amman; the attack killed five members of the intelligence.

3 – Al -Rukban camp (21 June 2016): explosion near the Al-Rukban refugee camp killed six Jordanian soldiers.

4 – Irbid cell (2 March 2016): a Jordanian officer and seven extremists were killed in an exchange of fire in Irbid, northern Jordan.

6.9 Changes in the Jordanian Political Discourse:

Since the burning of the Jordanian pilot by ISIS on 3 February 2015, Jordan reappeared with an unprecedented political and media discourse that varied from the previous neutral approach. In a report published by Al Quds Al Arabi, commenting on targeting of a Jordanian drone aircraft at sites belonging to ISIS in southern Syria, indicated this change. The Jordanian media used for the first time the term “Syrian Arab Army” instead of “the army of the regime”. The term indicated coordination and military cooperation between the two sides, Jordan and Syria.²³⁵

The Jordanian leadership took up various strategies to return to the Syrian scene. These strategies allowed the kingdom to put a foot in the circle of the crisis in order to preserve

²³⁵ Ibid.

its national security, and involved adoption of both, political and military, methods by the King of Jordan.

6.9.1 First: Political Strategy

After a long absence, Jordan returned to the negotiating platforms on the future of the Syrian crisis, where a number of experts from Jordan and the United Nations participated in the Astana meetings, to discuss ways out of the bloody quagmire and find a political solution to the crisis. Jordan's participated in the meetings under the auspices of the Russian-Turkish-Iranian Operations Committee to discuss several issues:²³⁶

1. To monitor the cessation of hostilities in Syria.
2. To establish measures to control and prevent violations of the ceasefire agreement.
3. To strengthen confidence between the Syrian government and the opposition.
4. To discuss the international aid issue, which was considered an implicit recognition of the situation on ground in Syria and the neighboring countries regarding the refugees in light of recent developments.

6.9.2 Second: Military Strategy

Jordan took advantage of the second anniversary of the burning of the Jordanian pilot, to present itself as one of the regional forces fighting terrorism and supporting the American-Russian approach to the elimination of the Islamic State. The Jordanian army said in a statement that the Royal Air Force fighter jets hit the positions of the ISIS in southern Syria.²³⁷ The statement added that “the fighters of the Royal Air Force, in the memory of

²³⁶ Al-Hayat Newspaper. (2016, December 30). *Khitatan Lilhali 'Amam Mufawadat Asatana* [Two Plans For A Solution To The Astana Negotiations]. Retrieved from <http://www.alhayat.com/article/799058/خطتان-للحل-أمام-مفاوضات-أستانة>

²³⁷ Al Arabiya. (2015, February 6). *Alardun: Silah Aljaw Yunafidh Darabat Li'ahdaf Muntakhabat L"Daesh"* [Jordan: Air Force Strikes For Elected Targets Of "ISIS"]. Retrieved from <https://www.alarabiya.net/ar/arab-and-world/2015/02/06/الأردن-سلاح-الجو-ينفذ-ضربات-لأهداف-منتخبة-ل-داعش>

our martyrs who died in our war against terrorism, destroyed different targets” occupied by ISIS in the south of Syria, including a military site. The Jordanian army added that the air raid destroyed ammunition depots and a warehouse used to modify and improvise the vehicles and barracks of ISIS members, using unmanned drones and smart guided bombs. The operation resulted in the killing and wounding of several members of the terrorist group and the destruction of a number of vehicles. Jordanian aircrafts proved to be capable of reaching the Syrian depth.²³⁸

The attacks of the Jordanian army on ISIS in the Syrian south were not commented on by Assad’s regime. This was interpreted as an implicit approval of such operations and led analysts to speculate on the military intelligence cooperation between the Jordanian army and the regime's army in Syria²³⁹ in an unprecedented shifting. The new operations of the Jordanian Army were considered a clear and direct translation of Jordan’s political position.

The importance of King Abdullah II's visit to Russia came after the Syria and its allies won the Battle of Aleppo in 2016, and then moved to Astana. In addition, it coincided with the concentration of combat operations in Syria on the removal of terrorist groups outside

²³⁸ Sputnik News. (2016, January 16). *Jordan Establishes Joint War Room With Russia To Combat Daesh*. Retrieved from <https://sputniknews.com/middleeast/201601161033229615-jordan-russia-war-room/>

²³⁹ Maraqa, Farah. (2016, December 31). *Qayid Aljaysh Al'urduniyi Fi 'Itlatatih Al'uwlaa Yahdhar Min Hizam Bryin Yasil 'Tiran Balubnan.. Wayuakid 'Ana Alkhatar Alwahid Ealaa Biladih Min Alkhilaya Alnaayimat Fi "Alrukban Walhadalata" Wayuqalil Min 'Aedad Al'urduniyyn Bayn Sufuf "Daesh" Wafath Alsham.. Waltansiq Qayim Mae Alnizam Alsuwrii Eabr "Dbat Artibat"*. [The Commander Of The Jordanian Army In His First Appearance Warns Of A Land Belt Linking Iran With Lebanon. He Stresses That The Only Danger To His Country Of Sleeper Cells In The "Al-Rukban And Hadlat" And Reduces The Number Of Jordanians Among "ISIS" And Fateh Of The Levant. There Is Coordination With The Syrian Regime Through "Liaison Officers"]. Retrieved from <https://www.raialyoum.com/index.php/قائد-الجيش-الأردني-في-إطلالته-الأولى-ي->

Syrian territory, which would have repercussions for Jordan in areas close to Syrian south.²⁴⁰

As a result of the situation on the battlefield in Syria, it became necessary to initiate Jordanian-Russian coordination to ensure the continuity of channels of communication with the Syrian government. There is nothing that prevents any country today to engage in the experience of re-positioning in relation to alliances and external relations.²⁴¹ Jordan connections with Russia sought to pre-empt events and coordination with the Russians, to manage the security situation in southern Syria to prevent the movement of any armed elements belonging to the jihadi groups into Jordan.

A justification for the motives of Jordanian leaders for the transformation is that the kingdom is in dire need to diversify its options to ensure its security and address its economic problems. Through the new moves led by Russia in the Syrian arena, Jordan seeks to find a key role, in light of the weakness of the American role²⁴² since the administration of Barack Obama and the expected directions of the new President Donald Trump. The American policy failed to control things in Syria; consequently, propelling Jordanian-Russian coordination and activity on issues related to Syria in 2016.

²⁴⁰ Al-Fudelat, Mohammed. (2017, January 27). *Ziarat Malik Al'urdun 'Iilaa Rusia: Aineitafat Diblumasia?* [King Abdullah's Visit To Russia: A Diplomatic Turnaround?] Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/politics/2017/1/26/زيارة-ملك-الأردن-إلى-روسيا-انعطافة-دبلوماسية>

²⁴¹ Alalam News Network. (2017, February 6). *Al'urdun Taqsif Dawaeish Daraean Liaizhar Hasan Alniyat Tujah Dmshq! Ma Sira Altahawul Almfajy?* [Jordan Bombarded ISIS In Daraa To Show Goodwill Towards Damascus! What Is The Secret Of The Sudden Shift?] Retrieved from <http://www.alalam.ir/news/1921340>

²⁴² Jafra News. (2016). *Alealaqat Al'urduniyat Al'amrikiat Ealaa Safih Sakhin* [Jordanian-American Relations On A Hot Tin Roof]. Retrieved from <http://www.jfranews.com.jo/article-25361-العلاقات-الاردنية-الامريكية-على-صفيح-ساخن>

Jordan is concerned with its security and stability, given the many political and military instabilities especially in the areas adjacent to it. Jordan has become quite particular about communicating directly with political actors who hold the ability to impact these instabilities. The changing dynamics have led the Jordanian leadership to search for political and military partnership with Russia to face economic and security challenges on the one hand, and to maintain some point of contact with the Syrian regime to ensure security of its northern border on the other hand.²⁴³

6.10 Conclusion:

This chapter showed that the Jordanian foreign policy was very careful in dealing with the components and consequences of the Syrian crisis. Jordan adopted policies that were seen as adequate by the Jordanian leadership. The changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations compelled the Jordanian policy to move gradually from easy steps to more difficult procedures.

The Jordanian diplomacy's position on the crisis was leaning towards establishing unity of the Syrian territories with no intervention issues; no resettlement for the Syrian refugees; prioritizing the Jordanian interests; supporting the Syrian peace process; no intentions of engaging in military intervention unless necessary and still limited as Jordan's national security and stability were red lines; no efforts to dethrone the Syrian rule; stopping fights and violence immediately; not bearing the burden of Syrian refugees alone; and following international laws regarding receiving the refugees.

²⁴³ Al-Fudelat, Mohammed. (2017, January 27). *Ziarat Malik Al'urdun 'Iilaa Rusia: Aineitafat Diblumasia?* [King Abdullah's Visit To Russia: A Diplomatic Turnaround?] Retrieved from <https://www.alaraby.co.uk/politics/2017/1/26/زيارة-ملك-الأردن-إلى-روسيا-انعطافة-دبلوماسية>

Originally the Jordanian community came across economic and social obstacles to its development. It had previously been hit four times by waves of refugees—two from Palestine and two from the Iraq war. The Jordanian leadership led by King Abdullah II set up a program for the kingdom's development, which was based on initiating economic cooperation with potential partners in Europe, the US, and other countries.

The Syrian crisis affected the Jordanian state externally as well as internally. However, the complexity of the Jordanian-Syrian relations does not arise only from the conflict in Syria, but also from other major factors. The regional and international superpowers played a major role in forming the Jordanian position and policies in the context of the Syrian crisis. So Jordan's position and policy towards the Syrian crisis, and their factors and consequences had several levels.

With respect to the Syrian refugees and the economic consequences brought on by them, Jordan declared that it will not bear the responsibilities and burdens of hosting refugees alone. The kingdom's poor resources were not enough for the Jordanians themselves, and the economy was growing slowly even with the help of external aid. Further, the external assistance, financial and military, were conditioned on the influence of the parties extending such assistance. The Jordanian government, with the help of international organizations – governmental and non-governmental – formulated response plans that tried to remedy these difficult situations.

The Jordanian response plans were comprehensive in dealing with all civil aspects of life, for both the hosting communities and for the Syrian refugees in camps and in rural areas through Jordan. The continuation of response plans demanded more and more funds to cover the needs in 12 civil fields: education, energy, environment, food security, health,

justice, livelihood, local governance and municipal affairs, shelter, social protection, transport, and wash. These 12 sectors form the elements of Jordan's economy and social life. The Jordanian authorities demanded the international community to stand for its duties and responsibilities – morally and financially – before the Syrian refugee influx into Jordan. The major changes that occurred in the Jordanian communities due to the influx affected the public budget which came under huge pressure because of gradual public expenditures.

The Jordanian government put efforts to secure a decent life for Jordanian citizens, prioritizing it over everything. The development projects were directed towards the vulnerable hosting communities, especially infrastructure projects encompassing water, healthcare, and education. At the same time, the government prevented the Syrians from working 19 specific jobs, and by introducing permits, allowed them to work in sectors such as agriculture, that the Jordanian did not work in. The reason was that the growing unemployment as skillful Syrian workers took up more opportunities, agreeing to work for lesser wages than the Jordanians.

Jordan's relationship with the Syrian opposition was carefully handled. Semi adaptation of the Western characterization of opposition parties made Jordan pick the suitable parties against its main opponent in Syria, ISIS. The Free Army and other tribal small armies were hosted in the Jordanian territories, trained and equipped from Jordan and its allies, and then sent back to fight back ISIS, and the target of Jordan was to protect its northern and eastern borders.

As for the security policies, the Jordanian government established two levels. The internal level of security for Jordan's territories and the external level which dealt with military

means. Internally, the government kept fluctuating in imposing security means. The rise of crime rate in Jordan because of Syrian refugee presence led the government to act firmly with the Syrians, especially with those who indicated danger and were not welcome from the perspective of security agencies. These policies translated into procedures such as refoulement, movement restrictions, and no access to education and healthcare services, in addition to a list of jobs that they were not allowed to occupy.

Rising terrorism brought about a significant shift in the danger of terrorist attacks with growing threats till 2016. This maximized the internal risk of threats as Jordanian militants were likely to return to their country after a crackdown on the Islamic State and other terrorist groups in Syria and Iraq. In order to face the internal threats of terrorism, the government put in place various measures to curb extremism and prevent the entry of extremists, as well as to censor social networks and develop programs to counter ministries and institutions involved in communication and financing of terrorism and money laundering. These actions aimed to provide the community immunity against extremist ideology and encourage the citizens to listen to moderate Islamic discourse, which was enlightened and balanced and reflected the reality of Islam. The government, also, passed modified laws to limit the threats of terrorism.

Externally, the Jordanian army practiced military operations against ISIS in Syria. Jordan managed to frustrate and hit several terrorist cells, some of which were planning to carry out their operations in Jordan. The Jordanian military operations mainly focused on the northern and eastern borders of the kingdom. As Jordan became a member of the international coalition to combat ISIS in 2014, the Jordanian Air Force launched air raids on ISIS sites. These raid were carried out with full coordination with the Syrian government and its allies, and this is what the MOC center did in Amman.

Politically, Jordan changed its position towards the Syrian crisis. The changing dynamics on ground made Jordan act towards its own interests. The Jordanian leadership kept contact with the Syrian government, and the kingdom adopted a policy that kept its relations with both, the US and Russia, balanced. This balanced policy enabled Jordan to maneuver to retain its internal stability in areas that were troubled with popular revolutions, and the impacts of economic, demographic, social, and security problems. As a result of the change in Jordan's policy towards the crisis, the Jordanian leadership became closer to its main ally in this regard, Russia on account of promises of economic and security assistance.

Chapter Six

Conclusion

Chapter Six: Conclusion

7.1 An Overall Summary:

The thesis attempted to explore the variables that affected and ruled the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis during 2011-2016 by clarifying and analyzing the internal and external factors that resulted from internal, regional, and international interactions regarding the Syrian conflict. The complex network of political, economic, and security relations and interests at domestic, regional, and international levels convinced the Jordanian decision makers to adopt the best, safest, and secure policies from the Jordanian perspective, to maintain, guarantee, and achieve national interests in the face of various threats or opportunities resulting from the Syrian conflict. As Jordan has many strategic, geopolitical, ideological, and geo-economic ties in the West Asia region which passed through a transitional stage, any fundamental change in the Jordanian policy taken by the political leadership would bring resounding strategic, geopolitical, balance of power, ideological, and geo-economic implications for all parties involved. Jordan's dealing with the Syrian issue is closely connected to other important issue on other fronts including political, economic, cultural, societal, and security dimensions in all levels.

The chapters mainly concentrated on addressing the consequences of the Syrian refugees' presence in Jordan, as the kingdom received over 600 thousand registered refugees seeking asylum and other unregistred 700 thousand. The refugees' crisis had created negative impacts on political, economic, social, and security fronts but did not cause a societal fragmentation like what happened in Syria. Security threats rose on account of the chaotic environment caused by the Syrian crisis and helped in the rise and strengthening of fundamental terrorism represented by the ISIS. The political developments at the regional

and international levels also influence policy decision-making, as the issue had direct implications for Jordan's relations with its surrounding environment, and its alliances with regional as well as international powers.

Through this thesis, I was able to achieve the five objectives outlined at the beginning of this research process:

The first objective was to define the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy through chapter two, which showed that the internal determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy were its geographic location, population, social structure, economy, natural resources, military power, public opinion, political system, leadership, and the personalities of leaders. Each of these determinants had a significant impact on Jordan's external policy. Geographically, Jordan is a landlocked area, poor with natural resources and water, and with very limited access to the Red Sea it shares its borders with countries that have the same ethnographic factors such as religion, language, and history. These factors made it difficult for the government to achieve sustainable economic development as Jordan depends on external aid for economic and military purposes, in addition to the high cost of energy that burdens the public budget driving up inflation, poverty, and unemployment. Jordan's population size and social structure is formed by the original inhabitants, that is the Trans-Jordanians, and the successive waves of refugees from Palestine, Iraq, Syria, and other Arab states.

The Jordanian political system gives the King exclusive authority of decision-making and controlling the foreign policy, even though there are six institutions that are authorized constitutionally to deal with foreign policy issues. These six institutions can be classified as: the King, who is the primary authority, and secondary institutions including the Royal

Court, the Cabinet, the Parliament, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and Expatriates Affairs, and the Security Institution.

The external determinants of Jordan's foreign policy are interrelated and interdependent. Jordan's interactions via its 53 diplomatic missions, its membership of 62 organizations, and the alliance policy in the international order, together affect the decision-making and implementation of Jordan's foreign policy.

The third chapter was focused on achieving the second objective, which was to elucidate the history of the Jordanian-Syrian relationship and the factors that affect this bilateral relationship. The Jordanian-Syrian relations were hit with waves of imbalance resulting in fluctuations between excellent, good, lukewarm, and bad associations. The main factor responsible for this imbalance in bilateral relations was the difference in ideologies as Syrian is pro-Russia whereas Jordan is pro-US; King Hussein and Hafiz Al-Assad were not on the same side. The new leaderships under of King Abdullah II and Bashar Al-Assad tried to have a peaceful political era, but things did not go well as they were still at different sides when it came to the great powers. The changing dynamics in the region because of the Syrian crisis, pushed the two countries into another phase of unstable relations but which did not reach military escalations.

In regards to the Syrian crisis, Jordan did not express its interests clearly about its final position on the Syrian crisis, but repeated its concerns on the unstable surrounding environment, the war in Syria and chaos in Iraq, in addition to the mysterious path to the peace process. Jordan chose the model of "moderation" to deal with utmost caution with what was happening in Syria, as a precaution in dealing with what was happening on the

kingdom's territory due to movements inspired by the Arab Spring despite all local justifications.

Jordan's relationships with the US and the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia were the strongest. The policy of alliances with Arab nations and its results, in addition to the positions and policies of the great powers and the allied parties in the region, were determinants for Jordan's foreign policy and influenced decision-making. Further, the scarcity of economic resources in Jordan plays an important role in shaping its foreign policy as it is always in need of assistance from abroad, which had been received continuously and without interruption.

With its foreign policy, Jordan pursued an approach that may have been difficult to deal with but was essential. It kept clear of sensitizing neighboring countries. In every action, this difficult process had to be carried out and a balance had to be struck between its neighboring countries and the regional and international environments.

The relationship with Israel is seen, despite the existence of a treaty, as a cessation of hostilities rather than a peace process. Jordan is always aware of the ongoing negotiations between the Palestinians and the Israelis to reach a final solution, with the permanent call to end the conflict by peaceful means.

The third and the fourth objectives were analyzing the Syrian crisis and its implications for Jordan and examining the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis. Chapter four discussed how the Syrian refugee influx into Jordan adversely affected the kingdom, raising its population by at least 13%. Most vulnerable people in Jordan were affected by the presence of Syrian refugees. Public services in the kingdom suffered great pressures, so much so, that Jordan declared that it would not take on the burdens of the refugees at

the expense of its national interests and the Jordanian people. Syrians affected the political system, economy, education, energy, environment, health, justice, livelihood and food security, local governance and municipalities, shelter, social protection, transport, wash, and security. As for the concerns of Syrian refugees' settlement in Jordan, the Jordanian government confirmed that the possibility was absolutely unthinkable.

In general, despite the small advantages from the Syrian refugees' presence, the largest cost to the Jordanian economy was the increase of Syrians in the local labor market, in addition to the pressure exerted on the infrastructure and public services that needed large investments to improve them. The external aid was provided in both directions, to help the Syrians living in Jordan on the one hand and to help the host Jordanian communities on the other.

The fifth objective was to examine the changes in the Jordanian policy vis-à-vis the Syrian crisis, discussed in chapter five. The changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations led to a gradual shift in the Jordanian policy from easy to stringent. The Jordanian-Syrian relations had been exposed to various variables that affected it sharply. The complexity of the Jordanian-Syrian relations came not only from the conflict in Syria, but also due to other factors in play, controlled by the policies of regional and international great powers which played a major role in formulation of the Jordanian position and policies.

The Jordanian response plans (JRPSC) were comprehensive in dealing with all civil aspects, but demanded more and more fund to cover the needs in the chosen 12 civil fields: education, energy, environment, food security, health, justice, livelihood, local governance and municipal affairs, shelter, social protection, transport, and wash.

Internally, the government imposed security means to secure its citizens. The rise of terrorist attacks and crime rate in Jordan was related to the Syrian refugees' presence and the government established several policies in that regard, including closing borders, refoulement, movement restrictions, and limited access to education and healthcare services, in addition to a list of jobs that Syrians were not allowed to occupy. Externally, the Jordanian army practiced military operations against ISIS in Syria, by joining the international coalition to combat ISIS and hosted the MOC center for military operations and exchange of intelligence data.

Politically, Jordanian changed its position towards the Syrian crisis because of the changing dynamics on ground and the Jordanian leadership kept a window of contact with the Syrian government despite evicting the Syrian ambassador in 2014. Jordan adopted a balanced policy between the US and Russia regarding its attitude towards the Syrian crisis. This balanced policy enabled Jordan to maneuver to retain internal stability in areas which were troubled with popular revolutions and economic, demographic, social, and terrorism impacts. The Jordanian leadership became more close to the main Syrian ally, Russia, as a result of the change in the battlefields in Syria. The association was based also on the economic assistance promised by the Russian side, but was still executed within the boundaries of freedom given to Jordan by the US.

7.2 Major Findings:

This thesis aimed to explain the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis during 2011–2016. Despite limitations, the respective chapters concentrated on defining the determinants of the Jordanian foreign policy, elucidating the history of the Jordanian-Syrian relations and the factors that affect this bilateral relationship, analyzing the Syrian

crisis and its implications for Jordan, and examining the Jordanian policy vis-à-vis the Syrian crisis.

The chapters also specified domestic, regional, and international factors and actors, including state and non-state actors, and their influence on the formulation of Jordan's internal and external policies toward the Syrian crisis. The complex network of domestic, regional, and international relations, and the changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relationship directed the Jordanian decision making authorities regarding all issues connected to the Syrian crisis.

Based on various chapter discussions, the objectives of the Jordanian policy regarding the Syrian crisis can be summarized as:

1. Maintaining Jordan's national security and internal stability through strategies based on the policy of alliance, and not to get involved in the conflict militarily without unjustified causes.
2. Fundraising internationally to help Jordan successfully host Syrian refugees and also help the government in implementing various response plans to achieve reform and recovery for the Jordanian economy while helping the Syrian refugees and the vulnerable hosting communities.
3. Fighting the terrorist organizations that form threats to Jordan through limited military interventions and as part of the international coalition.
4. Supporting the Syrian peace process and keeping the unity of the Syrian territories.

The thesis found that Jordan's policy regarding the Syrian crisis underwent some major changes between 2011 and 2016. The Syrian crisis, as it lasted for more than six years, affected the West Asia region during this period. The chain of changes which reached Syria

was originally initiated by the outbreak of the Arab Spring revolutions that started in Tunisia at the end of 2010, followed by the popular revolutions in Egypt, Libya, and Yemen.

Jordan's relationship with the Syrian opposition was carefully calculated. Semi adoption of the Western characterization of opposition parties made Jordan pick the suitable parties against its main opponent in Syria, the ISIS. The Free Army and other small tribal armies were hosted in the Jordanian territories, trained and equipped by Jordan and its allies, and then sent back to fight ISIS and so Jordan could protect its northern and eastern borders.

At the core of the political decision-making process of the Jordanian leadership was one goal- to preserve Jordan's highest national interest. This approach adopted by the Jordanian decision-makers resembled "Realism" which had dominated the leaderships of Jordan's international relations since the end of the World War II. So the decisions were meant to preserve the Jordanian political system, secure the state from various internal and external threats, achieve economic prosperity by natural growth and development of various sectors of the national economy, and preserve national identity and values. The policies that led to accomplishing the highest national interest came as a result of interaction of three variables:

First: The manifestations of the Syrian crisis implications on the internal environment of Jordan. The Jordanian society was originally crawling economically and facing failures of development processes initiated by the successive governments. Hence, it was not ready to absorb the huge number of people that had fled the torn of war in Syria causing 13% of sudden population growth in Jordan. The International Monetary Fund reports confirmed deficits in the natural growth of the Jordanian economy as the presence of Syrian refugees created pressures on basic services like education, energy, environment, healthcare, justice,

livelihood and food security, local governance and municipalities, shelter, social protection, transport, wash, and security. The Treasury encountered a loss in tax revenues due to Syrian asylum. The growing governmental spending to cope with the crisis caused a deficit in the state's public budget. This caused a delay in implementing the economic programs of Jordan, but the IMF gave Jordan leeway on these programs to help it endure the implications of the Syrian crisis better. Even the rate of unemployment (18.2%) was at its highest. Refugee presence increased the depletion of resources without any economic benefits. The Jordanian leadership and the government found themselves facing political, economic, social, and security challenges. Complaints were coming from both groups, the host communities and the Syrian refugees. In reaction, the Jordanian government, with the help of international community organization which provided 30% of the allocated funds, especially the United Nations, built response plans to the Syrian crisis as detailed in chapter four. Responding to the Syrian crisis implications exhausted the public budget by billions of dollars, to the extent that the government was forced to adopt new and harsh policies in politics, economic, and security aspects. The increasing demand for funds stimulated Jordan to follow new economic policies to meet the pressure on public services. Also, the government tried to ease the problem by signing an agreement with the EU, to create 200 thousand jobs for the Syrians in the kingdom taking advantage of the EU's attempt to convince them not to immigrate to Europe, in addition to giving the Syrians permits to work in specific jobs. The Jordanian government put enormous efforts to raise fund and introduce new security procedures to avoid and control probable security implications; these measures included regulating the movement of refugees, deporting them, and closing the borders to newcomers.

The security threat implications for Jordan were formed by internal and external factors connected firmly to the Syrian conflict. The Jordanian authorities took a balanced approach towards the security and the humanitarian needs. The military actions and procedures reflected policies followed by the Jordanian government in order to face the dangers that had emerged in its land, and in the southern and eastern borders between the kingdom and Syria. Jordan joined the international coalition to combat the Islamic State in Syria, which was a vital contribution of Jordan to fighting terrorist groups.

At the domestic level, these procedures were meant to avoid and combat terrorism hidden in sleeper cells that had come back from Syria and Iraq or that had managed to merge among Syrian refugees in camps and other urban areas. The terrorist attacks from 2014 till 2016 urged the government to draw comprehensive plans at multi social levels and security institutions in its efforts to combat terrorism through enlightenment, awareness, and security procedures.

Second: The change of political attitudes in countries surrounding Jordan because of the changes in leadership and their priorities in terms of foreign policies, especially when in cases where they were ideologically different from the previous leadership. Instability or elections resulted in establishment of new people in command in the regional countries around Jordan. As for Syria, the instability created full chaos in the Syrian state composed of weak government, with the presence of a huge number militant groups with opposition or against the regime or the Islamic State, military forces of regional countries such as Turkey and Iran, and Russia and its actions. Militant groups in the opposition were administrated by regional money from Israel, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, and Iran, in addition to smuggled weapons. Each regional power had its own political agenda in Syria and the

country had to deal with its own militants, all of which was governed by alliances with the US and Russia.

Amidst the tumultuous environment in Syria, Jordan sought to maintain a balancing point regarding its interests in relations with the Syrian state, the Syrian opposition, and the needs of allied countries. It is hard for a country the size of Jordan to sacrifice its economic interest built through the years. In the end, Jordan took a pragmatic policy politically, economically, and militarily.

Third: The emergence of new policies at international level in the West Asia region required changes in Jordan policies towards outside environments as well. The interaction of the complex networks of politics, economy, military and sectarian interests among regional countries and the great powers created the emergence of new policies and attitude specifically regarding the Syrian crisis. Russia and the US were back to the old cold war in politics, economy, and security policies which formed clear and direct threats and opportunities for the Jordanian state. The escalation of the international players' roles in the crisis indicated that the resolution of the conflict in Syria was no longer a matter of Syria or the UN alone, and would have to be resolved through international and regional cooperation. The conflict in Syria presented a historic opportunity for the US and the Western countries, and regional states like Israel, to end Iran's influence in the region. Thus, Jordan reprioritized its interests and followed new policies in order to align itself with the situation.

The effects of the Syrian conflict were wide-ranging. For Jordan, the consequences looked bleak regardless of whether the Assad regime fell or retained power. Growing challenges pushed the Jordanian leadership to adopt policies that did not put Jordan's national interest

at stake, even though sometimes foreign policy of the state was required to be offensive; political decisions for external expansion were limited by internal determinants and balances with regional and great powers, as Jordan wanted a privileged position to fortify itself by force, along with the ability to impose its wills in defense of its security and economic interests rather than aggression against other states.

So, the contemporary domestic, regional, and international changes in policy, economy, and security environments influenced the Jordanian policies towards the Syrian crisis, resulting in pragmatic policies based on achieving the highest interest of the kingdom.

By the end of 2016 Jordan had starting re-calculating its accounts of the Syrian crisis due to two main reasons in the international dimension. The successful Russian military intervention in Syria starting from September 2015 till the end of the year 2016. This military intervention turned the balance of power on the battlefields in Syria and this has provided great support to the Syrian government against the rebels from all sides. The American policy to retreat from its role in Syria since the American administration did not want to be involved in a new war in the Middle East.

The American policy would be followed by the majority of its allies in the region where Jordan is one of them. These two reasons gave the Jordanian leadership the thinking of a new stage would be in Syria of the end of the Syrian conflict by full dominance of the Syrian government on the Syrian land with a satisfying peace settlement- officially and keeping the unity of the Syrian territories supported by Jordan- satisfies all parts and guarantees the dominance of the Syrian government to regain its previous position in the Arab world especially in the Arab League. This motivates the thinking of political of the return of diplomatic relations between Jordan and Syria on new bases through Russian

mediation where Jordan would be able to change its stance for the favor of the Syrian government followed by procedures strengthening the policy.

The opportunity would be widely opened to the Syrian refugees to go back home their safe areas leading to relieve the Jordanian government from huge expenses for the favor of the Jordanian hosting communities as the Syrian crisis' implications exhausted the public budget by billions of dollars, to the extent that the government was forced to adopt new and harsh policies in politics, economic, and security aspects.

Economically, the chance to reconnect Jordan with Syria would be also very potent and there would be enormous economic advantages as there was an old economic interdependence between two countries.

7.3 Results in Regards of Hypotheses

The analysis leads to the following main conclusions regarding the three tested hypotheses to explain the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis during the period 2011-2016.

The first hypothesis was whether the security implications of the Syrian crisis pose an existential threat for Jordan. It was concluded that the security implications of the Syrian crisis had two levels: the internal security and terror threats and the external terrorism. Internally, the unknown Syrian refugees who might have been influenced by radicalization and terrorism, formed a source of fear for the Jordanian government. The rise of crime rate in Jordan due to the Syrian refugees' existence threatened the social stability in the country. Also noted were instances wherein a number of refugees had participated in violent actions in the country and had factional relations with a number of radical and terrorist organizations; these refugees represented a threat to the Jordanian society and to the authorities. Jordan recognized the risk that some Syrian refugees posed to their security,

economy, society, and even their culture. The internal security circumstances and efforts to combat terrorism inside Jordan were connected firmly to the external threats, mainly from Syria.

Based on the data collected by concerned military intelligence agencies on the battle ground in Syria, the great threat for Jordan came from extremist organizations in Syria. Jordan listed 160 terrorist organization and group, and the list was headed by organizations such as the ISIS, Al-Nusra Front, Al-Qaeda, Jaish al-Muhajireen wal-Ansar, Nour al-Din al-Zenki Movement, and Ahrar al-Sham. The greatest danger for Jordan was formed by the Islamic State that flourished in both Syria and Iraq. On the operational side, the environment for the success of the Islamic State was found on the Jordanian ground. There were indications that the Jordanian society –in some areas- had uncomfortable limited tendency towards supporting the State and the Islamist Jihadists and Salafist groups in Jordan were capable of flourishing easily among people because of several reasons that fueled discontent of people towards the government. This discontent was justified by the failure of successive governments in satisfying the people economically and politically.

The threats of ISIS to Jordan reached a dangerous level and the Jordanian government could not stand anymore in front of such threats, thus making combating terrorism a priority in 2015. The Islamic State threatened the Jordanian leadership with violent attacks if it did not let the fighters to Iraq and Syria pass through Jordan. What made it worse was that ISIS threatened to kill King Abdullah II himself, and to launch a series of suicide attacks inside Jordan, targeting intelligence agents in the kingdom. At the same time, the Islamic State did launch a number of terrorist attacks in Jordan through its sleeper cells. One such attack culminated into the burning of a Jordanian pilot by ISIS in February 2015.

The geopolitical logic of the Islamic State expansion in the northern and eastern borders of Jordan triggered military operations against it through the international coalition to combat ISIS. In addition to military operations, Jordan declared the northern and eastern borders of Jordan as closed military areas, to avoid approach of terrorist group fighters towards Jordan. Even after the defeat of ISIS in Syria and Iraq, the Jordanian authority feared the return of Jordanian fighters in ISIS and Al-Nusra Front and other terrorist groups. Naturally, those fighters would imitate sleeper cells taking actions at any time. Jordan's military actions against the ISIS came within its comprehensive strategy as part of its war against the Islamic State and other organizations. The Jordanian leadership worked to restore the Syrian government control over its territory, especially in the southern regions of Syria.

While the popular demonstrations that called for political and economic changes had been absorbed by the Jordanian governments, data suggests there were still chances of unrest. An example of that was the demonstration in support of ISIS that happened on 20 June 2014, in Ma'an city in south of Jordan. An important element was that the economy of Jordan was getting worse and people were grumbling, and so the internal environment could easily be led to take actions against the political system, as Jordan was in the middle of a troubled and unstable area.

Despite the threats of ISIS inside Syria next to Jordan's borders, the existence of Islamists inside Jordan whose thoughts and beliefs resembled the Salafists Jihadist groups, and the support of Muslim Brotherhood party, it is concluded that the security implications of the Syrian crisis did not pose an existential threat for Jordan. There are three reasons for this conclusion: The first is the environment in which ISIS came out from Syria or Iraq. The

two countries have their own special conditions, whether in politics or in religion; add to that the nature of the government that rules the state and what happened on the margins of conflicts there. In Jordan, the environment is not suitable to receive and encourage such phenomenon. The Jordanian environment as well as the Jordanian personality in general repel extremism and terrorism, practiced by ISIS in particular.

The second reason is that the expansion of ISIS and its presence in Syria and Iraq was linked to the violence of the regimes there and the collapse of the state or its failure to manage itself. Therefore, ISIS and other extremist organizations reacted to the brutality of the regimes and filled this vacuum as other parties also entered the arena, including those who contributed to financing and empowerment. The Jordanian state is not subject to such interventions and the system is characterized by moderation and no changes are expected in this regard in the foreseeable future.

The third reason relates to the geopolitical location of Jordan, which makes it different from the geopolitical environment in which ISIS emerged in Syria. The possibility of infiltration of members of the ISIS across the border is not possible and the possibility of smuggling fighters from abroad seems impossible too. The role played by Jordan in the war against terrorism and the intersection of interests and roles of the international coalition members, reflect the existence of regional and international will to keep it away from the circle of danger that ISIS represents.

The second hypothesis addressed the shift in the Jordanian foreign policy because of the changing in the overall regional environment. Since March 2011, the Syrian crisis has formed a clash point between regional countries and international regimes, and the crisis is no longer an internal crisis. Over the past decades, Jordan has established relations and

interests with countries involved in the ongoing conflict in Syria. Jordan did not escape from the regional instability, as the main regional countries including Turkey, Iran, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Israel, and Qatar, in addition to the great powers and Europe, had interfered heavily in the conflict. Thus, this whole system appears to be very interested in what is happening in Syria. Therefore, because of the strategic importance of the regional system in the Middle East, any changes and developments in surrounding countries affect Jordan as well. This has made the Jordanian foreign policy vulnerable to regional developments and it has to be constantly on the lookout for what is happening in the neighboring Arab and non-Arab countries.

The failure of the Syrian government to solve the crisis internally, while insisting on using security in suppressing the demonstrations, led to expansion of the conflict to international level. The Arab League then failed to solve it through Arab initiatives and the observers' mission. The prevailing extreme severity in the distribution of the regional alliances map and the complexity and contradictions of various regional agendas resulted in a marginalized role for Jordan. The international community looked at the role of Jordan, not as one of the leaders of the regional moderation camp, but rather as a disciplined member and a good and civilized state in a region full of bad regimes. But the reality of Jordan's role is totally in contrast to this perception. Jordan is trying to send messages to all that its positions and disciplined directions within the regional and international community should not be taken as mere acknowledged facts; Jordan continues to sit on the map of planning and policy guidance in the Middle East. It is in Jordan's highest interest to not get involved in playing a role in the swamp of the Syrian conflict. Jordan's foreign policy demands to see Jordan not just as a place to train the Syrian opposition militants efficiently

because Jordan has many outstanding interests in this conflict. In a very clear position to the regional policies of the Middle East countries, the Jordanian diplomacy does not have any interest in competing for the role of the various regional states such as Saudi finance or the Iranian influence. Jordan's foreign policy focuses on its role in planning the future of the conflict within certain limits. Thus, its interests have led it to act politically as a genuine part of the efforts of the regional political movement in this case.

Jordan is not interested in the disputes between regional countries involved in the Syrian scene such as Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Iran, and Israel; it is even committed to alliance policy. The changing regional politics, due to the emerging regional interference cycle, could not keep Jordan disconnected from the overall regional policies of the neighboring countries.

Saudi Arabia has always been a major competitor as a leader in the region because of its religious authority and control of oil, but it failed to play this role and was not affected by the uprisings in the Arab countries to a large extent, while seeking with the other GCC countries to include Jordan,¹ in addition to Morocco, to the system, in an attempt to strengthen the region's kingdoms to counter uprisings. The most important competition that defines the strategic landscape of the Middle East is between Iran and Saudi Arabia. It is true that the competition between these two countries is old, but it has gained great importance at the moment, especially with the attempts by Iran to impose itself as an influential regional power in the region at the expense of Saudi Arabia, especially in Syria, Iraq, Yemen, and Lebanon.

The regional powers in the Middle East are subject to changes and transformations not only because of the Syrian conflict but also because of other variables related to the economy. For example, Iran was strained by confrontation with Saddam Hussein in Iraq. Currently,

¹ Terrill, W. A. (2011). *The Saudi-Iranian Rivalry And The Future Of Middle East Security*. Army War Coll Strategic Studies Inst Carlisle Barracks PA. pp: 13-14.

it is considered a regional power practicing power freely in four Arab capitals: Baghdad, Damascus, Beirut, and Sanaa. The Turkish state, preoccupied for decades of internal construction, has been very open to the Middle East, especially in the last decade and particularly in the Syrian scene, and wants to restore the glory of the Ottoman Empire through the NATO membership and alliance with the US and balanced relationship with Israel.

The Syrian crisis, in its sixth year, continues to be adrift with some projects aimed at preserving the Syrian regime and others aimed at changing it. Each of these projects is represented by a major regional player in the Syrian arena. Turkey wanted to topple the regime of Bashar al-Assad, so it supports the opposition and the armed groups operating on the ground, receives them on its territory and provides them with sufficient support; its strategic depth in the Middle East is through Syria, the strategic ally of Iran which is Turkey's most important strategic balance in controlling the region. There is also a clear competition and a hidden conflict between Turkey and its allies on the one hand and Iran and its allies on the other.

The projects to maintain the Syrian rule, regionally, are controlled by Iran because it represents an extension of its strategy to dominate the region. Iran is known to have supported or pretended to support the “Arab Spring” in the Arab region, from Tunisia to Egypt and Yemen to Bahrain, but the situation changed when the change came to Syria. The Iranian regime is well aware that if the Syrian regime falls; it will be a serious challenge to Iran's regional expansionist policy. So Iran is doing its best to abort change in Syria. It supports the regime with fighters as well as logistical support. The fall of the Syrian state means cutting Iran's regional ties in the region.

The Syrian regime is an ally of Iran, the Iraqi regime, as well as Hezbollah in Lebanon. Syria is a strategic bridge for Iran's regional project, linking Tehran with its allies in the region, including some groups that have met its interests with Iran in Palestine and threatening Israel. Therefore, any change in Syria will impact Iran internally and consequently Iran's regional project.

Saudi Arabia and Turkey had agreed to coordinate the political and field efforts in the Syrian conflict. This coordination was not found between 2011 and 2015, and eventually the understanding between the two regional states ended the points of disagreement between them. It also resulted in an agreement regarding the dominance over the Syrian opposition abroad at the hands of Riyadh. As for the situation on the ground, the agreement resulted in a consensus between the armed factions sponsored by Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and Qatar. In simple words, the Syrian conflict became an arena for the regional conflicts between Saudi Arabia and Turkey vs. Iran, where each of them was supported by a great power.

Jordan, which seeks to maintain balance in its relations with rivals in the Syrian dilemma, found itself in a state of imbalance. The kingdom struggled to strengthen its political and economic relations with the countries of the world, and to exchange official visits with different countries. In order to achieve its goals, Jordan adopted the policy of regional alliances within the Arab-Arab and regional frames. The Jordanian-Gulf alliance, led by Saudi Arabia, is the really where Jordan's foreign policy is based. The Jordanian-Saudi relationship is closely related to economic determinants that Jordan needs, in addition to being within the Western alliance system. Jordan changed its foreign policy by hosting the MOC Center and joining the Saudi-led Islamic alliance against the Houthis in Yemen. Jordan's sense of isolation and the threat to its interests have

always led it to direct its regional policy towards more alliances with the stronger and closer states especially with regard to economic factors, by providing financial and military assistance and political support.

The third hypothesis addressed how the Jordanian foreign policy is acquiring new dimensions in the backdrop of changing international relations in West Asia. The West Asia region is undergoing a period of revolutionary change, making it an open field for foreign policies of the great powers and all the regional countries in its orbit as well as the European countries. This new environment has imposed challenges on a number of small and regional states regarding protection of their national interests. The Jordanian leadership is convinced that the solution to the Syrian crisis lies in a political solution by an agreement between the Syrians. The changing dynamics of the Jordanian-Syrian relations took the Jordanian policy gradually from easy to hard steps and procedures. The Jordanian political position towards the Syrian crisis is characterized by neutrality and openness to all parties without exception, which prevented Jordan from entering the Syrian war. The US, Russia, Turkey, Iran, Saudi Arabia, Israel and Qatar are the major actors in the Syrian crisis, while Jordan is associated with strong political and economic relations which allowed Jordan to receive 1.3 million Syrians.

The failure of the Syrian state in managing the crisis, transformed it first into a regional and then into an international crisis, polarized by great powers that sought to achieve their strategic interests at the expense of both parties by making Syria an open arena for them and providing military support to both sides of the crisis. The inability of the regional system to contain the crisis made Syria to get out from the Arab arena, especially after the use of the four veto by Russia and China in the Security Council, used against the second

Arab initiative. This reflects the weakness and exposure of the Arab system and its role in resolving the crisis. The entrance of great powers led to a change in the mapping of regional and international alliances to create an appropriate environment for dealing with political transformations according to the balance of major countries, and the traditional alliances were affected by a lot of changes. So, the regional and international great powers' policies played a major role in forming the Jordanian position and policies regarding Jordan's relation with Syria in the context of the Syrian crisis.

Jordan changed its position towards the Syrian crisis. The changing dynamics of international positions made the Jordanian stance to move for its favor. The Jordanian leadership kept a way of contact with the Syrian government and adopted a balanced policy between the US and Russia regarding its attitude toward the Syrian crisis. This balanced policy enabled Jordan to maneuver to retain its internal stability in an area troubled with popular revolutions and economic, demographic, social, and terrorism issues. The Jordanian leadership became more close to the main Syrian ally, Russia, as a result of the change in the battlefields in Syria by the by successful military intervention at least by the end of year 2016. The association is connected to economic assistance and promises given from the Russian side. Such cooperation from Jordan with both, the US and Russia, fit the Jordanian interests well. Jordan continued cooperation with the US and its Gulf allies, alongside Russia and its allies, due to three main reasons. First, the retreat of the American role in Syria. Second, the ISIS threats to Jordan. Third, the advancement of military achievement of the Syrian government under the flag of Russian forces.

The retreat of the American role in Syria since Washington did not want to be involved in a new war in the Middle East, despite the readiness of the US military to implement the

decisions of the President in the interests of national security. There was an opposition in the US Congress for the possible strike that Barack Obama wanted to direct to Syria, especially after the suffering of the Americans in the Iraq war and before that the Afghan war. As the Obama administration had inherited the costs of Bush's reckless administration in the Middle East, Obama had no choice but to work on structuring and shaping US foreign policy within available limits to the extent possible, to maintain the American prestige and influence in the region and take advantage of the ongoing events in light of the worsening of the Syrian crisis. With the climate of instability that hit Libya and the ongoing war in Yemen, and political instability in Egypt, Obama hoped to retain America's Gulf allies that had considerable influence in the region, not to mention the prosperity of the Gulf given that they account for nearly 50% of the world's oil supply.

The second reason for the decline in American influence was Washington's loss of its Arab allies in the Middle East, evident during the Arab Spring revolutions that overthrew its allied regimes such as Ben Ali in Tunisia, Mubarak in Egypt, and Ali Abdullah Saleh in Yemen. Despite the fact that the Arab kings in Jordan and Saudi Arabia continued their alliance with Washington, there were great problems between these countries and America's foreign policy which dictated America's position on the Palestinian issue and not taking a hard line from Israel. For a half of a century America may find itself without a real Arab partner, apart from the kingdoms, the Gulf States, and Israel.

The third reason for decline in America's role was the growing strength of Israel, and its independence that it enjoyed as a result of continued Western support in the face of Arab deficit. This made Israel the most powerful and secure state in the region ever. If Israel

acted unilaterally and wanted to launch a military strike against Syria or Iran, that would be proof of Washington's inability to exploit its influence in the region.

The fourth reason was the Russian-Turkish cooperation against the American influence in Syria in particular, and the Middle East in general. Russia and Turkey have systematically excluded the US from preparing and participating in events in Syria. The US could either demand a seat at the table for shaping negotiations or concede diplomacy to Russia and Turkey, meaning they will act in their own national interests to the detriment of Syrians. Turkey's rearrangement with Russia also had an economic cost; siding with the Russians would indeed postpone Turkey's EU membership.

The emergence of ISIS threats stimulated the Jordanian leadership to act instantly. Rising terrorism maximized the risk of threats as Jordanian militants were more likely to return to their country, with a crackdown on the Islamic State and other terrorist groups in Syria and Iraq. The Jordanian army practiced military operations against ISIS in Syria and consequently managed to frustrate and hit several terrorist cells, some of which planned to carry out operations in Jordan. The Jordanian military operations focused mainly on the northern and eastern borders. As Jordan became a member of the international coalition to combat ISIS in 2014, the Jordanian Air Force launched air raids on ISIS sites. These raids were carried out with full coordination from the Syrian government and its allies, and this is what the MOC center in Amman was meant for.

The effective Russian military intervention in October 2015 turned the table on all actors in the Syrian conflict. After five years of fierce battle between the armed revolutionary opposition supported by Turkey, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and the US, and the army of the Syrian government supported by Iran and Russia, there were moments of victories and

mutual defeats between the parties. In light of this multi-dimensional clash Moscow succeeded in becoming the main actor of all. Continuous victories prompted everyone to declare the desire to negotiate about the future of the Syrian crisis, especially after the crisis faced by Saudi Arabia in Yemen. At the same time, Ankara was handling the consequences of the failed coup attempt, in addition to the multiplicity of fronts in front of the US in Iraq, Afghanistan, and Libya. Russia maintained superiority in Syria with the use of advanced weapon, giving a direct message to all parties that Russia will not hesitate to use all its sophisticated weapons to achieve its objectives through this war. Russia's success in the fight against terrorism was the thing that put Moscow on the international map to combat terrorism. The Russian administration's success in crisis management by exploiting its presence as a permanent member of the UN Security Council, allowed it to hold a more influential position and role in the crisis, as compared to other regional countries such as Iran, Saudi Arabia, Qatar and Turkey. Also, the Russian leadership took advantage of the mistakes made by the US policy in the Middle East that helped create the atmosphere for the new Russian policy (especially in light of the American failure to manage issues in Iraq) for dealing with the Muslim Brotherhood in Egypt and filling the vacuum made by the American retreat via its policy of alliance with Syria and Iraq and cooperation with Iran and Hezbollah. The final factor is geopolitics; the geographical dimension helped establish Russian military presence inside Syria as the proximity between Russia and Syria paved the way for the construction of Russian military bases within the Syrian sphere².

² I24NEWS (2015, January 26) Fighters From Syria Army, Hezbollah, Iran Capture Town Close To Jordan Border. Retrieved from <https://www.i24news.tv/en/news/international/middle-east/100568-160126-fighters-from-syria-army-hezbollah-iran-capture-key-town-close-to-jordan-border>

There was a return to the traditional international rivalry forces of the West Asia. The years 2015 and 2016 witnessed a return to the escalating military intervention of international forces in internal conflicts in the region, especially the Syrian conflict. Among these forces were America, Russia, Britain, France and China. The main reasons for the international forces' intensification of their military presence in the Middle East included maintaining a sustainable presence in the region, preserving the strategic interests of their countries, and preempting the threats of terrorism by targeting the strongholds of the ISIS and addressing the sources of cross-border smuggling, illegal immigration and refugee flows that represented the most serious threat to the European continent. Overall, the consequences of the escalation of international roles in the West Asian region were several. First, the complexity of resolving the internal conflicts in the region was a result of the intertwining of the interests of various parties involved in the conflicts. The second was the restructuring of maps of regional alliances as the involvement of international powers in regional affairs increased. The third was linked to the possibility of threats going to international forces themselves.

As a result of international developments in the West Asia region, Jordan was quick to view the new dynamic as an opportunity rather than a threat. High-level visits to Moscow by the King and the Jordanian Chief-of-Staff set a cooperative tone. Indeed, such visits may have empowered a silent majority of top Jordanian ministers and security officials to act on longstanding agnostic—and, in some cases, positive—attitudes toward the Assad regime by encouraging further contact.

The international repercussions resulting from the Syrian crisis in particular, and in West Asia in general, formed a major challenge to Jordan politically, and in terms of security,

economy and social security; a threat that went beyond its ambition. The Jordanian policymakers were worried that even if Jordan remained an ally to the US and the Gulf countries, this did not form a guarantee to the kingdom that it would not be left behind. By gauging the changes in the international scene, the Jordanian decision was to take steps toward Russia. The steps went along with Jordan's declared policy of adopting a moderate approach with all parts of the crisis in Syria. As a matter of fact, these steps aligned well with steps in the previous years as the Jordanian-Russian political relations had peaked over the last ten years. Jordanian understood the Russian military presence in Syria and the leadership believed that it went along with the Jordanian interests of keeping Jordan safe.

Jordan and Russia had nearly an identical view of the two main issues in the region: the Palestinian-Israeli conflict and the Syrian crisis. Jordan was chosen by the participants at the Vienna Conference to resolve the Syrian crisis a few days ago to prepare a list of terrorist organizations in Syria because of Jordan's ability to maintain security and stability despite its complex population structure and the increasing complexity of the influx of hundreds of thousands of refugees from Iraq and Syria.

Another factor for Jordan's rapprochement towards Russia was the strategic military relations between Jordan and Russia at various levels, including a joint Jordanian-Russian project for the development and manufacture of anti-armor rockets. Economically, Jordanian-Russian relations focus on economic partnership, especially in areas of nuclear energy, food security projects, and the promotion of Russian tourism. Jordan went towards relying on Russian expertise in nuclear

energy to build the reactor, which is due to be completed in 2018, and did not want to lose these investments.

7.4 Limitations of the Study:

Clearly, there are some limitations to the study. The study focused only on the Jordanian perspective. Chapter three and five concentrated on Jordan's relations with the actors in the Syrian conflict without going deeply into other point of views. So, one of the major limitations of this dissertation is that justifications were provided for the Jordanian actions while no convincing justifications were given for the Syrian regime or regional or policies of great powers or even the various spectrums of opposition inside Syria.

This study does not claim complete objectivity when it comes to the description of some situations of the hosting communities and the refugees. It is dedicated exclusively to the voices that express official Jordanian story in regard to the Syrian crisis implications, and Jordan's reaction and interaction with events happening inside Syria and in the West Asia region. So, the study methodology did not rely on sampling the hosting communities in Jordan or the Syrian refugees inside Jordan. Another limitation is that this study did not address comparisons between the situation of Syrian refugees and hosting communities in Jordan, with those in other countries such as Lebanon, Turkey, Iraq, Sudan, and the European Union, or with the previous Palestinian and Iraqi waves of refugees. Also, the legal situations of the Syrian refugees inside Jordan and the point of view of human rights organization were not included in the chapters, although the study did take some information from their reports and publications to ensure authenticity of governmental data.

In general, there is a lack of research that focuses on the Jordanian official point of view. This lack of studies did not help identify the scope of research, on account of having a wider view of the Jordanian official position in the literature review. Literature review findings were used as foundation for the research to be built upon existing gaps to achieve the research objectives. However, prior research on this topic focused on either the most contemporary and evolving research problem or too narrow a research problem. I have tried to compensate for the shortage of resources through books, researches, reports, and studies that have direct and indirect relation to the main topic. The shortage of official Jordanian documents and press releases from official Jordanian institutions, especially the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Ministry of Interior, and the security institutions, formed another obstacle.

7.5 Recommendations for Further Research:

The research process for this thesis based on the Jordanian policy towards the Syrian crisis during 2011-2016, has led to useful results and conclusions. Still, there is a dearth in our knowledge regarding many areas related to the subject of this thesis. It would benefit to conduct further studies, and carry out more researches in other aspects. Further research could fruitfully explore the Jordanian policy towards the Arab refugees' crises from 1948-2018. Future research could also be investigate the waves of Arab refugees that hit Jordan as a result of the surrounding conflicts and wars: the two Palestinian refugees waves 1948 and 1967; the Jordanians and refugees coming back from Kuwait and the Gulf countries and Iraq 1991; the Iraqi refugees 2003; and the Syrian refugees 2011-2018. It would also help to examine the effects of sudden increase in the Kingdom's population that caused political, economic, social, and security implications for Jordan. Also, I strongly suggest initiating studies on the Syrian Crisis that concentrate on addressing the various aspects of

the conflict and its implications on the Syrian refugees and the hosting countries, encompassing issues like resettlement, immigration, and the international responsibility to protect them. In addition to that, on a broader scale I recommend more studies devoted to and targeting conflict resolution in Syria, which would prove useful in presenting alternative models for solving the conflicts.

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